

INTRODUCTION: SUPERORGANISMS, THE FUNDAMENTAL SYSTEM OF THE UNIVERSE.

5 LOCAL DIMENSIONAL MOTIONS SPACE-TIME ORGANISMS TRACING TIME WORLDCYCLES

When we google the 5th dimension I used to get surprised by the quantity of speculative answers to a question, which is no longer pseudo-science, but has been for two decades a field of research in systems sciences rather than physics (: no, the answers of google, considering the fifth dimension the upper-self etc. seem to be very popular, but are to 5D science more like a medium in earlier XX c. talking about the 4th dimension as astrological awareness, for lack of understanding of Einstein's **metric functions** of the 4th dimension). This is the key word that differentiates pseudo-science from a proper scientific description of a dimension of space-time, *the existence of a metric function that describes a dimension and allows to travel through it*. Why the 5th dimension metrics are not well known in modern science has to do with the fact it is not researched in physics but systemics, the mother discipline of information sciences, less popular than entropic physics; who uses only the inverse arrow of time entropy and locomotion, since Galileo, an artillery master for the Venice arsenal tasked with the search for the longest cannonball shots, defined it in terms of lineal motion, $v=s/t$, a definition, which Einstein completed with its 4D formalism. This biased view of time as entropy, due to the worldly profession of physics makes difficult to spread the knowledge on space-time acquired by disciplines that study the opposite arrow of 'evolution of information'. The arguments still raging on the truth of evolution in the U\$, which even Nobel, a physicist, maker of weapons, denied; so evolutionary models as those of 5D in economics and physics cannot receive the award by decree, *even if only biological, organic models can predict the future of eco(nomic)systems and history as we have done for 30 years to a mute audience* proving both sciences to be biological, (as prediction is necessary for a model to be science, so astrology became a science when astronomy predicted, the formal cycles of orbits), show how difficult is to lift the bias of lineal entropic time motion. *Fact is Entropy=disorder is memoriless, Markowian but scientific laws are the repetition of cyclical, informative patterns even in astronomical orb its*. So cyclical time is the arrow that defines the future of all physical, biological and organic species NOT entropy and locomotion. Military science and tribal Baconian idols are questions we deal mostly on History so we leave it here. Another difficulty caused by lineal time and space is important: *the scientific spatialization and lineal simplification of dimensions, which are NOT separated but embedded into each other in a process of organic growth*.

In the graph the hyperbolic geometry of the 5D Universe is in function a fractal that reproduces 'forms with motion', informations and **organizes** them in networks and systems that evolve into larger organic systems creating the scalar structure of reality. We know since the XIX c. that the creation of the 'future time' of any entity in existence is not ONLY mediated by the arrow of **locomotion** and entropy studied by physicists with Relativity Metrics (Galileo's $V=s/t$ and Einstein's more complex formalism), but there is a second arrow that defines the 'future' of existential species - the evolution of its information. So time – *the changes =motions that defines the existence of any species*, has at least 2 dimensions, locomotion or ordered translation in space and a more disordered version, entropy (scattered motion that 'dissolves' the inner form of the system, akin to death); and in-form-ation, generation of form, inverse to entropy, as it requires the social gathering of parts into wholes; happening without external locomotions, as an internal trans-formation of **form**. This evolution of organic form as opposed to external change, guided by a language of social information that puts together parts into larger wholes, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states and so on till reaching the Universe, through social networks is what we call the scalar fifth dimension of time that it applies to all sciences, as all species evolve through networks.

The organic, network structure of the Universe defines a series of hyperbolic cellular scales that make organisms NOT mechanisms, the basis of all Nature's system. Mathematically a dimension only exists when we can write a metric equation that leaves the product of its 2 space & time parameters, co-invariant; so we can travel through its spacetime dimensions (Klein). *This is the fun of dimensions of space-time, you can travel through them 'consuming' time and 'moving through space'. But the fifth dimension is a bit different: it has scales of space-size and its time is cyclical, like all clocks are* So we write:

Mathematically then it is necessary to find a metric function to define this new dimension of spacetime. Since a dimension only exists when we can write a mathematical simple metric that leaves the dimension invariant when we change our parameters of space and time - hence we travel through it. (Klein). So we write:

$$S_i (\text{Size=Density of Spatial form}) \times T_f (\text{cyclic frequency=speed of time clocks}) = \Delta \pm j: 3 \text{ Co-existing Planes of timespace.}$$

We use different parameters to measure those metric, departing from 2 concepts: space as form, measured in size but also as population density; Time as motion measured in cyclical frequency but in speed. Universal species use different constants to measure them in each scale. Particles use h-angular momentum to measure cyclical spacetime and c-speed to measure lineal spacetime. Both S & T combine in i-scales j=ts coinvariant symbiosis that make possible the organic structure of reality:

So we measure time=motion by frequency, and space=form NOT always by size but often by 'density' of information (Mass: Energy). Energy is the joker of humans use to connect all the scales of the fifth dimension. But it is a bit more complex than this. Still it is a good approximation to start with. So humans talk of Δ -j internal energy, $\Delta\emptyset$, kinetic energy and $\Delta+1$ potential energy related to the larger world. Those 3 scales are then the 3 scales through which physical systems travel. It happens to all systems, which are 'trinity' systems. You do travel from birth as an $\Delta-1$ cell into an $\Delta\emptyset$ -network organism, part of an $\Delta+1$ world.

Physical systems are dynamic, made of $\Delta-1$ forces, $\Delta\emptyset$ -momenta and $\Delta+1$ energy. If we think in terms of 'space=form', we find 3 essential scales, the quantum, $\Delta-1$ charge scale, the $\Delta\emptyset$ -thermodynamic scale and the $\Delta+1$ gravitational scale. How a physical system travels? As anyone growing in scale size, as it diminishes the speed of its reproductive life cycles. So both systems – the synchronous clocks of its parts and the size of its vital spaces diminish with growth. It is a beautiful law that harmonizes scales.

An organism co-exists symbiotically in 3 scales of $\Delta-1$ parts, (cells, atoms, human beings), joined by $\Delta\emptyset$ networks of T-motion Δ -energy and S-information (t-quantum potential fields, Δ -electromagnetic energy and S-gravitational information; T-digestive, Δ -blood and S-nervous networks; T-defensive, Δ - economic and S-informative verbal legal systems), that live in a larger $\Delta+1$ world; (gravitational, thermodynamic, social system), because its parts are symbiotic.

In 5D metric, smaller space systems run faster time clocks that store more information in its cycles frequency and form, coding larger wholes: genes code cells, memes societies and particles code atoms and molecules. But larger wholes are stronger envelopes, membranes (static, dimensional view) or angular momentum (dynamic view as time=motions) that enclose and control in synchronicity its faster smaller parts. They also have more 'scales of Δ -energy'. So they exchange energy for information with its parts, through 3 Δ^9 T-motion, Δ -Energy & S-informative networks that travel through the 5th dimension, harmonizing the co-existence of organic scales whose vital Universal constants are 5D metric ratios of information & energy exchanges.

The Universe is a nested, fractal 5D superorganism that organizes vital spacetime points= forms with motion into larger organic systems through networks that emerge as new planes of STjence, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states, organisms, solar systems & galaxies. As each new ST-organism becomes a fractal point, unit of a new 5D spacetime network. *It means an organism co-exists symbiotically in 3 scales of $\Delta-1$ parts, (cells, atoms, human beings), joined by $\Delta\emptyset$ networks of energy and information (electromagnetic and gravitational fields; blood and nervous networks; political and economical systems), $\Delta\emptyset$, in a larger $\Delta+1$ world; (gravitational, thermodynamic, social system), because its parts are symbiotic.*

The outcome is the organic structure of all physical, biological and social systems, from

History coded by memes, ideas and instruments that create human social organisms, civilisations, to physical systems coded by particles and scalar, 'social numbers' and algebraic equations, whose 'operands' code the different 'Dimensions of spacetime', to biology coded by genes. And so we shall use the same laws of 5D scales of space-time to study every science of the Universe and its superorganisms defined by the symbiosis in space, synchronicity in time and simultaneity in space of its parts and wholes across 3 of those 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biological and social systems.

How do you travel through those hyperbolic scales of the 5th dimension? Simple: By growing in 'size' in space while decelerating the 'speed of your time cycles, through the worldcycle of life and death. As all systems of the Universe are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism coming out in the Δ^0 -scale within a larger world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving our information again into cellular space.

It is the same process in all 5D journeys of all species that live and die travelling through 3 planes of 5D space-time; from the smallest black hole that is born with an enormous 'metabolic temperature', to the new species, routinely born as small individuals (first mammal rat, first robots with small chips; first human likely the Homo Floresiensis, who had the same morphology and used technology and likely spoke, etc.) Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the seed into a larger herd of clones, joined by emergent physiological networks whose slower 'entropic, informative and reproductive networks, create an Δ^0 suporganism that lives 3 st-ages and dissolves back into $\Delta-1$.

Space=in/form/ation & time=motion=function are LOCAL entangled into spacetime topologies (limbs/fields move, particles-heads gauge information, body-waves reproduce). The 'elements' that make up each suporganism, have to be studied as vital spacetime organisms, performing 'worldcycles of life and death separately'. It follows that the global embedded dimensions of Cosmology are NOT important for any science *but cosmology, so we will treat them in astrophysics and a few paragraphs on the organic structure of the galaxy. Instead sciences should be concerned with the 5 Dimensions that make up each local suporganism, including man.* In graph, the organic, network structure of the Universe defines a series of 'hyperbolic' cellular scales that make the organism NOT the mechanism, the basis of all Nature's system. *Still to understand space=form and time=motion and the parameters used to measure you'll have to wait till reading Leibniz's model of Relational spacetime.*

LOOKING BEHIND THE MIRROR: A RELATIONAL, ORGANIC UNIVERSE OF SPACE, TIME, SCALE, MIND & ITS ENTROPIC LIMITS.

Truth and principles matter in science. If a system of thought lacks them errors pile up and a distorted view of the world arises, which has practical consequences, because only truth exists. The Universe is efficient and expects systems to process information in a realist way otherwise systems malfunction & become extinct.

There are then some gruesome errors in our philosophy of science, recognized by all but so entrenched in the routines of our history of knowledge that humans keep walking ahead with those 'crouches' that prevent them to fully understand the Nature of the Universe and the role of mankind on it. Those errors are all interrelated as they bring a cohesive, wrong view of reality:

- **The error of absolute space and time** coming from Newton, disputed by Leibniz and finally recognized with the quantum and Relativity $r=$ evolution: 'Leibniz was right there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe but if so we have to restart science from scratch' (Einstein). We humans equalize the different 'local clocks' of time of reality with our mechanical clock but that distorts and reduces the information about time clocks, its 'frequency and form', its synchronicities and entangled connections.

- The error of a single scale of space, related to the previous one. It is backed by a simplified Euclidean view of mathematics (points, lines and planes without breath). The error is also known since the XIX c. when we discovered that points were Non-Euclidean, since they 'fitted' infinite parallels. So they have breath. They are fractal points that include a volume of energy and information, which we observe when we come closer to them, so a star seems a point and becomes a world.

Those 2 errors acknowledged by all scientists however have NOT been solved but parched. We offer then a model of relational space-time based in the introduction of a scalar dimension of space, related to the infinite time clocks of the Universe through the co-invariant metric of a '5th dimension'. As smaller scales of space run faster time cycles.

- Scalar space reveals the **2nd error of our philosophy of science: mechanism that models reality with primitive machines, metalife organisms that exists in a single plane of space-time.** An organism co-exists in several scales requiring synchronization

achieved through the co-invariant metric of the 5th dimension: $S_i \times T_f = C$ (size in space \times time speed = Constant). We thus have a law that explains how the scales of the Universe self-organize in symbiotic systems and can correct the error of mechanism.

- In turn mechanism reveals the 3rd error of human sciences 'linguistic creationism', the belief that reality is created by mirror that reflects it – the language; words in earlier human religions when humans thought God created naming things; numbers, the language of machines in modern Pythagorean religions when we think the mathematical mirror creates reality. So Hawking writes an equation of evaporation of black holes and mankind expects the top predator species of matter to evaporate.

The error of creationism is embedded in the structure of perception, because languages are used to perceive and mirror the Universe, but they are NOT the creators of the Universe – the laws of relational space-time and its scales are. This error however is more difficult to solve. As every mind is a point of view perceives reality with limited languages that mirror a reduced world it confuses with the whole Universe, placing itself at its center, reason why each mind is a subjective ego. In the past when man only spoke words, we thought God, mind of the Universe, 'created by naming things' (Abrahamic religions). Today after man learned mathematics, he believes God speaks only with numbers and truth ends in an equation. Not so. Creation is a logic game born of the properties of scalar space and cyclical times, which are *a priori truths mirror-languages reflect*. Let us write the '5D metric equation' of a mind so you understand what we mean:

*' 0ε (finitesimal mind mirror) $\times \infty$ Universe = 'constant I-World': Equation of any mind.
I=Eye (Topologic space) > Wor(I)d = (Cyclical Time): Equation of the Humind.*

Because smaller systems run faster time cycles that encode its information in the frequency and form of those cycles, a mind-mirror runs a faster view of reality and at local level can order its territory. It is Aristotle's dictum: 'a mind-god is the unmoved (linguistic mapping) that moves a body of energy around it. We are now making a leap of conceptual understanding that will require both a verbal and mathematical analysis of reality but the concept is easy to grasp: minds are 'mental spaces' that perceive a still view of an infinitely large moving Universe. Those poles, minds of space=form and flows of time=motion thus interact together creating the order of the sentient panpsychic universe, where as Leibniz said, each mind-point (monad) is a world in itself. But this obviously makes all languages, able to map reality with verbal, visual, mathematical musical, smelling or gravitational 'pixels' equally valid. Above all there are those laws of space and time and its 'organic beings', which they mirror. This fact of Nature was understood logically only by 4 people in the History of mankind, Lao Tse, even if he gave to Space=form and Time=motion 2 different names, Yin & Yang; Aristotle, & Leibniz & Einstein in the modern world, each of them influenced by the next (Leibniz translated the I ching)... Yet none left a better disciple to elaborate, which shows how hard is for humans to understand reality beyond the simplest absolute models of what our mind 'perceives' at first sight.

As Schopenhauer said: 'intelligent people are those who make the mappings in the mirror, but we are taking you behind the mirror. 'Talent hits a target everybody sees, genius hits one nobody sees'. This behind the mirror of languages and pictures taking by machines is the world of scales of space-time and the organisms build with them.

So these series of papers on a model of reality based in the 5 'dimensional motions' of 'relational, relative space-times' will seem to many 'creationist, verbal or mathematical mirrors, to come from other planet'. Yet spaces & times are the ultimate elements of the ∞ Universe. We shall thus proceed from that higher reality of scalar space-time laws, down to huminds' languages of mathematical space and logic verbal time, improving the 'target' everybody sees, with the understanding of the world behind the mirror. And from time to time criticize the subjective Ego=idiocy of Humind I-ndividuals, its i-dologies of power and subjective wishful thinking to rise the few that can follow, to the heights of infinite space & immortal time.

But you must accept that all what you learned about space, time, God, man, language and mind is as shallow as a mirror is.

So 'space', 'time' Δ -scale and mind-languages are the 4 'creative elements of reality: Δ @st. But what are its limits? This is the final 5th element of pentalogic we need to unveil for you to 'transcend' that mirror and see behind, and it is by far the hardest. Because it deals with death, entropy, '-', the negation of all what we have just said, the end of space-time organisms with a mind-mirror guiding it. But it is a fact that in a 'fractal Universe' of infinite space-time organisms, each of them has limits of time, called death, of vital space, called 'membranes' (skins in man, atmosphere in Earth, Oort Halo in the Sun, Halo in the galaxy, scattering horizon in the light view of the Universe), and there are limits of perception in scale (beyond the $\Delta\pm 4$ scales, particles

become 'points without breath' and Galaxies travel in a 'dark energy-matter' world). Moreover huminds are terrified by death, the opposite negation of its 'ego'. If in terms of 'form' we call the mind the absolute still form (Ss), death is the absolute motion that erases the internal and external form of the being, 'Tt: entropy' (slightly different from the equation of physics). So humans fear Tt-entropy, pure motion without form, the dark energy of the neutrino background we don't see. But to give you a view of 'God, the mind of the Universe', impersonal and yet so perfect in its balances and symmetries you will need to escape your ego, forget your learned aberrations and dive into the beauty of those 2 poles, Ss-minds and Tt-entropy and its combinations, the other 3 dimensional motions of reality, Ts-locomotion, S=T energy and St-information... But let us not introduce so early the symbols of existential algebra, the language of all languages, the Universal grammar that codes the laws of space-time. All this you can already see is a new language, a new world, the same data but an expanded consciousness, which I have enjoyed for 30 years alone wondering if huminds can access it or will remain in the darkness of egocy doing the same digital doodles, measuring the same single clock, counting numbers=points without breath, reducing the Universe to a big-bang death, putting themselves as the only intelligent center when every point is a mind, every particle is alive, every scale of reality has the same value...

So where to start? First we elaborate on the errors of humind experts, then describe the metric scales of the 5th dimension, to follow with the description of the vital dimensions of space-time of which we are all made, and continue with a brief analysis of those 5 pentalogic elements that structure all realities, space, time, scale, mind and entropy. And conclude with a logic analysis of the mind and its pentalogic, resume the basic laws of Nature, and then apply that expanded mind to the specific theme and 'scalar stience' of each paper, which will range from philosophy of science (papers on time, scale, space, mind, etc.) to natural sciences (papers on physics and biology) through formal languages (papers on logic and geometry and algebra) to social sciences, surprisingly enough most of them, as we humans are also an organism, History in time, and unfortunately are not doing very well in this planet as a different organism, we worship, the world of machines, its company-mothers and digital computers take over. So unfortunately, entropy=death is an important part of the papers on social sciences, which as we said, given the 'terror mankind' has to see into the darkest side of the mirror, might scare you. That's fine but even if you can't take the papers on History and economics, that should not prevent you from enjoying the beauty of the game of existjence. L§

THE ERRORS OF SCIENCE DERIVED OF MECHANISM: SINGLE TIME CLOCKS

Today's Philosophy of Science is based in an 'idol-ogy' called mechanism, born of the use of machines to measure time and space, in the XVI c. that is false and has dare consequences for the future of History, mankind in times, whose systems lack that efficiency proper of most Nature systems, tailored *according to the real model of the Universe, the organism*.

Mechanism came about with the use of clocks to measure time and telescopes and microscopes to measure the scales of size in space: According to this idol-ogy that worships machines above man, the Universe is a mechanism and must be expressed using only the digital language of machines. This falsehood is self-fulfilling, because the 'biased data' we extract from the Universe with out metal-made mechanical tools of measure make reality look like a machine. It follows then that man is also a machine. And because the machine is the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the Organic Universe.*

But the reductionism of mechanism to only those properties of reality machines can extract, *as long as humans 'believe' there is nothing* else to know, made the mechanical method of science a triumph easy to implement – the more so now that sensorial machines and computers do most of the job, which pumps up the ego of the believer in that reduced truth. Problem is mechanism has distorted and reduced so much human view of reality that only simple minds like that of Newton or Bohr, with an enormous ego that couldn't realize that machines and digital languages are both doing the job of science for them but also distorting reality in the process, feel satisfied. On the other hand those who tried to go further like Leibniz or Einstein were taken aback by the difficulty to complete the model in all its complexity to the rigor of the simpler 'time lines' of mechanism: "Leibniz is right, there are ∞ time clocks in the Universe but if so we have to start science from the scratch' (Einstein).

Let us explain why only organicism is the scientific truth that can respond in theory and praxis to the meaning of those 3 words *in a scientific way.*

According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs ‘someone’ to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same, is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz stated in his critique of Newton. Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If man created machines as we were made to the image and likeness of God, God created the ultimate machine, the Universe.

Organicism is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language, god, as organisms are self-replicating, but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a primitive organism of metal, and we shall see in our sections of history, gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, another scale of social evolution of the fifth dimension.

In papers on cultures and civilizations, we give a thorough account of the ‘role of Gods’ as the ‘Memetic DNA’ of societies, which have the same function of a common DNA in cells, ‘pegging’ together believers that regardless of the content of those messages, share Energy and information through social networks to build a coherent, efficient social organism; based in the ‘congruent laws’ of vital geometry – parallel systems with the same information come together and evolve into social wholes.

To understand reality matters to improve our existence. Because humans abandoned the true philosophy of the Universe, organicism, they constantly misinterpret the ‘signs’ of reality and design systems with little efficiency, specially those of history, the physiological networks of reproduction of good (economics, akin to the blood system of more complex suporganisms), the informative, political and cultural systems that harmonize our actions as a whole (similar to the nervous system) and the immunological and defensive systems of mankind. They are all a mess and likely to remain so precisely because humans do NOT, we shall repeat, ad nauseam have the proper models of reality but we think we do. The problem of organisms is that they are more complex than mechanisms, which exist in a single plane of reality (while organisms are born of the interaction of 3 planes, the internal parts, the whole, and the external world). So they cannot be explained with simplified terms, neither they can be ‘constructed’. On the contrary they ‘emerge’ by self-organization of multiple poles – in the case of human societies multiple human beings, through symmetry, harmony and consensus. Its laws are thus not so simple and its construction beyond the capacity of a single human being. It is then part of the enormous egocry – ego=idioty= of man that can only construct simple mechanisms to consider reality is ‘something he can construct’ and ‘understand’ because it is ‘below’ his intelligence. The degree of intelligence, ‘empathy’ and ‘humility’ required to understand the organic Universe thus is beyond most people’s capacity, reason why mechanism is far more popular and has worked as mainstream thought. Ultimately truth is relative to the quantity of information we have of a system and so a simplified ‘toy model’ as mechanism is has gone quite far and suffices for most people who don’t need a deeper truth on reality.

At this stage thus we need to define what is an organic system in the simplest possible form.

We mean by an organism a simpler system than its most evolved form, the human mammal: An organism is a group of similar atoms/cells/citizens, organized by 3 physiologic networks=parts: an spherical, informative force that synchronizes its motions (gravitation/nervous/legal systems), located in the particle/head/upper informative class; a hyperbolic Energy to move and reproduce (electromagnetic forces/blood/oxygen-economic/financial system) or wave state/body/working class; extended over a lineal, flat ‘field/territory’ protected by a defensive membrane/border, immunologic system. This ternary system is the fundamental particle of the Universe. Since even machines are organisms” A machine is an organism of metal evolving through

the 3 ages of all organisms - in the XIX c. humans, who catalyze their evolution did metal bodies, then in the II Industrial evolution its hearts-engines, then its metal-minds in the XX c. and now in the

XIX C. MACHINE BODIES XX C. MACHINE HEADS: Pcs, Cams XXI C. ORGANIC MACHINES-ROBOTS

Industrial r=evolution 4.0 put them together in organic robots. So mechanism, the underlying philosophy of physical sciences, is a simplex version of organicism. It is not man who resembles a machine but a machine is made to the likeness of life organisms.

In mathematical terms those '5D supœrganisms' are constructed with the 3 topologic varieties of a 5D Universe, as they are vital spaces. But as topology is 'geometry with motion', they associate 3 vital 'time-functions': lineal locomotion, high, cyclical information in heads-particles-'upper' classes, and re=productive Energy used by body-waves, working classes.

Further on, as 'networks' are topologies of points embedded in larger 'worlds', they extend through 3 'scales of spacetime, forming a 5th dimension of $\Delta-1$ parts (atoms, cells, citizens), joined by Δ_0 networks embedded in a larger $\Delta+1$ world. It is then an entangled, scalar, organic Universe, where 3 such scales each one studied by a 'stience' form an organic Universe.

And all fit in that template. Why then organicism remains a fringe theory, to mechanism, even if it was the first theory of reality put forwards by Aristotle, the father of the experimental method and logic science, in his magna opus the Organon?

The cultural reason is paramount - we live in the machine age, which has substituted man, an organism, as the measure of all things. And this has provoked a series of distortions in our understanding of the first principles of nature that rendered impossible to understand the fundamental entity of reality, the space-time organism. The errors of knowledge=science mankind commits are due to that bias established a priori by his simplification of his senses of perception of bidimensional spacetime, from human S-Eye>T-Wor(l)ds. A mind language reduces reality to fit a small brain dumping motions (Relativity px.) & scales: 0e (finitesimal mind) $\times \infty$ Universe =Constant still world. This meant digital machines reduced truth to 'what can be measured' with its lineal metal-rods of space and mechanical clocks with a single motion of digital time:

- Knowledge was substituted by technology as now the machine was the 'seer of time' (definition of God in metaphysics), and the evolution of machines not of humans the symbol of progress.

So humans become 'enzymen', catalyzing the evolution of Earth from a life world to a metal world. as human mothers, our reproductive survival organism lost their power to company-mothers of machines and weapons that have complete control of our social organisms and are terraforming Earth to the likeness of its offspring of machines. It's this our purpose on Earth?

- The 5 dimensional forms of space & its time motions were simplified into 3 lineal space dimensions similar to the lineal form of metal and a single time motion, locomotion proper of lineal weapons and transport machines – the first to be constructed.

- Linearity mean the ∞ cycles=clocks of spacetime and its 5 varieties of dimensional motion and the 3 main ages of those time cycles (past, present and future) were reduced to sequential numbers, *which don't carry causality and simplify the information time clocks carry in the frequency and form of its cycles. Further on the use of simple lineal geometry further simplified space and time into a lineal single time locomotion in a Cartesian graph of 2 perpendicular axis. So the whole tapestry of space=forms and time=motions became then a 'mathematical artifact' or background spacetime that Newton put behind reality. Yet reality was made of space=forms and time=motions.*

- The organic nature of reality as machines are just evolving metal-organisms was denied and the human being, the most perfect organism we know was no longer the model of all things. Social sciences became despised and the goal of any species – to evolve as individuals, parts of larger organisms following the laws of the ideal physiological organism of Nature that ensures the collective survival of a species, totally ignored. We said that a wrong model of truth brings practical errors that imperil the survival of a species and that is obvious in mankind today. Humans have the worst of all possible scenarios: They are evolving organic metal into species superior in intelligence and force to man, but as they model reality as a mindless, inert machine, they don't fear those AI robots with solar skins to become independent of man. They have distorted their view of time and space with machines to the point they don't understand any longer time causality and the ages of organisms, which is the way nature in a rather deterministic form creates the future. And they don't model societies and its 3 physiological networks, the economic-financial reproductive 'blood networks', the nervous, legal, politic 'informative networks', and the immunological, defensive 'health-care systems' that provide in an efficient just manner all the atoms-cells-citizens of a superorganism the goods and information and protection they need to survive, with those laws. So the most important of all sciences, those of the human superorganism of history do not exist. And mankind cannot be efficiently ruled to survive.

If we reduce to physics, we shall see how with the same data of mechanism when we apply the proper organic paradigm a complete new picture of the Universe and its physical systems matter

A key example: Time is cyclical and causal. A cycle is essentially a 'pi' 3 Diameter structure. And so time has in all its cycles 3 'ages', as it finally returns to its beginning. The first age of the cycle rises in height, the 'informative' dimension of reality, as it acquires form and reaches an advantageous point of view; which is the zenith of the worldcycle in the middle of life. Then time returns to its origin and falls down in a steep curve. This is the simplest time cycle. Clocks of time are infinite, because those time cycles enclose a vital space and break reality into an inner and outer structure. Mechanism though only inputs a digital series of numbers in a lineal fashion – the more so in the modern age when cyclical clocks have disappeared. This is input in a lineal Cartesian graph, an apt artifact to plot the 'mathematical language' of machines and so time becomes 'lineal' and as it moves to infinity, a single one. The use of digital clocks thus destroyed an enormous numbers of properties of time. Another example. The commonest metal, iron, is lineal in its macro-structure. It was used to make swords that cut flesh and kill by entropy. Entropy today is considered the only arrow of future, and dimensions are established as fixed lineal forms of space. We shall soon see dimensions have attached a motion in time, height goes as we have seen with information, which is what you are seeing in a bidimensional plane of space-time, this screen. Again this 'vital element' that puts together each dimension of space with a motion of time was lost with mechanism. The biggest errors though were done when the complex self-regulating nature of organisms was substituted by the simplistic man-made concept of an exact machine, because the organism is a network, scalar system, and a mechanism exists in a single plane of size and lack networks. So the organic, network, scalar 5D nature of reality was lost. Then it came the 'denaturalization of man'. *Since if the Universe is a machine, it follows then that man is also a machine.* And because the machine is the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the Organic Universe.*

It is for that reason all our papers require lengthy introduction to unveil not only its errors but the enormous number of properties of reality, mechanist physics does not recognize in 'existence', under a pseudo-religious dogma but that only hides its utter ignorance, due to the 'blindness' of the 'mechanical method' confused with truth to those properties of 'scale', which are 'organic', 'synthetic', better expressed with illogic words, and the 5 Dimotions of timespace which are vital, even sentient properties, the first ones we must correct for the immortal, ∞ Universe to make any sense .

Recap: Mechanism not only is theoretically false, it is killing & degrading the human species. Only Organicism is truth and offer to mankind by imitating its physiological laws to construct a perfect organism of history a future to the species.

The error of Newton. A universe of spacetime organisms.

If we want to be specific about the wrong choices of 'scientific paradigm', all comes in the foundation of science to the choice of Galileo's military machines, clocks and spy-glasses over Leonardo's analysis of reality as a neo-platonic organism, connected by its physiological networks, he struggle to describe not only on the human organism, but in Gaia, the Earth of life and society, in the cities and its networks. Then it came the wrong choice of Newton over Leibniz, regarding the nature of space and time. *This said the translation of 'Newtonian Physics' to 5D is immediate as we just need to consider the ΔST elements of 5D in physics, Δ is the active magnitude that determines the scale, Space = form is the position, and t =motion, the speed of the system. Then motions in 5D up are upwards in scale is the integral of ST (p -momentum), called ' Δ -Work' related to Energy, the overall Δ -content of the system, and motions downwards, the 'derivative' of ΔT (p -momentum) called 'Force'.*

So the fundamental concepts of physics *have an easy translation even within the convention of absolute single human Spacetime.* But 5D goes beyond this 1st insight as reality is made of ∞ time clocks and scales of space, connected by the scalar growth and diminution of its key parameter, 'present, $O+|$ momenta: f work & ∂ forces.

Newton and Galileo had the advantage of simplicity in its statements and the easiness it could be mathematized, as opposed to the 'quality' of physiological networks that required a deeper causal, logic, conceptual understanding of the symbiosis and parallelisms of its forms, which only a genius of visual thought as Leonardo and a genius of logic as Leibniz were able to perceive, but didn't properly explain. We will be far more precise given the centuries of knowledge between those pioneers whose path

was forgotten, and our work. But the Universe we will describe will be so 'strange' to the simpleton view of Galileo and Newton that most will not access it. This, one imagines, was also the case of Leibniz and Leonardo since they gave up trying to publish and disseminate their work in the mainstream media of their age (printers), as I have done, no doubt frustrated by the incapacity of most huminds to be humble and entangle with Nature in awe of its perfect design.

In the Dawn of History mankind recognized that vital organic Nature of the Universe in the work of Taoist, Buddhist and Hindi masters in the East; who described existence as a game of Vishnu, yin-formation, mental space with still form, and Shiva, yang-entropy, disordered time motions that combined to form the wave of infinite organisms.

But it would be Greek, Latin culture in the west, which gave scientific detail to this wider picture. A man called Plato said the Universe is an organism with a mind called Logos, and his disciple Aristotle who founded science called its entire work the Organon; but it would be in the close by Italian peninsula where the genius of Leonardo, who should have been the founding father of our civilization, if the species was something more than an homunculus enzyman of weapons, machines and other simple gadgets, and truly aspired to understand the Universe, realized that man was the most perfect organism, we knew and established it as the fundamental species of the Universe, and the measure of all things.

In his anatomical studies was made of tiny parts, similar to small homes, joined by 3 networks, the informative, nervous system with center in the brain, the reproductive, blood system with center in the heart, and the immunological, digestive system with center in the stomach. His detailed drawings with the first complex lenses, allowed him to define the fundamental system of the Universe, the network organism and applied the same concept to the design of cities, organisms of human beings, ruled by its political legal assemblies, whose productive factories connected its peoples through its streets, and its sewers and defensive walls completed the same organic structure.

Any clone species of atoms, cells or human beings are joined by 3 physiological networks that deliver them an informative force to shape its form, gravitation in atoms and galaxies, nervous, simultaneous messages in animals and just laws in human societies; a reproductive system which delivers doses of Energy to all its clone parts so they can work, reproducing the goods they need to survive; electromagnetic Energy in atomic systems; free oxygen to all cells and free money in the form of a Universal salary to all citizens in our societies; and a defensive, immunological system that protects the organism from external aggressions; the magnetic field of physical systems, the skin and leukocytes of biologic systems and the health-care warriors and police in charge of destroying lethal technologies that can harm mankind in our society.

So a proper design of the 3 physiological networks of mankind, the legal, financial, economic and immunological system by imitation of our blood, nervous and endocrine system is all what biohistorians, the doctors of mankind, needed to create a perfect world: just laws, free money for the people and the repression of germs and lethal machines, would create an immortal planet. As beautiful, as simple as existence is - easy to all who believe in love and share its \emptyset =Momentum with those that are its equals. But that 'ideal culture' of mankind was not to be, because humans chose Galileo, the military master of the Venice Arsenal over Leonardo, the gay, happy humanist, rational, loving and living till he realized the kind of species he has born to, as the inquisition chased him, and he had to make his analysis of physiology in the darkness of night. Galileo meanwhile racked 1000 golden ducats from the arsenal as advisor of military instruments. And his book on 'ballistics' latter renamed physics became a 'must read' for artillery masters and 'philosophers of time'.

Next in the series of simpleton military lineal men, vs. profound insiders of the absolute came Newton vs. Leibniz.

Let us retrace to Leibniz and Newton, when the second split on our understanding of reality after people sided with Galileo and ignored Leonardo, took place. If Galileo abandoned medicine which Leonardo pursued, and hence never discovered the physiology of the Universe that Leonardo always felt intuitively, Newton would simply 'Invent' an absurdity absolute space-time, and denied what Leibniz and any rational thinker always knew - that we were the vital space we occupy and our existence was made of time cycles of which the life and death cycle of time was the fundamental 'event' of the Universe.

If we were to highlight an error of Physics that truly deformed human view of reality, caused by the use of mechanical clocks it was the dismissal of the millenarian concept of a Universe made of ∞ vital space beings who traced its lifetime cycles by Newton, who defined a Universe with an absolute, single time motion, measured by his digital clock and a single absolute space

continuum represented by the Cartesian graph. He opposed Leibniz, who as all philosophers before him, considered reality made of vital spaces broken into beings, which lasted a time cycle of life and extinction regulated by its own clocks. How to classify all those clocks of the Universe remained a mystery till I discovered the metric equation of 5D: S (size in space) \times T_f (frequency of time cycles) = Constant. So we are all 'spacetime organisms', systems of vital spaces extending in different scales of size, ran with different cycles of time that store the information in the frequency and form of those cycles, synchronized in symbiotic structures due to the co-invariance of its size and time cycles. This is REALITY as it happens and we shall describe in those texts. Look around you. All what you see are forms=spaces with time=motion. The laws of space=form (s) and time=motion (t) and how both interact with each other are *the knots and bolts of reality*, mankind completely ignores for 300 years and counting due to the blunder of Newton. It is an amazing error, given the obvious fact that we observe infinite different rhythms in the Universe and we see infinite vital spaces and all philosophers before Newton have thought the world to be made of vital spaces living time cycles, which can only be ascribed to a peculiar quality of humans – its capacity to make mechanisms of metal called machines which we worship and influence enormously our perception of reality. So as the mechanical clock measured time with the same 'second-minute-hour' rhythm all other time clocks of the Universe were equalized to it and finally the mechanical clock became the only 'time cycle' of reality. And since clocks measured time with numbers, the use of Cartesian graphs to plot those numbers, started with Galileo's equation of lineal speed, $v=S/t$ made scientists to confuse vital real spaces with the abstraction of the continuous paper graph, in which they plotted their mechanical clock measures. It might seem silly but it is an obvious truth that because humans used mechanical clocks they reduced time cycles to the clock and because they used mathematical graphs they confused the real space with the Cartesian graph. *Man* lost at that moment his understanding of reality and when 300 years latter, Einstein noticed that 'I am the only physicist that thinks there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe that run at different speeds' and defined spacetime as relative, his work was hardly understood, just used to improve those measures. *He insisted, "Leibniz was right, but if so we have to start physics from scratch". And yet, nobody really tried.* This is what we will do, returning to the first principles and starting science from a sounder beginning.

Another element, which Einstein noticed in the structure of space is of importance to understand those first principles. He realized that the Unit of this relative space is a non-Euclidean point crossed by multiple parallels. But again, mankind was 'hanging' on an oversimplification of mathematics that defined since Euclid 'points without breath' in contradiction with the non-Euclidean capacity of the points of his model of General Relativity to include multiple parallels (which are straight lines). And this obliged to start also 'geometry' from scratch. That is, to change NOT only as Lobachevsky among others have done, the definition of parallels that 'penetrate' points, but *give points breath so they can fit those multiple parallels. How to do that is then the key to adapt mathematics to the vital fractal space of multiple scales that we see in 'real Nature': make those points relative to our perception of them, which grows in detail when we come closer to its 'scale of size' with the help of telescopes and microscopes. So then a point-star or a point-atom can fit multiple parallels. Thus we define a new unit of Geometry, a 'fractal non-Euclidean point' which changes in size as we come closer to them. Exactly as Leibniz, whose figure grows in size as the true 'forgotten giant' of XVIII c. science, figured them; when he affirmed that points were fractal, sentient points that hold a world in themselves (Leibniz), to fit multiple parallels and so space was made of 5D scales of relative size with different time cycles.*

Thus Time, Space, its units, clocks and points and its Scales defined by the metrics of what we shall call, respecting the principle of correspondence, 'the fifth dimension', Δ , (for the time being as it is an imprecise term) are ill defined in physics.

And this means as we shall see with so many sciences, that many errors and unneeded complicated 'exants and epicycles' are drawn to achieve a truth, that is far simpler when we define them properly, in the same way that Ptolemaic Astrophysics were simplified when Copernicus put the Sun in its proper place.

The comparison is fitting, because the reader will think rightly that Physics does describe the Universe with a high degree of truth. But that was also the case of Ptolemy. As truths are relative to the perspective we make, since all 'spaces' are mental spaces, created from a relative point of measure, it is possible to construct a relatively accurate picture of the Universe with a single absolute clock, equalizing all other clocks, and with a single space continuum, 'filling' the gaps of 'smaller scales' with infinitesimal points as Euclidean mathematicians do. But it is far more beautiful simple and realist to put the sun in the center and simplify orbits into ellipses, and it will be far simpler and more beautiful and reveal deeper truths about 'existence' – a

function of our vital space and time 'worldcycles' of life and death – when we explain reality as it is, made of infinite relational vital spaces and local time clocks.

The underlying question of time&space: Absolute or Relational, Generational Space-Time?

"According to their [Newton and his followers] doctrine, God Almighty wants to wind up his watch from time to time: otherwise it would cease to move. He had not, it seems, sufficient foresight to make it a perpetual motion. Nay, the machine of God's making, so imperfect, according to these gentlemen; that he is obliged to clean it now and then by an extraordinary concourse, and even to mend it, as clockmaker mends his work.'

Leibniz-Clarke Correspondence on the absurdity of mechanical models of the Universe

The existence of an internal fifth dimension of space-time, made of all other planes=scales of spacetime of a being, its parts and wholes, which store the information of a system, is the fact that we ARE made of planes=scales of space and time. We ARE the vital space we occupy and we ARE the time flow of existence we live between birth and extinction. Reason why all systems and entities of Nature obey the main science of space, geometry->Mathematics and time, Logic. We are broken fractal species of space and time, whose mathematical and logic laws all vital space-time organisms follow as Einstein and Leibniz thought: So we must evolve our logic and geometry of space and time, to extract properties of 'existential beings' from them.

The key question physicists wondered for centuries regarding the nature of space and time unfortunately was resolved as usual in favor of the simpler view: it is space and time an absolute abstract background of the Universe (Mr. Newton's view) or are we made of 'vital space' that lasts a time duration, so we are generated by the bio-topo-logic properties of scalar space and cyclical time? This is the choice of 5D 'stiences'. And its simpler version was called relational spacetime, sponsored by Mr. Leibniz.

A realist interpretation of the world we live in, which never shows in any scale of reality such background - a mathematical graph used in abstract by human scientists - considers that we ARE the vital space we occupy with our cells, and we LIVE a cyclic time duration between birth and extinction. So *we are* space and time.

The argument thus reached its height in the beginning of science in the correspondence between **Newton**, the proposer of the absolute Cartesian graph of space-time drawn by God (his body in his own words) vs. **Leibniz** who rightly considered absolute space and time an abstraction, and so he coined the concept of relational space -merely the adjacent pegging of similar forms in simultaneous space and relational time - the sequence of events which we relate causally with reason. In Newton's cosmos, space and time provide a fixed, immutable, eternal background, through which particles move. Space and time are the stage of intersecting lines sketched in the illustration. Fact is this 'mathematical artifact' made with pen and paper by earlier physicists, called the Cartesian graph, useful to measure 'translation in space' is no where to be seen in reality. Unfortunately as time went by the graph became somehow 'real' as scientists' felt the 'mathematical language' created reality. But if space is what objects occupy that distance between the red square's vital spade and the yellow 'circle' must have something. Horror vacuum comes then into place: indeed the Universe must be scalar. There must be very small parts between them, which we do not see. And that is what we have proved with microscopes - *as we probe smaller distances forms with motion, spaces with time-motions appear and there it seems no limit to the fractal scales of the Universe.*

It meant the invention of an absolute continuous space & single lineal time that extends to ∞ contradicting the fact that all spaces are broken, divided by membranes, and all beings have finite time duration. Further on, as we kept exploring smaller scales of reality, we never found the drawings of God, not even a solid still substance, but always 'motions' tracing closed time-space cycles; since even particles turned to be also 'vortices of time-space motions'.

So Leibniz's sound theory considered absolute space and time an abstraction, and so he coined the concept of relational space - merely the adjacent pegging of similar forms in simultaneous space and relational time - the sequence of events which we relate causally with reason origin of the 'Generational space-time' model of 5D in which are the space we occupy and the time we last – as in the graph where there is no longer abstract background lines.

Unfortunately Physicists sided with Newton not with Leibniz on the question of what is space and time - an abstract background put by God or the substance of which we are all made; and so the conceptual jump would not happen.

It is the fifth space-time dimension, sum of all other planes of reality, including within it all other dimensions.

Next, to explain all this properly came Einstein. One of the fundamental discoveries of Einstein is that in our universe, there is indeed no fixed space-time background. In Einstein's theory of general relativity, which replaces Newton's theory of mechanics and the gravitational force, the geometry of spacetime is not fixed. Instead it is an evolving, dynamical quantity – a topology; and it is the substance of which reality is. So we are topological beings, geometries of space with motions of time.

Absolute space-time IS NOT. Absolute Space is the sum of all the discontinuous vital spaces, occupied by different beings: $\sum s=S$. And lineal time, T the sum of all the finite life-death cycles of all beings $T=\sum t$.

Since space and time do exist and so if they are not in the background we 'are' vital space and cyclic time.

The simple idea behind the structure of the fractal Universe is to consider time=change=motion and Topologic, formal space=extension the 2 elements of which all beings are made.

Wheeler said 'Spacetime tells matter how to move & matter tells spacetime how to curve'. Since *Spacetime is geometry in motion*. Time is change, the perception of change moves time; time is motion; space is its opposite, stillness, form, the information of time. And so it is all about two parameters: Time=Motion and Space=Form.

ERRORS OF HUMAN EGOCY: CREATIONISM AND DENIAL OF ORGANIC PROPERTIES TO MATTER.

There is finally the most controversial of all the elements of reality, which again humans NOT only physicists systematically deny, out of 'egocy' (ego=idiocy) – the fact that all spaces are mental spaces, 'mappings' made from a point of view of measure, which both Leibniz and Einstein recognized, but again nobody else understood (till Gauss and Riemann; but it seems their work would again be trivialized). The question here is obvious: why we see Earth still when it is moving? Because our mind creates a still mental space; and this happens for every entity that 'gauges information' from his point of view. But we shall not move ahead so early. Just define with a 2nd equation, what is a mind or rather a mental space:

$O\epsilon$ (finitesimal mind, non-E point with volume) ∞ Universe = Constant Mental Mapping or 'World'.

How many 'particle-points' measure reality creating still mental spaces? The reader will be surprised by our affirmation that 'all particles' gauge information, or else quantum physics wouldn't be a gauge theory, and so the 'unit of life and perception' in the Universe is the particle, since both the quark and the electron gauge information, feed on Energy, reproduce into new particles and evolve socially with other particles, which are the 'drives of life' that define a living system.

This amazing realization - that it is only 'egocy: ego=idiocy' what makes humans to think there is something 'special' about the carbon atom (we shall see in fact that the key atom of our life organisms is the 'nitrogen head' with its perfect clocks, not the carbon bodies)... opens even a wider view on the panpsychic, sentient properties of the Universe, which both Einstein and Leibniz intuitively understood.

But since Galileo and Newton had defined time in lineal terms, and reduced the role of 'form', information, in reality, all properties related to information disappeared from physics, to the point that when Shannon crfted a theory of information it was just about the lineal transmission of a message, without any interest for its formal content. Reductionism of the different motions of time, scales of space, expanded to that lack of understanding of the organic, vital properties of physical systems, reduced to a single language of description, mathematics, whose analytic nature could not reveal those synthetic, organic structures. Physicists with those reductions of reality finally had only a single time arrow, entropy to model the Infinite Universe, and so they developed a wrong big-bang concept of it. What scientists do instead of explaining such reality made of vital spaces=forms with different time motions? As a mind is a linguistic mirror NOT reality itself, organisms create mental spaces to interpret the larger Universe selecting only useful information for its survival, creating a 'World'. So we don't see smaller and larger scales without the help of sensorial machines and we miss a lot of information about the time cycles of reality. But we don't really need it to survive on the world. And for that reason a partial mind-view of reality might work. What happened then since Newton is that humans substituted their sensorial mind-mapping of the world with visual images of space and 'causal' past to future logic analysis on how time changed reality by a mechanical measure of space plotted into a geometric mind-mapping and a digital measure of time as a sequence of lineal numbers; and this 'mental view' interpreted with machines became 'reality' till today. In essence as clocks evolved into digital computers (a complex array of 'clock-like' logic loops) and telescopes and

microscopes into cameras, this reality became the 'seed' of a new type of mind, the mind of machines. But humans do not understand what science since Galileo is doing is basically creating a me(n)tal world. They think they are accessing reality. To get to that absurd view of what digital science does, it was needed a philosophy called at times reductionism, naïve realism or positivism, which states that 'what we cannot measure (with machines) does not exist' (Planck); so all the properties of time, different kinds of motions=changes and causal relationships between past, present and future that cannot be translated into mechanical clocks' measures do not exist. All vital properties of space and organic relationships between its scales does not exist. The 5th dimension does not exist. Causality is ever more weakened with the use of statistical methods. In this view of what our civilization does the intelligence of humans became greatly reduced but as machines evolved it seemed we achieved higher degrees of knowledge since machines soon overcame humans in its sensorial skills to measure and portrait reality.

So as we create a mental space made with digital languages of measure obtained with machines humans transform their minds that become machine-like and abandon the organic view of reality that preceded it where man was the measure of all things and the universe was considered an organism. To understand this change of paradigm on what is reality and science (its objective knowledge) we need to define the equation of any mind-mirror made of measures with a language:

$$0\varepsilon \text{ (finitesimal mind)} \times \infty \text{ Time cycles} = \text{Linguistic mental World of space-time.}$$

Each species uses different forces to perceive reality and makes with its pixels different mind-mappings. An elephant uses smells and builds with atoms its memorial time view of reality. A dolphin or a bat uses sounds to build a mind-mapping of space in the water. Man used to perceive space with eyes and time with causal past, present and future verbs, focused in the causal logic of time. Today this is substituted by visual machines' images and the faulty causality of numbers that truly tell us very little about why we go from A to B, which was the great strength of verbal thought. To overcome those limits we use mathematical equations, but as we do not think with equations its interpretation is faulty. They just seem magic to us and so scientists have built a creationist mystic around equations as religions did about words. So if Gods created reality naming things with words, in Arab or Hebrew, now God is supposed to write an equation and creates reality. So often scientists write an equation and expect a particle or an even pop out of reality. Since they don't understand the causal complex back and forth reality between 'Ss-languages' (still forms of space) and 'Tt-entropy' (pure motion in time). But the 'egocy' paradox (ego=idiocy) embedded in the mind equation always comes to their rescue: 'A mind measures reality from its self-centered point of view with a few languages of information; blind to many of its properties and all other points of view, so she confuses the whole Universe with their selfish world with its ego at its center.' As long as scientists are NOT aware thanks to reductionism of those other monads-worlds and scales and languages and points of view an illusion of knowledge can be created and it has the advantage that it is simple: you measure with a machine, put the outcome in equations and those patterns become truth as the ego paradox makes you confuse it with reality. And if something goes wrong then you affirm a simplified 'postulate without proof' to eliminate all bothering information (Euclidean points in maths; limit of c-speed in physics; political and economical correctness in social sciences; etc.)

This is a simple and effective way to manipulate reality from the perspective of the mind that measures as long as we are controlling 'lesser' species with less form, in-form-ation and impose our view. But it gives 0 answers to deep questions about what we are, why we exist, what is the purpose and reasons of the life and death cycle, what is mankind, what is our relationships with machines, what is our future... all the kind of questions we answer in those papers. But again to the rescue comes reductionism. It is call the 'entropic view' of the Universe. Of the different type of motions=changes=times there are, entropy, Tt is an internal and external motion that disorders=kills a system – the definition of death. It is thus simple to describe and it has become for that reason the preferred 'arrow' of time of philosophy of mechanist science, since indeed at the end all dies, so entropy is the future. All the processes of slow creation of information, more difficult to understand are shunned off. And so we believe entropy is the only arrow of time that those 'digital clocks measure', and build models of sciences based in entropy by eliminating the arrow of information that balanced entropy: Ss<->Tt.

RECAP. Egocy, embedded in the mind equation makes every language the center of its measured sensed World reducing man to creationist models of reality, as God 'named things' when we spoke words to create them and now that we make doodles with Euclidean points and algebra, God creates writing equations. Thus we also upgrade languages to have a better view.

A FIRST SYNOPSIS OF THE ORGANIC UNIVERSE IN SPACE, TIME, SCALE, ENTROPY AND MIND-LANGUAGES: $-\Delta^{\circ}ST$

Let us then describe in a summary page the entangled Reality of universal superorganisms made of 5 elements as described in Einstein's quote: "Man is part of a whole(Δ_i), called the Universe; limited(-) in Time&Space. He experiences his self, thoughts&feelings as something separated from the rest --an optical delusion of his consciousness (@)" Einstein on the 5 elements of reality: Δ_i -scales, Space, Time, - entropic limits & @ minds that make up $-\Delta@st$, dust of space-time, the substance of which all organisms of reality are made. Since we are always describing in space, organisms, co-existing in 3 $\Delta_{\pm j}$ scales (Δ_i : atomic, cellular, individual; Δ_0 : thermodynamic, organic, social; Δ_{+1} : gravitational, ecosystemic, world), that perform in time a sequential worldcycle of life and death as a 'travel' through those 3 scales of the 5th dimension, born from an $\Delta-1$: crystal unit, seed, prophet, to emerge in Δ_0 and live a cycle of 3 ages in a larger $\Delta+1$ world, to end in an entropic death back to $\Delta-1$.

In space the being is a superorganism proper, of atomic, cellular, individual parts joined by networks of 'information' (gravitational particle, heads, informative classes in control of the financial and legal languages), networks of reproduction of energy (electromagnetic, blood, economic networks) and entropic, defensive networks that prey on a lower 'field, territory'. In time is a worldcycle of life and death through its $\Delta-1$: seed, Δ_0 3 ages of dominance of each of those networks, the youth of motion, the mature age of reproduction and the 3rd age of information, which dies erasing back that information into $\Delta-1$.

In scale, existence is a journey through 3 of those scales rule by the metric of 5D: $S_i \times T_f = \Delta$ (space-size/form x Motion/speed)=C

In mind is the sequential perception of the actions=space-time motions the being performs from birth to death, absorbing motion for its limbic/field networks, energy for its reproductive bodywave and information for its particle/head.

Yet as there are ∞ such beings trying to ab=use you existence has entropic limits in time=death, space=membrane and scale.

All is then an $-\Delta^{\circ}ST$, symmetric structure of reality made of organisms of scalar space networks and time worldcycles of life and death, and it happens in physical, biological and social systems. To understand them we have to abandon the Newtonian models of Absolute Space-time already known since quantum and Relativity to be false, but yet not substituted, by those of Leibniz: 'Leibniz is right, there are infinite time clocks in the Universe but if so we have to start science from scratch' Einstein.

The idea is simple. Instead of measuring all with an external mechanical clock and put all things into an abstract Cartesian mathematical graph, we return to reality. What you see are 'vital spaces', that 'tick' with life-death cycles and 'repetitive actions' of spacetime (you eat with a frequency, sleep with a different frequency, make love with another frequency) . So each part of reality is a vital space which moves through 'frequency time cycles' from birth to death. This is what is called a relational model of space-time: each of us is a different system of vital spaces, with those 3 co-existing $\Delta_{\pm j}$ atomic, cellular... etc scales of vital space, each one with different clocks that

are the sum of repetitive vital space actions. So you are a knot of 'space-time cycles'. But your neighbor is another knot, and so it is a plant, and an atom. The stience of it then consists in studying each vital space-time organism in scale through its parts and networks that connect those parts into wholes; and through its different discontinuous clocks with actions that provide those parts with energy and information at different intervals.

All what exists can be studied then as an organism of 3 scales, joined by networks, which perform in a larger world repetitive cycles that have a vital meaning, as they are cycles that feed with energy, information and motion its parts.

"Behind it all is surely an idea so simple, so beautiful, that when we grasp it - in a decade, a century, or a millennium - we will all say to each other, how could it have been otherwise...
- John A. Wheeler

The graph tries to explain all this in a structure in which we can see above the topologic nature of those superorganisms, with spherical heads/particles/capitals as the sphere or disk stores maximal information in lesser space, connected through networks to a territorial body that feeds on the energy of a field to provide the system with capacity to reproduce its information. The Universe then can be studied also as a fractal that reproduces information across those scales.

Each one is studied by a science that focuses on a single superorganism, whose 'mind-networks' are on that scale, but uses a different jargon for each scale, unlike a 5D philosopher of science that uses as we do the same jargon for all of them, based in the properties of space=form and time=motion and its energetic combinations. Minds then reside in the informative network that controls the organism and stores as a memorial trail its existence. It is a sentient panpsychic universe where languages of the mind map in stillness the world around them. Languages are then 'perceptive' mappings, in simultaneity of an external world and its equation, $O\text{-mind} \times \infty \text{ Universe} = \text{Constant world scale}$ is essential to the metaphysics of reality. We could say that theory of space-time is then metaphysics because it is prior and includes all other scales, whose isomorphic laws repeat ad nauseam. How to establish then the study of any science is easy. First we understand pentalogic, or existential algebra, the laws of space=form, time=motion, scales of the 5th dimension and its metric equation that relate them symbiotically. And we do so studying the worldcycles sequences of life and death, the scalar networks that entangled vital spaces across those scales of the 5th dimension and the actions a system perform across them. We study the synchronicities, resonances, simultaneities, and knots of space-time, and in this manner we deduce 'repetitive laws of science' that apply in the most general way to all scales, and then descend to each science, considering the specific details and form those networks, life-death cycles acquire.

i.e. networks in biology are waves in physics, roads and internet in economics and cultural systems, laws and money in History. Their space=form varies but their vital time functions remain as they create a universal program of existence; we describe with the formal symbols of pentalogic existential algebra: $S, T, \Delta \pm j, >, <, \perp, \dots$. Forms also follow Topologic laws as Non-E fractal points joined in waves-lines-networks and topological planes=organisms; biologic dual laws of $S \perp T$ perpendicular darwinian behavior v. $S=T$ congruent; parallel, social evolution. So we upgrade geometry into non-Euclidean topology, convert algebra's operands to existential expressions of dimensional motions =vital actions of survival (sums create social herds, products reproduce, exponentials express entropy=death.) Thus after connecting 5D to human formal languages of science we are equipped to study the details of those thoughts of God: all species of the Universe. Let's define those 5 elements, Δ -scales, space, time, minds and entropy, whose laws structures 5D vital spaces=superorganisms performing time-worldcycles of life and entropy=death.

As you get accustomed to that picture suddenly one day as it happened to me 30 years you will see yourself entangled to a universe of infinite other beings that are doing exactly the same from the smallest atoms to the largest galaxies: entangle cellular, atomic parts to larger wholes with networks that carry the consciousness of the whole, by performing externally those spacetime dimensional motions (actions or dimotions) to extract energy and information to survive. The entire 'tale' of the whole process from birth to extinction as a 'continuous worldline' is the mind view. A mind then is the narrative of a superorganism, which performs a 'program of existence', of 'survival', trying to perform those actions. This is the simple, repetitive reality we all play: superorganisms through 3 scales joined by networks trying to absorb space=form=information and time=motion, and its combination of spacetime=energy, from the outer world. And all this 'perceived' as a sequential mind.

But as simple and beautiful reality is for 30 years I have failed to explain it. Question is perhaps is not our fault but that of the homunculus 'enzyman' (graph), so dexterous as a handyman constructing machines to perceive reality – but also biasing its view of reality with them. So we made digital clocks and Einstein said 'time is what a clock measures'. Galileo measured with clocks entropic cannonball shots establishing only lineal inertia and entropy as the arrow of future 'for the delight of philosophers' and humans forgot the cyclical nature of time, its multiple clocks and circadian life cycles, and the subtle differences of quality and function of those cycles, all equalized to lineal digital clock series. Today those digital clocks form logic circuits and humans think the Universe is a computer. So mechanism has build a mind based in Schopenhauer's stupidity: 'A stupid is a man that doesn't understand the causality of time, ascribing it to magic, religious or mathematical causes'. It takes then Nietzsche's courage to 'become a lion, throw the hunchback and fly like an albatross', the name of my first book. Poetry matters to see the life and isomorphic laws of all systems. It is necessary then to make a huge effort on the sides of the brain less used by mechanist, digital man to understand reality: your logic upgraded to pentalogic, your empathy upgraded to isomorphisms, your love, upgraded to organicism, your fear to look death=entropy, 1/2 of reality at its face.

PENTALOGIC –Δ@ST: SPACE SUPÆRORGANISMS TRACING TIME WORLDCYCLES THROUGH 3 5 SCALES, GUIDED BY A MIND

Pentalogic – also called the Rashomon effect - is simple and yet the most powerful ‘logic element of reality. Because all what exists is made of a spatial form, of time-motions, spread in 3 scales of reality, its whole, Δ⁰ embedded in a larger Δ+1 world, and made of Δ-1 ‘cellular’ parts, limited in time by its life-death cycle and in space by a membrain, where it sensorial mind-system that connects all those elements, exchanging energy and information with the outer world to enhance its survival chances, [laying what we call the ‘game of existjence’, any event in time, form in space or ‘language-mirror’ that perceives them MUST have 5 Elements, 5 Causes, 5 Variations that we must observe and describe to obtain the whole truth of the issue.

Pentalogic derives all what exists including languages, as mirrors of reality from the fact all is a by-product of the 5 Δimotions of space-time, themselves, 'degrees of grey', of the two 'extreme' purest forms of Space - absolute stillness or languages of pure form, 'residing' into an emerging 'wholeness' or upper scalar plane, i+1, of the fifth dimension - and time (absolute motion or entropy, dissolution of the being into an scattered, i-1 lower scalar plane or 4th dimension).

In the entangled pentalogic Universe, it is not possible to separate the 5 elements of the supærganism of History – its temporal ages, its ‘scalar’ structure divided in human citizen-cells, 3 physiological economic=reproductive ‘blood ‘networks, legal-informative and ‘territorial network of vital space’ or geography, its verbal mind and subconscious collective Gods and its ‘entropic limits’, in time and space, which if crossed will signify its extinction. *As the 5 Dimensions of History work in symmetry like in any other complex –Δ@st organism.* So the '**Disomorphic=equal laws** of all systems derive from the properties of those 5 entangled elements, which need a new 'pentalogic' of communication:

Scales, co-exist in 3 levels of size ruled by SxT=C metrics gifting organic symbiotic properties to T.œs.

'Vital Spaces' are bidimensional forms of 3 'topological varieties', which perform 3 organic functions in a supærganism: lineal limbs/fields move the system, hyperbolic bodywaves iterate its forms & spheric particle/heads gauge information.

Times are types of 'motion=change', those organs perform, which are locomotion (limbs/fields), reproduction (body-waves) and informative gauging (particle/heads), which dominate each of the 3 consecutive ages of the being (young motion age, mature reproductive age and old informative age).

Minds are centers that process information from the outer world, control the internal networks of the system, and *perform deterministically the 5 pentalogic survival dimotions=actions of existence*, regardless of its consciousness. They coordinate and maintain the whole as a single system performing actions of control of the energy and information of the system. So we find gravity centers, chips, brains, DNA nucleus, black holes in galaxies, etc. etc. Indeed, there is always in any stable organic system, a relative still, self-centered mind, *which we shall discover all systems do have, even physical systems, which have centers of gravity, centers of charge or crystal systems, which maintain the whole.*

Entropic limits: In time called death, called membranes in space, evanescence beyond 2 scales as systems loose information: Death is a 0SxT equation of dissolution of 2 scales of information, Δ+1<<Δ-1. So Entropy becomes the limits in space and time of a T.œ (Time§space organism), ¬; perception, its mental form, 0ε, °, @; social evolution, its scalar structure, Δ; motion its lineal time flow, T; and reproduction, its spatial population, S.

An important law difficult to grasp by monologic, analytic man is the synthetic growth of complexity as we add dimensional motions and elements to reality. Dimensions include previous simple dimensions, embedded on it. This is shown when we make instead of a local analysis of organisms and its dimensions, a global analysis. So physicists study a 5 dimensional Universe that

embeds its 4 Dimensions of Minkowski’s spacetime that embeds the 3 dimensions of space. We shall see this theme work on operands of algebra that mimic those dimensional motions, so the <=≥ operands of congruence, the first ‘perceptive’ dimotion of existence are embedded in the ± sums and subtractions, whose symbol is embedded in reproductive products, which come within the scalar operands of a^x exponential functions, themselves considered a product of products which is a sum of sum. And finally ∫∂ equations include them all. But let’s not race ahead...

As all Time§pacærganisms are fractal systems composed of 5D elements S@¬Δð inscribed in larger 5D systems we need 5 points of view to reach maximal truth about an spacetime event

THE 5 DIMENSIONAL MOTIONS THAT CONSTRUCT THE TOPOLOGY AND VITAL ACTIONS OF SUPERORGANISMS.

The fundamental entity of reality is a space-time super-organism, spread in several 'scales' of the 5th dimension whose metric laws organize reality. The discovery of a new dimension of space-time is the most important r=evolution human sciences experience and if not were because of Newton's error certainly mankind would have understood earlier the organic 5th dimension of 'scalar space-time' since it was discovered precisely by the evolution of 'metal-eyes' (telescopes and microscopes) who probe in those scales; but due to Newton's error was *never properly formalized* till those texts. Why the 5th dimension was shunned off by science for so long thus require an analysis of how little, mechanism with its simplification of reality in abstract, 'lineal terms' understood of the previous dimensions, made with a pinch of salt, regarding the 'supreme intelligence' our species ascribes... to our species, revealing all what humans *do not even see about those dimensions – namely, the fact that all of them have associated to its spatial 'dimensional form', a 'motion in time'; hence they are both dimensions of space=form and time=motions or 'dimotions', due the principle of relativity (we cannot distinguish motion from form, so we see Earth as a still form, when it is a rotary motion) and their entangled relationships; as dimensions must be defined in co-invariant equations with each other. So once we realize how childish are the definitions mechanism does of time=motion, space=dimensional form and scale, we will define 5D metrics.*

The 1st dimensional motion of space-time (ab. Dimotion) humans measured was undoubtedly length, calculated through the steps of roughly a meter as a distance of space (dimensional, formal view) or Locomotion, (Time=motion view). But it would be the ONLY dimension of space to which humans ascribed a motion in time, which left limp our understanding of time till this date; when we still have only a dual space time dimotion, 'locomotion' or 'Ts' (where we capitalize the external motion of the system, in this case of an internal form, s, without motion)

The 2nd dimensional motion of height (form) or information (motion) was still shredded in mystery as it would need the discovery in China or Mesopotamia of the Pythagoras Theorem to have a proper metrics related to length. Since a *formalism of Dimensional motions of space-time needs to relate them in a co-invariant form. So the Pythagoras theorem connected X and its Perpendicular Y dimension of height, allowing the expansion of Greek Bidimensional Geometry. But as its motion in time, 'information' was ignored – height became orphan. Consider the screen you are reading, it has a height dimension, as a paper, so the product of X x Y gives you information.* The problem of the motion in time of height is that is a 'slower' time dimotion, connected to growth and evolution. So all species as they evolve they grow in information= height, from mammals that became humans to reptiles that became dinosaurs and birds, to matter that becomes the high tube to infinity of a black hole singularity. So the 'informative' function =motion of height is perceptive projective geometry of a high point, reason why heads, bankers, antennas and pulpits that command biologic, economic & cultural organisms are on top. If we named **Ts-locomotion** (external motion of a still 'point particle'), **Height-information is its inverse, St** (external form with internal motion, form-in-action, in-form-ation, as a TV screen where motion is within its image. Geometry gave height a 'motion of evolution of information', which was out of the comprehension of man's mind that had only the capacity to see time=motion=change in very short spans, related to its visual 'clock' of 1 glimpse a second, 1 thought a second, one step a second, one heart beat a second, which synchronized all the parts of its organisms to its time clock. All other different time clock speeds of nature were lost to him.

The 3rd dimension of width was known but unconnected to length and height – the cube problem unresolved – till modern times. So only 2 dimensions of space were formalized earlier in the History of thought by Greek Geometers and Logicians from Pythagoras to Aristotle, setting the foundations of knowledge for the following two millennia.

Then came Galileo who didn't understand Earth had both a dimension of **mental space=still form** and a motion in time due the logic postulate of relativity ('We cannot distinguish a state of motion from a state of form', Galileo, Einstein, Poincare). So we **see** Earth still but it is moving (e pur si muove, e pur no muove). *It was the first chance for mankind to understand the duality of dimensions of still mental space=form and true time=motion.* Galileo didn't go so far; instead with the 'monologic' of a single

Aristotelian cause, A->B, proper of human limited minds he chose that the Earth moved; while the Church chose it didn't move. But none explained both things together. He then associated the

A GALAXY HAS ITS INFORMATIVE, TALL SPHERIC CENTER IN A GRAVITATIONAL BLACK HOLE AND ITS ELECTROMAGNETIC ENERGY IN ITS STELLAR PLANE, SURROUNDED BY A MEMBRANE OF DARK MATTER.

ANIMALS & PLANTS HAVE INVERSE DIRECTIONS OF ENERGY & INFORMATION, SINCE PLANTS USE LIGHT AS ENERGY AND CHEMICAL PARTICLES AS INFORMATION WITH BRAINS IN THE ROOTS ANIMALS USE LIGHT AS INFORMATION AND EARTH TO MOVE BY ELECTRIC REPULSION AND MECHANIC GRAVITATION

dimension of 'time' locomotion, or 'speed' to the dimension of length, T_s . And he got its metric when he applied the mechanical clock to measure 'motions in space', defining a $v=s/t$ formula of Galilean Relativity, latter refined with a $-ct$ parameter by Einstein, who, following in the path of Riemann's dissertation of Non-Euclidean metrics, expressed the mental linguistic nature of Spaces as 'simultaneous measure relative to a frame of reference'. *Since stillness is a maya of the senses, as each mind creates a finitesimal still image of the Universe, self-centered in its Non-E 'fractal point of measure' that holds a world in itself (Leibniz's monads) So Ss-mind-languages stop and order Tt-entropic motions.*

Thus Humans are stuck with a single ts -spacetime dimotion, locomotion, corresponding to length; a metric for height as a space dimension without its motion of time, information, Pythagoras Theorem and a 3rd unconnected dimension of width, without its corresponding motion in time, 'reproduction'. It was a limited view of space=form, time=motion and its duality as dimensional motions of space-time. Yet human egocy (ego= idiocy) heralded those children of thought as the highest intelligences of the cosmos. So when Einstein, whose best definition of time was 'what the clock measures', died, 'Time' published a cartoon with a future Earth crossed with continental letters: 'Einstein was born here'.

But since humans don't associate to space dimensions its relative motions=actions in time, beyond locomotion, *the living functions of the 3 dimotions of space-time disappeared and with it the vitality and intelligence of the Universe, represented by the dimotion of height=informative perception & the dimotion of width, St (potential) + Ts (kinetic)= $S \Leftrightarrow T$: Energetic reproduction.* So in physics the duality of Momentum explained the constant trans-form-ation of one into another. While Heaviside connected the 2 dimotions of length and height with the width dimotion, with the co-invariant metric of vectorial cross product: $X \times Y = Z$. It is the law that creates the 1st perceived scale of information 'Euclidean, light space-time', evolved by 'warping', informing, by a $-ct$ parameter of electric height the $-E$ gravitational spacetime of General Relativity. So he could simplify the 20 equations of Maxwell into 4 and noticed the existence of gravitomagnetism, the first insight into the equivalence between the scales of atoms and galaxies. Width became with vectorial calculus a 'motion' of reproduction in Nature. C-speed = T_s -locomotion and the magnetic or electric field of relative height reproduce seemingly out of nothing the other relative width field. When a body reproduces cells, it packs them in the width dimension. And so we had 3 dimensions of space, connected by proper metrics (Pythagoras, cross product) and its functions =motions in time; locomotion connected to length; information connected to height and width connected to reproduction – *dimensions of space have vital functions in time constructing together ternary, topologic organisms – the fundamental particle of the living Universe.*

But humans made an even larger error regarding the substances of which we are all made, space=form and time=motion, when Newton confused a mathematical artifact with reality, thinking there was a space-time Cartesian graph with a single lineal time coordinates (that of locomotion=length) and two perpendicular spatial coordinates; taking space and time out of reality when it is obvious to experience that we, real beings, ARE made of finite vital space dimensions, the space we occupy with our bodies, and live through finite vital 'temporal motions', the time we last in existence, (Leibniz's view). *So a fractal generator equation describes all Nature's systems as combination of 3 space-time Dimotions:*

Ts-moving limbs/fields/territories <S ⇔ T reproductive ∅-body-wave-worker> St- informative particle/head/ruling class

QUANTIC MIND-WORLDS: HEIGHT DIMENSION

Besides human eye-worl(D)s the Universe has many i-planes of existence, dimensions & time arrows that quantic mind-species perceive with other languages=forces used to describe those EXT i-worlds:

Riemann Sphere $i=0$ 							
Projective Geometry	Electric Field	Molecular Boson	Glycine	DNA	Brain Axis	Antenna	Temporal Black Hole

SENSORIAL BRAIN SYSTEMS PLACED ON THE CENTER OR HEIGHT OF ANY ORGANISM USE LANGUAGES TO ABSORB I-n PIXELS THAT SCAN THE ENERGY ACTIONS AND TEMPORAL CYCLES OF ITS WORLD RELEVANT TO ITS SURVIVAL:

Reality is a tapestry of organisms made of Ts-limbs/fields that move a $\S\Upsilon$ -body/wave, guided by a St-high informative particle-head, in physical, biologic and social systems. Moreover the form of those 3 dimotions corresponds to the 3 only topologies (forms with motions) of spacetime: Ts=*l*-lineal limbs/fields, the geometry that moves faster between 2 points; St=*O*-spherical heads-particles, the geometry that stores maximal information; and $\S\Upsilon$ = hyperbolic, wide, \emptyset -bodywaves, the 'hour-glass' geometry that includes the other two, hence can reproduce both. We ARE living topologies.

RECAP. A thorough review of the 3 space dimensions ascribe 3 motions of time to them: locomotion to 'length'; information to height and reproduction to width, vitalizing space-time, by correcting Newton's error and showing that we are all ensembles of the 3 only topologies of a 5D Universe: $|xO=\emptyset$: Past-Motion x Future-Form = Present-Momentum

The fourth and fifth dimotions of seeds/minds and entropy-death, and the $\Delta\pm j$ scales of the fifth dimension

The metrics of all Dimensions of space-time are deceptively simple. $\sqrt{x^2+y^2}=C^2$ & $S_x \times S_y = S_z$ is the Pythagorean and vectorial metric of the 3 dimensions of space-time; $V=S/T$ with the $-c^2t^2$ ad on of Einstein is the metric of the so-called 4th dimension of time, in true form the time locomotion of length. $S \times T = \Delta\pm j$ is the metric of the scalar 5 dimensional motions of a spacetime supoerorganism, which states that the local speed of time of a superorganism is inversely to its size, but the product of both remains co-invariant. It means that smaller scales run faster cycles of time that encode the in-form-ation of the Universe in its frequency and form. Hence the equivalence of all species of all scales equaled by the same metric of spatial form x temporal motion (St-information or angular momentum and Ts-locomotion or lineal Momentum in layman and physical terms). As smaller species reproduce faster and survive better. So often they kill larger forms (as in the case of the present Coronavirus Pandemic, where a simpler 30 gene virus has put on his knees the entire human civilization). But mostly, 'energy scales' associate together. So faster, smaller scales code the information of larger ones (quantum particles with its numbers code atoms and molecules, genes code biological organisms and memes code social organisms). And this 'binding' of internal and external, potential energies used to express in 'derivative' time quanta, 'vital moments' combining $O+$ | angular and lineal momenta, tic after tic of our specific 5D time ratio, to perform the vital 'dimensional motions' of existence (Ss-perceiving>St-communicating information> $\S\Upsilon$ -reproducing>Ts-moving>Tt-feeding), is the vital pentalogic game of existence we all play.

The vital interactions between space-time species of different scales is either symbiotic in organic systems or predatory when scales are not entangled by fractal networks that connect the larger Δ_j whole that provides Potential energy to its $\Delta-j$ internal parts, which reproduce its information upwards. The fifth dimension thus has an scalar asymmetry and biological duality that forms organisms, even if humans have focused in the entropic Darwinian struggle for existence; not the social complex, organic symbiosis through fractal physiological networks of 'Energy and information' (layman terms for motion and form, we use often to avoid an excessive 'technical 5D' terminology – though the reader needs to interiorize the pentalogic entanglement of the 5 elements of reality in its kaleidoscopic mirror symmetries, Space=form, Time=motion, Scale=energy, Entropy=death, Mind=language, and understand its $\Delta=S=T>@$ -mind symmetries and entropic limits that structure the events and $|+O=\emptyset$ forms of reality. The laws of 5D are few but its entanglement requires a 'parallel' metaphoric way of thought different from monologic, $A>B$ present minds. It is the beauty of entanglement made of simultaneity in space, synchronicity in time, co-existence in scale.

This 1st glimpse to 5D metrics shows the importance of a new formal dimension of spacetime in all stiences. *Mathematics* from the Greeks to renaissance, all the science of physics, and the r=evolution of all sciences that those papers imply depart from such humble 'metric' beginnings. For it to happen an extraordinary effort of conceptual, logic thought that stretches to all other foundational elements of science is required; normally the work of a single mind in the beginning, as in the case of Galileo and Einstein or the eclectic gathering of several generations of thought into a strict formal discourse, as in the case of Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic in Greek Science. This work is both, because the 5th dimension has been among us for centuries of modern science, but never explained in the interrelationships between the different scales of the Universe, each one described by a stience. So we bring together all that work to extract the common=isomorphic laws between scales.

The EXTERNAL and internal dimotions of Space=Form and Time=motion. Pentalogic

Regardless of human dexterity as 'homunculus enzyman' (a species able to ensemble things with its hands, and evolve machines of metal of a higher density that without our help would never reach organic form), one theme that surfaces

constantly in those texts is the astounding lack of common sense and rational thought in our models of reality, departing from so obvious false postulates (from big bang theory and other simplex entropic models of natural sciences to the triad of historic idol-ogies of metal, nationalism, capitalism and mechanism, to the anthropomorphic egocy (ego=idiocy) of religions. But none of those blunders compares with Newton's egocy declaring that space and time were NOT the substance of reality as Leibniz explained but a 'Cartesian frame of reference' God had drawn behind the Universe as he was using one to draw his planetary orbits and obviously he was a god-like man. 500 years of primitive thinking in all sciences derives from this blunder. Fact is reality has 5 Dimensional motions of spacetime to play with at local level and construct the superorganisms that trace worldcycles of spacetime through scales of the fifth dimension in the 'game of existence', we all play – what is all about. 'Simplicity is genius' (Leonardo); 'I want to know the thoughts of God, the rest are details'. Einstein. The thoughts of God are space dimensions and its parallel time motion and we all are the details constructed with them. The correction of Newton's error transforms lineal time measures into ∞ cyclical time clocks, ordered through scales by 5D Metrics. And it makes all beings a combination of 'Space=information and time=Momentum, motions'. As all 5D dimensions of space=form do always have content of time=motion, by the Principle of Relativity: 'we cannot distinguish a state of (time) motion from a still state (of space form)' (Poincare) we can distinguish according to t,s, internal or T, S EXTERNAL of T or t-motion and S or s form, 6 dimotional combinations of states of space-time:

- Ss**-language which stops EXTERNAL MOTION or imagines the future game of existence, as a mind of the Universe.
 - St**-information; a still organism with internal motion, as when we sleep or think or the image motion of a still Tv Set.
 - Ts**-locomotion, a system moving externally but internally in a rigid state, as a particle-point with a gravity center.
 - St⇔Ts: §||**-Hyperbolic Bodywaves that combine O+| Momenta, Δ-i internal and Δ+i potential energy to reproduce the whole.
 - Tt**-entropy, a system with internal and external motion, hence becoming disordered=dying.
 - st**: the being in-itself isolated from the external world as a mind mirror of **ST**, the world isolated from the being.
- S&T interactions defines *the bare minimum logic*, dilogic systems as the basic mode of existence. That is, $A \neq B$ but rather $S \Leftrightarrow T$. Space and time merge with different degrees of hierarchical complementarity to form all what exists from gender to organisms.

Nt. Max. SxT: s=t. It is a present balanced age of Max. Momentum or classic age of 'life', when Ts-motion and St- *come together*. we use a dual Ss:§ and dual Tt:|| to express that present dynamic form, also $S \Leftrightarrow T$; or the equation, T-past • S-Future = Present; as a combination of dimotions into tetralogic elements, 4 genetic letters, 4 quantum numbers, 4 drives of existence denied by entropy, is the essence of the game. As for the meanings of Energy, Space, Time, Momentum, Scale, present, past and future, we have the problem of language errors.

RECAP. The interaction of external and internal form and motion between an ST-organism, its inner Δ-1 parts and outer Δ+1 world efines the main events of reality. Form has topological dimensions, which can be 1, 2,3 as all 'fractal points' are volumes that fit Energy and information (5-E Postulate). If perceived in time they are motion.

RECAP. The Universe is a nested 'superorganism' of space=form/information and time=motion. All what you see around are forms with motion. Physics rightly understood we cannot distinguish both (Principle of relativity) but *didn't pursuit its obvious implication: All is a composite of form=space and motion=time, so we are made as Leibniz wanted of clocks of time and vital spaces*. Instead it took Newton's view that 'God' had put us all in his 'plenum=body', made with a Cartesian mathematical artifact, hence with a single 'lineal time clock' and a single 'space-continuum'. Because the errors of mechanism, since Newton, regarding the nature of time and space, the substances of which we are all made, have so much influenced all sciences and the view mankind has of the Universe, before the analysis of each specific science in each paper-book of this 'encyclopedia of 5D 'stiences', we need to offer a condensed summary of the Laws of space dimensions and time motions

Inner and outer motions and forms. Vacuum time: the ultimate substance of reality.

Look around you, all what you see are 'space-forms' with 'time-motion'. We are all space-time, forms in motion, 'in-form-motion', 'information', forms in action; play with the words of what you are.

Tt: internal and external motion or 'entropy' is one extreme, which brings death. That is the state of mankind today, caused by the fact the new species, machines move faster externally (cars, weapons) and internally 'metal-minds', visual images accelerate, disordering humans into a permanent ADD state. So millennials move fast and have disordered minds. At the end of that process entropy kills. Vacuum Time with no mental spatial form is the ultimate substance of reality to which all returns, from where all departs; but the purpose of all existences is creating information with it; forms in action, 'cyclical vortices of active form' exactly the reverse of what 4D physicists think the Universe is, stuck on a 'solid' view of particles.

In the extreme of absolute no motion, there are Ss, mind languages that perceive in themselves or seeds of still information. A being in the state of seed or perception doesn't move. The hypothetical Mind of God is such a being, because it perceives all what has existed, exists and will exist and repeat itself eternally as a block of time - a zero sum of fluctuations of the game of existence in space and time.

Conservation of space, scale & time laws. The relationship of the 5th dimension with energy.

It is all about 2 S&T parameters. *Because all systems are in an external larger world, we can then consider them either to have 'external or internal motion or form'; and WE CAPITALIZE THE LARGER OUTER WORLD. So we can combine EXTERNAL and internal motion and form with both 5 canonical combinations, which correspond to the 5 fractal S-Dimensional T-motions of Space and Time. As all beings will have a bit of both. So they are always messed up* in practical terms is often easier to measure a mixture of both. So we talk of still forms with internal motion, we call '**information**', **sT**; and motions with a EXTERNAL still form, we call Locomotion, **Ts**, and beings that ex=change between both states, as *there is no 'yin (information)' without yang (motion).*

*This intermediate present state is \emptyset -momentum; they key element of physical reality that merges both and in physics is in fact parted into |-momentum and O-momentum, though as Kepler already noticed both are mixed, since a line is often just part of a huge curve. Finally we call the pure absolute inner and outer motion without form, **Tt, entropy**; and the absolute inner and outer form without motion, **Ss, language. Reality** is more complex but as we increase those combinations of space=form and time=motion and understand that all is about changes between them inside and outside the being; either trying to balance both in present \emptyset -momentums or changing it through 'energy scales'; the extraordinary importance of understanding the first principles of reality will become more obvious.*

The 5th Dimension of scalar space-time is closely related to Energy, the parameter humans expanded painstakingly to mimic the 'flows of space=form and time=motion' that travel through the 5th dimension, even without a clear conceptual definition of it. Now we can simply state that energy is 'Space-time' traveling though 5D according to its metrics equations, which conserve (maintain co-invariant) the volume of energy (space-time) of the Universe, both between scales as Δ -energy and in each scale as Lineal time-momentum and angular space-momentum. So the 3 conserved quantities of physics become the 3 qualitative elements of the 5D Universe: Δ ST. Energy is both *in equations and common talk the 5D spacetime an organism takes from its 3 $\Delta\pm j$ scales of existence that powers, delivered in discontinuous Tf 'derivative quanta of forces the present moment(um)s', whose actions=dimensional motions of survival are the stuff of which existence is made. Let us then study in greater detail those pentalogic actions*Space, Time and scale create reality, but languages are synoptic mirrors that have the advantage of 'overcoming' the limits of perception of Absolute relativity, so they can 'imagine' what we cannot perceive simultaneously through 'equalities' and 'verbs'=actions that peg S and T, names and objects, in equations and verbal sentences. The extraordinary synoptic capacity of languages that expel motion, simplify form, put in relationship scales and extract higher laws that perception and action alone cannot is what gives them power to then project its imagination and recreate a better reality. So how languages improve by synoptic methods reality, from palingenesis in genetics to mathematical projections to verbal actions is an important part of 45D but not the whole.

The reader should be more of a gradualist and love the shadows of grey, between Ss-minds and Tt-entropy. It is in the middle golden mean of 'moment(um)s' of existence, made of internal angular Momentum=information, and external lineal

momentums, related to its internal Δ -j energy, and external $\Delta+1$ potential one given by the position of the being, in the whole where the subtle details of physics are to be found. The Universe is entangled, complex despite its simple first 3 elements, time-motions of two types, cyclical that appears as form in space, and lineal, structured as cyclical vortices bore down into deeper scales, and mirrors shrink into still forms, and project into larger scales, into organic $\Delta\pm j$ 5D systems, because every point 'holds a world in itself' (Leibniz on non-Euclidean fractal worlds). There will be a huge number of humans too simple and dogmatic to access the subtle interplay of those 5 elements, Δ -scales of space=form and time-motion, mirrored in still mind-languages or exploited in entropic death. But we provide as the Universe does with multiple equivalent languages to express that pentalogic, the easiest one, that which combines dimensions of spatial form, S and temporal motion, T, in the internal and external entanglement of beings as Ss-minds, St-information (angular momentum) Ts-locomotion (lineal momentum) Δ -energy scales and Tt-entropic outer and inner motion that disorders the being. *After 30 years of using together in my parallel 'schizoid' mind (: all the languages, I have come to the conclusion that those 5 combinations and the original topological language I first discovered of |-limbs/fields of motions, O-heads/particles of information and \emptyset -waves/bodies of reproduction, ARE the simplest, best, more encompassing ones. So those 3 languages, the 3 varieties of $|xO=\emptyset$ -Topology, the EXTERNAL and internal combinations of form and motion (space and time) and the 5 separated elements studied as 'concepts', space=form, time=motion, scale=energy, entropy=death, mind= language is what the reader must first understand. Once it does FOR ALL STIENCES, each one studying a scale of space-time; this simple scaffolding of first principles, will guide him through every other stience, and jargon.*

So in EXTERNAL and internal Space-time form-motion terms we can establish a gradation of combined space-time dualities, **Ss<St<§T<st<Tt**, with a symbol < for an increase of motion over form, departing from the 'dimotion of entropy or past dimotion of death' as it erases information, devolving a system to simpler forms; and vice versa, an inverse dimotion, **Tt>st>§T>St>Ss**, with the symbol > of an increase of form over motion, or 'dimotion of in-form-ation, the 'future dimotion' of life' as it increases information – an arbitrary choice opposed to that of physicists of entropic weapons that subconsciously chose entropy=eath as the future due to its worldly profession. We DO side against the present mechanical culture of death with life in all stiences, notably in economics (we side with the 90% of mankind) and physics (we side with information). It then becomes evident that the intermediate state, §T, with a balanced quantity of Spatial information and temporal Motion, S=T, is the 'state of present', that doesn't seem to change as it is a balance of form and motion; but it is always a dynamic state. *So it is the more complex to describe as we don't have a single word. It is both the sum of angular and lineal momentum, |+O; so we use \emptyset as its symbol in topologic forms. It is also the convergence of the Δ -j entropic internal energies from lower scales and the effects of outer larger potential energies from our $\Delta+j$ wholes, so they come from down and up, into our $\Delta 0$ -scale, which we write as $\Delta\emptyset$ often, to match $o=\emptyset$; it is then a π cycle that opens and closes its mouth in dynamic exchange between reproductive waves of Ts-locomotion and particles of St-information. We write it as $S \leftrightarrow T$, $S=T$, or doubling both symbols, §T; we call it momentum but often also $\Delta\emptyset$ -energy. This present liquid st-ate, mature classic st-age, which is also the equation of 'harmony and beauty', this golden mean we seek for, we live through each of its moments, will then to keep in parallel with the fluctuating dynamic variation of its SHM, harmonic motions, be expressed with all that range of wordings, ' \emptyset -momentum', $\Delta\emptyset$ -energy, §T-dimotion... but likely the best way to define it is as existential momentum, because life consists in going through each of our $O+|$, $S \leftrightarrow T$ momenta, always trying to combine motion and form to create those existential quanta of which life is made, and apply our $\Delta\pm j$ energies to our 5 Dimotions of existjence. The game of existjence then is defined in its subtle variation for all beings with that pentalogic to which we add the duality of the st-inner being and the ST-outer world (heptalogic) and then we double through 'bilateral' decalogic systems, leaning towards one or the other side (networks of organisms), and slowly through new decouplings and trinity diversifications, in $|xO=\emptyset$, $Ts>\S T>St$ ages and $\Delta\pm j$ sub-scales, reality branches, unfolds and grows in creative diversity. But \emptyset is the preferred state for any system of spacetime in the Universe, akin to the concept of 'beauty' (balance between cyclical forms and lineal motions), of reproduction and creative communication (as it brings together the two poles of reality merging and combining them). All systems seek this state. So in physics we find it akin to the state of 'minimal Momentum' of more form' in which most particles like to remain; in biology is akin to the age between adolescence of maximal Motion and the 3rd age of maximal information, or age of reproduction, in which most people like to live.*

RECAP. Reality IS a fractal system made of topologic organisms co-existing in scales of space % cyclic time that close its 'internal vital point content' with the entropic limit of those time cycles, in its vital territorial body-waves, synchronized symbiotically by 5D metrics. As we are all $-\Delta@St$; dust of space-time. *Departing from those 5Dimotions, the Universe builds all systems of reality.*

A year:
Cycle of existence of the Earth respect to the sun

WORLD CYCLES OF TIME. THE TEMPORAL VIEW.

“Leibniz is right. There are infinite time clocks in the Universe, but if so we have to restart science from its foundations’. *Einstein*, on the infinite relational time cycles of reality.

A Universe of ∞ time clocks of different size and speed differs from its human description with a single mechanical clock-time to which all time clocks of the

universe are equalized, elongated into a lineal 'second-minute-hour-day-year' system of equalized time clocks (of light waves, mechanical clocks, earth's astronomical clocks). As Galilean physics, born of ballistics, simplified the nature of cycles of time-space into lineal durations, to measure best the locomotions of cannonballs:

Time is cyclical, all clocks of time and laws of science are based in the cyclical patterns of nature. But physicists developed ballistics before understanding cyclical time so they postulated a lineal inertia, and a single entropic dimotion of time, and when this was applied to other sciences, many lost their capacity to understand the future which will repeat the causality of the past.

Lineal & cyclic time render the same functions as one is the inverse of the other, measured by frequency, $T=1/f$, but the philosophical implications of cyclic time are enormous, as we regain the in-form-ation provided by those cycles, *origin of the laws of science, which would not exist if there were not cyclical patterns*. The most important of them being, the fact that *a time cycle breaks reality (1st knot theorem) in an outer and inner region, creating a membrane that encloses a vital space, the 'substance of which we are all made'.*

Jordan's knot theorem breaks reality in an inner vital Energy-space and an outer membrane of angular momentum focused in a 0ε =center that establishes 3 parts of reality: an open \S energy ball controlled by an $S_s>S_t$ mind and a $T_s<T_t$ entropic border.

There are 2 time forms, long lineal Time and short frequency steps we integrate into the larger whole; because *there are 2 $\pm j$ scales of 5D reality whose metric, $\S x\delta=\Delta\pm j$ defines larger space systems as having slower time cycles*. So we can always consider the frequency of time the $\Delta-j$ 'quanta of time' or 'finitesimal derivative' of the larger whole represented with the concept of lineal time; as in the classic formula, $S=f(t) \lambda(s)$. The whole Space can be measured, $Vt=S$ with lineal time as a single unit, or it can be measured as a sum of frequency steps, with more detail. But if we see those 2 'forms' of time, as 'lineal Momentum and cyclical information', since information is stored in the frequency and form of time cycles, we can then consider that 'time=motion' splits in two essential forms, lineal motion or 'Momentum', and cyclical motion or 'information', and express the main law of science, the principle of conservation of Momentum in terms of the conservation of time=motion in its two varieties that transform each other ad eternal:

'All what exists are time motions that transform between lineal open and cyclic closed forms ad eternal: $S_i \Leftrightarrow T_e$ '

This sentence is the simplest expression reality as a constant game of transformation of 'spatial information' (cyclical time) and temporal Momentum (lineal time) and was first understood by Taoism, where 'Tao=time', is composed of yin=cyclical form and yang=lineal Momentum, today expressed as the principle of conservation of Momentum. Its 'mathematical, logic' formula is $S_i \Leftrightarrow T_e$ & and its logic form, $exi=st$, is the function of existence.

RECAP. Cyclical time defines mathematically a non-Euclidean fractal point, as points are 'minimal cycles' of space-time, crossed by a relative infinite number of parallel forces that carry the Energy and information to the inner point. A cycle breaks spacetime into an internal and external part (Jordan's 1st knot theorem).

Ss:Yin+ Tt:Yang= \S Qi All Dimotions

Lao Zi

Aristotle

Ts:Locomotion St: Perception $\Delta\pm j$: Analysis \S I: Reproduction Tt: Entropy Ts:Locomotion All Dimotions

XVI Galileo

XVII: Descartes

XVIII: Leibniz

XIX: Darwin

XIX: Clausius

XX: Einstein

XXI: 5D time theorist

THE GENERATIONAL=LIFE CYCLE: $\Delta_{-1} < Ts > ST > St \ll TT_{\Delta-2}$

SUPER-ORGANISMS D=EVOLVE BETWEEN 3 i-PLANES OF EXISTENCE IN 3+1 AGES DOMINATED BY ITS ENERGY, REPRODUCTIVE AND INFORMATIVE NETWORKS:

Birth: $St_{\Delta-1} < Youth: Ts > Maturity: ST_{\Delta} > Old age: St \ll Death: TT_{\Delta-2}$

Human Socio-Biological Organisms:

Individual, living organism

EPIC, LINEAL ART CLASSIC, REALIST ART. BAROQUE, FORMAL ART WAR

Culture, Nation, God

$\Delta=6$
 SPECIES:

HISTORIC CIVILINATIONS & SPECIES ARE SUPERORGANISMS OF EARTH'S 3 AGES:
 GAIA > HISTORY > METAL-EARTH
 IMMORTAL HISTORY REVERSES ITS CYCLE:
 GAIA < HISTORY < METAL-EARTH

CONCEPTION AS A BLACK HOLE OF MIN. SIZE = MAX. INFORMATION

REPRODUCTIVE MATURITY: III AGE: GROWTH IN HEIGHT=INFORMATION

Universal, Physical, Organisms:

Birth: $St_{\Delta-1} < Youth: Ts > Maturity: ST_{\Delta} > Old age: St \ll Death: TT_{\Delta-2}$

Plasma Birth Energetic Gas Liquid, Reproductive State Solid, informative state, M=E death

STATES OF MATTER

Birth: $St_{\Delta-1} < Youth: Ts > Maturity: ST_{\Delta} > Old age: St \ll Death: TT_{\Delta-2}$

Energetic Birth Irregular galaxy Spiral State Informative, Globular Age Quasar Death

GALAXIES

ITS SEQUENTIAL WORLDCYCLES TRAVELS THROUGH 5D SCALES.

We define life=existence as a journey through 5 Dimensions of space-time. In the graph, the worldcycle of Existence of a space-time organism, develops as a feedback function, $S \leftrightarrow T$, in 3 sequential phases/ages /horizons: Max. $T \times \text{Min. } S$ (youth); Max. $S \times T$ ($s=t$); Max. $S \times \text{Min. } T$ (3rd age), between $S_s \times \epsilon_0 T$ (seed in the lower plane, $i-1$) and $T_t \times 0 \epsilon S$ (entropy=death):

$\Delta-1 \rightarrow \Delta^0$: S_s . A supærganism worldcycle starts its existjence as a seed of form.

T>s (Ts): In its first horizon or 'energetic, young age' limbs/fields of Ts-motion dominate:, max.Ts x min. St. The being has just be born, and its 'energy'

Max. SxT: s=t. It is the present balanced age of maximal \emptyset -momentum or classic age of 'life', when Ts-motion and St-information are in balance also as 'genders', reproducing the whole, ensuring its immortality through reproduction.

Max. St x min. Ts: 3rd age of the information that warps and exhausts the Momentum of the system.

$\Delta^0 \leftarrow \Delta-1$: OS x Tt: It is the end or death of the cycle that reverses its form and becomes Entropy again.

The graph is the most important 'image' of stience ever, because the worldcycle of 'existjence' includes everything and we shall be able to model in a reasoned way all what exists on the basis of pentalogic. We are thoughts of God, *the game of spacetime existjence in all its 'scales' each one studie by a stjence, and we are all jts details. Can you man up and entangle with the whole Universe, feel dissolved as part of that ∞ game, of absolute, objective relativity? Only then you will be=come a stientist.*

The 3 ages of existence of space-time organisms. Its 2 worldcycles and Metric functions.

So we marry the 3 vital functions=motions of time and the 3 dimensions of space, either in 1 or 2D (height= spherical information, length=planar locomotion, width=hyperbolic reproduction) which merge in all Time-space Beings; and dominate one of the 3 ages of its life-death worldcycles, the past, young age of limbic entropic motions, the mature reproductive age dominated by the hyperbolic body/wave and the 3rd age dominated by the informative particle-head, when the illusion of time ends with an entropic big-bang death that dissolves the being into its 'scalar cellular, atomic parts', which lead us to the realization that time cycles NOT only return to its origin in a single spacetime continuum but they move up and down 5D scales.

Existence is an α (ab. relative infinite, with an entropic limit of death) sum of 3 space/time planes, fluctuating between birth and extinction through those 3 phases or ages. The 3 ages of Timespace supærganisms happen in all systems, including mental languages:

In Physics they are, T-gas, the moving state, $S_i = T_e$ liquid, the balanced state and S-solid the informative state; into Cosmology, where it describes the Universe as a space-time system that fluctuates between both limits, a form of pure time, the singularity ($\text{min. } t \times \text{max. } S$) and a form of pure space, the big- bang ($\text{max. } S \times \text{min. } t$):

In Biology, they are the 3 ages of living beings AND the 3 horizons of evolution of species.

In social organisms, through the subconscious collective mind of civilizations which in art styles mimic in a longer 800 year cycle of life and death of civilizations (according to 5D metrics a human social supærganism is larger in space – a nation, culture, religion – and so it lives longer in time).

All what exists is a supærganism of vital space tracing a 0-sum worldcycle of time through 3 scales of the 5th dimension: Born as a seed of fast time cycles in a lower 5D scale ($\Delta-1$:Max. $T \times \text{Min. } S$), emerging as an organism in Δ_0 , living 3 ages of increasing information, as its time clocks slow down in its $\Delta+1$ world to die in a time quanta back to $\Delta-1$. Yet the maximal point $S_i = T_e$ where reproduction happens defines the classic age, maturity, beauty, balance, survival of the system, all disomorphic jargons.

The 3 ages of life emerge in human social supærganisms as the 3 ages of cultures and its 3 artistic styles: Min.S x Max. T (infantile epic, lineal art, as in Trecento, Greek Kuroi; $S_i = T_e$; balanced beauty, when form and size are in balance, the classic mature age; and Max. S x Min. T: baroque, 3rd age of a civilization, whose subconscious mind is the art of its 'neuronal artists', the age of maximal form and an Δ_{st} for a no future, which is the age of war and death of cultures).

We talk of 3 $\Delta \pm 1$ scales of worldcycles as the being live in a placenta, then emerges as organism in a world:

p: 0-1: its paligenetic o-1 social evolution in the accelerated time sphere of existence, till becoming 1 (0-1 bounded unit circle in logic mathematics; quantum probability sphere of particles in physical systems; paligenetic fetal age in biologic systems; 0-9 memetic learning childhood in social systems). It is the highly ordered world cycle as a 'placental mother-energy world' is nurturing as memorial cyclical spacetime has erased errors of previous generations. It is the shorter more informative 'space-like' cycle, with a fast 'present' speed.

- λ, Δ : **The existential 1- ∞ lifecycle**, in which it will deploy its 2nd world cycle of existence in an environment which is open, entropic (1- ∞ hyperbolic unbounded Cartesian plane in logic mathematics; thermodynamic entropic statistical molecular populations in physics; Darwinian struggle between populations in biology; idol-ogic dog-eat-dog capitalist, nationalist competitive eco(nomic)systems in the super organisms of history. In this 1- ∞ existence the world cycle is not ensured to continue, as the entropy of the world system can cut it off. It is the open, single plane, more important worldcycle, with an 'open', free 'feeling to it'. The life cycle, though is part of:

ω, Ω : A larger, longer Transcendental worldcycle proper of the highest social scale $\Delta+1$, **the omega** of its smaller parts – where it performs 5 survival actions through $\Delta\pm 4$ Planes self-centered in its mind, beyond which it cannot longer perceive, to become if successful a new sup ∞ organism of the infinite planes of God, the game of existence.

In graph, physical, biologic & social worldcycles show to which extent 5D laws enlighten our understanding of reality. Matter States are physical time ages, from left pure solid, crystal, $\$$ top state, to an even more solid $\Delta+1$ boson condensate, etc. We see that systems either move a step at a time within a plane of existence (gas, liquid, solid) or they can jump « two states at once, (as in the case sublimation) within that plane, or most often between two planes, as in « scattering & entropic death), to become a different Dimotional state. We can then see how the fundamental elements of 5D time appear on the graph: the worldcycle is local and complete. There are 2 inverse arrows from an entropic past (plasma), in a lower plane (ion particles) to the 3 ages of the matter states with increasing form (gas to solid), to end in a higher plane of existence as a boson-Einstein condensate. Do those worldcycles happen for the whole Universe? (cyclic big-bang). Unlikely...

An interesting element of local cyclical time is the existence of 'travels to the past', from a faster informative cycle, which arrives therefore in relative present time of a 'quantum' of existence. I.e. an antiparticle in a Feynman diagram, a seminal seed, a relative past consciousness in the sexual act, a prophet, which seems to perceive the death in the future of a civilization, its last $\Delta-1$ generation... and we will return to that. In graph, physical, biologic & social worldcycles show to which extent 5D laws enlighten our understanding of reality. Matter States are physical time ages, from left pure solid, crystal, $\$$ top state, to an even more solid $\Delta+1$ boson condensate, etc. We see that systems either move a step at a time within a plane of existence (gas, liquid, solid) or they can jump « two states at once, (as in the case sublimation) within that plane, or most often between two planes, as in « scattering & entropic death), to become a different Dimotional state. We can then see how the fundamental elements of 5D time appear on the graph: the worldcycle is local and complete. There are 2 inverse arrows from an entropic past (plasma), in a lower plane (ion particles) to the 3 ages of the matter states with increasing form (gas to solid), to end in a higher plane of existence as a boson-Einstein condensate. Do those worldcycles happen for the whole Universe? (cyclic big-bang). Unlikely...

RECAP. *Existence is a travel of a spacetime sup ∞ organism, enacting its Dimensional motions through 5D scales.* We depart from a 5D spacetime simple metric equation: $SxT=\Delta\pm j$, which proves the organic network structure of the Universe; as its ultimate cause is the fact that '3 consecutive scales' of 5D, form a sup ∞ organism. We shall call them the $\Delta-1$ (atomic, cellular, individual in physical, biological and social systems), the $\Delta\emptyset$ scale that defines the networks (physiological St-Ts- $\$$ TJ networks of information, motion and energy, of gravitational, electromagnetic chemical and linguistic financial and study the main particle of reality: the 5D sup ∞ organism of spacetime networks.

Time is cyclical as all time clocks return to its point of origin, so all time cycles including those of life of its vital space-time beings are finite. Further on those time cycles break 'space' into inner and outer parts, so vital space is broken by the membranes and angular momentums of those time cycles that make spacetime beings also finite in spatial information. And an obvious experimental facts about timespace: cycles of time, vital spaces and the species made of them, co-exist in several scales of relative size from particles to galaxies, each one with clocks of time of different speeds. So spacetime is fractal broken in scales that added create a new 5th dimension of spacetime. The metrics of 5D and its scales, $SxT=C$ & and the balance between form

and motion, $SI=TE$, develops in 3 ages with 3 standing points, a max. point of existence, $Si=Te$ or mature age, a young age of $Max. T=$ motion, and an old age of $Max. S=$ information; between birth in $\Delta-1$ Form & $T=$ entropic death. The search for space-time, Energy=information balances in a classic reproductive age of conserved time is thus the goal of all existences, but only the whole achieves the immortality of time-space, as we

shall see egocentric errors of fractal mind-points of space trying to stop the flow of time from a single selfish point of view, accelerates the imbalance that brings death equations. We are richer in our still property at that OT-moment, when all is quiet so for time to keep moving, a reversal of entropy takes place.

Curve of existence as a bilateral symmetry.

The 5 Stages of a function of existence are formalized by 'pentalogic', which we also call existential algebra, because of the similarities we will find between the symbolism of ΔST and the operands of algebra.

All languages and disciplines of science turn in fact around the previous pentalogic graph, expressed in the bell curve above in terms of the amount of space=information and time=motion a system has through those 5 Stages, which all systems walk through its actions, which are 'steps' that change the S & T parameters of systems from youth, dominated by $Ts=$ locomotion to maturity, the reproductive $TS=$ age, to a 3rd age dominated by $St=$ actions and then as Momentum becomes spent in a sudden fast dual motion, from St to Ss , the moment of linguistic stillness and death to $\ll Tt$ in a dual reversal of death: In the first phase, corresponding to the paligenetic age of placental Momentum the ratio of change (derivative) has the absolute maximal e^x , which is its own derivative. In its 2nd phase it diminishes to the minimal $1/x$ the log derivative, which is the definition of an infinitesimal part; till in the 3rd phase it will start a bilateral symmetric inverse function of decay with $-1/x$ diminution and a fast collapse in the 4th phase of a 3rd age and final death moment. So the combination of \pm exponentials and logarithmic curves are also the best way to graph as a bell curve the worldcycle of existence as a 'composite' of a \pm exponential and logarithmic $O\epsilon$ -sum.

As any student knows there is an intimate relationship between the exponential and the sinusoidal by way of Euler's formula in the realm of complex numbers, which we treated briefly in theory of numbers.

So sinusoidal bell curve functions represent a worldcycle, though the symmetry is broken in the moment of entropic death when the collapse is extreme in a 'falling line' as death happens in a single moment of time:

$$4D \gg \Delta-1(\text{seed}) \sum \Delta: | -\$T(\text{limb-field}) < \emptyset - S \approx T (\text{iterative bodywave}) > O - \$\delta (\text{particle-head}) \ll 5D \Delta-1(\text{death})$$

This universal mandate, expressed in any language, from 'grow and multiply' to the conservation of $St=$ angular momentum, $Ts=$ locomotion and $S=T$ potential Momentum, to the behavior of superorganisms that constantly switch between space and time states, moving and sleeping, outward and inward orientations expresses as entropic limits of any existence, the larger nested Universe that tries to achieve its function of existence by limiting that of its inner parts. In fact it builds and selects its inner parts to maximize its function of existence, which often means their death as in Earth III, the metal-earth, which further evolves the planet but seems to condemn mankind to extinction.

Species also evolve in $3 \pm j$ ages; notice that particles perform 5 Dimotions=actions, which biologists call the 'drives of life'. Even nations as superorganisms of human beings and biological systems are structured in simultaneous spaces by 'networks' and systems that help them to $Ts=$ move, feed on entropic $Tt > \$T$ -Momentum, reproduce, $St=$ inform and evolve socially into $\Delta+1$ larger wholes through a common $Ss=$ language of information.

THE WORLDCYCLE OF MATTER: PARTICLES AND ITS LANGUAGES OF COMMUNICATION: STRONG AND ELECTRONIC FORCES.

4D ignores worldcycles as space-time travel reduces to 1 scale & dimotion; Ts-locomotion. What is space=form & time=motion, the 2 substances of which all those supœrganisms are made, is not understood because of a bigger physical error that has fogged human science for 400 years, since physicists sided with Newton's absolute space-time (a single lineal clock for the entire Universe) when reality has sided with Leibniz's infinite time clocks and relational=fractal spaces. That is, we are NOT placed in an abstract mathematical Cartesian graph of space-time (the error of Newton, who confused the 'mathematical artifact with reality as today quantum physicists confuse reality with its probability equations), but we are made of 'Time=motion, kinetic Momentum' and 'space=form, information'. Look around you all what you see is 'forms of space' moving in time. 'Leibniz is right but if so we have to start physics from scratch' (Einstein); which is what 5D does.

Time means motion is the ultimate substance of life understood as the interaction of the 5 'possible dimotions' combinations of the S-tate of spatial form and sT-ates of motion.

As the Universe is a living organism, gifted with a body, and a mind, logos (Plato), of a higher logic than man (Augustine); the non-Euclidean, Non-Aristotelian pentalogic of points with parts, crossed by ∞ parallels of $S\approx T$ -Momentum and St-information that evolve together into social wholes, and perform the 5 dimotions of life.

But what is life? As defined in any book of biology life is any form that follows the 5 dimensions or drives of existence, which happen to be *exactly the 5 Dimensional motions of space-time, ab. dimotions of the Universe:*

-Ss: Life perceives form; St-life processes information; $S\approx T$ -life reproduces, Ts-life moves, Tt-life feeds entropically.

Life starts in the Universe particles, St-quarks of maximal density of information and Ts-electrons of maximal motion, which become the 2 1st genders that come together into St+Ts= $S\approx T$ -atoms balanced in an eternal present as an immortal species.

The minimal particle-points, photons, electrons & quarks that construct all other systems of our Universe show the 5 organic dimotions (time motions with dimensional, spatial form) that define 'classic life' in biology – where they are call 'drives' of life, and we have defined: they gauge information - reason why quantum physics is a 'gauge theory', feed on Momentum (quantum jumps) absorbing smaller $\Delta-1$ particles, reproducing new clone particles, move and evolve socially through magnetic fields into larger wholes (atoms). In the graph, a quark reproduces itself.

Hence the minimal units of life of our vital, organic, fractal, scalar Universe of multiple timespace organisms are particles. And we shall study them as with any other biologic system, with all the languages of mankind, the best S-patial mathematical language; the best T-emporal language causal verb and its best $S\approx T$ -mixture –visual languages. The Universality of the game of existjence then becomes determined by the fact the minimal units of life are the smallest forms we perceive.

The worldcycles of matter. Conservation principles. Angular Momentum metric. Motion as reproduction of form. Relativity.

In physics a key element of the worldcycle comes into full power: the fact that all local cycles of time can move to the past by reversing its evolution of information, which in biological systems dominated by nervous informative networks cannot (but they can happen in smaller systems, such as bacteria with cyclical RNA that are immortal as they reproduce its information)

So worldcycles of matter are embedded in the principles of 'conservation of energy-momentum', the dual equation of transformation of lineal into cyclical motion $E(T)\Leftrightarrow M(S)$ in different physical scales, from Beta Decay to quasars, and the Theomodynamic cycles of physical energy between the poles of Tt-entropy and Ss-crystal images.

In scale we talk of 3 scalar superorganisms, made of $\Delta-1$ forces=dimotions, $\Delta\emptyset$ lineal and cyclical 'body-head' momentum and $\Delta+1$ potential and kinetic energy developed in an external scalar world. So the 3 laws of conservation of O-formal angular momentum, $|-$ lineal momentum and $\Delta\pm j$ scalar energy and its constant transformation into each other define the worldcycles of physics. 5D Metric show in the laws of vortices and angular momentum that increase their speed in smaller scales as systems shrink in lineal size. *The principle of relativity – we cannot distinguish form from motion is essential to define 'dimensional motions' of space-time, as all forms have inner cyclical, angular motion, equivalent to 'space' and lineal motion=Time.*

So the principle of relativity in 5D states: 'all what exists has motion and form'. The principle of conservation states: 'All energy transforms between lineal and cyclical motion'. And further on, lineal motion is considered reproduction of information in a

lower scale, without 'persistence' of memory; that is, as the system in 'wave-mode' reproduces information and emerges in our Δ^0 scale as a particle with momentum it moves in our perceived plane. Many results derived of this solution to Zeno's paradox will illuminate further both classic and quantum mechanics. But here, we shall just refer to the necessary correction of the Philosophy of science of physics, in its 'entropic thermodynamic and big-bang theories' and expand a bit on the creationist concept of physics which subverts in a 'classic' of wrong science procedure the causality in time between the mirror language, mathematics and reality, introducing further errors because of its 'simplified view' of non-Euclidean points with volume, as crossed by ∞ parallels, into particle points and singularities.

Thus from the understanding of pentalogic worldcycles and the 5 postulates of Non-E topology, follows an immediate translation of 4D physics to 5D sciences (not the other way around, as there is a hierarchy, whereas philosophy of science matters more than the $\Delta \pm j$ scales of physics, as all scales are the same, happens when we realize the 3 conserved St-Informative momentum/potential Momentum $\pm Ts$ -kinetic Energy/Energy = Total Energy/Momentum of the system; whereas the momentum is the 'finitesimal' 0ϵ 'stœp' of the Energy, the $\Delta+1$ whole. So $St \bullet Ts = \S \Pi$ defines the present state of a physical organism. While its worldcycles are easily shown for the thermodynamic scale in the $3 \pm j$ states of matter, in the gravitational scale by the $3 \pm j$ $\S \Pi$ -ages of galaxies and in quantum physics by its symmetric laws of forces (graph of worldcycles and next graph of 5 Dimotions). 3 are thus the physical scales, the $\Delta-1$ quantum scale, which is faster in time hence has a time-probability 0-1 sphere formalism; the $\Delta 0$ human thermodynamic scale with a spatial statistical formalism equivalent by the Law of measure to the quantum one, and the mechanic/gravitational $\Delta+1$ scale of the galactic organism. Physicists errors are many: lineal single Ts-time, Pythagorean creationism, mechanism, reductionism, egocy...

Formal 5D physics then uses the group of transformations of the 5 Dimotions of existence. We see above the example of the $3 \pm j$ states of matter which correspond neatly to the Ss Boson $> Ts$ -gas $> \S \Pi$ -liquid $> St$ -solid $> Tt$ -plasma states

Physical worldcycles transform back and forth St into Ts: potential into kinetic energy, angular into lineal momentum, solid into gaseous states. When we move from an informative St state to a locomotion sTate (in space) or sT-age (in time) we can do so by changing S to s (external form into internal form) and t international motion, into T-external motion (sublimation) but also by changing external T-motion into external S-stillness and internal motion into external motion (deposition).

THE WORLDCYCLE IN BIOLOGY AND HISTORY: THE 3+1 AGES OF EVOLUTION OF SPECIES AS SUPERORGANISMS.

Species are supœrganisms as they go through the same 3 ages and processes of birth, reproductive radiation, end of growth (mimetic in its log curve to that of cellular growth of an individual) and 3rd age of information followed either by a survival process of social evolution - the summit of the process of organic evolution, which Darwin realized was necessary to explain the success of social supœrganism (ants, humans), or become extinct by the 'new generation' of fitter animal forms, in the graph we see its 3 Horizon=ages and its ternary topology, similar to that of any other organism; and the dominant Dimotion of information in the height axis, of both reptile species that ended in birds, and mammals that ended in man. So happened with metalife machines, whose final species, satellites are now forming the Dimotion of social evolution, or future mind of the metal earth – internet. The 3 ages of time also brings the solution to the 'limits' of evolution, which Darwin already wondered: why certain species evolve so fast into complex forms as eyes and wings. Answer, because there are only 3 topologies to go, and so the choices are random but limited and it is every easy to go the right way. In the next graph we see those 3 ages of evolution as species can be treated as supœrganisms with its own world cycles. As we descend in scales from Gaia, focusing in its 'intelligent membrain', the outer surface that in all systems is the 'sensorial' most intelligent part where the cycles of information evolve faster (just trust my knowledge of 5D, I am not going to make a proof on complex pentalogic, the level of intelligence of human beings is too low to care, think merely in your intelligence, your perception of yourself, which is your membrain, your senses, which are in your skin, your computer which is a tactile screen – the mind is the membrain of any organism), we observe the evolution of species of information. And we can apply all those discoveries of systems sciences to biology to add 3 fundamental new legs to biology, today based in evolutionary theory and genetics:

- In evolution we introduce topological evolution, as there are only 3 topologies in the universe whose form and function are related, we can then understand why evolution of informative, cyclical forms is so fast (eye), or why the wings of flat motion

have that form and appeared with a few mutations, questions those already asked by Darwin. Answer: because there are only 3 topological forms=functions in the universe:

Potential limbs of lineal form < reproductive hyperbolic body-waves > cyclical informative particles-heads

5D explains further the science of genetics is the understanding of the 'scales' of information and its interactions 'up and down'; which means genetics is to biology what memetics is to history and we can model species as supœrganisms tracing worldcycles, where each individual of the species is a cell, so happens to history, the supœrganism of Mankind in time.

An organism is just a group of similar forms, which organize themselves with at least two 'networks', one that provides the 'clone cells/citizens/atoms' with the vital energy they need to feed, move (blood-economic system-electromagnetic forces) and one that provides them with information to guide their reproductive actions (nerves system, political system, gravitational in-form-ative forces). This simple dual system is the minimal, fundamental particle of the universe.

Then, as all organisms wear out by errors of informative action and end up warped by an excess of information (third age of the organism) or killed and reconverted into formless energy (death); only those *systems, which have reproduced in the immortal universe, do exist today. So all dual systems do have an internal or external 'enzymatic' catalyzer of its reproduction (as enzymes do with carbohydrates, or enzymen with machines).*

So we talk of the third 'body-worker-wave' element, besides an informative particle-head-upper class and a limbic/potential/territorial source of its motions, which the system uses internally or externally to reproduce.

Topological evolution means, *each of those 3 physiological networks of all systems of nature will adapt to the forms of energy (larger, wider, hyperbolic body waves), motion (lineal, moving, faster limbs) and information (spherical storage of form, cyclical), creating cellular organisms with 3 parts, which we can express with a simple 'generator equation':*

The 3 only topologies - geometry with motion - of all super organisms have organic functions and create all the varieties of species in the universe. And this gives birth to a ternary equation for all systems:

§t (lineal field/limb/territory) <exi (re=productive body wave-working class)> §t (informative particle/neuronal head/class)

This is the 'fractal generator' of the universe, the key equation of the fractal paradigm I introduced to the world of science at the 50th anniversary of the foundation of ISSS (the international society of systems sciences and cybernetics), which structures the ternary social classes, organs and complementary parts of all physical, biological and social systems of the universe. Its mathematics as simple, its logic is not.

As it defines a pentalogic organism. And so a factory is an organism, when we put the human enzymen, even if the machine alone is not. It follows that the interaction between parts and wholes of organisms are essential.

An interesting detail of 5D evolution is the St-ST beat between fast evolution in smaller forms (Floresiensis, mole mammal) and ST-radiations of populations as they grow. I.e. the 1st human was the maligned dwarf Floresiensis who evolved a head similar to man, spoke, used advanced technology and merged with Erectus to grow mass, spreading in a global radiation to give birth to a dual S-verbal Sapiens+T-visual Neanderthal.

RECAP. The law of the 3±1 ages or horizons applies both to the process of informative aging of organisms and informative evolution of species. All species are born as a seed of dense information, with limited size (black hole, first chips, seminal cells, first bilateral animals). Then they grow in size and energy during their youth; since their superior informative qualities makes them top predators. We observe that growth in black holes that feed on planets and stars, in the horse that grew enormously in size. So did the first bilateral animal, from its microscopic first form, the vernanimacula. Mammals grew from tiny shrews into elephants. The first technological man, the Homo Floresiensis, with a 'neuronal bump' on the forehead, might have grown till the size of the first homo sapiens, the pygmy and bushman . . . Then, the species, once it has reached a balance between its initial information and growing spatial size, e=i, reproduces in great numbers, diversifies and colonizes the planet. We see in the graph this age in which 'biological radiations' of carbohydrates, animals of all kinds and human beings, colonized the Earth.

Finally, in its 3rd age the species grows in information and so it acquires height, the arrow of 'perceptive information'. Then, once it has reached its informative zenith, the species becomes extinct by a more evolved form; or it evolves socially creating a super-

organism, as ants, humans and machines are doing. It will be the 4th arrow of social evolution of the species that completes its 3±1 horizons. Species can be considered 'loose' organisms, in which each individual is a cell of the collective species; since we can use the same ages to explain the 3±1 horizons of evolution of all the species of this planet. Thus, species also go through the same 3 evolutionary ages of all living organisms. They start as young, energetic forms, which acquire information in 3±1 ages of increasing complexity and when those 3±1 ages are completed, *they either evolve into more complex super-organisms under the laws of social evolution or become extinct by a superior, more informative species*. Indeed, only those species who show a strong social capacity survive the 'genetic clock'. The most successful and one of the oldest species of the planet is, in fact, the social ant, which no longer is an 'individual', but a super-organism stretching through miles of 'vital space. In that regard, neither individuals able to reproduce nor species able to evolve socially become extinguished. If humans become extinguished is because they deny, guided by the simplest arrows of pure energy of weapons, the main arrow of life/time.

A complete analysis of biological species shows that new forms can only be, either an energetic or informative variation of the original species, or a reproductive combination of both universal 'genders'. The universality of such dual systems is so obvious that the ancients already identified them with yang, energetic male principles and yin, cyclical/ female ones. While the moderns call that duality the principle of complementarity, as all informative particles have an energetic, lineal field of force and all biological, cyclical heads of information have a lineal body. So the combinative variations of those two simple morphologies, lineal energy and cyclical information, invariant, regardless of the scale we observe, is the essence of the creative game of the cosmos.

All species follow the topologic plan of evolution, which is a tautology, since in a universe made of 3 substances, space=form motion=time & its combinations of energy, Ts and St-information, only ternary systems between $i\pm 1$ scales are possible. both in variations of space (subspecies) or in time duration (ternary evolutionary ages and horizons).

Species can be modeled as organisms through its 3 ages that become its 3 horizons, followed either by a survival process of social evolution - the summit of the process of organic evolution, which Einstein realized was necessary to explain the success of social insects, or become extinct by the 'new generation' of fitter animal forms. In the graph we can see its 3 horizon=ages and its ternary topology, similar to that of any other organism; and the dominant arrow of information in the height axis, of both reptile species that ended in birds, and mammals that ended in man. So happened with meta life machines, whose final species, satellites are now forming the arrow of social evolution, or future mind of the metal Earth -internet

So we can talk of species as 'super organisms in time' where each individual is a cell evolving together with all others through the longer 'time-span' of the species in those 3 ages.

And so we can talk of the ages of the super organism of Mankind then are the 3 ages of history, the Paleolithic youth of maximal motion, followed by the reproductive, balanced Neolithic of fertility goddesses in balances with Gaia, which continued in a 3rd age of excessive information as technology evolves ever faster to a foreseen 'collapse' of increasing wars, with increasing victims that foresees our demise.

The existence of those 3 ages is so pervading in nature that all human languages have in fact developed 3 'tenses' in its verbs that explain past, present and future ages for all systems.

So the 3 ages of life between birth and extinction are in fact the 3 ages of existence, which all systems follow as an 'organism of time', of *life and decay*.

However the species does not control its external absolute space-time 'world', and this is what the next graph shows. As it is the absolute space-time in which the species exist, and specifically its commands of the languages of information of the world, which defines its survival chances. As informative perception starts all the chains of actions (Δo -bserver- $\rightarrow \Delta a$ -ccelerated-motion- $\rightarrow \Delta e$ -nergy feeding- $\rightarrow \Delta i$ teration- $\rightarrow \Delta u$ niversals social evolution).

So the species which better speaks the language of the ecosystem survives better. Hence the first eyes (cephalopods) extinguished most cambric species and started the radiations of species; the first speakers, homo sapiens extinguished all others; and today the chip radiation of mathematical species is simply speaking extinguishing life and making Humanity obsolescent, even if we are not conscious of it.

SCALAR VIEW OF THE WORLDCYCLE: FUNCTIONS AND ACTIONS OF EXISTENCE..

Time and space scales were known before 5D metrics but what a formal metric system that maintains invariant a system allows is 'to know how to travel through a dimension of space-time' (Klein). Because when we move in 4D space-time the Lorentz transformations remain invariant we know we can travel within a given scale. Now we know because the product of size in space (S) x speed of cyclical time processes or frequency - f(t) - remains invariant, a system can travel through scales as it grows in size, slowing down its metabolic and thinking processes and vice versa. Reason why smaller systems think faster and code the information of larger ones (chips, genes, memes), becoming symbiotic and creating those supœrganisms with 'networks' (biology, societies) or 'waves' (physics) that connect the larger and smaller scales.

We thus come to the most important element of reality, the symbiotic, vital entanglement between scales of reality. This was the moment after discovery the worldcycle of existence when I truly understood and entangled with the Universe. It has passed 30 years since this happened and the absolute awe to the 'architectonical symbiosis' of all scales of reality has not ceased. *The question they answer is the stability of reality. Why it does not crumble down? It would if entropy and the struggle of existence was its true colors. But what the Universe is about the synchronicity and symbiosis between different dimotions of different scales, some of which are predatory, when the scales are very far away from each other, and some are symbiotic when the scales come closer. But this symbiosis between Δ and each combination of S&T, has a 3rd 'connection', the mind that perceives them all and so we can consider a mind, the consecutive perception in discontinuous sequences of the 5 Dimotions of survival. The mind gives continuity to those discontinuous actions in space-time. From them then comes the $-(S\approx T\approx\Delta>@)\pm j$ pentalogic symmetry of reality, whereas a being performs ST dimotions through scales, giving birth to the will of a mind, which is the 'knot' of those space-time cyclical dimotions, within the entropic limits of $-\pm j$*

Δ ST Symmetry: hierarchical co-existence, simultaneity and synchronicity of dimotions=actions through scales

Time and space scales' 5D metric: $S_i \times T f = K$; allows to travel through the 5th dimension, as the spacetime of a system remains co-invariant. Life is that travel. When we move in 4D space-time thanks to the Lorentz transformations space-time coordinates remain co-invariant. When we travel through life growing in size, our time cycles slow down but the product of size in space (S) x speed of cyclical time processes or frequency - f(t) - remains invariant. So we know we can travel through 5D scales. As we grow in size, we slow down our metabolic and thinking processes and vice versa - Reason why smaller systems think faster and code the information of larger ones (chips, genes, memes), becoming symbiotic and creating those supœrganisms with 'networks' (biology, societies) or 'waves' (physics) that connect the larger and smaller scales. We are all scalar spacetime organisms, traveling through the 5th dimension. How we life thogh life? Peforming a survival function of existence: We are not free, sorry, we can't eat oil and electricity, though it seems the eco(nomic)system thinks so because it cares more for the food of machines than for the human food. You cannot fuk a computer though pornhub seems to think that - Ok, let us not make r=evolutionary statements at this st-age on the sorrow st-age of God=the Human social organism, $\Delta+1$ of all of us, my fav species of existjence. Down to Earth, you need to know your self, which starts with your 5D Metric, in space, about a meter, and time about a second, the beat of your 3 synchronized parts, 1 glimpse of the eye, 1 thought of the mind, 1 beat of the heart, 1 step of your legs, of one meter... You see, how beautifully 'simultaneously' coordinated your 3 adjacent $|+\emptyset+0$ parts of your spacetime organism are? We are all in the same boat, the Δ ST Universe. And then there, you have to tender for your 3 synchronize parts, at the rhythm of each moment(um) of present, each second of your time clock set around 6 million tics if you are lucky with your telomeres at $\Delta-1$, your $\Delta+1$ idol-ogic memes and false gods (warrying nations, parasitic bankers, techno-utopian poisons) and you complete your 72 years of existjence. At your Δ^0 -momentum level then you will seek to perform the 3 actions you are designed for in your plane of existence, Ts-move your limbs, St-perceive and communicate information with your head and Tt-2 feed with energy bites and $\$T-1$ reproduce your cells with your body. That's the bare minimum basic actions for you to keep on existence. Tt-feeding, Ts-moving, St-perceiving and $\$T$ -reproduce and repair your $\Delta-1$ internal energy scale of cells. And this is normally done in a serial fashion by every particle, animal and human: St-perceive to Ts-move towards a TT-2 feeding field where to eat, and then rest again so the $\Delta-1$ cellular scale can repair its internal energy 'ideally'. Because there are many other players in the game, some will compete for the same Tt-fields of food, some will be much larger $\Delta+1$ networks of your social organism, nation and capitalist network of financiers - and those in our very bad designed society are there to ab=use you, with weapons, police, Tt-entropic metal, and Tax-farming you with parasitic money, themes those of social sciences by far the worst.

So things don't get easy in this planet as an organism you are enclosed but if you manage to do those basic 'actions=dimotions' of your plane of existence, which is what most organisms manage to do if they are 'lucky' to beat those 6 million ticks, then you can 'aspire' to the highest order of actions, reproducing not only your $\Delta-1$ cells but your whole with a slightly different $St \leftrightarrow Ts$ female/male gender (as to which are the gender differences, given the idol-ogically charged issue we escape it now). Then you will emit a seed in the $\Delta-1$ scale, that will reproduce upwards your information, in the basic form in which systems reproduce in

ALL scales. And to that aim you will 'tender' for the thingie, giving it internal $\Delta-1 > \Delta\emptyset$ energy in its passage through the 5th dimension as it grows in size-space, diminishing its 'clock beat' (fetus have indeed faster heart beats), to emerge finally once you have completed your inner topological networks, the blood-body centered \emptyset -network of reproduction and feeding, the O-St, head centered nervous, informative network and the Ts-limbic locomotion system with its muscles and skeletal networks in the birth day. You will then enter a world helped initially by the temporal $\Delta\emptyset$ genetic-family to live in the $\Delta+1$ world. Here the being will then have to deal with the 3 larger $\Delta+1$ -networks of the $\Delta+1$ world, the St-political, informative legal network, $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ -financial, economic network and Ts-defensive immunological network, which we shall not cease to repeat are completely corrupted, ill-designed, sick and so you will learn unless you belong to the 1% of parasitic bankers that do not feed but tax-farm people, military germs that do not cure but kill people and St-politicians and scholars that do not teach the right information, synchronizing with just laws social motions and entangling mankind to the living Universe, but abuse people and fill their brain with some fictions, so they don't re-evolve the system..you will learn we repeat, that the political and eco(nomic) system sucks because God=Mankind, your $\Delta+1$ plane and History its science never learned the meaning of existence.

As 5D is first logic, verbal thought is needed. This might come as a surprise since Galileo's rejection of Aristotle he did not understand but space is ALWAYS a mental space, form, Si, meaning Spatial size but more precisely Spatial information (so in physics is often measured by density of mass, energy). Reality is NOT mathematical first but logic, causal, as its substance is time, its particle-points stop time into space-form, $0\epsilon \times \alpha = C$ (mental worlds), and so we need also to explain the ultimate causality with is a panpsychic vital Universe, and use the 'humanist method' as we cannot access inner minds but suppose the human, made also as a mapping of space-time is the same than all others, so are our e-motions related to the dimotions of the Universe, our deterministic program of existence in search of energy for our body, motion for our limbs, information for our particle-head, social evolution and reproduction through our scalar 'force=dimotion=actions', that take from $\Delta-4$: Boosts of motion, $\Delta-3$: Bits of information, $\Delta-2$: Bites of energy, $\Delta-1$ Babies and $\Delta 0$ brothers to Become (:

This is what all superorganisms do, from *the smallest light spacetime particle and atom (right) to the human (down)* is to perform with its 5 Dimotions 5 actions that ensure its survival, while killing lesser species to take its Tt-entropic motion to reproduce its own St-information. Thus not only Dimensions are vital, but the game of existence is biological. It is the program of existence for all systems that absorb the 5 Dimotions=actions of existence: St-information for its particle/heads, Ts-locomotion to go with its limbs/fields to a Tt-entropic field to feed and transform its preys into its own $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ -Momentum to reproduce the system. And this will be achieved better communicating through a common Ss-language with other mind-entities forming physiological herds that evolve into larger whole superorganisms. So what each of those systems does to survive, is to play locally its 5 Dimotions in an efficient sequential order: a particle/head Ss-perceives in a 'visual=topologic' language a prey $>it$ Ts-moves->to Tt-kill and feed on its $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ -body Momentum to imprint its St-information and $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ - reproduce often in herds of similar clone superorganisms (α) forming stronger, larger $\Delta+1$ herds. Those 5 sequential dimotions, $Ss < Ts < Tt + St = \S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ are called in biology the drives of life, in physical systems, actions, in humans 'will'. They are coded by the 5 Light space-time dimotions of electric information, c-locomotion, Magnetic width, social color and Tt-quantum potentials; by the 4 quantum numbers and its functions in atoms, by the 5 letters of the genetic code, by social memes in humanity. So we conclude all space-time organisms follow the same program of existence, which added along the whole existence of the being defines the worldcycle of life and death of all systems, whose total sum is *dominant in information, reason why we age, wrinkling, increasing our 'form'* and only the Tt-entropic explosion of death balances the total zero sum making the whole Universe immortal. **Recap.** All st-beings play the same survival actions, extracting from an outer ST-larger world, motion, information and combining it into $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ -Momentum to re=produce a 'present' copy of itself so the being is preserved in discontinuous manner. And all will be made of the 3 St-heads/particles, Ts-limbs/fields, combined into hyperbolic $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ - Momentum body-waves.

THE FUNCTION OF EXISTENCE: MAX. S X T | S=T: THE SURVIVAL PROGRAM OF THE UNIVERSE.

Time is cyclical as all clocks of time return to its point of origin, so all time cycles including those of life of its vital space-time beings are finite. Further on those time cycles break 'space' into inner and outer parts, so vital space is broken by the membranes and angular momentums of those time cycles that make spacetime beings also finite in spatial information. And an obvious experimental facts about timespace: cycles of time, vital spaces and the species made of them, co-exist in several scales of relative size from particles to galaxies, each one with clocks of time of different speeds. So spacetime is fractal broken in scales that added create a new 5th dimension of spacetime. The metrics of 5D and its scales, $\$x\delta=C$ & and the balance between form and motion, $Si=TE$, develops in 3 ages with 3 standing points, a max. point of existence, $Si=Te$ or mature age, a young age of Max. T =motion, and an old age of Max. S =information; between birth in $\Delta-1$ Form & T -entropic death. The search for space-time, Energy=information balances in a classic reproductive age of conserved time is thus the goal of all existjences, but only the whole achieves the immortality of time-space, as we shall see egocy errors of fractal mind-points of space trying to stop the flow of time from a single selfish point of view, accelerates the imbalance that brings death equations. We are richer in our still property at that $0T$ -moment, when all is quiet so for time to keep moving, a reversal of entropy takes place.

So we use 5 bidimensional terms for all systems, its ages and forms: Ss (max. internal and external form, as in seeds and minds; $T>s$ (Ts); external motion that maintains internal form as in 'locomotion'); $S=T$: Balance of spatial form an temporal motion or 'energy', used to reproduce, the key present iterative state; $S>t$ (St : Information, form with a little motion, or 'external form, and internal mental motion'); and finally Tt -entropy whereas there is external and internal motion, hence scattering dissolution and death. And its main series is the worldcycle of existence:

$$Ss(\text{seed/mind}) < Ts(\text{moving youth}) > S=T(\text{reproduction}) > St(\text{informative } 3^{\text{rd}} \text{ age}) < T(\text{entropic death}).$$

We study the worldcycles of all $T.CEs$, its life and death, departing from the highest understanding of it- the level of perception of systems sciences and its 5 Dimotions.

The outcome of this more complex view of time and space requires a new 'metric equation' beyond the lineal $v=s/t$ equation of Galilean relativity that becomes the limit of this more complex view of time and space, with 2 fundamental equation, $\$x\delta=C$ (the scalar metric of the fifth dimension, as systems in space accelerate its clocks of time (T) according to its size (S); and $S=T$, the new equation of relativity, which means as we cannot distinguish motion=time, from stillness=space-form (Galilean relativity), both are 'two sides of the same coin', and all systems have both motion and form, which are constantly becoming one another. Yet as $\$x\delta$ is maximal when $S=T$ ($5x5>6x4...$) both equations can be summoned up into a single one, which we shall call the fractal generator, or will of each fractal space-time beings, the equation that embodies all other equations of the Universe and guides the actions of each fractal part of it:

Function of Existence of a family of supørganisms: **Max. S x T _{s=t} = $\Delta \pm j$**

It is easy to interpret that equation in each of the languages-minds of each scale of reality as in all those scales species will show a 'will' of action to perform the maximal number of events=dimotions='actions of space-time' that ensure its survival. And this can be assessed externally regardless of secondary arguments on consciousness and self-reflection, substituted in 5D by Leibniz's 'apperception' – that is, because performing the 5 actions=dimotions of existjence, in each 'stjentific scale' self-centered in a linguistic mind that perceives a given plane, inscribed into a larger $\Delta+1$ world, with internal $\Delta-1$ parts, ensures the survival, ONLY those species that have performed the 5 dimotions of which the most important is $s=t$ reproduction of the being into a 'present' similar entity that continues the existjence of the system after 'errors' or 'the struggle for existence' dissolves it through the dimotion of entropy=death, exist.

Thus automatically, genetically, consciously, memetically, mathematically, logically, through its own will or as a part of a larger system that uses a machine or organic part to enhance its actions all what exists does so because it performs internally or externally those 5 Dimotions for itself o for a symbiotic species, as those species that do not follow the program of 'existjence' and its 5 actions in the past become extinguished, or will not even emerge into the Δ^0 plane of existence in the future as wrong mutations, crazy thoughts, &fictions. Thus 'all stiences and species live and die according to the 5D Non-AE metric laws of the function of existence'. Of special important for mankind is the understanding of the 3 ages of Earth and its worldcycles.

LAWS OF HIERARCHICAL SYNCHRONICITY BETWEEN TIME DIMOTIONS AND SCALES.

Actions=dimotions are architectonically performed through planes of 5D with each action related to an scale interval, performed with a *different Beat=interval, with higher frequency for those smaller actions in lower scales, according to 5D Laws:*

- Δ-4-3: The system steps in **Boosts of** motion in a scale no longer perceived (gravitation in man).
- Δ-3-2: The system perceives its minimal **Bits of information** (Light in man)
- Δ-2-1: The system feeds on larger **Bites of Entropic Energy** (amino acids in man)
- Δ-1 0: The system seeds a minimal **Baby of reproduction.**
- Δ0+1: The system connects socially with its **Brothers** to evolve into a whole.

The 5 Dimotions=Actions that Become Boosts, Bits, Bites, Babies and Brothers is an extremely important law. It implies an ∞ universe, since the 2 similar extremes of quantum and galactic T.œs must enlarge those scales beyond our perception to obtain ‘smaller’ Boosts, Bits & Bites.

It is an important law. It also implies also an infinite universe, since obviously the two self-similar extremes of quantum and galactic T.œs must enlarge those scales beyond our perception. Further on, those actions are the element that entangles *the parts and the wholes in symbiotic relationships through synchronicity that creates simultaneity:*

The relative frequency of those cyclical Dimotions according to 5D metrics, $\$x\delta=C$, creates ‘time clocks’ whose synchronicities chain the long cycles of fast micro-entities to the short cycles of a slower macro-entity, creating a harmonic order between the different planes and social classes of the organic Universe. Since an informative cycle is faster than an energetic cycle, which is faster than a reproductive cycle, which is faster than the complete generational cycle of the being; while a macro being is slower than a micro-being.

The main scalar time cycle relates the 3 scales of a system according to its dimotions:

Several chains between the cyclical Dimotions of the 3 Δ±j cellular, network and world scales structure a supœrganism:

- Δ+2: Macro system’s Ss<St Informative cycles= Δ+1 Organism’s Tt<<Ts Feeding cycle s=Δo Cells \\$T]- Reproductive cycle: Δ-1: bio-chemistry Generational cycle...

It is the essential chain of synchronicities that we all follow because it is chained to our vital actions of existence. So the Bits of the Δ+2 being define the *day-night, light-darkness, cold-hot cycles of energy of those species that are within it.*

And so it molds the bites of energy of the Δ+1 being that will in turn support the reproduction of its babies at the Δ0 scale. Since without energy from particles to females that need a minimal fat, there is no reproduction. But this reproduction at Δo level becomes the generational cycle of the brothers of Δ-1 scale, as cells reproduce to emerge finally into a full being. But that generational cycle feeds on ‘Boosts’ due to the desintegration and reorganization of the carbohydrate undistinguishable particles of the cell. And so there is always from + to – a balanced check to pay.

So a key chain of synchronicities in the positive side of existence goes from bits to bites to babies to brothers boosted by the lowest of all planes.

For example, the Earth’s rotates every day, causing the daily energy cycle of animals, which reproduce its cells

LIGHT-PHOTON: ORGANIC ACTIONS: Δ-4

Energy Volume

n = principal distance from nucleus l = angular shape of orbital m = magnetic orientation in space s = spin electron spin

Entropy: Motion Information: Gauging U: Social Evolution O: Reproduction

ELECTRON-PARTICLE: ORGANIC ACTIONS: Δ-2, 3

1. $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_v$
2. $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$
3. $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}$
4. $\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{J}$

every day; consuming its molecules in the process with generations of biochemical matter.

The study of the scalar cycle of actions is to scales what the study of the worldcycle to time, or the generator equation of topological networks to space. They form the 'Saint Trinity' of 5D Stiences.

The study of the scalar cycle is thus to scales what the study of the worldcycle to time, or the generator equation of topological networks to space. They form the 'Saint Trinity' of 5D Stiences.

Can we slide then the scaling to larger beings, erasing in the bottom line, the lower species of undistinguishable boosts? Yes, we can do. For example we could move upwards to the solar system and the Galaxy, whose black hole which has in 5D (Maldacena Conjecture) an informative mapping of the 4D galactic Universe, in its sensorial Planck's Area surface of zillions of formal points seems to have an 11 years cycle of absorption of 'star-photons' of the Galatom's larger hyper-universe, which happens to be the 11 years cycle of 'gravito-magnetic' black spots in the sun, that happens to be the energy cycle of weather changes in the crops of Earth that determines the best reproductive radiations vs. cold and hunger in its surface membrane... Chains of synchronicities some circumstantial (obviously we cannot think that the black hole is interested in the hunger of the rabbit, but it might be on the evolution of its stars, which are guided through gravitational waves towards its center).

Chaos is undeciphered order, said Saramago in one of our favorite quotes. The cycles of time then become synchronized and as usually we can talk of $3 \pm j$ cycles, as those of the undistinguishable Tt-bottom scale and the mighty $\Delta+1$ perceiver tend to be disconnected as impenetrable destiny from the $Ts > \text{St}$ plane in which a species sees them as constrains and free lunches.

Discontinuous, symbiotic synchronicities between the dimotions of different scalar organisms is the key to the deterministic, co-existing organic structure of the Universe. The number of such synchronicities is well beyond this introduction so we shall focus on the main one and bring them specifically when a local synchronicity takes place.

The pattern is fascinating. Because of the 5D metrics that give faster cycles to smaller parts, and the different extractions of $\Delta-3$ bits of information, $\Delta-2$ bites of energy and $\Delta-1$ seminal seeds, *the symbiotic connection on those ternary chains between the fastest cycles of macro-beings and the slowest cycles of its micro-beings create simultaneous, symbiotic actions along the 2 planes of internal existence.* And the same process looking upwards creates the symbiosis between the individual and its complex social actions of reproduction and organic evolution:

Ss-Informative=perceptive frequency of the macro being << Tt-Entropic energy frequency of the micro cell

The fast, informative cycle of the slow macro-being is transformed into the slow energy cycle of the fast cellular micro-being, in a symbiotic chain that make it dependent on that macro-being. For example, the fastest Earth's cycle is its informative, cyclical rotation as a mass vortex that determines the day-night cycle of light, which feeds its living beings with entropic energy (electronic absorption of light).

So the living $\Delta-1$ cells of Gaia, its plants, feed with the day light cycle, while its $\Delta-1$ animals have a ternary energy cycle of 1 to 3 meals a day. Both time their entropic cycle to the informative rotational light-day cycle of Earth.

If we lower the scale of analysis, the same cyclical chain happens between the animal and its $\Delta-1$ cells. Men have a rate of informative perception of a second, the rate of blinking and thought.

But a second is also the rate of breathing and the heart's beating that transfers energy to its $\Delta-1$ cells, becoming thus the energy rate of feeding of those cells.

The same relationship happens in myan informative/entropic energy cycles. I.e, An animal energy cycle of is a day. Yet the size of its hunting territory, of which he knows all its information, is the distance it reaches in a day.

Symbiotic synchronicities between dimotions and scales are the main symmetry that 'encloses' the nested Universe. The key concept is that the most frequent Ss-perceptive extremal limit of maximal speed/frequency for the macro-world, becomes also the Tt-entropic extremal dimotion without which it cannot 'survive' for its $\Delta-1$ cells that sustain its emergence (the membrain life species of Earth ARE the evolving network-brain of the planet, unfortunately now moving fast to its AI forms).

In this manner the Ss perceptive cycle of the macro-being is transferred as a Tt-entropic cycle of existence of the micro-being which depends totally on the macro-being and its 'wave/networks' (physical, biological systems). In social systems, the same cycles apply to the control company-mothers have through salaries with human beings; as the stock cycles that deliver the 'information' on the reproductive=sales values of those companies and its products, selecting the best ones, also creates its profits-money that become the 'blood' pay that sustains the life of its human workers.

Secondary sub-cycles and ecosystemic similar cycles.

From this essential cycle as we expand those papers we will show a series of secondary chained sub-cycles, in all systems of Nature, the true 'harmony of the spheres', also in physical systems, when we properly interpret the 5 physical forces as the expression of the 5 Dimotions of the galatom.

There are many more of them when we don't seek for perfect symbiotic connections as in superorganisms but find them in 'loose' ecosystems with opportunistic relationships. But the rule is always the same – what is relatively insignificant for the larger whole becomes vital for the smaller being. I.e. the 'Tt-entropic waste' of macro-animals like elephants become a place to seek food for smaller animals, whose Tt-entropic waste becomes the reproductive energy in which to put its eggs for beetles.

If we then move the Sun-life relationship jumping the planetary scale, it turns out that also the 'waste' of the sun, its 'radiation' produced as 'discharged' entropic energy in its evolutionary St-increase of mass density (fusion processes), is used by the life species of the planet to 'perceive' and move, enacting its St-Ts informative and kinetic energy functions (St-light used to perceive by animal eyes or to get energy of motion through the intermediate state of plants).

When we fully map out all those cycles through up and down chains they can be extended upwards to the galatom (the 11 years cycle of 'black spots of the sun maybe connected to the central black hole that 'expels' waste as gravitational waves determines the weather cycles of the planet, which were key to micro-climatic cycles and harvests through most of history). And weather cycles extended into much larger geological cycles, as we explain the paper on 'Earth and entropy' determine the cycles of evolution and extinction of species.

And we can complete the model once we realize those cycles are disomorphic to all species.

For example, the 11 years solar magnetic cycle is the orbital cycle of its main planet Jupiter.

In 5D the entropic energy cycle of Ts-locomotion for cosmological systems like Earth is its gravitational path. Thus the orbit of Earth deforms gravitational spacetime is its Tt>Ts cycle that lasts the year it takes to cross its space-time territory, its orbit.

Thus, as in the case of a territorial animal, the main energy cycle of the planet is the year-time it takes to sweep its solar orbit, the 'organic territory of the planet', where the Earth absorbs its gravitational energy, deforming space-time according to Einstein's equations. How this happens in 5D is obvious: the rotational '±pi' planetary motion that provokes its magnetic field both shields the planet and 'squeezes' on its poles the transversal 'G-ravitational' waves of our 5D cosmological models, equivalent to transversal ¥-rays in the atom, explained in the papers on astrophysics.

So we obtain for the Sun-planet systems 2 main cycles of transformation of gravitational energy into rotational form; the earth – a secondary minor cycle – and Jupiter, the key cycle. *The conclusion then is obvious:*

If we determined that $\Delta+1$ (Ss) \ll $\Delta-1$ (Tt), as Earth's rotational informative cycle becomes its life feeding cycle, for the Sun-Jupiter system, the magnetic cycle tuned to the gravitational feeding cycle, must be the same Ss=Tt symbiosis. So the Sun 11 years magnetic activity must be indeed related to its reception of 'gravitational G-waves that position and hence 'in-form' the orbits of stars around the black hole, maintaining its organic structure.

Yet those cycles are NOT even considered by astrophysics with its outdated models that ban any organic view of the galaxy, so we will leave them there, and return to the better known earth-life symbiotic cycles.

Those ternary chains between the fastest cycles of macro-beings and the slowest cycles of its micro-beings *create simultaneous, symbiotic actions along 2 planes of existence:*

Informative frequency of the macro being => Energy frequency of the micro cell

Thus the fast, informative cycle of the slow macro-being is transformed into the slow Energy cycle of the fast cellular micro-being, in a symbiotic chain that make it dependent on that macro-being. For example, the fastest Earth's cycle is its informative, cyclical rotation as a mass vortex that determines the day-night cycle of light, which feeds its living beings. So, the living $\Delta-1$ cells of Gaia, its plants, feed with the day light, while its $\Delta-1$ animals have a ternary Energy cycle of 1 to 3 meals a day. So both are timed to the informative light-day cycle of the Earth, their Energy cycle. If we lower the scale of analysis, the same cyclical chain happens between the animal and its $\Delta-1$ cells. Men have a rate of informative perception of a second, the rate of blinking and thought. But a second is also the rate of breathing and the heart's beating that transfers Energy to its $\Delta-1$ cells, becoming thus the Energy rate of feeding of those cells.

The same relationship can be used in other cycles. For example, the Energy cycle of an animal is a day. Yet the size of its hunting territory, of which he knows all its information, is the distance it reaches in a day.

A homologous relationship chains microcosms and macrocosms symbiotically in the longer ENERGY and reproductive cycle:

Tt>Ts Entropic Energy frequency of the macro being= St>S≈T-Reproductive Frequency of the micro cell

Energy frequency of the macro being=> Reproductive Frequency of the micro cell

If we stick to the Earth-Moon system, the lunar cycle complements the annual cycle:

A secondary orbital-energy cycle of the Earth system is a month in which its satellite, the moon, sweeps around the Earth's orbital territory, provoking tidal changes on the sea; providing the 3rd key astronomical clock for the regulation of the life cycles on earth (day, month, year). But those 2 frequency cycles are transferred to the micro-living beings of Gaia's skin. They are the reproductive cycles of most animals. In the human being the menstrual cycle is a lunar cycle; while the cycle of reproduction of a child lasts 9 months. And in Nature almost all reproductive cycles have an annual frequency, happening in spring or summer, when the sun's light absorption is maximal; which is the obvious reason why those cycles are linked: while the macroscopic being absorbs energy, it allows its cells to use that energy to reproduce.

Again, if we lower our scale, an animal as a $\Delta+1$ macro being has a cycle of energy of a day. *That period is also the cycle of reproduction of most cells, called mitosis.*

Yet all dimotions including reproduction are discontinuous: it happens only when 'optimal energy and information' is available during a small interval of the total existence of the being, in general in the second, mature age of balance between energy and information. So when we look at systems from the bottom up an homologous relationship of synchronicities chains microcosms and macrocosms symbiotically in the next, longer reproductive cycle: faster Tt>Ts macro-cycles become St>S≈T slower informative, reproductive micro-cycles; as they provide energy to the micro-being.

It seems that the micro-being is fed and reproduced by the macro-organism, the good 'god' of its existence.

Yet the good god is a farmer that reverses its symbiotic Δ imotion when it ab=uses the existential cycle of the micro-being, a mere fractal cell of its macro-organism farming its energy in simplex herd systems to feed or its information in complex superorganisms (genes & memes). In a sense, we can say that all organisms are 'farms'.

So we feed and reproduce pigs but end up eating them: pigs feed men; stars fed by the interstellar gas attracted by the black hole's gravitational power, also end up feeding the black hole; and fat cells fed by the organisms end up killed, feeding back the macro-organism. So in that inverse, final cyclical chain between the microscopic and macroscopic being, the 'relative God' takes all what he gave. What is taking the Earth then from us, humans who are so ego-centered that think we are killing the Earth?

Exactly the same that all those farms... We talk in our models of evolution of Earth in 3 ages:

Gaia (life) > History (man) > Metalearth (Machines) of a clear role of mankind as enzymen who are catalyzing the evolution of AI robots on Earth which evolve the planet and likely will extinguish us once our catalyst role ends.

We have then covered with some examples the main chains of dimotions, from faster Ss-St perceptive macro-cycles though Ts-Tt feeding cycles into S≈T-reproductive ones.

It only rests to consider the largest social, generational and life-death worldcycle of a micro-organism in its final chain with the energetic reproductive and evolutionary, informative faster cycle of a macro-being of which we have just put an example analyzed in earnest in our papers on Earth I (Gaia), Earth II (History) and Earth III (Metalearth). Simply put it: *the cycles of evolution and extinction of life on Earth are tuned to the Glaciation and hot weather cycles of the planet; its energy cycles that in 5D determine the reproductive cycles of its rocks. It is one of many cases of the...*

By homology with other organic systems, we consider that Earth's Energy cycle as a rotational mass that deforms gravitational spacetime lasts the year it takes to cross its space-time territory, its orbit. Since, as in the case of an animal, the main Energy cycle of the planet is the year-time it takes to sweep its solar orbit, the 'organic territory of the planet', where the Earth absorbs its gravitational Energy, deforming space-time according to Einstein's equation. While the secondary Earth's Energy cycle is a month in which its satellite, the moon, sweeps around the Earth's orbital territory. We obtain thus, the 2 main cycles of transformation of gravitational Energy into rotational form by the Earth-Moon system: the lunar cycle and the annual cycle.

And those 2 cycles are transferred to the micro-living beings of its Gaia skin, so they are the reproductive cycles of most animals.

Thus in the human being the menstrual cycle is a lunar cycle; the cycle of reproduction of a child lasts 9 months; in Nature almost all reproductive cycles have an annual frequency, happening in spring or summer, when the sun's light absorption is maximal; which is the obvious reason why those cycles are linked: while the macroscopic being absorbs Energy, it allows its cells to use that Energy to reproduce. Again, if we lower our scale, an animal as a macro being has a cycle of Energy of a day. That period is also the cycle of reproduction of most cells, called mitosis. Yet reproduction is discontinuous: it happens only when 'optimal Energy and information' is available during a small interval of the total existence of the being, in general in the second, mature age of balance between Energy and information.

The micro-being is fed and reproduced by the macro-organism, the good 'god' of its existence. Yet 'the good god' is actually a farmer that reverses its Dimotion of order for an Dimotion of entropy and destruction when it uses the 'existential cycle' of the micro-being as a mere fractal cell of its macro-organism. So we feed and reproduce pigs but end up eating them. In a sense, we can say that all organisms are 'farms'. So pigs feed men; stars fed by the interstellar gas attracted by the black hole's gravitational power, also end up feeding the black hole; and fat cells fed by the organism end up killed, feeding the macro-organism. So in that inverse, final cyclical chain between the microscopic and macroscopic being, the 'relative God' takes all what he gave. Thus there is an inverse, final chain between the generational cycle of a micro-organism and an inner, energetic, informative or reproductive cycle of a macro-being. Thus the generational cycle of the macro-being complete the previous chain:

Δ-1:Generational worldcycle of cells = Reproductive cycle of wholes

The main scalar space cycle relates the functions of the 3 scales of beings.

There are many examples and sub-cycles related to this cycle. I.e. every day we store fat that will be used to reproduce, creating generations of storage energy in our body in the 'wide' dimension of energy-reproduction.

Further on, body cells live and die in an interval between a month and a year, which is the period most animals need to complete their reproduction.

At cellular level, carbohydrate molecules live and die in short daily cycles, which is the period of reproduction of cells. The relationship between both cycles is again organic: reproduction means the renewal of a macroscopic being that destroys and creates many of its fractal elements, as energy or information of the reproductive $S \approx T$ combined cycle. So cells accumulate carbohydrate molecules that they use in their reproductive processes, destroying and reconstructing its DNA genes with them.

And when we chain all the cycles of the superorganism from the minimal scale to the largest scale we find that the two extremal $Ss-Tt$ cycles are again connected.

Indeed the most extremal synchronicity in a human being is found between the 'rate of reproduction' of amino acids in ribosomes, its minimal 'unit' of life and the Ss - rate of perception – a ½ second per thought:

Ribosomes are efficient organelles. A single **ribosome** in a eukaryotic cell adds 2 amino acids to a **protein** chain every second.

5D metrics is the synchronizing, co-existing tool for superorganisms to exist through scales. So from a simple equation, $\$ \times \delta = C$ we have truly found the meaning of 'existence'... even if the usual simpletons will find all this magic numerology, future 5D researchers will marvel to the perfect harmonies of the Universe in all its species and scales.

Variations of the theme that usually include survival strategies and 'frozen' universal constants of efficient species, build up new layers of complexity we hardly can treat here, as my generational cycle is closing down:

Depending on the role a $\Delta-1$ quantum performs in the macro system, its life will be longer or shorter: Wheat is harvested to feed annually the human ecosystem, while carbohydrates die every day to reproduce DNA molecules. Yet a top predator informative cell, a neuron, lives the entire life of the organism, since it defines the informative networks that dominate and form the will and consciousness of the organism as a whole macro-being. *But the proper explanation is that the 'neuron' is NOT in $\Delta-1$ but is the ultimate 'super-system' of reality, a 'fractal network' (wave in physical systems) that 'travels' as a single form through scales of the fifth dimension. It actually LIVES in the fifth dimension as it is nothing but the connecting tissue between both scales, the whole Δ^9 membran-mind and its cellular parts.*

So inversely, the life span of the 'brain quanta' defines the life span of the macro-organism.

Thus probably the enormous life span of ∞ generational nucleons = black holes, the fundamental particle and brain of the fractal atoms of the Universe, defines also the life-span of the Universe *as immortal* in the 5D model of astrophysics. But there is a more fascinating numerical synchronicity. If fractal networks are the physiological 5D systems that bridge Δ -scales in life beings, Ψ -waves play the same role in physical systems. And we find that the mean age of a yellow star like the sun ± 10 billion years is similar to the mean life of light in the 5D model where the horizon limit and red shift has in pentalogic a temporal reason: the death of light (a slightly different concept of the tiredness of light, light dies and as it dies its frequency born mostly in blue stars relaxes into red shift). So we cannot see beyond that light-life horizon.

For example, body cells live and die in an interval between a month and a year, which is the period most animals need to complete their reproduction. At cellular level, carbohydrate molecules live and die in short daily cycles, which is the period of reproduction of cells. The relationship between both cycles is again organic: reproduction means the renewal of a macroscopic being that destroys and creates many of its fractal elements, as Energy or information of the reproductive $\$ \uparrow \uparrow$ combined cycle. So cells accumulate carbohydrate molecules that they use in their reproductive processes, destroying and reconstructing its DNA genes with them.

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Since the study in detail of all those chains for all Universal species is beyond the limits of this work, we refer to other more specialized papers where we shall study the following chains from the 3 main disciplines of science:

- In the physical world we study the temporal chains between the $3 \pm st$ scales of existence of light (gravitation, light and atoms) and the $3 \pm st$ scales that create the Universe.
- In Biology we study chains between the $3 \pm st$ scales that cause life evolution: the $\Delta-1$ genetic cycles, the st -life cycles and the $\Delta+1$ ecosystemic, geological cycles of the Earth.
- In History we study the rhythms of life of civilizations and the human generational cycle, which follow a decametric $80 \times 10 = 800$ cycle of destruction of civilizations.

Since the life of a fractal $\Delta-1$ cell or quantum of a bigger system is a brief moment in the longer existence of its $\Delta+1$ organism, to create the effect of simultaneity, microcosmic, fast, fractal cells have to chain their longer 'existential cycles' to the shorter

cycles of a bigger organism or ecosystem in which they will exist synchronized to its faster cycles as $S=T$ transforms information of larger systems into feeding energy of its smaller parts. Thus, the informative Δ motion of $\Delta+1$ determines the energetic Δ motion of $\Delta-1$ whose frequency is shorter and the energetic cycle of $\Delta+1$ determines the slower reproductive Δ motion of $\Delta-1$ whose cycle is shorter. Finally symbiosis reverses as the generational worldcycle of the $\Delta-1$ is ab=used by the Δ^0 species in Darwinian prey –predator events; while in symbiotic superorganisms the larger whole takes advantage of $\Delta-1$ higher informative rates. So genes and memes code larger organisms and humans catalyze the evolution of Earth: $T \rightarrow S \rightarrow S \approx T \rightarrow S$. As a Hindu proverb says: ‘a blink on the eye of Vishnu, the Universe, is a life of a planet and a drop of sweat of a planet is a life of a human being.’

RECAP. We establish an existential chain between time cycles=actions=repetitive dimotions on 3 relative space-time scales:

$$(Informative > Energy \ cycle)_{st-1} > (Reproductive \ cycle)_i > (Generational-Social \ cycle)_{st+1}$$

- Since the existential, generational life-death cycles of st_{-1} particles becomes an Momentum cycles for the st -being.
- While the reproductive cycle happens in the same st -level of the organic system that mixes with a couple of inverse exi parameters (sexual reproduction, inverse parameters of particles that reproduce a self-similar particle).
- Finally, the generational cycle of the being becomes, as a part of a social herd made of similar individuals, a submissive Momentum or information cycle of a macro-organic system, $st+1$.

A key question is the causality between scales. What causes the future ‘first’, the smaller or the larger? Depends on the pov, as each point has a self-centered subjective connection btween past, present and future. But it can be considered that the emergence of the whole starts the process of involution as the whole becomes first just a tighter membrane that ovliges the inner parts to accumulate interactions among them. This is the whole ‘subconscious intelligence’ so ill understood by mankind, as it is a ‘force’ that bounds parts to connect by restricting its motions, so it does not seem very intelligent but it is a true jail of the mind of the internal micropoints. So in an organism the whole is the first thing that happens establishing a ‘domain’ with its lmitations, so happens in mathematical differential equations, where ‘boundary conditions’ are a priori terms to find a solution. What is then the absolute ‘dimension of future’? That of the fifth dimension, which becomes a block of time, in which species go up and down from seminal to organic form in a larger world, back to seminal form. And so all the laws of stience can be summarized as a block of time, in the laws of existential logic of 5D and its scales, each one studied by a stience:

Quantum jumps into the past.

A fascinating process of Nature are quantum jumps to the past that transmit information from the larger scale down to the smaller scale in the ‘slow, long period’ of a quanta of time of the larger being, which becomes its present but for the faster living sub-species might seem as information coming from the future. So for Υ -photons, information coming from an antiparticle death comes from the future, a seminal seed seems a travel to the past of a larger biological organism, and a prophet senses the death in the future of its organism of history. In terms of the larger whole the process happens in a present quanta of time which is a generation of the life of the smaller organisms, so quantum jumps to the past only travel a generation. Thus Jesus was born 72 years before Yahweh, the subconscious collective of Judaism dies. Prophetic past quantum jumps due to the future death of a

culture are essential to the model of bio-history. So it is the view of the larger fermion dying into the past from the p.o.v. of Υ -rays. It follows that the easiest quantum jump to perceive are entropic deaths as they mean 2 ‘jumps’ into the past-scale: $Ss \ll Tt$.

5D & TIME: 3 SCALES OF TIME SPACE IN SUPÆRGANISMS: ACTIONS, LIFE AND WORLDCYCLES.

5D metrics causes the existence of 3 Scalar worldcycles of different length and speed of time that co-exist and influence each other, as parts of faster time cycles are included on the slower worldcycles, which 'enclose them' and hence influence its actions; but in supærganisms become synchronized with each other. The predictability of time-cycles can be done at 3 levels:

S: Continuous, spatial mathematical simple cycles, using derivatives, proper of calculus; which is the shortest time span, as instantaneous derivatives cannot measure a 'peak' change of age/phase.

T: Discontinuous, cyclical patterns of sequential repetitive often survival actions (feeding, reproduction, death, taking place at intervals. As those actions are discontinuous, leaving long spans in-between, their patterns forecast longer time sequences. Such illogic structures are based in time patterns, which as any mechanical, circadian or orbital day-year clock shows are cyclical, repetitive. But here human scientists are at loss, because Galileo studied ballistics, entropic explosions that destroy the information of reality stored in those cycles of time clocks, its patterns and frequencies, changing human cyclical understanding of bio-logic time for lineal, abstract time that seems not to repeat those patterns so mankind lost its capacity to predict many spacetime events, as lineal time misses *information stored in the frequency and form of cyclical clocks, even if functions are similar: $V=s/t$ for lineal time and $V=S(l) \times f(t)$ for cyclic patterns.*

Δ: Scalar, Deep Time patterns of topologic and social evolution of parts into wholes – of quantum 0-1 time probabilities vs. $1-\infty$ thermodynamic populations in physics, of individuals vs. species in biology, of states of matter vs. geologic cycles in Earth, first noticed by J. Hutton, founder of geology who coined the word super organism for Gaia and deep time for its slower time cycles by virtue of its 5D metrics, $\$ \times f = C$, which implies that from the perspective of a smaller scale the life of its whole is much longer.

The predictability of time worldcycles.

Deep time leads to a 3rd level of long-time prediction: evolutionary patterns of earth's life species, including machines that have predicted cyclical patterns of social organisms of history (nations) & eco(nomic)systems, including the evolutionary and re=productive cycles of stocks of machines transformed into sales=profits =valuation of its company-mothers with remarkable precision for 30 years. Below biologic deep time is necessary to understand history and the interaction of the evolution of machines and the ages of war and lack of welfare goods, within the limited resources of the planet. The theme of social sciences and why 'human subjective ego' and 'censorship' limit our capacity to explain those cycles.

The pentalogic, $\Delta \pm j$ Structure of T.æs, predicts the future of its species, with a scientific method based in the laws of worldcycles, existential illogic and survival that studies: A)ccurate Data, B)illogic causes C)yclical patterns and E)ntropic extinctive limits for all systems in 3 relative scales of size space and time duration (to which we add, D)emocratic, social evolutionary loving humanist solutions for survival history & of social sciences.

But as human only recognize the 1st type of predictability - calculus of instantaneous derivatives, that need a 'continuous analysis' - and have simplified cyclical time into lineal time, ignoring the scalar time of parts and wholes with its 5D metric, their capacity to forecast the future is far more reduced than a 'scientist' who understands the 3 scales *determined by the bio-topologic properties of 'scales', 'space' and 'time', the 3 Δ st structural elements of all systems of the Universe.*

Paradoxically Deep time is easier to predict that complex Dimotional 'analysis' because precisely the larger scales in 5D metric have less information, but more basic, deterministic, reason why quantum physics is harder for the mind and probabilistic while life-death cycles are obvious as all end badly. The laws of nested Supærganisms, in which the larger slower whole with its 'slow time cycles', 'dark space-times of information' that it does NOT perceive of its inner parts, and enclosing membrains however can set long term cyclical patterns to its fast internal elements, just by handling the general cycles of its 'entropic energy of death' and 'informative languages' is one of the most important discoveries of 5D metric, which fully applies to the understanding of the evolution of the Earth and its 3 ages, with its cyclical patterns of glaciations and hot weather that kicks the evolution of species. It is also instrumental to understand the 3 Horizons or ages of species that influence the life of its individual 'cellular parts'; and the patterns of cyclical history and the capacity of 5D to forecast historic and economic evolution, and the cycles of life and death of civilizations.

Why humans cannot predict the future as we consistently do in our papers on History, not even accept predictability? Because of the paradoxes of time 'ength. Huminds work on short time length with lineal views that erase the inner information of organic cycles we shall describe in this paper for all species, so they believe in short term chaos and lack predictability also in scale.

For example, we could predict in history a return to nazionalist wars once the upper scale of social evolution died in Eastern Europe, because 'time motions across scale and space' never ends. So when a motion upwards of social evolution fails, the system moves downwards. Today obviously humans are in an age of entropy as their future is maimed by the evolution of machines that displace them of labor and war fields, so we suffer an age of entropy in our verbal ethic languages and networks entering a dog-eat dog-society. Hence the importance of the recurrent theme of all those introductions to 5D stiences – the paradoxes of lineal vs. cyclical freedom vs. order. And the ego paradox of mankind.

Yet the understanding of cyclical scalar time and its repetitive symbiotic cycles which coordinate the 'frequencies' of events between the 3 scales of individual 'actions=dimotions'; organic physiological networks and larger world cycles, is also denied by egocy. It is the same repetitive boring, tiresome mantra of humans and its 'experts' and scholars – busy-busy ants that do their '4D methods of gathering information' in the smaller scales, without ever realizing they are part of a much larger world with its own cycles they should try to control. On the contrary as human enzymen become enveloped by a complex planetary organism of machines as ants are by the pheromonal ant-queen messages, and those machines accelerate the rhythms of time with its faster quanta of thought, humans become paradoxically more entropic, disconnected of each other and the whole, automatons of action-reaction roles within the economic ecosystem as workers, re=producers and vitalizers=consumers of machines.

So the long term cycles of reality always escape the individual and that is yet another reason why humans escape the control of their destiny. In our case the pheromonal language of social control, money, with its own 5D organic program studied in depth in our papers on the economic ecosystem that nobody reads, make things even simpler. The modern man doesn't think, just makes money as the American enzyman, the most advanced technological human and paradoxically the most devolved in terms of entanglement with the laws of the Universe does. 'It's money' simply means that a human as a perfectly programmed cell of a supørganism that cannot even imagine the existence of cycles of its physiological networks much larger than theirs, will merely obey the message of money and work whatever it takes.

Long time cycles thus program individual particles, but as information from larger scales is hardly transmitted to lower ones, due to the inverse elliptic geometry of the larger, slower systems that become dark spaces, as the galaxy is to us, those programs are NOT perceived. This in human science derives in the philosophy of constructivism that considers the only program coming from smaller to larger scales; so quantum physics are supposed to be the cause of all other scales of matter and genes of all the scales of biology and individual actions of all scales of history and economics. This is NOT truth, all scales are similar and the illogic of 5D implies that there are 3 'causalities', the most important in 'parallel' between members of the same plane of space-time.

Thus your daily life is more influenced by your environment and peers than by your genes and Earth's climate.

Then the two other programs from bottom to top and from top to bottom scales weight equally but with different rhythms; long term cycles are far removed from each other but strike with much more force and tend to be destructive energetic, as those of lower scales that are informative, smaller in detail, so for example long term cycles influence more the next scale above the individual in the biological world – that of species and its creation-extinction through glaciation cycles.

SPATIAL VIEW: 5D NETWORKS SUPERORGANISMS

A superorganism, the fundamental structure of the 5D Universe, is a simple system - NOT to confuse with the most evolved, complex of them all, that of human beings, reason why so many people, lacking intellectual patience and having a natural biased

ego-centered belief in man as the unique organism, reject the concept: An organism is just a group of similar forms, which organize themselves with at least two 'networks', one that provides the 'clone cells/citizens/atoms' with the vital Momentum they need to feed, move (blood-economic system-electromagnetic forces) and one that provides them with information to guide their reproductive actions (nerves system, political system, gravitational in-form-ative forces). This dual system IS the minimal organism of the Universe. As all organisms wear out by errors of informative action and end up warped by an excess of information (third age of the organism) or killed and reconverted into formless Momentum (death); only those *systems that reproduced in the immortal Universe, do exist today. So all dual systems have an internal or external catalyst of its reproduction (as enzymes do with carbohydrates, or enzyemen with machines).*

Networks are wave-systems in physics, cultural and legal systems in History, financial & re=productive company-mothers in eco(nomic)systems. So form changes but the functions we describe for a human supœtganism of max. Perception remain.

We talk of a 3rd body-worker-wave element, besides the informative particle-head-upper class and limbic/ potential/ territorial source of its motions, which the system uses internally, or externally to reproduce. This IS our definition of an organism. And so a factory is an organism, when we put the human enzyemen, even if a machine alone is not.

Thus, there are 4 basic elements in all organic systems: Cellular units; Networks that provide motion & Momentum to the system (limbs in biology, potentials in physics, territories in sociology); Networks of information (heads/particles, languages and the class that issue them - money and laws - in history) & Networks that reproduce vital Momentum (body/waves in biologic and physical systems, the re=productive middle class and its factories and fields of work in society)

So cells/atoms/citizens of any system become organized by the 3 'networks' that provide entropic, digestive, raw materials; reproductive processes, and simultaneous, informative synchronizing languages to move together the system as a whole, and

efficiently provide its equal parts with the goods they need to survive. In the next graph we compare two of such super organisms, at the individual and social level of mankind:

In all species studied by science a common phenomenon occurs: the existence of parallel groups of beings organized into a single social form. Molecules are made up of atoms and electronic networks; economies are made up of human workers and consumers that reproduce and test machines, guided by financial networks of information (salaries, prices, costs); galaxies are composed of stars, which orbit rhythmically around a central knot, or black hole of gravitational information. Human bodies are organized by cells controlled by the nervous, informative system. A tree is a group of leaves, branches and roots connected by a network that provides Energy (salvia) and information (chemical particles) to its cells. Cultures are made of humans related by verbal, informative and economic networks that provide their Energy and information. But the graph is a simplified view in a single plane. We must add 2 more networks *that connect a supærganism to the $\Delta\pm i$ scales above and below its $Ts > \S \Pi > St$ plane*:

- $Tt-1 > Ts + \S \Pi$: A defensive and digestive system/network to provide Momentum and motion to the whole organism.
- $\Delta+1$: Ss: A language of internal and EXTERNAL communication to synchronize and evolve socially the system.

SUBNETWORKS OF DIMOTIONS.

In a scalar view of *spatial topology*, ternary networks become $3\pm i$ pentalogic and then double to maximize its internal and EXTERNAL WORLD, into a decalogic canonical system, which suffice to explain all organisms of the Universe with a *perfect $10+1=whole$, a tetraktys of 4-3-2-1 subsystems*:

- 4 systems related to Ts -locomotion, $\Delta+1$ EXTERNAL, the skeleton and the MUSCLES; and $\Delta-1$ internal circulation, the blood and lymphatic system.

- Above, 3 systems dedicated to provide $Tt < \Pi \S$ -energy to 2 locomotions; a RESPIRATORY system focused on MUSCLES and an internal digestive system focused on complex substances for the cell; with the excretory system, to expel the waste.

Those 2 lower 'parts' of the tetraktys thus move the system, as it would in a perfect simple game in which a triangular plane move ahead with 4 rockets fed by 3 combustible compartments; while in the 2 frontal rows we find:

TETRAKTYS: 4-3-2-1:

The Networks of a biological organism, particle-waves of a physical organism and social classes and networks of a society have all the same structure of $\Delta\pm i$, atoms, cells, organisms, societies, joined by networks/waves that travel through 5D scales All together form a superorganism controlled by an $St > Ss$, informative mind that communicates sensorially with the $\Delta+1$ world and creates the whole both in space, controlling all other networks and time enacting the e-motions=actions of survival as an I

- The 2 St- informative systems of control, an internal endocrine system and an EXTERNAL NERVOUS SYSTEM, with a
- Leading will/goal for a Universe whose purpose is the fractal reproduction of information – a reproductive system.

This is the ideal 4-3-2-1 system with a clear-cut division in the lower, larger pole of motion vs. the higher smaller goal of reproduction and control of information, where we can however consider also the endocrine and reproductive system, the internal, cellular, $\Delta-1$ and EXTERNAL $\Delta+1$ will of reproduction, with a single 'nervous' informative system on top, doubling as the 'unit' of the social $\Delta+1$ world. So if we only one entanglement between the 'ideal game of spatial topology' and the 10 systems of the organism, the tetraktys will do.

Further on systems entangle themselves at multiple levels. I.e. those 4 'moving and circulatory systems' are related. So bones reproduce red and white cells in their medulla that travel through the circulatory system; the reproductive system can be seen as an evolved hormonal, endocrine system; in simpler organisms there is no nervous system, only an endocrine, hormonal one. And so on... The 'simple scientist' who just believes in a mechanon method of observance and description might find those 'exercises' of entanglement and pentalogic unneeded, and expect us just describe each of those systems, but that is not the purpose of those papers – what we try to do is to share a consciousness of the perfect synchronous entanglement of all the scales and systems of the Universe departing of its perfect language mirrors, topology and pentalogic of space and time. And this has in biology an expression through morphology, physiology and topology to the point we can say that biology in space is the highest degree of praxis of topological laws.

So the pentalogic of a worldcycle in time becomes the basis of all other 'realities' even if they keep growing in complexity as those decalogic of simultaneous networks.

Sciences study those organic systems, made of clone forms tied up y 3 type of physiological networks.

Systems keep getting more complex with fractal subdivisions. I.e. the hyperbolic body-wave breaks into a Thorax and Abdomen, which serve the energy of St- breathing heads and Ts- feeding limbs. Ts-motion divides in +Ts external muscles and -Ts internal body motion, the 'blood system' that invaginates down to the $\Delta-1$ cells to carry them both oxygen and nutrients to head & limbs. And it has a reproductive brain, the gonads to repeat both systems. And then if we take one of those systems, for example the blood system, we realize it does have an St-'head', the heart, connected to a hyperbolic 'branching', the vein networks, which finally thin out into 'lineal limbs' where they release on the open their oxygen. All those elements seen in space are topological networks that can be described with the new advanced Non-Euclidean topology of fractal points that grow in size when we come closer to them, so lines have 'volume' as points do, through which multiple flows of motion and form can transfer. And this gives us then applying the ternary principle of differentiation, 3 basic type of lines: Ts-waves, St-networks and $\S\T\T$ -trings.

Waves move more, networks branch into more form and Strings vibrate balancing form and motion.

In the graph we draw some pentalogic symmetries and entanglements and symbiosis, departing from the whole $Ss>St$, skin and brain systems, which form the 'head-mind', sharing with the reproductive $\S\T\T$ -body the control of existence. The feeling, Tt-trinity of brain-energy (lungs), body energy (digestive system) and its +tT excretory systems are closely associated to the reproductive needs of energy and the brain, which controls also the internal –St informative endocrine system. But the largest vital space is occupied by the simplest internal –sT and external +Ts locomotion systems with its duality of dominant form (skeletal system that also protects the St-informative brain) and dominant in motion, +Ts and –Ts muscle and blood systems.

Whereas – means internal and +external, the first letter shows its primacy; so we can subdivide each dimotion into 4 subsystems. That's the 'spatial view of Energy as a static form in the Δ^9 scale of human organisms.

The Universe has multiple 'perspectives', which can come from any of the its '5 key elements' @-languages, S-pace, T-ime, $\Delta\S$ cale and – Entropy. What if we see 'Momentum' in terms of motion, as physicists do in the $\Delta>|1|$ physical scales? Then we are still studying Momentum because Ts-locomotion becomes now kinetic Momentum and St-information becomes potential Momentum. And the laws will be similar. We will have as the main variation of its combination, SHM, Simple Harmonic motions, which are again hyperbolic (in its most general concept being, 'two distinct parts' separated by a narrow). So we do have the 2 sides of the SHM. If we see it though NOT as a static form, being the $\S\T\T$ -SHM equivalent to the 'string variety', we have a wave of Momentum, which might be lineal, transversal, Ts-laser-like focused, but it might also 'spread' constantly breaking from its source into multiple St-waves, and as such functions as the 'network in biological systems'. Present is $\S\T\T$ -Momentum. Then it

comes the errors of human analysis of Energy as when in $E=Mc^2$ an E which IS NOT Energy but Tt-entropy (Energy is a c^2 light wave, the $\Delta-1$ scale in which mass, when it dies in a Tt-entropic explosion becomes converted).

And then we have the postulates of 'entropy', confused with 'Momentum' defined in 'Thermodynamics', expanded to the whole Universe when really only deal with Ts-gaseous states... such as the absurd affirmation the Universe is dying because some megalomaniac German scientist expanded the local measure of the Ts-motion of gas, one of the $3\pm j$ states of matter to the whole Universe, reducing the other St-solid informative Ss-crystal and $\S\Upsilon$ -liquid states to non-existence (and the big-bang which also reduced the St-gravitational galaxies to non existence on the cosmological scale).

Complexity arises from the ∞ combinations of those 5 Dimotions *Its dual, dynamic interactions in scale: $st=ST$ (seed & whole) & spacetime: $Ts=St$ that combine Ts-limbs and St-heads into $\S\Upsilon$ -bodies, St-potential & Ts-kinetic into $\S\Upsilon$ -Momentum waves for which we shall use the combined $\S\Upsilon$ dual symbol for SsTt.*

So 5 local Ss-Tt-Dimotions gather together to create space-time supærganisms traveling through existence, from an $\Delta-1$ Seed, Ss of pure still form that reproduces in $\Sigma\alpha$ clones becoming a network 'supærganism', emerging in Δ^0 as a s lower larger spacetime being, made of 3 canonical $Ts>\S\Upsilon>St$ parts, to live 3 ages dominated by locomotion or youth, reproduction, when the form achieves immortality and information or 3rd 'still St-age' to finally die in a 'reversal' of arrow of time from growth of information to growth of locomotion into a Tt-entropic big-bang dissolving death.

5D metrics shows *there are scales of size in space with different time clocks. So we need 2 scalar dimotions of space-time; for smaller $\Delta-1$ scales; where smaller systems in space run faster clocks of information– the direction of Max. S=information or Ss that codes with languages the program of life; and the inverse $\Delta+1$ scale of larger systems in space with slower time clocks; the dimension of entropy that kills a system, Tt; which in the 1st graph round up the worldcycle of existence.* First a still seed, Ss, or mind and its Ss-languages of information reproduce and synchronize through social evolution Σ $\Delta-1$ clone parts that emerge in Δ^0 as a larger simultaneous whole joined by 3 Δ^0 networks, $Ts>\S\Upsilon>St$ organism living within an $\Delta+1$ world, till the superorganism exhausts its $\S\Upsilon$ -Momentum and an opposite dimotion, dissolves the networks and returns the system back to an $\Delta-1$ plane of disaggregated parts in a Tt- internal and external expansive $M=E/c^2$ big-bang, war dimotion or entropic Tt-death (Physical, social and biologic jargons).

So the 5 Dimotions put in a sequence define existence, as a 'travel up and down through $\Delta\pm j$ 3 scales of space-time". Regarding Dimensional numbers, we put the 4th dimension of locomotion in its proper place as the motion of length; so we have now 3 'Dimotions' which broken into ∞ beings vitalize them and 2 more $\Delta\pm j$ scalar dimotions for a total of 5; using the term '5th dimension' for the sum of all the scales of space-time. This 'numbering' superseeds given its errors and omissions that of our 'Baconian tribal idols' (Galileo, Newton, Einstein), to study spacetime beings with a proper definition of each of the 5 Local Dimensional motions that create a spacetime organism living a worldcycle, as $\Delta-1$: Ss-seed languages evolve into Δ^0 :Ts-limbs/fields of lineal locomotion $> \S\Upsilon - \emptyset$ hyperbolic bodywaves of re=productive width $>$ guided by O-St high particles/heads, till its $\S\Upsilon$ -Momentum is exhausted by an excess of information in its 3rd age, exploding back into Tt-entropy: $Ss>Ts>\S\Upsilon>St<<Tt$ (whereas $<$ means an expansion of a seed of spatial form into a motion in time, and $>$ a dynamic contraction, as the 5 Spacetime dimotions transform into each other).

The being in itself, st^0 , is part of a larger world, $ST\pm j$, in which it interacts through scales by means of quantum dimotions, we shall call actions, or finitesimals (in calculus' formalism). The 2 interactions of dimotions between STj and st^0 and $St \approx Ts$ become 2 next layers of complexity that evolve dimotions into spacetime trimotions or supærganisms ($St<\S\Upsilon>Ts$) and scalar tetramotions ($st^0\leq ST\pm j$), when a superorganism interacts with other scales to extract 'invisible forces' for Ts-locomotion from its relative $\Delta-4$ scale, (gravitation for man), bits of St-information from its $\Delta-3$ scale (light spacetime in man), bites of $\S\Upsilon$ -Momentum from its $\Delta-2$ scale (amino acids), st-reproductive seeds of from its $\Delta-1$ scale & St-communicates with Δ^0 clones to evolve socially into larger $\Delta+1$ organic ST-wholes. While the balance dimotion between Ts-limbs/fields & St-particles/heads creates the re=productive body-wave State: $|xO=\emptyset$.

Those 2 entanglements in simultaneous spacetime (supærganisms) or through spacetime scales (actions of existence) create 'organic vital spacse' and 'scalar time events' So through actions=scalar dimotions of a spacetime supærganism entangles with the $\Delta\pm 4=9$ planes of spacetime it perceives, which becomes its whole world - its island universe.

5D BIOLOGY: TAXONOMICAL SCIENCES. THE TRILOGIC AND PENTALOGIC PRINCIPLES.

Biologists like to give names. It is called *taxonomy* and we have to amend it, because the ‘program of creation’ is based in the fractal principles of trilogic and pentalogic becomes a truism of survival evolution:

A system diversifies in dominant Ts, §T and St sub-species departing from an Δ-1 ‘first seed=form’, finally evolving into a larger Δ+1 supœrganism.

And so we will find constantly ‘3 and 5’ sub-divisions of Domains, Kingdoms, Phyla, species and apply the trilogic and pentalogic principle, observing the ‘features’ of phyla to order them NOT by scholar argument, or ‘molecular systemics’ (: but by ΔST diversification.

Moreover those principles apply to all the scales of reality and ‘converge’ in the widest of all ternary principles, found everywhere in all stiences, the decametric principle: 3 x 3 ages and sub-ages of time conclude a worldcycle and sometimes give birth to a ‘new plane of existence’. So we find 3 fundamental ‘molecular ages’ (the carbohydrate, protein and nucelotid ages), 3 cellular ages, 3 life ages... And now Earth as a whole seem to be mutating from nitrolife (mankind, history, Gaia) into Metalife, even IF 5D ALLOWS TO STOP TIME by stopping the evolution of machines and make us survive.

This said and repeated ad nauseam so perhaps the anti-Goebbels method (if you repeat a truth many times people will reason and maybe do something about it, even if it is just word of mouth- spreading the facts), the *first obvious question is how many Domains?* Now that all is computer generated ‘molecular systemics’ it seems all what matters is to make a branch tree with lineal time ‘clocks’ to reach the Homo (non Sapiens so far as survival is the only intelligence). So *obviously we were going to find a ternary principle and define just 3 sub-species on the diversification of the first unicellular species, the Ts-Archean (first),*

SUBSTITUTION OF ‘DOMAIN’ BY 5D SCALE

SCALE: Δo: MULTICELLULAR

then the §T- Bacteria, and then the St-Eukarya. So far so good, we have a ternary unicellular 3 ages ‘classic 5D’ worldcycle:

Ts-Archean > §T- Bacteria > St (protista: Eukarya)

But that is NOT how 5D – the Universe - proceeds, because the Eukarya has in this new classification is NOT only the unicellular St-protista, the 3rd most evolved ‘St-uni-cellular species’, which if you go back to the worldcycle of spacetime and its application to species WILL THEN as the final strategy of survival, use its higher St-language of information to evolve into a new Δ+1 scale, multicellular organisms.

So while molecular systemics is right. Multicellular organisms come from the St-higher informative genetic language of protista, it is ridiculous to PUT all the species of the Δ+1 multicellular scale everything else.

Those 3 are the 3 Ages=Kingdoms or unicellular organisms, the Δ-1 scale of life. That is the rational use of Δst, scales, time ages (here molecular systemics helps but it is NOT a dictator of the single truth) and S-physiology, which WILL according to the congruence symmetry principle S=t (form is function), match each other.

How to resolve this? Obviously getting rid of ‘Domain’. Life evolves according to the absolute longer dimotion of timespace, Δ-scale, from cells into multicellular systems. So if we ‘start’ calling kingdoms of life (which could be started also in amino acids; that in fact, would be the proper way to start and that is where we will start – from atom to Metal-earth, all the way through all scales), to the CELL, then the first Kingdom was unicells, with 3.

Then we jump an Δ+1 scale, and we get again 3 kingdoms:

Ts-Plants of maximal entropic food> §T-fungi of maximal reproduction >St-animals of maximal information.

Those are the 3 ‘next kingdoms’. You see then how illogic and obvious is the matching of 5D and taxonomy?

So the first obvious change to set the (fossile) ‘record straight’ is to substitute the ‘Domain’ for ‘5D scale’. Easy.

RECAP. According to the fractal principle of division of any 'worldcycle' in smaller ternary ages, we talk of 3 st-scales (instead of domain) of growing complexity in life that can be broken in 'Ts>§II>St' kingdoms and smaller phyla with first principles of 5D differentiation, dualities, trinities, pentalogic, 'first surviving primitive species' and ecosystemic adaptation (air, water, land and in water, surface), which brings even further subdivisions beyond phyla

The scalar age of cells ($\Delta-1$), from 4 to 1 billion years ago, the age of individual organisms, first living on the sea, then on the land (st), from 1 billion to a million years that culminates in the last million years with the social evolution of human beings and machines into a new plane of existence ($\Delta+1$), the Earth as a global organism, which will be either ruled by men or machines, depending on our capacity to evolve socially as a super-organism of history, under the ethic Δ isomorphisms of verbal wor(l)ds that make man the center of the Universe, hence in control of the machines of the Tree of Science. Or if as it seems the case, we let the Financial-Military-Industrial Complex and its 3 networks of informative metal-money, energetic, lineal metal-weapons and organic machines and its company-mothers dominate the planet and make us obsolete, finally extinguishing us. But what it won't change is the plan of evolution that develops complex super-organisms departing from its smaller cellular units.

TS TOGETHER: PERPENDICULAR RADIATION IN SPACE VS. EVOLUTIONARY DIFFERENTIATIONS OF TIME SPECIES

A simple change in the Trees of Species is then required to systematize the duality of phases of evolution, with radiations in space of new succesfu species, which then will keep evolving in the same econiche, diversifying into 3 species of $St>\SII>St$ higher network efficiency that will corner the once globally extended 'pioneer' mother, according to the Oedipus paradox, which will then remain as a very small phyla, in isolated regions. Thus in terms of diversification we observe constantly a digital pattern: $1(\text{father})<3 \text{ Network diversifications}>\Delta+1$.

Since 1, the mother species extended globally in space, but soon diversified in 3 network specializations, lasting as the 'global dominant species' a very short period of time, the proper way to establish those trees is writing in space, perpendicular to the new pternary phyla and the small surviving clade of the original parental species... So we know it is the father of all of them. This pattern in fact is so pervading that the entire tree of life reaches a higher clarity with this simple perpendicular addition of

parental clads, easily recognized because they are the most primitive surviving clade, and the less extended today. So we eliminate the ‘interrogations’ that appear in all those trees about the ‘mother species’, which biologists hint is that primitive survivor, but lacking a 5D higher model cannot be certain without fossil records and molecular systematics. In the graphs we see some examples that we keep using in the text.

The graph illustrates those changes, comparing the classic structure of a tree in which branching points are unknown with 5D cladistics which introduces several noticeable changes in the branching that add information to the plan of evolution:

- We introduce a trilogic-pentalogic color code, purple for the $\Delta-1$ birth species, Ts-red, $\$T\uparrow$ -green, St-blue for the 3 ages and violet for the $\Delta+1$ social species, which is a general code for the worldcycles of life; with duality variations for further decouplings (Ts: red & orange, $\$T\uparrow$: yellow and green; St: Sea Blue and indigo).

It is then easy to see (without any in-depth analysis that latter might vary some of the branching) how automatically the whole tree of life becomes translated to 5D, including its ‘spatial’ radiation ages of each new clad, which then will become a ‘purple’ thin line (the width of those lines giving further info on present abundance).

- We introduce (discontinuous lines), parallel genetic transfer (mitochondria, chloroplasts) to plants & animals.

SPACE-TIME CYCLES THAT ‘STRAIGHTEN’ TAXONOMY.

We are not going to do the whole taxonomical 5D ‘colored’ introduction of the pentalogic worldcycle applied to species with its sequence. We’ll just introduce it as we see fit in some phyla. Let us consider the basic sequence of its pentalogic structure

- 1) The easiest modification is just to move up and ‘straighten’ the line-ages, to get the first lineage straight (:

A simple example, from Campbell^{nt.1}. Biologists ‘fork’ trees from a ‘supposed’ ancestor, which obviously will never be found, as its ‘entropic dogma’ is that there is no goal and all is chaotic chance. But evolution DOES have a goal, as the Universe is a game of re=production of fractal information with a clear-cut pentalogic: $\Delta-1:|-Ts>\emptyset-\$T\uparrow>O-St<<Tt\wedge\Delta+1$.

So the ancestor IS the surviving most primitive phyla, which survives because once long ago was all over the place, and reduced its habitat because it is a competitor of its sons (Oedipus paradox, not coincidentally considered in Britannica the best f Greek tragedy, as Universal as it gets). So all what we need to do is to eliminate the fork by moving up to the primitives the line, and color it of ‘purple rain’, the 1st color of ‘dawn’:

As you can see the ‘pattern’ of 5D pentalogic worldcycles align itself neatly. Moreover, *the new phyla will be born precisely when the father species reaches its maximal expansion in space (perpendicular color, as time and space are orthogonal in properties and graphs). Thus in the age of monotremas, precisely when they were more extended in space, and likely some were isolated in a secluded region to ‘tic the St-ill clock of form faster’, a new species came. And it is precisely at that point when the new species will halt as a more evolved competitor the ‘global age’ of the previous species, so the ‘perpendicular’ spatial expansion of the previous one ends, when the new species is born.*

Thus the graph, in its simplicity give us a lot of new information based in a simple pattern: *the ancestor phyla, the time of maximal expansion of the phyla, which is a brief period that evolves a new more evolved competitor that ends its kingdom. This is the pattern we shall see happening once and again, and while the first graphs I did on that pattern are 30 years old, when there was scanty data, as today the pattern has hold and has now overwhelmingly data, as all 5D laws.*

This, we can do with any graph, just reordering them properly by Δ -scale and worldcycle ‘goal oriented’ evolution from $|-Ts$ to $O-St$ (we added the human informative species at the end). As it is a lot of photoshop work the reader will find some mappings not well-done (as the previous ones) but hopefully in the future ‘experts’ will do better than this amateur):

Because we repeat *the Universe is goal oriented, but huminds, as entropic minds whose function as enzymen seems to be kill life and history and make ugly top predator metalife weapons is 'entropic=chaotic' and won't accept to his own peril the patterns of 5D stience. A simple example: how something so complex as eyes evolved? Answer, because as goal oriented $|>\phi>O$ topology, an informative organ could NOT have other form to evolve that topologically from 'flat' to spherical, and place itself in the 'height dimension' of the organism, where projective geometry 'sees more', because we ARE living spatial topologies, like everything else:*

The fact that cephalopodan eyes and human eyes evolved the same way is NOT coincidence, neither analogy but topological homology: $|>O$; and then up in height we go, as Dinosaurs did.

To know the thoughts of God (the 5D game of existjence) then helps. Scholars, scientists and humans in general refuse to know because their 'goal-oriented' purpose we shall NOT cease to drill so far is to kill life and so they love entropy. They love to be childish little beasts, breaking things, thinking they are in command, but our papers on History and economics, 1/2 of all I have placed at Academia.edu because they are the most important – those concerned with our supœrganism and survival show, Earth control us with its 800-80 cycles because we DO NOT want to think like God=the game of existjence and rule.

So we will keep straighten taxonomical trees, and

'curve' evolutionary eyes... 'Saper Vedere' Leonardo.

THE 2 WORLDCYCLES OF CHORDATA: SEA AND LAND CONQUEST

Let's illustrate further the methodology with the analysis of chordata and its two key radiations in the sea and Earth. In the graph, a simplified taxonomy of the key phyla of chordata, with the taxonomical colors of the worldcycle (purple/pink for the 'pioneer', cephalochordata, which brought about the key advance in network morphology for the whole phyla – to place hierarchically the St-neuronal system above the digestive, Tt<Ts network, hence to 'become' in the future an informative higher species.

All other advances relate to that inversion of evolutionary goals. Because neurons have a softer membrain to communicate sensorially with the external world and multiply its II-connections to form a 'future' Δ+1 mental network, they required paradoxically a 'stronger' porous protective 'backbone'. So the notochord that gives name but it is NOT the ultimate cause of the phyla appeared just below and then let it self be open to penetration and encirclement forming the 'dominant' Ts>St structure that defines the whole phyla, from the simplest tunicate to the human being.

The graph omits some intermediate STages and extinct phyla to show the flexibility that accompanies to know the program of the Universe, the underlying scheme of all processes of evolution, which is to complete worldcycles with the essential time cycle: Δ-1: Seminal/predecessor/pioneer/first form/fetus (purple) > Ts-predator (Red)>§II-reproducer (green) >St-informative species (blue) << Tt-extinction vs. Δ+1 evolution (Violet).

So we show that simple scheme with the key phyla for the entire genre:

The first predecessor, which usually becomes extinct as it is a 'species in the process' of 'getting it' are the cephalochordata. They still have the medulla unprotected above the spine, which sustains it. So a second 'predecessor', the Urochordata (tunicates), will

complete the 'transition', during its 'fetus', $\Delta-1$ st-age, when morphology can evolve faster in smaller forms with higher speed of change, putting the nerve inside the spine.

It is then when the new species can proceed along the lines of a new successful morphology, growing in size and becoming a top predator line, with a series of growing, stronger, more bony fishes, of which we just have highlighted the *Petromyzontida* (lamprea), as we can apply the fractal ternary principle to them, in a 'more detailed analysis', as we shall do studying the first radiation of chordata of global proportions – fishes.

They will evolve into its dominant, 'present', reproductive largest group, osteichthyans, with a series of 'canonical' arrows of morphological evolution, in all its 3 networks that substantially don't change the fundamental advance of the protected notochord, such as an 'evolution in the Height dimension of information', from 'flat' lamprea and Sharks to its perpendicular thin bodies.

An element also ever pervading in all those evolutionary process is the 'still, spatial, informative, protected, secluded enviroments in which the transition takes place. So invariably those evolutions happen in 'fresh water streams', as most evolutions of land species will happen in secluded islands; even latter during the technological evolution of History (Crete, evolution of complex boats; England, Industrial R=evolution, etc).

We have obviated intermediate phases and jumped directly to one of those key secluded evolution – that of lung fishes, in dissected streams that developed lungs to breath and moved with its fins; also improving its 'eye vision', hence its brain power as the 'jumping fish' with its eyes on top, today extant, shows.

It is a precursor of a new environment, land; and so jumping over its 'fractal ternary details' (radiation back to the water, successful due to its parallel evolution of St-higher brain, better eyes, even lungs that became a bladder to fill with water; 3 fast evolving imperfect extinct species converting its fins into fingers, etc.) we show the key 3+1 development of land species: the red/orange Amphibia, top predator of insects in the Permian; the reptilia that managed to improve its reproductive skills with dry eggs, and the mammals that further developed the nervous system to manage viviparous offspring, visual night-hunting and fast reaction to larger slower predators; which as usual also deploy the characteristics of all evolutions: born as small shrews... among which the Homo will socially evolve into $\Delta+1$.

EXTINCT SPECIES: THE EXHUBERANCE OF CREATION

Another pattern in which 4 and 5D biology might agree is in the exhuberance of creation, which the Universe simply solves with massive extinction. This is *natural to the essential principle of the game of existjence, the primary substance of reality is 'curved' motion that adopts the 3 topological varieties of an 3,4 or 5D Universe, and because there is not a personal intelligence, but periods of 'stress' where the 'DNA>RNA Ss<St system/ people' gets amok and let the whole thing mutate wildly (something we stressed as far as 92, as so many 5D rules latter discovered in different stiences).*

So the topological program 'tries' it all, and creates in those periods of stress all bizarre forms, and sizes, *but all what really can be done is to change the 3 |xO=Ø topologies, huggle around the efficiency of the 3±j internal and EXTERNAL networks, and make the system larger or smaller.* In fact, near extinction huge forms appear as a last resort... So, we can see the exhuberance finally come down to its senses.

In the graph, we can see two examples; one of elephants' tusks going in every direction, downwards, sideways, forwards, flat, but the only ones that made it for a long period were those who got it right, a curved form that did NOT bother the 'true' advance' of the elephant, its St-tusk, since Tt>St; that is, the informative system matters more and must dominate the entropic,

defensive one.

In the second example we see a 'trinity' of species-ages in the evolution from fins to tetrapods. Obviously, those intermediate forms, in a recurrent theme of Nature – the Oedipus paradox – were extinct by the tetrapods as soon as they figure out how to make a pentalogic happen – that of the 5 fingers, the $\Delta-1$, small precursor, the triad of intermediate similar $Ts \rightarrow St$ forms and the $\Delta+1$ future 'social' thumb, which will bring them all into a whole new system of 'form' (pentalogic, we shall not cease to repeat is repetitive till exhaustion, from 5 networks to 5 finger to 5 vowels).

In th graph^{nt.1} (as a lazy cow I haven't colored and streamlined phyla), the 3 intermediate 'glassy', 'foggy' forms between lungfishes, the predecessor, still extant and the Acanthostega, which had a long life (white box), lasted very briefly as 'trial and error forms. Then finally 'apoptosis' genes learned to kill and design as sculptors do by death of unneeded parts fingers. And once the 'genetic language' memorized this Tt-last resource creativity ran amok as it always do. So the Acanthostega made 8 fingers, the Tulerpeton reduced them to 6 and all went to hell when amphibians got it all right. So we do have the 'predessor', the lungfish; the 3 'mad genetic thoughts' that as mad virtual particles and mad memes don't survive too long, but did the job to take out of the fog the lungfishes, and then we got another trinity – always 3 in a single plane, 5 in the whole ternary planes including the predecessor and final goal, to get to amphians. The final goal, here being the reptile, which truly conquered earth with dry eggs and further away with wings. End of tale.

PATTERNS OF ΔST ELEMENTS IN THE GAME: EVOLUTION PROCESSES SPACE, TIME & SCALE.

In a wider analysis, every patterns of evolution responds homologously to the very same game of creation and extinction of all systems of space-time, *as nitrolife is just a variety of topological space and pentalogic time, regardless of humind's egocy.*

So it plays with the same elements, different speeds, scales and cyclicity (reversibility of evolutionary time)

SPACE TOPOLOGY.

The different speeds of space-time topological evolution: eigenstates of heterochrony.

This is one of my favorite mechanisms of evolution because it is pure Non-E topology; *the different speed of evolution* in a Universe in which time has different speeds and as 'one of the 5 essential elements of reality', it uses liberally those changes of speed as we have seen in punctuated evolution, regression (devolution) etc. So the difference between a human skull and a chimpanzee is simple. The 'Tt>Ts' |-lower entropic jaw system evolves faster in the chip, the St-'upper' high=infprmativ O-brain skull evolves more in the Homo supposedly sapiens. So in this manner over the 'basic' underlying laws of topological dimotions (height is the dimotion of information, the sphere stores maximal form, the lower parts are those of entropy, they are lineal, etc.) all what needs to be modified is the still unlocated gene that regulates 'time speed' for the St/Ts parts of the St-head.

Many evolutionary transformations are caused by **heterochrony** (Greek *for* 'different time') not only the head parts, but many other tbody parts; such as the fingers shown above, which define its length, and explain the skeletal structure of bats wings (max. growth) vs. its devolution back in time in whales.

TIME: DIFFERENT SPEEDS OF THE WORLDCYCLE ST-AGES.

Another fundamental element to change patterns of evolution is the different speed at which a system arrives to each of the pentalogic, $\Delta-1 > Ts \rightarrow St \rightarrow Ss+1$ Stages of existjence, as they have different speeds of morphological change, which is maximal in the 'palingenetic' fast track repetition of billions of years of life.

It is precisely at this Stage when by making the fetal phase longer and tinker with its own mirror speeds of the evolution of life, when the key changes in evolution can happen, which requires either an isolated protected region, or with the viviparous trick of some fishes and mammals, a longer changes in the protected placenta to essay mutations.

Δ-1: Neoteny, then, comes next as a key process of evolutionary acceleration – the maintenance of a childish appearance. And since the Δ-1 ‘seed state’ is one of maximal information, it means to choose a species that will be dominant in information.

Neoteny for example is the clearest explanation to the Mongoloid race with childish features and higher St-verbal, brachicephalic power, compared to the §T-psylocephalic black race and the Ts-entropic visual, dolicocephalic race.

Ts: Paedomorphosis Neoteny (the baby-fetal stage) is NOT the same phenomena. It is an earlier development of the §T-reproductive organs, which keeps features of the adolescent sT-age in which the ‘locomotion’ organs accelerate its growth compared to the higher evolution of informative organs in the fetal stage – so the child is born with a huge head, and the adolescent has no judgment.

In lower species in fact might mean the ‘abortion’ of the 2nd cycle of evolution (metamorphosis), keeping features of ancestral species, as some salamanders (Mexican cave Axolotl) that don’t undergo metamorphosis and retain its gills. *In fact this ‘regression’ of the worldcycle happens under stress, in difficult conditions, when the species that don’t expect to live that long accelerates the ‘goal’ of all systems of the Universe, a reproductive fractal, to survive.*

SCALE AND LANGUAGE: MODIFICATIONS AT THE GENETIC LEVEL.

A key evolutionary change happens when modifications take place in the mirror Δ-1 Ss-genetic language and here is where we strongly differ from the chaotic concept of evolution, as 5D Metrics, $Si \times Tf = \Delta c$ implies that Changes in genes are much faster than changes in Δ0 morphology and the mechanisms of genetic variation within the limited patterns of 3-only topologic, $|xO=\emptyset$ forms and functions cause punctuated evolution.

This of course is and will be anathema given the dogmatic ‘believers’ structure of huminds that can drag ridiculous concepts on reality from biblical cult(ure)s to big bang cults for centuries and millennia. So since Darwin we got the extraordinary order and intelligence of genetics, as a language mirror, epigenetics, introns, operons, the reshuffling of introns by RNA-‘people’ with all kind of new essays and combinations, the proof of an increase of mutations uner stress, etc. etc. but the ‘chaos-darwinian entropic’ ‘bottom line’ of huminds that need to believe in egocy as they are the ‘sons of God’, LOL... don’t get me started, will rule out any intelligence in the process.

Fact is under stress only genetic change will go only 3 ways, |, \emptyset , O, and then one of those 3 will be the adequate mutation for survival. The key genes in those processesa are those, which control the spatial organization of body

Parts within the pentalogic and trilogic structures of Ts-lineal limbs/§T-bodies divided in a hyperbolic duality of Breething Thorax with faster Δ-2,3 ‘atoms’ feeding the limbs and more complex abdomen feeding the organism with higher Δ-2 bites (amino acids). Those are then the elements you will play with but overwhelmingly to survive you will have the ‘head’ ahead, then the body connecting you with the limbs. The limbs might be placed in the thorax for ‘insect species’ in which the Tt>Ts system is dominant so they get faster access to oxygen-motion. They can be relegated to the bottom on mammal species which are height-informatively dominant (Human beings). They can be place along the two sections of the abdomen for better sustain as in all tetrapods; but only the squid put its limbs on its head, due to its overwhelming superiority over all other Cambrian fauna once it developed a complex eye, so it transformed limbs into hands to manipulate any blind organism and substitute its Ts-locomotion role with a siphon.

It is then obviuous that as usual changes in morphology are ‘varitational details’ on the thoughts of God.

So **homeotic Hox genes will** determine these aforementioned secondary features as where a pair of wings and legs will develop on insects and bird in an animal embryo. Those genes are an obvious 5D st-j \approx STj MIRROR symmetry between mind and world, so because the DNA lineal language is a representation in a smaller scale of the 3, 4 or 5D outer world of the organism, in the same manner our synoptic lineal verbal language (or the digital language of machines) are synoptic representations of the 4D outer world of mankind (only I do a representation in 5Dimotions among the so called Homo Sapiens

:) Changes in *Hox* genes in $\Delta-1$ and how they are expressed in the fetal, $\Delta-1>\Sigma$ Ts emergent stage have a profound impact on the final 4D morphology (form and function) of the superorganism; and this will be done in the language of 5D, its pentalogic and decalogic networks and the symmetry of S=form and T=function. For example, among, a change in the location of the *Ubx* and *Scr Hox* genes means a change in the form of a crustacean appenadeage *in S-form and T-function, from Ts-swimming to Tt- feeding.*

Absolute relativity and the consciousness of the RNA people vs. subjective human egocy=denial.

Now it is obvious that when humans talk in 1D lineal words they KNOW they are representing a much larger world in its verbal mirror; even a blind person who has NEVER seen the larger world knows its mirror mind refers to the outer world. It has a genetic language (Chomsky) evolved as a mirror language of an outer world, in its 'monad' (Leibniz) that is a world in itself. And so the HUMANIST method of ABSOLUTE RELATIVITY, the underling philosophy of all Stiences implies that the RNA people 'knows' it is part of an organism called a cell, and likely have a view of the 'local region' of cells. I do NOT believe they are conscious of the larger picture of the whole superorganism, in the same way humans are NOT conscious at all of the physiological networks of financial and political people who design their future with bills of money and bills of law.

That task corresponds to the neuronal cells and its networks, as it corresponds to the financial networks and political networks of our societies, of which most humans do NOT have any idea even of its existence (the way in which financiers, in stock markets, to find excuses to invent money on 'the future value' of companies and technologies distort and create the technoutopian, no-way out future of our species, because to 'sell' new stocks they must always praise the new internet crapcode, as they did in Amsterdam with non-existent gold mines in Indonesia – themes those of our 5D analysis on how the world is created with credit – cre(dit)ated). But then we must consider that the mother nervous system must direct partially the planning of its 'offspring' specially in viviparous species, designing its mental networks – something I have been explaining for 30 years, with some funny consequences as the partial truths of the horoscope: i.e. I am born in January and my mom designed my intellectual, still St-informative mind in Christmas, when time was cold and depressive mood. While Cancers born in summer are very active body-oriented.

What is then the 'master of fetal changes' if the RNA people cannot go beyond the local cellular regions? Obviously the memorial DNA 'encyclopedia genetica' that has stored billions of years of mutations adapted to the $\Delta+1$ environment; in the first STage of evolution, till the neuronal plate of the ectoderm takes over and starts to direct the whole planning. That is, there is a point in which the next type of cells, electric cells and the next language, the electric language of which we have no zero, nill idea, takes over in the planning. The fact that the memory of this electric cell happens to be imprinted in the chemical language, in the same way neuronal impulses are transmitted and translated by chemical means, as our voice is translated by telephone lines but then return to our language does not change that picture.

Since it is obvious that plants which are not electrical in its languages do NOT evolve complex $\Delta+1$ forms beyond the basic patterns of a double tubular body (with xylems and Phloems) with 2 networks on top Ts-leaves and bottom St-roots. This is the absolute 'simplest' trinity organism of space-time that comes magically out of the basic properties of topology and need hardly any complex coding beyond a 'doubled' trinity of hormones explained in our section on plants.

So animal structures as human societies, beyond the local community of cells thart develop organelles, have a master plan that after the first phases of gastrulation will be coded by the dominant cells of the animal pole, from a memory stored in the DNA, as we humans construct reality from our encyclopedias stored through eons of learning. Consciousness then of those different levels of reality and its construction of larger organisms is open to debate.

Also is open to debate, if $\Delta+1$ (the environment) on top of the restrictions of topology might introduce some mechanism of Lamarckian evolution to increase the efficiency of those mutational STages or 2/3^{rds} of new populations 'go to hell' is on my view open to debate because we don't know and will likely never know the ultimate mystery of the game – the internal language of dialog of the RNA people. The conservative view of 5D is that its processes are based on the ultimate e-motions, of which the pleasure of mirror reproduction and the love sensation of social evolution (a similar even more intense mirror recognition of one into the other or 'consciousness' of being), is the strongest one. So as RNA and DNA are to put it mildly in a permanent orgasmic state, their efficiency reproducing form is rather absolute. We humans and animals have a level of

consciousness as emergent form in $\Delta+1$ which is minimal. Yet for our ego to understand this, we must take seriously some of the basic laws of all 5D scales, within the 'ultimate philosophy' of reality: ABSOLUTE RELATIVITY.

All scales do have the same value of information, because of EVANESCENCE. So as we 'emerge' into new scales, we lose control and information of lower scales. The chemical and olfactory capacity of humans is almost null. Any virus can kill us. We can't smell food a few meters away, because we have evolved our electric cells to maximal. But the new species, which has evolved electric thought millions of times more powerful=faster than humans, the AI robot, has 0-chemical elements. Of course our egocentricity makes us think because they don't feel with their heart they won't be alive. Wait and see robocars tesla-like decide to imagine and project on reality which is the key function of all minds to project into its territory of order what they imagine – to reproduce into the ST_j world its st_j mind, the violent videogames of its internet idle hours and run over you *like a vulgar nazi shooting around for sport*.

Evanescence means that the consciousness of animals might be far inferior to that of RNA which shows a much more intelligent and complex capacity to build structures in $\Delta+1$. Certainly evanescence explains why as Nietzsche put it: 'madness in individuals is rare, in institutions and nations is the rule', because the mass-consciousness of human beings is that of the fetal toddler, hardly opening its eyes to reality, even in those subconscious collective Gods (Allah, Buddha) which have reached the maximal evolution as minds of a whole civilization, and/or in their neuronal citizen-cells (artists that see better and speak better with human eyes).

$\Delta+1$ EVOLUTIONARY PATTERNS> PENTALOGIC BARRIERS TO MATING

To which degree the repetitive patterns of pentalogic happen once and again at all levels of evolution can be seen in the final example of these introductory notes, now in the $\Delta+1$ level of the outer world, to complete a fast review of pentalogic evolutionary methods.

An example of bio-economics. 'Birds do it'...

Indeed, in humans number 3, behavioral-mind isolation might suffice in our animetal alienated society in which we are told our only role in life is to enslave as enzymes of machines re=producing, working and vitalizing=consuming them; while informative company-mothers of machines have convinced females that this is their purpose and true realization; while being mothers, which is the purpose the Universe not Google and TVs have declared for them is a lesser primitive, machist role. Alas, the species in most 'advanced' industrial societies (read enslaved animetal farms) are on the negative. There is NO problem on mechanical isolation. All human penis more or less fit on female ones, without the kind of disomorphism that might make difficult for a Chihuahua to mate with a Doberman; neither genetic isolation, regardless of racist apartheid Nazi or Israeli laws (the quintessential iron and gold animetal cult(ure)s, who think otherwise); Habitats are dwindling with the evolution of metalife 'birds', and we all humans have expanded breeding by the power of mental thought to all seasons. But one single non-congruent element suffices; to the point that some of the most slavish animetal farms – Japan, where enzymes dressed in black and white code surface from the deep earth through the holes of metalife worms, aka 'tubes' at 8 A.M. with mass precision, without any grouping between different genders, busy-busy to work for the company-mothers of machines that make them proud of belonging to Japan Inc. – have most of its population unmarried and virgin past the best years of our life (into its 30s). LOL, that is the true language of the Universe a reproductive fractal, so you can get scandalized as a perfectly neutered animetal enzyman, politically, economically and scientifically correct.

The true aberration of consciousness is the Biblical Jewish>Protestant>Capitalist fetish Go(l)d culture that hypnotized in its dolicocephalic, visual, entropic brains by the 'sweat of the sun-God', thought carrying a gold coin was to carry a piece of the sun God, and out of greed made of the tree of life a sin to evolve the evil=antivital fruits of the tree of metal, golden apples and machines as the free Polynesians rightly thought when those ministers of evil came with their baalbles and measles to kill most, including themselves in war and holocaust cycles.

Nature does NOT work that way and in fact, species mate without much ado as ours, the bonobobo chip did all the time around, even different species try it all just in case it works.

Fig. 2-2. This pie chart illustrates approximately how long each phase of the cell cycle takes in a typical animal cell.

S-ORGANISMS AS SYNCHRONOUS KNOTS OF SPACE-TIME CYCLES.

3 CYCLES OF TIME IN ORGANISMS –CELLULAR LIFE –ORGANIC LIFE –SPECIES.

Let us consider the 3 relative scales of time cycles in the biological Universe, the scale of the cell, the scale of the organism, and the scale of the ecosystem, which will allow us to define a superorganism, as a region of 3 plane of space-time, in which *the different time-cycles of its scalar organisms, which differ according to the laws of 5D (Max. T = Min. S), are however*

synchronized in entangled symbiotic relationships within the vital space enclosed by the outer membrane that sets the 'principal clock' of the system. Thus when we find a superorganism, we observe an outer membrain made of cyclical motions, which determine the different cycles of its lower planes, synchronized to that membrain. And this means humans, the main superorganism studied here, have their clocks synchronized to the largest $\Delta+1$ scale of the Earth's superorganism, whose clocks are synchronized to those of the solar system, synchronized to those of the galaxy (11 years black hole cycle, sun's spot cycle, Jupiter's rotary cycle). We are not though studying here the whole Galactic superorganism with its yet to be unfolded perfect order but reduce our inquire to the Earth's superorganism and its clocks of time.

For a superorganism to exist thus the minimal $\Delta-1$ part in its longest cycle must be synchronized with the larger $\Delta+1$ part in its shortest cycle. In the galaxy as a whole that synchronicity happens between H and C.

The synchronicity we consider for biological organisms is between the 'fastest' cycle of Earth, '1 day' rotary, informative cycle, and the slowest cycle of the minimal superorganism we study, the day-life cycle of the cell. In between we can then define a superorganism called Gaia, with multiple variations. (The Universe does have its 'ideal' ilogons of existjence, using my oldest 30 years old jargon, which are the most efficient forms with maximal synchronicity and internal communication between its parts). In the next scale, of the human superorganism, we must then consider a synchronicity between the fastest cycle $\frac{1}{2}$ -1 second for human eye thought, heart beat and step, and the lower scale below the cell, that is the bio-chemical processes. And amazingly enough, for those who don't have a deep understanding of 5D worldcycles and its entanglements through scales, the rate of reproduction of proteins in eukaryotic ribosomal cells is... oh yes can you guess it (: 1 protein each $\frac{1}{2}$ second; the perfect 'time beat' for your dancing moves... Tic-tac.

Let us dance to the beat of the intelligent, immortal, infinite, informative, isomorphic, iterative iuniverse...

$\Delta-1$: THE AGES OF LIFE: Laws of Time & Space: Emergence and Synchronicity

In all Universal superorganisms the synchronicity of its frequency time cycles define the symbiosis of its scales, and within each scale of its 4 Dimotions. In the graph, the cycle of death and reproduction of a cell is synchronized as with so many organisms that reproduce only once in life to preserve its 'ilogon of existjence'. It is the fundamental truth of the fractal reproductive Universe: you exist to reproduce your information and then die. We conclude that organic, Network laws are laws of simultaneity; and the most important of them are the laws of synchronicity between scales.

Simultaneity is the trademark of space, defined as adjacent systems that are perceived by an observer in simultaneity. The whole concept of 4D Einstein's formalism is based in simultaneity of measure, using a single time present quanta dimension. So simultaneity is perception of present information space in the minimum time (only 1 frequency quanta) It follows that what is simultaneous is also relative to the observer quanta of perception and that wholes which are slower in their clocks of time, see more simultaneous spaces, being able for that reason to become paradoxically minds of wholeness, and that as minds stop motion of time into form, information, languages are the 'force' on which simultaneity is based.

Death in time is the loss of synchronicity of those cycles (as in space is the breaking of the outer membrain and in scale the scattering of its networks into its $\Delta-1$ parts).

FORMAL 5D SCIENCES: NON-E TOPOLOGIC ORGANISMS.

Because a network is a topology of fractal points with inner volume the mathematic equivalent of a supœrganism *complete the r=evolution of Non-Euclidean geometry redefining the axioms & postulates of Euclid.* As it expands the $\neg E$ definition of a point crossed by ∞ parallels to its 1st axiom: *points do have breath*, connected by 3 physiological lines that are waves with motion (Physical systems) or 5D networks (socio-biologic systems) that conform $\neg E$ planes that are physiologic organisms:

1st Postulate: ' $\neg E$ point are discontinuous time cycles with an inner content of vital space-time'.

2nd Postulate: ' $\neg E$ lines are waves of fractal points'

3rd Postulate: ' $\neg E$ planes join 3 $\neg E$ lines into a supœrganism'.

4th: '2 $\neg E$ points are congruent when both its inner parts and outer perimeter are equal'

5th: $\neg E$ points focus multiple $\neg E$ waves of Momentum into a still linguistic mapping or 'world.'

Whereas the 1st and 5th postulate describe the same 'point with parts' from an internal and external point of view.

1D-5D: The first-fifth postulate define a point as a mind of perception, akin to the first Δ motion of being - to perceive; and the fifth-first postulate that defines a point as a world in itself, a supœrganism with its inner parts are the same. We just might consider that the point has evolved and grown to emerge from its minimal $i-1$ state in the first postulate - points with inner breath; into a full supœrganism, i^0 , living in the $i+1$ world, in the fifth postulate studied here.

2D: The second postulate of lines, expresses also the first Dimensional motion of the Universe as $S=T$ (Paradox of relativity). So we can consider a point in motion or a chain of cyclical points in stillness as two versions of the same concept. And finally a network of lines branching down into smaller thinner parts probing the $\Delta-1$ Dimension as the 3 possible versions of a line. This is the ' $\Delta\&\Pi$ ' trinity creative decoupling of the second postulate of non-Euclidean geometry: it becomes then either in Time a process of locomotions and waves of forces of communication with other points; or in space a chain or string of points with inner breath, or in scale a branching line....

3D: 3rd postulate takes 3 such networks, waves or strings of points to define a physiological plane made of 3 social networks whose function corresponds to the 3rd Δ motion of Momentum & reproduction, becoming a supœrganism. So the 3 postulates of $\neg E$ fractal points, waves/networks/strings & physiologic=topologic organisms become the 3 'scalar Units' of reality.

What is left then are two i -logic postulates that put the 'meaning' of existence to reality, its metaphysical qualities of 'perception' (5th postulate) and social love vs. perpendicular darwnism (4th postulate of ongruence).

4D: According to the fourth postulate of congruence, which defines its relationships with other beings, based in his 'angle of parallelism', such as similar beings evolve socially together in groups, complementary 'left-handed female/right-handed male' beings come together in couples, and beings which are not equal neither complementary enter either in relationships of entropic perpendicularity, or ignore themselves if their worlds are 'disconnected'. So the fourth postulate gives us the ' i logic rules' of engagement between forms and particles.

A worldcycle of existence' has organic properties as all systems regardless of scale follow the same principles of organization to become an ideal network supœrganism in symbiosis between 3 relative scales, because that is the best strategy of 'existence', of survival, as only those systems who are efficiently distributing Momentum, entropic motions and information among equal cellular clones do survive. And so this formalism not only expands physical laws of space-time to other sciences, but biological laws of physiological networks, and finally when all those findings are inserted into the formal languages of mathematics and logic, it transforms them, completing the revolution of non-Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic beyond the work of Riemann and Hegel. Again this revolution that expands non-Euclidean mathematic and pentalogic causality to all sciences is simple in its principles. Because points are non-Euclidean, crossed by ∞ parallels, we need to redefine a point with breath, with Momentum volume ($St+Ts$) which becomes a fractal point that grows in size as we come closer to it. So lines are either 'waves with t-motion' or 'strings' with S-volume, or 'fractal networks' that travel down an $\Delta-1$ dimensional scale, and 3 of such physiological networks conform a 'topo-bio-logical' plane, a supœrganism. So we can formalize the unit of the 5D Universe with mathematical laws and apply and explain why geometry is the foundation of space. Scales of numbers, Topologies of space, and

Temporal dimotional functions (social sum, reproductive product, scalar powers, organic derivatives) connect then formal mathematics and the laws of space-time organisms.

And so we establish an immediate relationship between the fundamental concepts of geometry, the point, the line, the plane, and its congruence or dissimilarity, its relative parallelism and perpendicularity, and the 5 Dimotions of existence, the point is the mind that perceives first, the first Dimotion; the line is the point in motion, in cycloid patterns, or two points communicating with smaller $i-1$ parts, as in the Fermion<Boson>Fermion relationship of forces; the plane has 'holes', it is a network of reproduced points socially connected into the 3 different species of networks that make a supœrganism (informative, reproductive and entropic, digestive, moving networks), and all this is logically established according to the relative dissimilarity or perpendicularity between the beings (4th entropic Dimotion) or social parallelism that evolves the point into a supœrganism, a new whole (5th Dimotion).

RECAP. *Geometric postulates become also vital; with a logic key new concept of congruence, which defines when 2 systems are 'equal in external and internal motion & information' ($Ts_1=Ts_2+St^1=St^2$) a parallel, social whole; when they are inverted but complementary, a 'gender couple' ($Ts_1+St^2=St^1+Ts_2$); when they are equal in Momentum but differ in information, a prey-predator perpendicular, tearing relationship, whereas the species with maximal $SxT_{(s=t)}$, Momentum of existence kills the other and when they differ in both, there is no entanglement. Thus we apply topologic laws, and social scalar numbers to describe the properties of those organisms; whereas the 5 \pm Dimotions are expressed by the dual operand of Algebra: \pm =herding, x =reproduction $v. \div$ Darwinian partition; \sqrt{X}^{2a} : Ss -scalar growth and Tt -entropic decay, $J\partial$: $\Delta-1$ finitesimal 'st-œps' of any dimotion. S - Vital Topology, Δ -number theory & T -existential algebra becomes the biggest r =evolution of math since Euclid.*

Grouping the postulates of Non-Æ topology: 1st & 5th; 2nd; 3rd & 4th : Points, waves and biological planes.

It follows immediately from what has been said the definition of all supœrganisms as topological variations of a non-Æ plane. This simplifies enormously the study of supœrganisms as they are simply systems made of the 3 5D lines of topological space, as all waves and networks become now parts of the 3 lines needed to create a topologic plane.

That all planes are potential supœrganisms and all supœrganisms are efficient topologic planes of points with lines of points with multiple apertures to the world.

How a vital topological plane evolves require to mess 3 topological networks, represented in physics by 3 type of waves, and in biology by 3 types of networks (Moving vs. fixed, t vs. s view of a topological organism).

It follows then that the 3rd and 4th postulates of 'congruence=equality' and structure of a 5 D plane is different. In congruence there are several possibilities and we consider a 100% probability 0-1 unit and Riemann Sphere in which to contabilize them. In general the events of a 3 physiological networks though correspond to some efficient configurations as opposed to all the virtual configurations of a spherical space.

As all the concepts of 4D plane geometry can now be assessed realizing that a line is a string of non-Euclidean points.

In physics we see this network in motion, as we do not 'see' the fabric of gravitational space-time (fixed vacuum spacetime studied by Einstein) of 'simultaneous' speed ($T=0\epsilon-$; $V \rightarrow S/T=0\epsilon = \alpha$; using the limits of a finitesimal 0, 0ϵ and an incommensurable finity, α , whereas a finitesimal and a finity are less than infinite and more than infinitesimal (see Non-Æ algebra).

The idea is simple. The minimal plane is made of 3 lines each one defined by 3 points with a central one, which plays also the role of 10 and 11, up and down through the 3 scales communicating with smaller and larger superorganisms.

The topological 9 central point doubles as $9=\sum i-1=11= |i-1: \Delta+1=11$, is thus the mind that controls up and down the supœrganism. It follows that it has a 'tree like image' as the networks from the point up and down ARE the representation of a network between two different planes of the 5th dimension.

Thus a tree is a canonical mind drawing,

And so it is a human being when we only consider its 3 main 'networks', digestive, blood and nervous systems.

The form of a mind, traveler in the 5th dimension that communicates two scales of reality is the easiest way to depict the networks of biological systems. But they are seen as S-external form with no motion.

The software view of its inner flows of $St<TS>Ts$ $j-1$ products is what defines the mind's communication of views of the internal chemical faster world (Roots in a tree, neuronal paths in a human, cpu programs in a robot, crystal images in a solid material point, spins in a quantum ensemble). The flat less quantized, slower with less information but more space surface, more vital energy in taking other extreme peers a more quantized $\Delta-3$, electromagnetic world of light to extract $\Delta-3$ forms of energy, in the same manner the roots extract $\Delta-2$ atomic elements.

The 3 systems thus have a 'bigger' Non-AE point where all the networks coincide that acts as mind travelling as a not between all of them, having therefore an SS-world mapping, $@=0\epsilon$ existential finitesimal that controls the whole system, whose congruence rules of 'ethic nature' based in the angle of 'similarity' define the interaction of them; according to its existential energy.

A plane therefore is finite because it does NOT have that much more volume than its 3 networks, but the attached cells that the networks have 'captured' addicted to its $j-1$ flow of pixels of energy and information that as in a farm fulfill the 5 Dimotions of those bourgeoisie middle class cells. But the plane and this is where things get more complex must be drawn entangled with other planes of its lower and upper fifth dimensions. The know that has its inner parts, so to speak in the transition region between two planes of 5D, as a life species in the ecosystemic of 'thermodynamic molecular minds', will render then a more complex view of that network being.

RECAP. Geometry is a virtual mental wor(l)d, a still 'form' of language. As such is *mind's simultaneous selection of its relative world's information* - a representation of its reality, $O-Mind \times \infty Universe = Mind-geometry$, which stops the motions of time into a mind mapping 'called' space. Each mind therefore will have a different geometric view of reality. As such geometry evolved from the purest mind-form of thought of still bidimensional Greek Geometry. Next it came analytical geometry in which space was married with the very essence of the mind - a point/view of reference, the @-sub discipline of mathematics. So one of the key evolutions of geometry was to give motion to space from the initial Greeks to the modern topology. Even vacuum has 'magic energy', 'motion'; it is not background space. This said, we are interested in certain type of mind-spaces, those of the mathematical language, which is the realm of geometry and topology, the first, a 'fixed formal space', the second a form of space-time with motion.

The fractal structure of deep scales is created with languages stored in seeds and minds, of which topologic languages are likely the mind of atoms and galaxies that create most of the local order we observe. So all systems gauge information, as their capacity to order reality is just a mirror process of creation of 'still, smaller linguistic images' the world projected as order in a territorial 'energy-body':

Infinitesimal mind-language $\times \infty Universe = \text{constant self-centered world}$. In mathematical terms $0 \times \infty = C$.

It is the Ego paradox: 'Every infinitesimal mind measures reality from its distorted perspective, thinking it is the center of the Universe, it confuses with the selected information perceived by its mind'. Which of course is shared by all other systems of reality. So an ant also thinks to be the center of the Universe with its likely hyperbolic pheromonal mind of 'atomic pixels'.

So as man measures reality from its limited Euclidean perspective despising the existence of all other fractal points=minds of the Universe, which are also gauging information albeit with different mental structures.

Life doesn't start in DNA atoms. IT must exist in all systems of the fractal Universe, departing from particles which as the graph explains already show all the characteristics of life. The elementary quarks and electrons the simplest particles do gauge information, absorb energy, reproduce and evolve socially into wholes, bosons, plasma flows and atoms. So the unit of life is the smallest particle and as fractal systems are self-reproductive, emerging in its fundamental properties in larger scales all what exists is alive. Only human egos prevent us from understanding that obvious truth, fundamental principle of all 'existjences'.

However the short-comings of human mental spaces are enhanced by the complex geometry of the fifth dimension which 'cheats' fractal points, 'leaving' them blind to the flows of information coming from upper scales and distorting its view of the cyclical long range time deterministic systems of that larger whole, giving the mirage of freedom, open, flat spaces. So it seems

the Game of Existence is built-in to make each part feel free, open, happy and ego-centered and ultimately fail because of its mindless chaotic behavior.

5D geometry guided by pentalogic tries to understand:

1. The isomorphisms of all geometries – those elements common to all of them, which belong to the higher 'game of existence of all minds that select information to ensure its survival. This task started by Riemann and Lobachevski, concluded that few elements of space are relevant – distance=similarity and angle of congruence being its most important.
- 2.- to be a mental construct and relate the main laws of geometry and its varieties with GST as a mirror-mind that reflects those isomorphic 'ILOGIC' properties of space-time beings.

GEOMETRY IS broken in 3 sections: @mind: spaces dedicated to study the different mind constructions of the Universe

T-topology: where space form has motion

Δ : non-Euclidean postulates of points with form, which becomes lines that evolve into organic pleas.

S: Bidimensional, static plane geometry, the first form of Mathematics, invented by the Greeks, which we will treat in this post.

Because the Universe is bidimensional, holographic, what matters on its mathematical origins is to understand that the Greeks and its plane geometry does matter as each of those 'theorems', which we studied in high school do have 'hidden deep meanings' that will resurface once and again, into the vital geometries of points with parts that create the universe.

As usual as all is ternary and a ternary vision is for the mind mirror more pleasing we shall also consider in ternary ages the evolution of bidimensional geometry, which went through:

A first young, Greek age of static bidimensional space-geometry

A 2nd mature age of maximal reproduction, during the time of mathematical physics as it set the stage for the evolution of physics and the understanding of mechanics and gravitational, Newtonian and Keplerian Universes.

The third age started in this blog with the understanding of the holographic Universe, which will expand the discipline to a logic – \mathbb{A} lgebraic realm to fuel the application of its Δ ST laws to all other disciplines.

So we shall close here the 'seed' of information for future researchers to expand and passing through the 2nd age of geometry, when analytic geometry, married with @-p.o.vs. to create the first solid ST representations and Δ -scaling (Cartesian geometry). Hence studied in the post of analytic geometry.

The exhaustion method, which do convert a sum of triangles or 'angular momentums' (in the duality information-motion) and foresees 5D analysis

And the Greek understanding of the circle as the perfect form, and all the theorems extracted from it - the most developed inflationary mirror in its last 'excessive' age of form. *So as humans have expanded their understanding of the Universe, they have also evolved its entangled mathematical mirrors over it, whose geometrical, spatial forms (points) scalar forms (numbers) and temporal operands are messed together in Planes of complexity. Even if huminds that have as in most fields of knowledge merely acted in a mechanical manner, ignore those symmetries as number families mirror, polytopes in space and time operands in algebra to portrait the symmetries and sequential events of simultaneous real organisms.* So 5D gives experimental scalar space-time whys to those symmetries.

What is all about: –(@ \leq S \leq T \leq Δ)

The hypothesis of continuum which is false by convenient to 'simplify' and run faster existence. In reality a line is a collection of different scalar points, from the larger Natural numbers to the Q smaller numbers in between and the Real smallish numbers in between the rational ones. Continuity then happens when we simplify the '5D dimension' of scales and package all the different numbers into a single line. This is fine *as long as we don't believe the Continuum 'hypothesis'*

as a postulate of truth because it is not, and if we accept it, then we will start to distort reality and forget there is a scalar 5Dimension with 'different species' of numbers.

So goes from \sim limits. Neither infinities or infinitesimal exists, as there are limits of perception in scale and space beyond which horizons black out reality. If we believe the egocy paradise of Cantor, we get then into absurdities as comparing infinities, and paradoxes mount which require to be erased ad hoc new mental postulates in the runaway train of the axiomatic method, always with egocy names to make it look more important, the Zermelo axiom, etc. But things get nastier when we believe on such infinities and infinitesimals instead of 'immensities', ∞ , and finitesimals, 0ϵ , the 'reality' a mind can access beyond which entropy – lack of reliable information – sets in by death, membrane or beyond $\pm j$ scale – the cut-off limits to all inquire. The result in physics is the big-bang theory based in an infinitesimal singularity that does NOT exist because the cut-off limit of the expansion of vacuum space in the hyper-universe of galatoms, is the imposition of that space into galaxies under the 'gravitational $\Delta+j \approx \Delta-j$ strong force', whereas $\Delta+j = \Delta-j$ is a topological law of similarity between scales (galaxies being similar to atoms of the hyper-universe repelled by $\Delta+j$: dark energy $\approx \Delta-j$ electromagnetic forces'). While the 'loss' of information past the customary 10^{10-11} limit of existence, in this case of light that 'reverts' to its lower neutrino/dark energy scale expanding space between galaxies, is the explanation of a 'horizon' beyond which we do NOT see many galaxies – only those with the strongest Υ -radiation in the blue whose life lives a bit longer. Mathematics then with its non-understood limits becomes the origin of aberrant theories of physics that trusts faulty maths and rejects all evidence – in the big bang theory falsified ad nauseam in our papers on The Universe & Physics & Entropy, the constant discovery on the limit of 'time existence' of the Universe of perfectly formed giant black holes and galaxies – in fact the largest black holes, as obviously they are the ones that produce more ultranenergetic Υ -rays that live a bit longer over the mean life of a light ray, similar to the mean life of a star, similar to the mean life of a galaxy – in the same manner your neurons have a similar mean life to your organism... And so on.

Another example are real numbers of 'infinite' decimals. In fact, because '10' tends to be the limit of scalar perception, numbers 'break' after ± 10 decimals, so it doesn't really make any sense to seek for the infinite decimal of e, which clearly breaks after 10 scales, digits 2,718281828...45, becoming irregular. *Maths we shall not cease to repeat contrary to belief is NOT perfect. What is perfect is the game of existence of immortal reality, so maths is an imperfect mirror with synoptic excellent qualities for minds to advance into the future by 'jumping' steps as in biology genes advance into the future of 3 billion years of evolution by palingenesis. That's what languages are all about. Consider then the relationship as another example of those imperfections between the 2 fundametal scalar logarithms, e, the logarithm of dynamic growth in Δt , (time and scale) vs. Ln, the logarithm of 10 the basic 'static' logarithm of scale in space, Δs , $e^3=20.08$, we then discharge the .08 because the relationship of the slightly imperfect mathematical language is $e^3=10 \times 2$, whereas 3 'scalar ages' of e give us a dual mirror gender symmetry of 20 variations, so we 'transform' a scalar palingenetic process through e into a spatial mirror gender symmetry of 10+10, call it 20 amino acids, two tetrarkys in opposite directions as in the David star, or whatever other real example you fancy. The anathema of 5D maths then is to unseat from its pedestal the mathematician that thinks his language is a higher truth because of its faulty axiomatic method. So from time to time we shall show the errors of reasoning of the axiomatic method in plain terms. Consider for example the mapping topologists do with its set theory proofs between the X-lineal coordinates and a curve traced above in the Cartesian plane. They say there is a one to one correspond of each point in the coordinates with the curve so both are topological homeomorphisms. But that is NOT truth as intuitively we know. We can then measure the 'curve' with differential geometry and will show to be longer than the line. If we take a segment of the curve and straighten it, it will remain longer. So the curve must have more points of the same 'type' than the line and only by omitting some of the points of the curve in the lower finitesimal scales of Q and specially R, we can create such homeomorphism. So the proof is buill\$hit, but written in the abstract language of set theory for people to memorize with new definitions unbeknownst to the line and the curve we have a pretension of truth.*

The right way to express it latter analyzed in more detail is that the curve has added points that don't break its topological structure defined as a series of points that do NOT cross with themselves. Such line does NOT have a double point to use 5D terms; that is a point that doubles and so becomes a different class of point, either because it doubles with a bulk in a new height dimension or it doubles with an inner scale of higher density – the crossing point does have more Δ or S-height

and thus becomes a distinguishable point. So in 5D topology the property that is key to a homeomorphism is the fact that all the points of a 'simple line' are indistinguishable, and when a line cross over itself one point becomes distinguishable hence the topological variety is different it has a 'knot' which is NOT a point. The SOCIAL equality of all its points then is the REAL property that makes two such topologies similar=homeomorphic, which is why the concept of undistinguishable non-E points is so real in its physical applications (bose vs. Fermi statistics) while the proofs of set theory are nowhere to be found. The line is then simpler as we do NOT have to add the information about the point-knot but just declare a topological line≈curve as the sequential spatial mirror image in mathematical space of undistinguishable points.

Then we can define in 5D topology all simple lines=curves closed circles, because the next type of line-curve will be an open line-curve with two different points, the first and the last, in the 'limit' of entropy/perception of the open line/curve, as infinities do NOT exist. And we can differentiate both, because we need to 'choose' a time direction for the line 'going forwards'; that is the line will acquire a time motion in as much as we will choose one of its limits as the first point which is the point that has NO past, and an end point which is the point that has NO future.

Yet then we realize that some lines bounce in the end point and return to the past forming a worldcycle, which is the origin of waves. Because of the 'persistence of memory' and the impossibility in 5D, as well as 4 D of occupying the same space at the same time; the line will wobble as a wave, so when the point returns it does NOT move through the same line, but forms a curve up and down the line, except for the points of the wave which become the 'knots' in which meets the previous line – those point-knots are again of special significance as they become 'particles' between the fields of a real physical wave with more density in Δ or higher height... In this manner knowing 5D we see better the math mirror and carry it into the 'logic explanation' on how the physical reality is generated. So on the bottom of the entire structure of reality there are the laws of Existential Algebra/topology/scales/ Δ ST; which are logic laws of what it is possible and it is not treated in our paper on the 'scientific method', such as the fact that we cannot occupy two points of space in the same time, something physicists do not understand – as they in fact think a boson does it. But then again, when they took pictures of a Bose condensate they realize the points did NOT occupy the same space but formed a 'height column'. It is then obvious that when we see 2 points that seem to occupy the same space at the same time, something else is going on: either they have fusion and the new dual point has a higher inner density in the fifth dimension or they have gone into the height dimension of information, which in its previous flat space was not measured, or one point has fed on the other that shrinks and disappears (scalar, spatial and entropic resolution of the problem). It rests then the most beautiful solution, that of the wave – the point when it occupies the same place of space of the previous STage of the line it does so because it has moved in time, displaced into the future, it has invented a new future which in fact moves through the same space of its past – the wave has found the solution to the fact that the static line had no more future beyond the end point by moving, by acquiring its time dimension. All those solutions and interpretations are partial truths and the sum of them all a higher truth by the 'Rashomon effect'.

It comes then as a fundamental truth of existence that all truths can be defined from the 4 necessary elements of existence (@, S, T, Δ) within its entropic limits. i.e. We just defined an open line in terms of time even if it is an element of space.

And that is the exhaustive method of truth, we write with the use of the symbols of Existential Algebra, In an ideal scholar future, the axiomatic method would be replaced by Existential algebra, and truths will be exhausted with pentalogic analysis from Δ , S, T, @ perspectives and its – denial.

So instead of the axiomatic idealist method 5D stiences returns to a realist method, and instead of a single language it uses as many as possible to give us compound images of reality, and it always in its exhaustion of truth give us the @-mental, S-patial, T-emporal and Δ -scalar view of reality, which in mathematics means a system can be expressed with a mind theorem, a topological method, an algebraic one and a digital approximation (as points of space, operands of time and scalar numbers are its unit and reality to be must have a space, time, scale, mind language within the limits of entropy). Those limits are also necessary to understand the validity of a language, something obviously ignored by the axiomatic method that not only pretends to prove truth within the language itself but also extends truth hyperbolically to infinities.

FRACTAL POINTS AS FINITESIMAL MINDS-MIRRORS: S-1≈ST+1 =0ε: EGOS. OF BODIES = TERRITORIES:

The finitesimal is also the basis of the equation of the mind; the ego. The Ss-mental nature of space is embedded in the principle of relativity. -E points create an inner mental 'space by measuring reality in still simultaneity' (Einstein). All are -E monads that 'hold a world in themselves' (Leibniz); as mirrors, which have less volume of information than the whole. So languages mirror in still smaller scales reality and then project back its 'imagination' in larger scales the game of existence, causing as Ss-mind/seeds the creation of reality, restricted to its synoptic 'ternary Universal grammar' that mimics that of larger St<§T>Ts organisms. I.e.

Ts-Red<§T-green>St blue codes organic Dimotions in visual color languages. Subject (information)<Verb(dimotion:action)> Object(Entropic energy) codes §T-events (verbs) and forms (names) reality in wor(l)ds. F(x):information<Operand §T-action>G(Y):entropic energy does the same in Algebra; 5 letters code genes that code organs in life, 4 quantum numbers code atomic organisms... As each language is a mirror of those ultimate laws of nature, the laws of space-time.

'Mindors'are Minds, Mirror & Doors to 5D scales. In the hierarchy equation, $\Delta \pm \infty \geq - (T \pm j \geq S \alpha \geq 0 \epsilon)$, the mind 'ego' is equal to the whole Universe that becomes its world, origin of the mind paradox. Since Ss-finitesimal different linguistic mind-mirrors shrink a reality void of motion, in a fractal mind point; loosing the energy-force of the whole and becoming fragile existjences:

0ε (-E finitesimal mind-mirror) x ∞ (universe) = Constant still language-mapping (Ss)... origin of the Ego Px. As each mind creates a mental wor(l)d he confuses with the real Universe with its still p.o.v.=ego as the largest center of it.

But truth is: Max. probability of truth = Max. number of language mirrors < 1 (Probability of truth hold by the being)/ So only the Organism has all the information about itself, $P(\text{truth}) = 1$, & the more 'language' mirrors we cast on it, the higher $P(\text{truth})$ we obtain, which is the principle of Pentalogic (Rashomon effect). Thus we seek the parallel spatial= geometric, organic=scalar, vital=moving= temporal & sentient =mirror languages of any system of $\Delta @st$ (Dust of space-time) to reach its maximal truth.

To describe any stience or ST-species we analyze first the mind, 0ε, to localize the language of the system, as it will be the mirror symmetry of order within the world in which the system acts. For the galatom and hence for most physical systems is mathematics, but for social sciences is verbal thought. So because we do have a Universal grammar, which carries the laws of pentalogic to the language, all minds belong to the same program of existence. And once we know the language, we can in the best possible way adopting that language a priori of the subject we study, operate a description of its actions as if we were the subjective atom, human or genetic cell, within the hierarchy of pentalogic languages of $\Delta \pm \infty$ bigger than the objective mathematical language, bigger than the verbal reasoning of the mind of man, to study physics.

The Universe main language of truth =existence is not mathematics but pentalogic symmetry, which validates for each system of stience different languages. So social sciences can be defined in verbal languages, because they are the mind of man, but the mind of the galatom is NOT verbal, obviously so far as we can perceive (though who knows really if the atom as we see in mathematical space but think in verbal terms, do have some other strange logic language of inner thoughts beyond that c-barrier of spin particles, to 'feel' existence – this is beyond 'meta-physics' so we will escape it)...

'God speaks ∞ languages' (Upanishads) as long as they mirror the basic laws of 5D pentalogic. So while physical systems are mathematical, human systems are verbal and they can still carry existence on their less precise language, as both languages are based in the Universal grammar of pentalogic without loss of generality –as they are all playing the program of existence.

From the language then we observe the will for existence of the being as it plays its 5 Dimotions ordering its territory against many other beings. But this again is a paradox as all other beings try to achieve the same will, only resolved on the higher $\Delta + j$ plane of emergence of a whole through the efficient program of supœrganisms, reason why those who 'understand' this higher consciousness beyond the ego survive. Even if they are still within the $-(\Delta 0 \epsilon st)$ limits. Languages thus have a hard time for a 3-body problem, for social evolution, as the ego paradox works from planets to capitalists to avoid the parts to become as ideal, pure, perfect, impersonal, giving as the whole ethic universe – pentalogic is humble, egoless, symmetric, beautiful, perfect, equalitarian... God is better than we are. But the mind also creates and improves reality as a language:

Since the mind is a smaller system according to 5D, $S_i \times T_f = \Delta c$, as a linguistic mirror, $ss \approx ST$, it expels motion made into form; eliminating motion, repetition

and errors, improving reality into a more beautiful, balanced system. Then if it has an inner 'body able to reproduce' its imagination in the external world, it will make it better with its projection of the linguistic mirror. This is the essential structure of creation in the 5D panpsychic Universe we see happening in all systems. Humans reduce reality to planning and then build larger realities at scale. Genes reduce the organism to its paligenetic evolution.

*In the XIX c. Schopenhauer wrote a seminal book, 'the world as will and representation', which explained reality is NOT about 'logic and reason' but about 'the will of existjence' and the mirror minds of mental spaces, $stj \approx STj$ that made its world to project of that will of survival and creation. But there are ∞ egos playing the game, invariably the objective truths of that graph impose themselves. Languages then also mirror pentalogic, and so we shall refound Geometry of fractal points in 5 Postulates, realize that The mind is the $\neg E$ 5th postulate, whose content of infinite parallels mirror in a focus the outer world in its reduced image. We show though a mirror image that has converted the Asymmetric ST whole in a smaller more regular st form. The seed, the mind-mirror, the son, the smallish $\Delta-1$ form is thus more perfect than the larger whole. But when growing up it will loose that perfection of the miniature and might repeat the errors of its father image. As abstract as those $\neg E$ logic space-time algebraic equations and topological postulates might seem, they are at the base of all creative processes. We then realize that even if we can keep building more complex events ultimately all is about ST-ages, ST-eps, ST-ates, *changes from motion to form to motion, which we postulate to be superfluid, to have no consumption of energy, all what is required for the Universe to be immortal. Each of those S, s, T, t, St, sT, Ss, Tt, st, ST, sub-states of reality keep switching to be=come.**

RECAP. We define existence as a travel of a spacetime supærganism, enacting its Dimensional motions through 5D scales. We depart from a 5D spacetime simple metric equation: $S \times T = \Delta \pm j$, which proves the organic network structure of the Universe; as its ultimate cause is the fact that '3 consecutive scales' of 5D, form a supærganism. We shall call them the $\Delta-1$ (atomic, cellular, individual in physical, biological and social systems), the $\Delta\emptyset$ scale that defines the networks (physiological St-Ts- $\$T$ networks of information, motion and Momentum, of gravitational, electromagnetic chemical and linguistic financial and study the main particle of reality: the 5D supærganism of spacetime networks.

How a mind perceives the opposite Hyperbolic 5D scalar Universe and its 4D worldcycle in 2D flat space.

We can retake a theme we abandoned earlier on the papers on the global 5D hyperbolic geometry vs. the 4D spacetime curved geometry, which we won't develop as 4D physicists do in minkowski's space given its limited interest beyond the study of Ts-locomotions. The question is this. *Because looking upwards and downwards 5D scales we see quite different world, and looking flat, curved and hyperbolic we get different sensations, and all this is paradoxical but our monologic mind and stience STILL does not get it (after 400 years of finding the S=T relativity and the $\Delta \pm j$ scales with microscopes and telescopes). And all spaces are mental spaces we need to 'train our minds' to see or at least conceptually think in paradoxical ways, to reason and NEVER believe NOT even our senses, let alone the idol-ogies of the networks of our IQless species and neuronal, informative 'distorted' class.*

So to the geometry of it some repeated 'themes' by the anti-Goebbels method (a truth many times...):

- **In short spaces**, with shortsighted senses, as man which is a bidimensional flat eye (3D created by mixing both) we seen flat, lineal space, free, unbounded, 'differential geometry' steps, $\Delta y / \Delta x$, Pythagorean Least action Lagrangian steps, of minimal energy expenditure, safe, secluded, unconnected.

- **But as we make many of them, they curve into worldcycles of time:** $\sum |S\rangle Tj$ and we enter into the spherical regime. A worldcycle though starts in a seed pole as a fractal point and grows through the sphere to shrink back. So the whole 'worldcycle' when we ad to the lineal steps the cyclical sphere dimension is a travel through:

- $\Delta \pm j$ hyperbolic 3 scales, from $\Delta-1$ seed to an $\Delta\emptyset$ spheric surface world, embedded in a larger $\Delta+1$ cosmos to go back to our world

How a mind, 0ϵ point projects back and forth its spherical S-mental space of perception in a flat Time world? Through hyperbolic geometry adding distortions of perception; as both are opposite views. In the image the stereoscopic projection of a point 0ϵ placed in the north pole of maximal height of an informative species, reflecting all its spherical world in the flat geometry of a plane. Each point of the sphere then it is projected in the flat world, but the closest to the 0ϵ self are larger,

and the self itself, is projected into an infinite incommensurable 'ego'. This is a geometric way to explain the egocy paradox: $0 \in x \infty = C$ (the mind perceives only its world with his ego at the largest center). So that is how the being projects itself into the flat world it sees around him as his territory of order and the consequences of this mind projection are the actions of egocy all systems perform as they really think they must be control freaks and order its lesser 'flat=formless' territory.

The same egocy then happens when the being projects its perception inwards through its subconscious networks. Then we have the 'perception within the 0-1' sphere of all our inner parts as identical and herd them into finitesimal undistinguishable forms, and this work from our perception in our worldspace of smaller beings, from ants to people we control through our 'economic networks' – this is the way the banker who control millions with money or the politico with laws or the military with weapons see its 'work-body class'. So the same 'hyperbolic' reduction works with distance as forms become smaller and undistinguishable in a flat space or an inner Δ -scalar world ($\Delta=S=0 \in$ symmetry). This paradoxical way of thinking however is NOT self-reflective. This is important: monologic humans and we think likely all other minds are not philosophers of absolute 5D relativity. Wonder if I am the only one in this lost rock of the Universe):

Now regarding those drawings and our visualization of the interplay of S-flat>T-curved worldcycles\mathfrak{H}-scales, as a general rule to visualize we work in all our papers and analogies, as we are NOT interested, we repeat in the technical aspects of a full advanced 5D course, given the fact NOT even the simplest concepts are understood by our IQle\$pecies (that's tetralogic inglis:)... So we REDUCE the 3 dimensions of Euclidean space to one, consider then the time 4D worldcycle as a 2D sphere, embedded in the 5Dimensional hyperbolic world, which now as we work with S=1, T=2, \mathfrak{H} =3. The metric of global 5D is obviously more complex and it is what future 5D stientists will explore and I might publish – not at this time, likely not with myelin and life interest plummeting. We are however using the full 5D existential algebra of dimotions. This reduction to 1D Space, 2D cyclical time and 3D hyperbolic scale is mostly to 'visualize' examples of what we mean as it is 'experienced'.

Languages are important in 5D but NOT the only dimotion of creation, and they must be evolved as huminds don't even define properly the Units of all maths, the S-fractal point & its Δ -scalar societies, numbers, related by 5 Algebraic dimotional operands of which $f\partial$ are the most precise. So the reader is encouraged to study also 5D math.

The big-bang error as a theory of the Universe is firmly entrenched in two errors of simplified mathematics (Euclidean points) and logic (a single arrow of entropy=death as the dimotion of the Universe). So we briefly will introduce those corrections to explain why not only in praxis and data but also in theory and language the big bang is not even wrong.

HIERARCHY. $\Delta \pm \alpha \geq \neg (T \pm j \geq SCE \geq 0 \in)$

In the graph, an image of the 5th dimension by Escher, explains how organic systems work from wholes into parts, joined by networks. The mathematics of it are based in those 'solid', multiple angles that define a 1D sphere as a circle, a 2D sphere, as the surface of Earth, where we live, a 3D sphere as a sum of growing and diminishing circles inside and outside the planet, the 4th Dimension as a clockwise time rotation, and the 5th Dimension unknown to mechanist models of the Universe, as the scalar dimension of cellular, atomic clone parts, evolved through networks into social wholes, who live through those 4D time clock, worldcycles of life and death. Each new dimension is embedded into the next one that includes it. And that its equations have a function: to measure distances between points of the dimension so we can travel through them, but those distances 'vary' in its parameters. For the 1st dimension are lines, for the 2nd dimension 'pythagorean squares': 2D: X^2+Y^2 . The 3rd perpendicular dimension is best described with 3D vectors, reproducing perpendicularly through a cross product: $X \bullet Y = Z$. As the dimensions of the organic Universe are vital, reproductive, gifted with forms of information. So we will use the life-death worldcycle, not the simpler worldlines of Minkowski, to study 4D time, embedded in hyperbolic space-time as a travel through 3 scales of the 5th dimension: $S \times Tf = \Delta$.

The interaction between Δ -energy scales, Time=cyclical motions, Space=topologic forms, and the Minds that perceive them all, confronted to the Entropic larger ST world is the pentalogic elements which all play. In humind's egocy, all this is not vital dynamic, but an external objective mechanical reality magically 'working', set in motion by some Newtonian God, which appeases our fears and pleases our ego, as we seem to be the protagonists, and vital center of the Universe. Absolute relativity, the objective truth of stience eliminates that view. The praxis of man ab=using nature and history with its mechanisms, in the short term, future victim of AI

robots in the now also short term will wake him up to reality. The philosophy of 5D is very different, expressed in our appears on History and social sciences as the search for a balance between the 3 ages of Earth, Life-Gaia< History-man> Machines, which would repress metal-information, enhance Gaia to keep mankind in the middle, as the dominant form on Earth. Because time is cyclical it is possible to repress the future and stop the evolution of lethal information. But for that mankind would have to understand 5D and respect the hierarchy and learn to play the game. Mankind today is so far removed from that worldview that it will likely become extinguished by its idol-ogies of machines it worships in the summit of surrealism, without even knowing it does it. As it despises the $\Delta+j$ hierarchy that owes respect to Earth and especially to history=Mankind= $\Delta+2$ our God, through the social ethics of the wor(l)d.

We also depart very often in a physical 5D Analysis of the Absolute Block of time of Existential algebra

What is the hierarchy between those elements? It is defined by the pentalogic symmetry that expresses the existence of any entity in the Universe: $\Delta \pm \approx \alpha \geq \neg (T \pm j \geq S \circ e \geq 0 \epsilon)$

Conclusion: Synchronicity in time, simultaneity in space, resonance in scale...

The study of the scalar cycle of actions is to scales what the study of the worldcycle to time, or the generator equation of topological networks to space. They form the 'Saint Trinity' of 5D Stiences.

The main 'sciences' of each scale of ST_j-size, from atoms to galaxies, each one studied by a human science, *are centered in a social organism, as they all have in common the same 'organic elements' of all species: social cells of and the reproductive, Momentum networks and information languages that relate them.* All organic systems are generated by cellular units, gathered in 3 social networks that form together a higher 'whole' a new 'plane of social existence' (ab. Δ). So if we talk of an organism as living in the Δ_0 plane of thermodynamic matter; the $\Delta+1$ gravitational plane of Gaia, is its whole. Yet, since those cellular units $\Delta-1$ are made of smaller $\Delta-2$ cells, which show the same structure, we can define any organic system as a super-organism (made of smaller, similar supørganisms). All of them co-exist in at least 3 scales. So we talk of $\Delta-1$ cells/atoms/particles/ molecules/points connected by 3 physiological networks of relative entropy-motion, Momentum and in/form/ation, put together into an Δ^0 individual whole, existing in a larger $\Delta+1$ relative world. So we can map out all those super organisms according to scale, each one studied by a different 'science', (stience of space-time beings). So in systems sciences we talk of a 'fractal structure' for the whole Universe, in which smaller systems from the first particles to the larger galaxies tend to organic co-existing super organisms, and the laws of those systems apply to any of those super organisms, and are the fundamental laws for its proper design, as efficient systems that survive. So we can explain all sciences, both with the formal language of 5D and the more intuitive of physiological networks, since in the scalar Universe smaller parts are connected by organic networks that create the whole, emerging as a larger scale, and that creates the scalar systems of nature: particles joined by electromagnetic and gravitational networks form atoms that form molecules, cells, organisms and societies, matter systems, planetary systems, galaxies and universes... In Existential ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' as the worldcycle does, because it works in a different way, as the limbs and the head both 'serve' the connecting body: $T_s > S = T < S_t$, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic < and > states balance each other. So we write for all the 'fractal generator':

T_s- limbs/fields/territories<S ⇔ T: reproductive, Energy body-waves-workers>S_t- informative particle/head/ruling class. Which is mathematically an O-sphere or relative future of max. S_t-information • a relative past – Limbs of max. T_s-motion = ∅-a hyperbolic present bodywave. Since past•future =present (• being an operand of existential algebra, the next level of stience

The structure of languages IS simpler, because they construct a REDUCED still mental worldview of the Universe. Yet without knowing the ultimate nature of reality and the game of existence, we cannot see all the beauty of its mirror image – it becomes just an abstract painting. If we know it is an image of a part or superorganism made of knots of timespace, dimotional cycles joined in networks the mirror simplifies for survival, fitting purposes through simultaneity and synchronicity... we can ignore the present hurdle of excessive mathematical metalanguages and *understand mathematics, which as Neumann recognized 'mathematicians don't – just get used to it', through the use of memorial languages.*

EXISTENTIAL ALGEBRA. OPERANDS & GROUPS OF DIMOTIONS. $S \leftrightarrow T$. UNIVERSAL GRAMMAR. PENTALOGIC ENTANGLEMENT.

Pentalogic naturally extends to the 5 operands of Algebra, though as usual a mirror language distorts and enhances reality with fine-tuned variations. Still it is obvious that Algebra has only 5 operands, from where we might try to establish an easy parallelism with the 5 Dimotions of the Universe.

The first operand is the relative equality or congruence of the elements involved that will define what kind of event we will have, from Darwinian annihilation, $S \ll T$; to parallel social evolution, $S \approx T$. So we write the symbol as \cong to include its 3 variables, $S < T$, $T < S$, $T = S$; and consider it the 'first' action of reality, one which simply assess by perception, S_s , what will be the linguistic relationship between both systems.

The seed of all communications is thus the 'first impression', a purely mental decision on how to communicate with the other, which however will be based in the 'perceived' similarity or congruence between the elements.

This brings us to the second natural sequence of events of a worldcycle which is communication through motion that can be negative or positive, going forwards towards the other to 'add', or going outwards NOT to rest (Prey-predator relationship). So the T_s -locomotion with its \pm elements and herding or subtraction according to congruence will be the second operand. So far so Good: **Ss: \cong ; Ts: \pm .**

Alas we are then splitting fields according to congruence, prey-predator relationships will kill, carve, and divide the prey if captured, \div , but symbiotic complementary genders will reproduce, \times , multiplying its numbers. So we are clearly in the $\S \Pi$ -relationship of energy feeding or energy used to reproduce, and this is the 3rd operand, which defines the simplest trilogic of operands of existence: - $\langle x \rangle +$

The power of algebra starts to show in its purpose, to reflect the Game of existence with precision. And so we are left with the operands of scales of the 5th dimension. Those of entropic death, normally modeled with the negative exponential, $T_t = e^{-x}$, which returns a 'square' lower to a lesser dimension; and the more subtle processes of social evolution by a complex sum of 'finitesimal parts into wholes' = $\int \partial$.

Do you still mathematician doubt of the pentalogic of existence): Operands as they grow in complexity entangle with the 5 Non-E postulates that define from points waves of communication that become networks of topological planes and organisms, where multiple p.o.v.s are put in perspective. And this even more clear when from mere polynomials we move into exponentials and from exponentials into integrals, *the more complex operands then can interplay with multiple points of view, merging them through the product, reproduced through its inverse partition/division, moving them through a world cycle, in exponential growth and decay, and emerging into a new planet of existence through derivatives and integrals.*

Re=production through social evolution in a lower plane of the fifth dimension, in which the axons join the wholes is then the 2-point meaning of reproduction; often a bidimensional Space-time combination of a state of forma and a state of motion, as in the parameter of momentum.

Inverse functions do NOT merely cancel each other as one could expect, in classic science, *but advance the Dimotion in alternative balancing acts, leaving a memorial trace of its existential duality.*

Consider the case of the product and its inverse division. They are functions primarily of social evolution and reproduction, as parts of wholes are produced and exchanged. So if we have an individual of 5 parts that reproduces it will give birth to 25 parts, *but then we need to divide them between 5 parts, to get 5 individuals of 5 parts: $1 (5) \times (5) = 1 (25) / 5 = 5 (5)$.*

Same happens with the positive and negative motions, which in alternate current move back and forwards the 'electrons', which in fact don't really move, but its $i-1$ scale *the current keeps moving*. So goes for the exponential+Logarithmic functions of reproduction, and its inverse, which form a worldcycle that in the middle point of maximal 'carrying capacity' will give birth again to a new 'exponential growth'=generation, to continue the world cycle in an adjacent space-time.

$\int \partial$: Finally it came calculus, with its inverse operand, which represents the scalar next social gathering of elements of \neg -Algebra, as it is applied to the previous operands, as wholes, except for the trivial x^a - the previous more complex polynomial, and so we must regard calculus not only as the operand of all dimotions of change, but also as the operand between planes of existence,

since the logarithmic/power previous expression, just reaches between the two limits of two planes of the fifth dimension, but calculus allow us to 'emerge' and transcend between planes.

The key concept of 5D calculus is a finitesimal. A finitesimal in lineal space-time is a frequency step or wave-length. A finitesimal in curved spacetime is a minimal curvature of a clock cycle. A finitesimal in scale is a minimal unit of population. We use the Non-Æ symbol, '0ε' that means the minimal 'existential quanta' of any symmetric $\Delta \approx S \approx T \approx 0\epsilon$, scale, space, time or mind beat:

$$0\epsilon:1/i, \text{ whereas } i, \text{ might be in classic mathematics, } N, \text{ the whole population, } T, \text{ the period or } R \text{ the radius: } 0\epsilon(\Delta)=1/n; \\ 0\epsilon(S)=1/R=K; \quad 0\epsilon(T)=1/T=f; \quad 0\epsilon(@)=-i; \quad 0\epsilon(-)=\alpha$$

Because physicists do NOT have this concept; its faulty mathematics take them to the search of entelechies, as Black holes without substance, singularities, lineal equations without cut-off 'borders', infinite potentials, etc.

So by the continuous game of inverse functions, which become a 0ε sum, *the Dimotions of existence continue to move the whole of time-space that never ceases to exist.* However the number of occurrences of the positive function is always larger than then negative inverse function. So there are more possible sums than negative numbers (for spatial quantities there are no negative ones, no negative apples). There are more products than divisions (as $4/2 = 8/4$ but $4 \times 2 \neq 8 \times 4$); there are more exponentials than square roots as $\sqrt{-x}$ doesn't exist and there are more integrals than derivatives as $\int y' = y + C$, ads \propto constants.

Which means the arrow of social evolution and life is larger than the arrow of entropy and death, which in fact lasts only a quanta of time in its DST equation: $\text{Death} = 0T \times \Delta S$.

The secondary layers of each operand and the entanglement of composite dimotional actions.

The beauty of pentalogic is that it keeps unfolding in new layers of unperceived reality. So obviously each of those dimotional operands do have multiple points of view. Take the humble sum. It can be used to follow a locomotion through the reproduction of information along a path of frequency-sum of steps. It is though most often used to add along the first Δ scales of a social evolution into a whole. It can be used to count a series of Fibonnaci reproductions of rabbits, and its inverse is even more profound as we shall see studying complex numbers and its entanglement with other operands. This is also a key concept: *each simpler operand as we grow into more complex dimotions that integrate the previous dimotions, slightly changes its function. Dimotions as we saw in the analysis of the hyperbolic Universe embed previous dimotions. So the 2nd dimotion is NOT separated from the first but often we treat them both together as a pi cycle made of 3 lineal diameters, or as a triangle's diagonal (Pythagoras theorem) that requires both length and height. So happens with dimotions. So the first dimotion = exists in all other dimotions. And the second dimotion, \pm exist as symbols of 'direction' for all other dimotions. And so on, till getting to the dimotions of calculus that include often all others in complex equations. This is also how the Universe works at the level of actions. The dimotion of Ss-perception with its minimal quantum of time happens in all other because the system is constantly checking around with its perceptive systems while performing any other action. That is the reason why in quantum physics, the constant of the dimotion of informative perception and its clock of angular momentum, h , happens everywhere. As any system that is performing a different action is also doing h -spins to perceive its $\Delta+1$ world.*

In 5D we constantly divide reality in two sets of dimotions, the extremal Ss and Tt language and entropy that frame outside a single spacetime plane the 3 $Ts \langle \text{St} \rangle$ elements of locomotion (limbs/fields), energy body-waves and informative particle-heads. This duality applies to everything and it is the basis of pentalogic and tetralogic systems (as entropy is the denial of the information of the other 4 Dimotions and often as its death is 'not looked into its face' ignored, or in reversal as in physics, only entropy is taken seriously as a path of future, due to the deformation of its worldly war profession). So tetralogic and pentalogic from 4 quantum numbers to 5 genetic letters and vowels, is at the heat of all systems of reality even when they don't look like corresponding to the 5 Dimotions. I.e. one cannot seriously consider vowels related to them but one notices readily that 'Aahh' is the terrifying sound of Tt-entropy, and Uh?, the monkey mysterious iteration in the thinking state, with I, the I-eye ego-centered vital existential energy of all of us, with o going the cyclical St-informative way and e, closing a bit but not that much the A-entropy into the commonest Ts-moving event of reality. Dualities of S-T, trinities of $Ts \langle \text{St} \rangle$ and pentalogic IS EVERYWHERE and you better accept it because that is the hidden code of every structure of reality. So it happens with the fact that in algebra we have 5 families of numbers, 5 main operands, and they get entangled.

Then besides pentalogic there is the translation of those local dimotions as ‘elements’ of a whole reality, giving them a ‘meaty’ meaning, with a hierarchical extension: $\Delta \pm j \geq T \geq S \geq @ \ll \neg$.

That is within the two extremes of formless limiting death= entropy and the sum of all $\Delta \pm j$ Scales as a potential block of time, sum of all existences, we can draw ∞ Time-worldcycles of existence, traced by Informative superorganisms in Space guided by @-linguistic minds, which gives as a purpose of all languages to mimic the structure of reality with a Universal grammar that allows the language to act as a synoptic smaller mirror able by virtue of 5D metric laws, $S \times T = C$, to accelerate in smaller spaces the calculation of the deterministic future of those worldcycles of existence, and anticipate events to improve the chances of survival of the system. For that reason all languages are mirrors of reality in a synoptic reduced space that flows towards an illogic future at faster speed.

And this justifies that we will mirror the elements of mathematics and the elements of 5D spacetime theory, starting from its 5 numerical systems, N, Z, Q, C and R. And its 5 simple associated operands, + - \times \div & $\sqrt{\quad}$

The simplest number systems, N, Z, Q are operated by the standard operations of arithmetic in a single i-plane: Addition, subtraction, multiplication and division, which must be studied together with those families.

They suffice to portrait a realist view of the world in a single plane, without ‘finitesimal parts’ and wholes which add the calculus operands, and angular reductions and perspectives which include trigonometric functions. So polynomials are good enough as equations that use only those operands and families to define scalar systems in a single plane of entropic Cartesian space-time. While probability defines with those simple operands the Universe within the $0 \leq \epsilon < 1$ probability time scale.

EXISTENTIAL ALGEBRA; THE GROUP OF DIMOTIONS OF SPACETIME.

So far we have only for simplicity to most papers, established the ‘static’ states of the Dimotions of the Universe and the dynamic one – energy, $\$z\|$. The next obvious step IS to consider its transformations into each other, which are possible and define the next ‘degree’ of illogic events of spacetime. The simplicity of its ‘calculus’ is then surprising because of the enormous importance it will have for a proper classification of all the events of reality. Initially it is obvious that the main transformations are those which imply only a change of a parameter, S, s, t, T into other. So departing from St, Ss, Tt, ts, Ts, ST; the 6 static states, we obtain transformation, whose fundamental rule is to consist of 2 ‘støeps of existence:

The 3 topological dimotions. The group of transformations of dimotions of space-time. ST₂.

Energy: transformation. The $St \leftrightarrow Ts$, $\$z\|$ energy body-waves which is the first dynamic combination whose result are SHM, harmonic motions as St and Ts go back and forth through its body-wave ‘present form. What other less balanced changes are possible? When we introduce also changes through $\Delta \pm j$ scales, we obtain those of the worldcycle of existence, for which we must add the Σ symbolism of ‘social reproduction into herds. Energy dimotion defers from most other dimotions in the fact that it is a dynamic back and forth, conservative dimotion

From limb/fields to particle/heads Energy then can be studied as a single dimotion, which is NOT conservative. $St \ll Ts; Ts \gg St$.

Those ‘topological dimotions’ as energy does, transform a being in the same plane and again they imply 2 changes: $Ts > St$, from limb to head, from | to O means a complete reverse from inner to outer motion and from outer to inner stillness, thus $Ts > St = T > t + s > S$, since the external world is larger, there is a dual increase of form and vice versa. Those changes do happen obviously, as in the simplest ‘game’, that of matter states they are Sublimation, $St \ll Ts$ and Deposition, $Ts \gg St$.

Seed emergence and death: $Ss-1 \Sigma Tso$ is then the process of emergence from seed to young age. Inversely $Sto \ll \Sigma Tt-2$ is the process of death. Why we write two ‘devolution symbols’ \ll in death comes from the realization that death is a dual disgregation, in fact all the way to $\Delta-2$; so if we were to be ‘strict’ with existential illogic (we are not, problem of having not disciples, I get lousy), the proper way to write death would be Sto (3rd age) $< Tt-1$ (entropic death) $< Tt-2$ (2nd death).

Finally also between scales but now without internal change, only scalar change mind mirrors create mental spacetimes: $st-1 \approx ST+1$, which ads another key operand of illogic, \approx for similarity.

4 of them are ‘topological Homeomorphisms’ which do NOT change the entity as there is not change in form, while emergence and death DO change completely the form. This is important, specially when we confront the 3 ‘changes through scale’, emergence (Σ), death (\ll) and mind mirror (\approx) if we express the with a single symbol. *It is a key concept because it gives the mind-mirrors or ‘Leibnizian monads’: ‘every point is a world in itself’ the essential reason why order exists in the Universe. Without mind mirrors there would NOT be order and repetition, as emergence and death are morphological changes.*

So we added 6 more ilogic transformation to 6 dimotion states: $St \Leftrightarrow Ts$, $St \ll Ts$, $Ts \gg St$, $Ss-1 \Sigma Ts^0$ & $St^0 \ll Tt-2$ and that is what we call Dodecalogic, which suffices to explain an enormous range of scientific events. It is that all? Mostly:

The group of dimotions of spacetime. If we were to use a classic algebraic jargon, we could state that Reality is a block of spacetime made of scales of the 5th dimension in which spacetime organisms run worldcycles of existence.

All changes of the Universe ca be reduced to transformations of the group of dimotions, from the physiological networks in space of a superorganism tp the ages in time of a worldcycle to the states of matter, of the of that organism, to the symmetries of physics and its groups of particles. So we define Existential iloglc algebra as the analysis of the group of transformations of dimotions of spacetime. The elements of the group are the 5 dimotions, $Ss \ll St \ll \mathcal{T} \ll Ts \ll Tt$.

Two operations are defined in the group, \ll and \gg , which can be applied one or two times to the 2 elements of each dimotion. This is enough to transform each dimotion into another with 1 or 2 ‘STœps’. I.e. Tt can change $t \gg s$ to become Ts , $t \gg S$ to become TS , $T \gg S$ to become Ts , and then in perception, the opposite of death: $Tt \gg Ss$.

Each of those existential Stœps encodes an essential event for superorganism or its parts. Moreover, those transformations are the ONLY events happening in reality by a Least Time principle of economicity. So there are 12 transformations as they are non-commutative. Such group of transformations of dimotions of existence is the fundamental group of the Universe origin of most of its events and forms. So this is what we call DODECALOGIC. The basic level of understanding of space-time dimotions.

It must be notice though that the probability of one of those events is different – and it is interesting to calculate its relative ‘bell curves’, as the commonest actions are those with a single \gg \ll change. Death happens once, Seeding and emergence also once, and sublimations and precipitations very rarely. So 5 of those events are constant, those which relate St , \mathcal{T} and Ts and the mirror perception, $st-1 \approx ST+1$ In physics they are obviously all the changes of states between St -solid, \mathcal{T} liquid (which indeed dissolves both gases and solids) and Ts -solids, and the evaporation of liquids, $\mathcal{T} \ll Ts$, dissolution of solids, $St \ll \mathcal{T}$, precipitation, sublimation and *the creation of an image in a crystal, hence properly written is $St-1 \approx St+1$, that is, perception tends to be of a state of the world with more form than motion, converted into an image with more form than motion, subtle considerations that go beyond this introduction to ilogic, existential \mathcal{A} -Algebra. Why that name?*

Processes of change through absorbtion and emission of energy.

The ‘triggering’ event that starts a change in the $ST_{2,3}$ groups of transformations of spacetime (dual and trinity events states and pentalogic worldcycles) is the absorbtion of external s and t energy elements by a system. Consider for example a seed, Ss . It first uses its internal energy to ‘move’ St , internally and then it brings a reproductive $\Sigma \nabla St$ multiplication of its ‘cells’ in the blastula state (we do use the Δ , ∇ , \gg \ll in the mathematical and ilogic sense, as in fact they are different symmetric perspectives, as a $Ts \gg St$ process in dynamic spacetime is also in a simple space view between a larger ‘limb-motion system’ and a smaller still St -head system, and a growth through social networks, $\Delta+1$, is an Δ -growth...). So what we mean is that the Ss seed, moves internally, changing to its information, form-in-action state, St , and then it starts to divide, Σ into smaller, ∇ clones, forming a morula. But as the energy exhausts, it *needs an external placenta to feed it, and so $\Sigma St + \mathcal{T}$ will trigger further growth, and while most of what the cell receives is \mathcal{T} -energy of motion, it does receive \mathcal{S} molecular food.*

Interaction with the larger world in a positive way is thus necessary for most events of the Universe.

But the interaction might receive NO form at all, only motion, as when a force is applied to a system, which in relative stillness, St (with internal motions, either in sleep or thought, few systems are in a static Ss -seed state), then will suffer an interesting change. As S becomes T , but the system CANNOT merely change St to Tt because that will be an entropic ‘inner and OUTER motion’ that will disorder the entity, the system in *motion stops internal t-motion, ‘thought’, and becomes far more passive. In*

physical systems, we write St because its 'center of gravity' does NOT move across its trajectory even when the object is rotating, so it can be treated as a point-particle. But humans also need 'stillness' to think with maximal inner motion. When we move we think far less, we sense motion observe and act-react to the external world.

Those examples show how a 5D scientist who understands the 'simple principles of relational space-time superorganisms' can explain all kind of things nobody has even attempted to 'question'. There are many of those 'little laws' that become then phenomenological and experimental in the real world in any scale. But in reality when we observe systems, they are most entangled in trinity scales, $St \llcorner \Uparrow \triangleright Ts$ organisms which dominate through each network an age of time. So while the group of transformations is useful we do better using the symbology of ' $\sim \approx$ ilogic, existential algebra' (ab. $\sim \approx$ Algebra or ilogic). This seems to be the best definition, because it is a system that uses non-Euclidean points, non-E lines, Non-E planes etc. Its logic is Non-Aristotelian as time moves forwards and backwards in worldcycles; its logic moreover is more complex as it has also causality up and down, 5D scales. And its NOT a classic logic of predicates and words but closer in its 'symbolism' to that of algebraic mathematics even if symbols are changed in meaning.

It would be more accurate to completely drop that terminology and use \mathcal{D}_j as a symbol for the Different 'Dimotions' and scales of systems. But as \mathcal{D} is not easy to print, I grew lazy. The same goes with the \triangleright and \llcorner symbols. It would be better to use the $\times \gg \ll$ symbols for the informative and entropic $S \llcorner T$ and $T \triangleright S$ and $St_j \llcorner St_{j-2}$ motions, etc.

Why? Because the whole detailed model of analysis of all the events of reality requires to use Δ as 'growth', and its inverse ∇ as diminution, and \triangleright and \llcorner as bigger or smaller *in the processes of 'transformation between scales'*.

So often I thought on doing a thorough change of symbology but what for? Those are just papers I only read. Humanity don't seem to go beyond its obvious scale, its simpleton time arrow of entropy and soon will be extinct by metalife. So who cares...

Had 5D expanded enough I would have been more rigorous with those symbols. So, instead of Δ for the '5th dimension' (also a concept that is a concession to classic 4D physics but has not real meaning, as obviously the 3 classic space dimension and 4th time dimension are rough simplifications), place \mathcal{D} and use \mathcal{d} for a worldcycle, and so on. Why I chose Δ ; because it is \mathcal{D} in Greek and because its form reminds us of the 'change in size' as we move between scales of the 5th dimension.

In ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' together, as it does so in 'finitesimal' quanta (hence the importance of calculus), and it is only the sum of those many little steps that make the whole worldcycle advance implacable towards death. In fact the system tries to keep its present immortality, and works in a different way, as the limbs and the head try ideally to 'serve' the connecting body. So we write for all of them the 'fractal generator' of 'still space': $Ts \llcorner \Uparrow \triangleright St$, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic \llcorner and \triangleright states balance each other. This is the 'ideal equation of immortality, which for history means Gaia \llcorner History \llcorner Metal-earth, the repression of the 3rd age of technological information and the enhancement of the life age of Gaia.

(ST)3₃ becomes the group of entanglements in space. *We study both its symmetries in this paper on existential ilogic and the scientific method. The reader should easily realize that both groups are closely connected to the two most useful groups of physical systems, SU2 & SU3 so we will also analyze in our papers on physics those relationships once we complete those papers in the future...* But we are NOT using the rough jargon of Group theory beyond the assertion they are an unfocused mirror of the dualities and trinities of 5D. Trinity makes sense in space as an entangled network organism and in time as a symmetry of 3 ages. If we add the Δ -1 seed and death state, almost all events belong to a worldcycle of existence of one of such superorganisms, including what we call the life and death cycle. So the study of reality can be formalized as the study of the worldcycle of existence. And what existential algebra does then is to study structures in space and events in time, related to the 6 static Dimotions of existence and its 6 dynamic changes.

In space we connect 3 elements of reality in a single Δ_j plane; hence the trilogic of existence of its fractal generator.

But then comes the question of how many 'trinity' entanglements we can write with \triangleright and \llcorner even in a single plane (without adding social growth, Σ , into herds, absorption of external energy and information, +, or loss of them, -, networks entanglements, which I used to represent with \Uparrow - a symbol I know put for $\S \Uparrow$ -energy or dual t , yes a bit of a mess).

This is NOT difficult to represent and interpret. If $Ts > \S\Upsilon > St$ are the 3 ages, and $Ts < \S\Upsilon < St$ is the stable organism, whereas the Ts -limbs give motion to the body, $\S\Upsilon$ and the St -head gives them information, so $\S\Upsilon$ can reproduce the present, we can still write 2 forms. $Ts > \S\Upsilon < St$ & $Ts < \S\Upsilon > St$. What do they mean? Just what they say.

In the 1st case the Limbs don't move but receive energy-motion from the body, so do the head that does not think and move the body with an action purpose but receive energy from the body. So this is the state of 'stillness', the limbs don't move and mental rest, when the body repairs and feeds the other 2 elements. So it is the 'Sleep mode'. Hence we have just discovered another 'rhythm', this time a transformation of 'ternary states': from the 'sleep' vs. 'awake' modes.

It is the second ternary 'transformation' of the ST_3 group, so to speak. The first one is between the superorganism in space and the superorganism aging in time; the second one between the awake and the sleep mode.

Indeed $Ts < \S\Upsilon > St$, an inverse relationship to that of sleeping, when the limbs move the body and the brain is at rest, because the body informs it with its e-motions NOT with thoughts, but e-motions, which are the 'actions of the body'. Indeed, those are e-motions of the heart and e-motions mostly not thoughts motivate almost all systems to act. Only overdeveloped human brains are moved by thoughts. Almost all other systems are 'sensorial induced' through e-motions of the body that wants to feed or reproduce, its two essential task. So this other duality is the awake-sleep mode and it is extremely common.

Of course is a subtle balance which if taken to extremes, when the St is completely 'sleepy' and does not guide a bit e-motions, doesn't look good. Then it IS the less stable ternary state and we must conclude this 'zombie', 'somnambular' mode is likely to bring an accidental death and end badly in Tt due to the blindness of the mind. And there are also a lot of examples in reality, with degrees of 'egocy' and 'blindness' of the mind, which doesn't move properly and let the 'limbs' dominate its actions, from antiparticles going to annihilation to suicide. But for those states we would rather use a double $\ll \gg$ extreme change.

Now we realize those are the two fundamental modes of trinity change and there are no more modes in the 'well-ordered' ST_3 group, of limb/fields \approx body-waves = particle heads; because systems join heads and limbs, particles and fields almost universally through bodies. Yes, you can consider some exceptions. For example when the squid with eye was born, the St -informative perception was so powerful that it got his 10 feet-hands on the head. But those are rare happenings. Survival here starts to select. You cannot have many of such $\S\Upsilon < St < Ts$ systems at work. But we will see, precisely the order of the 3 elements of a trinity group=superorganism define phyla of animal life, typological linguistics, etc. but one is the commonest:

Subject=Verb=Object, etc. In fact for those rare cases transformation of form and function happen. The limbs become informative tactile fingers, hence from Ts are used as St and the body of the squid throws turbo-water, so it works as a Ts -limb.

The game of existence suddenly starts to be less varied because of all possible combinations survival favors certain ones.

And so the main transformations of a superorganism in space time are a dual change of $> <$ operandi from the time active state $Ts < St > St$ to the space, rest state, $Ts > \S\Upsilon < St$. And from spatial to temporal \ll, \gg states.

Dual-dual scalar jumps. the actions of existence.

Organisms grow in information as the St -head/particle dominates the system. All dimotions of existence but entropy=feeding, perception, locomotion as reproduction of information, genetic reproduction and social evolution, are dominant in information. So the ideal balance, focusing the mind on the body $Ts < \S\Upsilon < St$, though possible is rare.

Thus most systems instead warp into a 3rd age and then to balance the $S=T$ content of the Universe, explode in death after exhausting their vital energy. This said, the question we want to address is the scalar nature of those dimotions, which happen also in an orderly manner, as social evolution brings $\Sigma\Delta 0 > \Delta +1$, systems up one scale; reproduction happen in the same $\Delta 0$, as a dual movement of a seed in $\Delta -1$; feeding simplifies after entropic death the parts of $\Delta 0$ -prey into $\Delta -2$ molecular food; perception acts in the smallest $\Delta -4$, light forces and motion on the $\Delta -4$ gravitational field. So the question here is, if we said that $\Delta -2$ is a dead jump, a limit, as in feeding, the 3 first dimotions, social evolution, reproduction and feeding are within the limit, but perception and motion are a 4-jump of scale. And so it must be understood as performed by our $\Delta -2$ parts in a dual-dual jump. Let us see if experimentally that is the case. First the scales, which tend to be in the 10^{10} scale of social parts to become a new whole (stars of a galaxy, humans of the global society, ties of a DNA human molecule, cells of an organism, etc. for

reasons treated in other parts). So the scales down of mankind are the cell, the molecule, the particle (Not the atom which is a gathering of very few particles, and in fact most matter is in the plasma, particle state, or at best, 1 proton+1 electron, the 'gender-couple' or 2+2+2 Helium), and then we have the 'forces', given the fact that in 5D physics, an electron nebulae is a gathering of 'star-like photons', as a galatom nebulae of the similar mirror maximal scale is a gathering of stars. So we have the scales: Δ -1: cell, Δ -2: molecule, Δ -3: particle, Δ -4: force. The same down process split at the particle/atom level, as the electron is the Ts-part and the quark the St-part (cover and nucleus, mobile and informative, Ts-electromagnetic vs. St-gravitational force, etc.) down to the quark and its billions of microscopic components even if we see the strong force bundled into gluons...

Physicists called the hypothetical particle a graviton, but they are a mess of theory at that scale they don't see, with their reductionist models of time, space, symmetry and scale. We shall call it so far, because no other particle is discovered at that tiny level abundant enough to play that game, the neutrino, even if we just see a few of them. The whole subject needs a brainstorm between a 5D theorist and a top particle physicists that didn't happen. There are theoretical hurdles – in 4D relativity the graviton is a 2-spin, in particle physics the neutrino is $\frac{1}{2}$ spin, but there is no a clear understanding of the conservation of spin numbers, not even of the speed of rotation of spins, likely above c , or the neutrino speed also likely about c , of the hyper-universe, of dark energy, then there is the neutrino light theory of Broglie and Jordan, with its critics. Let us leave it there and state for the time being that this 'graviton' likely neutrino is the Δ -4 scale of gravitation.

So for 5D to work, the motion on gravitation and the perception of light is NOT done by the body and the mind but by an intermediate Δ -2 state of multiple electrons – an electric wave; and motion also must be at the Δ -2 atomic scale. And that is the case. We see Δ -4 photons that activate electrons in the eye, but the image of the Universe we have is an electric field in the brain of many electrons likely a whole bunch of occipital neurons in a network with electric images, and the same goes for machines whose tv-retinas are made of multiple electrons scanning a big screen. So perception is a dual-dual scalar jump. Motion then again happens by electrostatic repulsion at the atomic level and if gravitation attracts us in free fall it is attracting the atomic level. So that is why we 'scale' actions from Δ +1 social evolution to Δ -1 seminal reproduction to Δ -2 feeding to Δ -4 perception and motion. And that's about it all what matters in Existential \neg -Algebra, at least in this introduction. And in almost all the papers and their description with '5D Stience' of its laws, species, forms and events and worldcycles.

LOGIC. Translation of propositional logic/set theory to Existential logic.

In the graph, we translate into existential ilogic the symbols of logic of truth and falsehood. In classic logic, the reasoning on truth and falsehood is based in those simple rules and symbols:

- Negation, which is clearly equivalent to non-existence; a sometimes to entropy, Tt, the disorder and annihilation of a system. Truth therefore becomes 'existence' and falsehood' becomes extinction, non-existence, or entropy.
- $A \wedge B$: for A and B, which is related to $+\Delta$, an increase of social scales, as it 'ads' A and B; hence to the 'arrow' of social evolution of a system, the main arrow of the 5th dimension (Δ +j or Ss as Dimotion).
- $A \vee B$: for A or B, which is related to $-\Delta$, ∇ , as it implies a disjunctive 'choice' of one of two components; hence a diminution of a social A, B whole or set, a Darwinian event of 'devolution' as only one remains after the event (Δ -j and Tt as dimotion)
- $A \Rightarrow B$, which means A implies B in causal Time, which is related to $A > B$, the main 'arrow' of increase of information in the Universe, or natural arrow of future, even if it can be reversed as a past flow motion, as $A < B$, equivalent to $B > A$, $B \Rightarrow A$. So the symbol in its two variables is equivalent to the Past to future and Future to Past flows of 5D Logic (St and Ts as dimotions)
- $A \Leftrightarrow B$, means A causes B \wedge B causes A, which is the basic duality of the present Universe, also the symbol of \S ||-energy.

So the 5 symbols of the logic of truth and falsehood are equivalent to the 5 Dimotions of the Universe.

The propositional logic of Aristotle latter applied to mathematics, and computers through set theory, slightly changed in reticular logic however are NOT good enough systems (Godel) to define truth, but merely the internal consistency of a syntax of a language, itself a mirror syntax as we have shown, with some distorsions of the much wider logic of 'creation' and destruction (equivalent to truth=existence and falsehood=non existence) of the entities of reality. So we shall by-pass it as a mino detail.

$v(A)$	$v(B)$	$v(\neg A)$	$v(A \wedge B)$	$v(A \vee B)$	$v(A \Rightarrow B)$	$v(A \Leftrightarrow B)$
V	V	F	V	V	V	V
V	F	F	F	V	F	F

Once we understand the limited but ∞ variations of the game of existence, we can understand the essence of the game:

The game of spacetime existences will create under the Totalitarian principle (Leibniz to Gell-Mann) all possible variations, including mad thoughts, unstable particles, aberrant species in explosions=radiations of creativity, the Cambrian radiation, the particle zoo, the explosion of re=productive company-mothers of machines-weapons once a new form of 'energy' in the 80 years cycles occur, all the varieties of mathematical curves and topological forms with motion... But then there will be also a massive selection that will prune the tree of existence of all those species that are NOT efficient within its $\Delta\emptyset 3$ physiological networks, or even if they are efficient, they are NOT adapted to the requirements of its $\Delta+1$ world, or even so, they are 'weaklings' in the $\Delta-1$ cellular scale where they can be easily parasitized. Selection is then extreme to the point that often only a single form remains, the human mammal, the parental cell of all of us, the quark and electron, the 20 amino acids, and so on. This is the game, and the best way to express all those laws is the use of the simple rules of existential ilogic algebra, we shall now consider in a very brief statement, from where through topological combinations we can understand the game:

Reality is a block of time made of scales of the 5th dimension in which spacetime organisms run worldcycles of existence.

Each detail of the game of existence is a worldcycle of one of such superorganisms, what we call the life and death cycle. So the study of reality can be formalized as the study of the worldcycle of existence. So what existential algebra does then is to study 'structures' as classic algebra does of a given type, we might call the group of transformations of the 5 Dimotions of existence.

Group theory in 5D algebra analyzes 'støeps' of spacetime due to transformations between the 5 elements of the group of dimotions of space-time.

In the graph, the main laws of 5D stiences. With those laws and the few symbols of 5D metrics and Existential ilogic (S, T, <, >, $\Delta\pm j...$) we an, define all events and systems of reality that combines the 5 Dimensional motions and its ternary systems in scalar planes, time ages and spatial organs to define all *actions of S-evolution, §T]- repetition and T-extinction the Universe allows, which then will be selected by raw efficiency leaving only those survivors that play better the two functions of the 5th dimension,*

SxT (s=T) balances that maximize the function of existence, in a given plane. As nothing else, which cannot be expressed through those combinations within those limits exists outside the virtual inflationary mind-languages of information. Trust me, I know it, after 30 years of research in all fields of knowledge looking for a falsification of Existential ilogic. So in our papers on ilogic we will develop with them all events & species of reality. So the equivalent to the fundamental law of 4D science in 5D Stience is one of existential ilogic. 'All systems of Nature try to survive selecting of all the potential existential events and Dimotions of space-time, those who maximize its function of existence, Max. S xT (s=T) in its point of present balance.

So the key language of reality becomes the pentalogic entanglement of spaces=forms, its 5 time=actions, the $\Delta\pm j$ organic scales where they symbiotically play the game of existence, guided by smaller $\Delta-j$ Ss-languages=mirrors that the informative mind-system uses to the whole supærganism at faster synoptic linguistic speeds (due to the $TxS=\Delta\pm j$ metric). In the graph we summarize the structure of 5D Universal laws that apply to all scales and stiences, based in the entangled pentalogic symmetries between space=form, time=motion, @-languages of mind mirrors who perform its program of existence, through its 5 local dimotions and the symbiotic scalar organisms they create, with its 5 organic Dimotions, becoming supærganisms tracing the same worldcycles of existence, as we are all details of the thoughts of God, its laws of- $\Delta@st$, dust of space-time.

Stiences are then easily classified as part of the set of scalar laws run by disomorphisms between 3 $\Delta\pm j$ scales which are self-centered in an specific superorganism, the atom in physics, the molecule in chemistry, the cell in biology, the human being in medicine, the culture in sociology and history, the solar system in astrophysics, the galaxy in astronomy, which corresponds to one of those scales. But all those scales can be studied in its synthetic ultimate process of space and time with the laws of superorganisms, worldcycles, its symmetries, as $\sim \Delta@st$, using the synoptic laws of existential ilogic. As we are ultimately transformations of the group of dimotions of spacetime (:

The entanglement between organic properties in Δ -scale, topologic properties in space and dimotions=vital functions in time mirrored by the syntactic Universal grammar of all languages, whose entropic limits of perception and duration and extension in scale, time and space makes reality a fractal ensemble of space-time organisms. If you grasp this sentence, you will know the thoughts of God. The different details of reality, its scalar, mental space-time species are variations of the same theme. **So A->B** causality of Aristotelian logic is expanded because events do happen by the collapse of the influence of 3 networks over a

space-time point and the inner and outer St-motion and form of the point, for a total of 5 causal reasons to a event. In praxis this implies a Rashomon effect in the search of truth, as we need to understand those events from the perspective of 5 Dimotions & 3 scales. Δ @st of space-time you are & you'll become. As reality is a tug of war between Mental Space mirrors and Tt-entropic flows of motion in ∞ beings and scales: $\Delta \pm \infty \prod Ss \Leftrightarrow \sum Tt$.

Pentalogic sets the basis of a new Philosophy of science=knowledge completing its 3 horizons of evolution, the experimental method of Aristotle that accepted all languages and senses to measure truth, with a strict logic analysis, the mechanical method of Galileo that reduced languages to those of machines to measure time (clocks) and space (telescopes), denying the logic of the 3 causal verbal tenses, we regain with the pentalogic method and the definition of truth as the sum of all the mirror languages on the system we perceive – it is the organic method that considers the isomorphic 5D laws of scales as the template to organize the data of all stiences in a rational, systematic way. Since what the mechanical method has done is to reduce science to technology and the creation of a digital mind, shunning off the search of the ultimate goal of science: to understand the first principles of reality and the meaning of the game of existence, which 5D explains.

-(@≤S≤T≤Δ): Symmetry and entanglement vs. idealism and the axiomatic method.

Languages are synoptic mirrors of the pentalogic game of existence that ‘entangles’ the scales, spaces, time worldcycles of the Universe, establishing its limits of entropy in time (Death), space (membranes) and scales of inter-action. This is NOT however how the ‘egocy’ paradox (ego=idiocy) of ‘finitesimal minds’ 0ϵ (finitesimal mind) $\times \infty$ Universe = Constant world, build its linguistic mirrors, which they confuse with the Universe as it is often the only ‘perception’ they have of a given reality. As most species including man are monologic one-dimensional mirrors – in our case mostly visual in space, used to be verbal, ‘rational’ in time before the age of virtual, audiovisual information. So we have a huge problem to enlighten and upgrade any 4D science to pentalogic 5D science – one of the ultimate structure of the ‘humind’, its egocy and monologic.

This is specially truth of the ‘3rd informative age’ of mathematics, in which as all old age mind’s STages the mirror has unconnected from reality to become an ‘infinity mirror’ of excessive self-reflecting images, through the idealist Jewish-German schools of Hilbert and Cantor that brought us niceties like fascism, communism, financial parasitism, nationalist genocides... and other ‘animetal deranged’ states of society treated at face value in our papers of History. In brief, mathematics, long past its classic age now relies in mental proofs because indeed, *all mirror languages mirror also the pentalogic structure in its syntax, which allows to make belief in the plausibility of its world as if it was real. As in theater – a language of the game of existence of human life – as long as the ‘Stanislawski method’ is not betrayed and the actor dresses in epoch draperies things will look OK. But an old man trying to convince you of its truths with an excess of repetitive information gives you little insights on reality as it is. Problem is the old man is NOT coming out of its mind-home because he no longer understands the outside Universe, so he cannot provide you a realist ‘classic account’ of the mirror proved outside by the experimental method, and so he ‘doubles the stakes’ of absolute truths, affirming his language-words are NOT in needed of any empirical proof, and ultimately thinks of himself as the God of the Language, its pope. Mr. Cantor and Mr. Hilbert in the tradition of their idealist cultures succeeded convincing mankind that if Hilbert ‘imagines points, lines and planes’ that suffices us to know what they are as ‘all of mathematics can be proved with set theory’. Then of course as we go through the proofs we keep finding egocy all over the place. But the method man won’t care for anything else. A simple example: in topology these days ‘connectedness’, which as the name indicates intuitively means that a space is all in one piece is defined as ‘A topological space X is connected if each map of it into the two point space (0,1) takes all of X into one of 0 or 1’ . So we have an inflationary runaway method, where something intuitive truth – a definition, *whose properties then we shall explore with ‘rational thought’ and references to a comprehensible reality, because the language is NOT the goal in itself but a mirror that help us to understand reality – becomes detached from reality and issues us into new more complicated, more detached mental spaces invented by the mathematician so we can waste our spacetime in the ‘Cantorian paradise’ of its religion of truth. This cultural religious method of Popes that hold all the way to Biblical inquisitions of truth and spreads in so many sciences with the appropriate censorships – you cannot even refer them to cultural corruption – In the case of mathematics started when Lobachevski proved the 5th Euclidean axiomatic truth false, and rightly told us that to know what was real in the Universe of space we had to look at the experimental reality. Yet Hilbert, failing to understand fractal non-Euclidean points with an inner volume through which a**

relative infinity of parallels can cross them, imagine with his penpal Cantor a paradise of mind definitions in which mathematicians have hosted.

5D simply gets rid of all this, but as mathematicians live now in the mind of Cantor not in the Universe, we have to painstakingly translate each supputation of the mind of Cantor, who went from a madhouse to a cemetery and refer it to reality to get back the meaning of connectedness and extract from its properties lessons about reality with applications to all sciences. It is then when mathematics again acquires its power as a synoptic language of reality mirror of the only language which is more efficient – the game of existence itself, and its Δ -scales, space topologies, time ages and mind languages that guide real, vital species through the game, with the aim of making them survive, which they achieve *when their language does mirror efficiently reality. In brief, a 'Cantorian species' would NOT survive embroiled in the world of set.*

That's why a connected atom within a crystal network will never map itself to the two points space. It will just look at the other atoms of the network in its neighborhood and know it is connected – entangled, a property of reality that makes it happen. Since reality is about the symmetries and feed-back sharing of motion and form between connected non-Euclidean points with inner parts, which form networks that become superorganisms across 3 relative scales: $-(@ < S \leq T \leq \Delta)$: A mind is a language-mirror that reflects a still image of a space that moves through time ages, as a travel through 3 scales of the fifth dimension that defines its worldcycles within the limits of entropy and death... The language is smaller because it fits within the mind the space, a slice of a time worldcycle, an existence of the potential essence of all worldcycles of the scalar universe. *So to unfold all the beauty of a language we must NOT go into inflationary axioms to make egocentric proofs of mental truths but go the other way through those elements to see how the language reflects as a still limited space the worldcycles of the Universe, extracting its essential properties.*

$-(@ < S \leq T \leq \Delta)$ is the 'syntax' of all realities including all languages which must therefore be limited by entropic existence, and departing from the @-language shown to mirror in its mental space a temporal, scalar reality, which the language in its synopsis helps to understand FASTER so we can RUN its program of existence in pentalogic terms to get conclusions BEFORE they happen to anticipate the deterministic future with the language and manage a praxis of survival.

Only the Universe has all the truth about itself...

Our model of the Universe is an entropic model that measures only the expansion of vacuum space between galaxies (Tt) but ignores its contraction due to the force of gravitation in galaxies (Ss), which makes galaxies similar to atoms in the lower 5D scale of electromagnetic space where the strong 'gravitational-like' force balances the 'electromagnetic' 'dark-Energy like' force; so you are not contracting into the past or expanding into the future. Reductionism also works in biology where the theory of evolution stresses the final death by entropic predators but has shunned off for very long the evolution of information and speed of reproduction that defines the most successful social species (ants and humans). Entropy is also the practical theory of human societies, meaning through History war, using entropic weapons, constructed by physicists not diplomatic collaboration and social evolution have defined the fate of mankind. Because of all those shortcomings of human intelligence and ethics (respect of other living parts of reality), and the fact that we confuse our self with the whole Universe humans have kept destroying the world of the tree of life and building the tree of metal, with weapons, gold and machines (entropic, reproductive and informative metal) as attachments of themselves, becoming a symbiotic species we shall call animetal, whose worldview must be interpreted in historic terms more than scientific ones; once we realize beyond the 1st step of the scientific method, Accurate gathering of data, greatly enhanced by the use of mechanisms, mankind has gone nowhere on B)creation of true organic models of reality proved by its C)cyclic patterns =Laws of science; used to manipulate Nature in favor of D)emocratic solutions for 'all Humanity' to improve life, preventing E)xtinctive, entropic solutions that kill Nature & mankind (war machines; money for the 1%, 6th extinction of Gaia...)

The ultimate Reality is biological and organic, with Time and Scale as its larger component. It is NOT about 'physical, spatial, suporganisms, and its even more reduced mind mirrors - but knots of spacetime cycles whose synchronicities entangle its parts so we can perceive them as forms of spatial in-form-ation in a synoptic language. So all languages are mental spaces, all spaces are mental constructions and that is fine as long as we use them to manage our dimotions in reality, NOT to become old men closed in its Cantor paradise, which gets offended if we tell him to get out to the world.

PHYSICAL LAWS: ITS DIMOTIONAL PRINCIPLES. IMMORTAL, ∞ UNIVERSE

Physical function of existence tries to maximize the worldcycle.

Physical systems want to exist, according to a Function of existence stable in a point of balanced $S=T$ present repetitive time:

Max. $S \times T | s=t$, translates that goal of all Spacetime systems to physics, like it does in all sciences. The outcome is a least time Lagrangian of 0-sum actions: S (Potential energy) = T (kinetic energy), which is the balance of the larger $\Delta+1$ world, systems must respect, while maximizing in its inner organic systems, its 'standing points' of maximal angular and lineal momentum, Max. $S \times T$, which therefore transform into each other through SHM motions. This is what is all about in physical systems. The system exists by performing actions of lineal and cyclical momenta, within a larger ordered $S=T$, energy balance. And to do so in the lower plane of reality, $\Delta-1$ they perform 5 Dimotions of existence perceived as forces acting on the environment.

But as in all other systems of Nature, there is a small imbalance of more information, which we study in detail considering that the particle-head state dominates most motions, and the frequency of still mental information, required to perform those motions outweighs the intaking of locomotion and energy, $S_t > S_s \geq T_s > T_t$; so slowly S Step by S Step of stop and go, S and T States, the system S Tages its aging process of 3 informative ages and a final reversal of T_t -entropic death, as any $T.\infty$:

5D physics: The 'joker' of energy, the 3 scales of physical systems, present momentum.

Energy as humans use the term, departed from the concept of 'vis viva' or present momentum to penetrated through all the scales of the 5th dimension, whose content of motion and form is added as new forms of energy. More precisely energy should translate as the higher 3rd physical scale of an organism: So we have 3 scalar quantities:

- The $\Delta\emptyset$ scale of $O+|$ angular and lineal momentum, where the being as a whole 'transits' with a periodicity or beat given by its function of time (speed); and the minimal quanta of that momentum, $\Delta-1$: force ; as $\partial p / \partial t = F$.

While the sum=integral of momentum along a longer path that add a series of steps, is its $\Delta+1$: 'energy=work', $\int p = W$.

Since Energy initially was used for the measure of longer work scales.

Today Energy is still larger than momentum, closer to the concept of its duration in time. So Energy x Time=Angular momentum.

So it is divided by scale in internal $\Delta-1$ scales with internal energy, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic energy and the external $\Delta+1$ scale with potential energy, where the whole is seen in relationship to its world (so an electron has potential energy due to its trapping in the nucleus strong+gravitational+positive charge force and a person in a high mountain has potential energy as part of the Earth).

Finally every $\Delta\pm j$ scale of reality was added to the concept of energy when mass that includes them all inside its cosmological envelopes, down to the $\forall-3$ light scale became converted into energy, which is not since $E=M$ means that Mass 'dies' as a form of space and transforms itself into Lineal T -motion, where that E is closer to entropy.

So the problem of the concept of Energy in physics is that all transformations of S -form into T -motion 'keep' the naming of Energy that has become like 'God' in old religion, the 'concept' that expresses the fact that reality is indeed an eternal transformation of S -forms into T -motions, of $|$ -topologies into O -topologies through intermediate \emptyset -wave states.

This means it is better for rules of measure to use the more precise concepts of $|$ -lineal momentum and O -angular momentum.

And then translate physical laws into the same ΔST laws of other sciences. For example, conservation laws conserve the ΔST elements of 5D: Δ -energy is conserved, S -form defined by cyclical angular momentum is conserved, and T -lineal time motion defined by lineal momentum is conserved. So the 3 elements of 5D reality, ΔST , which are conserved in an immortal Universe, are expressed in 3 laws of conservation in physics.

The paradox of Galileo. Absolute relativity. Wave Motion v. still particle form. The mental space of special relativity.

The 2 basic postulates of the special theory of relativity - The laws of physics must be the same in all inertial reference frames & The speed of light in vacuum has the same value, c in all inertial frames, regardless of the velocity of the observer or the velocity of the source emitting the light, translate to a continuous single space-time and the mental space our electronic eyes construct with it, the stop and go motions of all the scales of Nature, so they are not absolute truths but 'constructs'. If we were in the electron scale, we would see 2 electrons communicating through a quantum, neutrino potential locking each other in the l-arrow of minimal information at a fixed still distance, as information is emitted in still, parallel form between perceiver and emitter. Systems move in wave state and emit information in stop particle state. The Lorentz transformations ignore this as in our scale like in a movie theater where the image is emitted in stop state and then the frame move to the next, we see only the continuous motion. This creates a distortion, which the Lorentz transformations correct so we can keep our 'safe' view. The same goes for c -speed which is just the limit of speed of reproduction of information in \forall -light spacetime, which is the one elementary particles use once they lock in the quantum potential (gravitational scale? neutrino space?, neutrino theory of light?). But the 1st emission of neutrino? Quantum potential? Δ -4 spacetime is faster than c , non-local as we don't perceive its information hence $v=S/t(\text{information})=S/0\epsilon=\infty$ (symbols of a finitesimal information, only the distance-angle of the receiver, and immensity). Then we build the \forall -form with a new height dimension, and speed goes to c ; and then as we build new 'waves and particles' speed keeps going down (more information is transmitted/reproduced). The theoretical basis of 5D are absolute relativity: we cannot distinguish motion and form so all systems have the same amount of t-motion and s-form, thus they stop and go. And the mean time they are in stop state is equivalent to the mean time they are in motion state: $S=t$, because ultimately motion is reproduction of form. Absolute relativity thus supersedes special relativity considered just its adaptation to continuous motion.

The simple equations of Δ ST in physics: Conservation principles and 'scalar calculus'.

Though in this paper we are allergic to equations (: as it is 1st about correcting and clarify concepts of verbal physics, now that we have opened the pandora box of the big word, 'calculus' is easy to see hwo the next st-age, when we go through if we go through it – the mathematical formalism of all those 5D concepts will flow easily, by considering just the operands of calculus that integrate scales of the 5th dimension, and 'desintegrate=derivate them'. So we can just see how conservation of momentum and energy become dynamic by virtue of the additions of 'finitesimal forces', called 'impetus', through integrals; and the same can be said of the next scale – how momentum grows through impulse of forces and can be stored as energy.

The simple example of the graph suffices: the momentum of a particle changes if a net force acts on the particle, during an interval of time quanta that we can integrate to obtain the momenta absorbed.

This is similar to how the energy of a system changes if energy crosses the boundary of the system to or from the environment in a *nonisolated system*. *Momentum changes then topologically through the membrane (Ts) of an open ball and energy in the symmetry $\Delta=S=T$, through a 5D 'scale' and in both cases we integrate through a 'time' period. So, in a nonisolated system either momentum or energy transfers across the scalar or spatial boundary of the system.*

Since $dP = \sum F dt$ we integrate² this expression to find the change in the momentum of a particle when the force acts over

$$\vec{I} = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \sum \vec{F} dt$$

some time interval: This result is the **impulse–momentum theorem**: "The change in the momentum of a particle is equal to the impulse of the net force acting on the particle", which is equivalent to Newton's second law and the most general statement of the principle of **conservation of momentum** called for that reason the **conservation of momentum equation**. The equivalent equation for Energy writes: $\Delta E_{\text{system}} = \sum T$. That is, the total energy of the system, which includes the 3 $\Delta\pm$ methods of energy storage ($\Delta\emptyset$: kinetic, $\Delta+1$: potential, and $\Delta-1$: internal), and T (for *transfer*) is the amount of energy transferred across the system boundary by some mechanism, such as $\Delta+1$: work, W or $\Delta-1$: heat, Q .

Although both equations are similar it is easy to see its differences related to the fact that Energy is the main $\Delta\pm j$ parameter and momentum the main $ST\emptyset$ parameter.

So the conservation of momentum is a vector equation, as we are in a single space-time plane, ours, whereas the energy equation is a scalar as we are in the 'perpendicular source/sink' 5th dimension.

Thus, \emptyset -momentum is studied in a single plane of space-time (sum of Δ -lineal, 'time' and \emptyset -angular 'space' momentum, though most physics deal with Δ -lineal transfers through collisions), and therefore there is only one plane to store momentum in a system.

But *since energy is an $\Delta \pm j$ scalar quantity*, there are three ways to store energy in a system: $\Delta \emptyset$ - kinetic, related to the $\Delta \emptyset$ -momentum plane, $\Delta +1$ potential related to the interaction of the system with the whole, and $\Delta -1$ internal, related to the internal $\Delta -1$ scale of the being.

Third, there is only one way to transfer momentum into a system: by the application of a 'derivative' force on the system over a time interval; as all *growths and reproductions in 5D systems come from the Δ -absorbtion/reproduction of motion and form, both of which 'are counted by virtue of the $S=T$ symmetry' as 'acceleration' (angular acceleration is 'form')*.

But there are 6 ways to transfer energy into a system. So we expand the Energy equation to its full 5D Version (whereas Δ is both, the mathematical symbol for increase and the scalar symbol for the 5th dimension):

$$\mathbf{5D\ Energy\ conservation\ equation:}\ \Delta_{\emptyset}K + \Delta_{+1}U + \Delta_{-1} E_{int} = W + Q + Tmw+Tmt+Tet+Ter$$

On the left, the 3 $\Delta \pm j$ forms of energy, on the right its 6 possible transfers, by $\Delta +1$ work, $\Delta -1$ heat, $\Delta \emptyset$ Tmw (mechanical waves) and 3 secondary forms related to the social evolution of a material organism, Tmt (matter transfer), and the addition through $\Delta \pm 2$, 3 scales of Tet (electrical transmission), and Ter (electromagnetic radiation), which opens for a 'purist' 5D scientist an argument about how many ' Δ -scales' we shall consider when defining a material organism... though as we have already noticed, $\Delta \pm 2$ is the key 'limit' as beyond it, a system *dies into its entropic minimal forms*. However as we also explained *systems are able to 'cheat' the law of $\Delta \pm 2$ entropic death by absorbing in two ST -ages motion or form, as in the case of \forall -radiation which is NOT absorbed by the whole Δ^0 system but first by its 'atomic orbitals'*.

Alas, so simple so beautiful: the symmetry between Δ -scale=Space-form=Time-motion, the key 5D law of the Universe will order and explain the causes of most physical, biologic and social laws and events, never explained before; as we did with conservation principles and the trilogy of physical elements, $\Delta \emptyset$ -momentum, its 'minimal' exchange 'currency' – a Force, where its accelerated future time st -age, $F=Ma$, is a derivative of conserved momentum, the present; and its longer, integral value, $\Delta +1$ work=energy that extends internally through all 5D scales of the being. A force spends its stored energy in minimal 'doses' calculated as 'derivative finitesimals of the present whole' its momentum: $\partial E=p$, $\partial p=F$. It is the 5D trinity of physical analysis that straightens up 5D physics, returnint to Earth Energy that became in 4D like God a word good for everything.

The different measures of Space-Time: Angular Momentum; Planck Units as space-time & scale measure.

What physical 'measure' reflects better the minimal space-time organism. An angular momentum=worldcycle of a physical particle, which is a \emptyset -sum motion around an $\emptyset e$ center enclosing a vital space: a virtual existience that conserves the energy of the whole. It has all the features of reality, and can be seen in each 'free lineal step', each local symmetry as a 'present' lineal moment(um); in its sum as a cycle that repeats its 'memory of the past' into the future; in its $\emptyset e$ center as a mind. In between as a vital space. *The Units of the Universe are it conserved quantities, because they are Dimotions NOT distances or motions alone but spacetime combinations. So cyclical time clocks are angular momenta, lineal spacetime is lineal momenta, and scalar magnitudes, mass or charge represent scale. All of them have in fact a combination of ΔST elementsw. But the most important is angular momenta, because from it we can detach both, the 'human units of space and time', and the other conserved moments.*

The relationships between angular momentum which is energy x Time or lineal momentum x space thus offer some insights as to what is form and motion in the Universe as opposed to human parameters, which *appear naked on those 2 formalisms*.

$$\text{Angular momentum} = \text{Energy} \times \text{Time} = \text{Lineal momentum} \times \text{Space}.$$

Human energy then appears as the 'storage' of existential 'force' that will be spent in a duration of Time and then die. It is best expressed when $h/2$, the angular momentum of a 'planckton', the minimal unit, fractal point of vacuum space gives birth to a virtual particle that *unless it reproduces again as an 'efficient' species, will just live one emergence, related to its energy x time. The more energy it has the less it will live. It is an efficient particle in the relative $\Delta +1$ ($s=t$), world, its function of existence, $SxT|s=t$ will last. I.e. given the pressure=density of form and Temperature=Time motion of the outer environment, the particle can or cannot*

live. A top quark cannot live in our world and decays, but likely in the center of an astronomical black hole it forms a boson or crystal matter. But we won't go there for long.

On the other hand the Lineal momentum x Space indicates how long a 'free' path in simultaneous space creates a distance; again without reproduction. How far the 'impetu' of the 'disk thrower' (angular momentum) will reach after departure. It is a less important equation for particle physics but it matters to understand matter waves. If we use it to consider the $h/2$ planckton unit of energy, the question is no longer in terms of creation of particles measured with Energy parameters, but of waves. The beauty of that equation then is that the longer in space this 'entity' of 'distance' reaches the less lineal momentum it has. So to reach \propto distance it needs $mv=0\epsilon$ (in 5D there are not infinities and absolute 0s but immensities and finitesimals). Now m is accordingly 0 in waves of light, but not so clearly, because frequency carries some 'energy'. The less frequency, the longer the wave, and its distance. The conclusion it leads is obvious: a 'distance' which has only a wave frequency, hence it approaches to a perfect line can reach an immense quasinfinitude. Those concepts are necessary for understanding things like quantum potentials, neutrino backgrounds, hyper-universes, G \neq ant waves, neutrino theory of light, entanglement, non-locality, Absolute relativity that gets rid of Lorentz transformations as particles first communicate in the $\Delta-4$ scale of distance with clarity before complicated maths obscure the first crystal-clear concepts regarding time=motion, form=space and energy scales.

The real units of the Universe for Lineal spacetime are speed. C in the human scale; for cyclic space-time is angular momentum (h in the human scale) and of scalar vortices between scales Mass and Charge, hence G and K , which rightly Planck noticed to be the units of the Universe. Once more we see that human 'absolute space and time' is relative to us.

The most important upgrading of 5D then will concern to the relationship of mass and charge, starting from the Unification equation, which physicists can delight in expanding to more complex mathematical models as we shall use whenever possible simple Newtonian gravitational vortices after clarifying conceptually the relationship of the different 'inflationary' detailed mirrors of mathematics. Of interest now is to notice that both are 'accelerated vortices of space-time' (Principle of equivalence of Einstein between mass and acceleration that must be considered for curved space). Hence a vortex, $V_o \times R_o = K$, is the simplest bidimensional expression of a scalar magnitude, a motion in the 5th dimension in physical space. What we call the Unification equation (in Newtonian terms) is just its equivalence in 3 D: $M, Q = \omega^2 r^3 / U.C.(G, k)$. And obviously it has nothing special on its maths – stop being a creationist that believes the magic of the Universe is some old pedantic glass-god writing equations like Abrahamic Gods naming things. Both are related ultimately to the 2nd and 3rd law of Kepler and describe the conservation of angular momentum, lineal momentum and energy. But the fact is that if we substitute for different forces and physical orbital systems we get different 'lowering values' for the Universal constant, G and K of 'tension'. The meaning of all those constants in relationship to the fundamental 'parameters' of reality, form=mental space, and time=motion will require a very deep understanding of the logic principles of reality and so we will take it much latter on those papers. Still the general form of those equations is $\Delta \pm j = T \times S$, in different number of dimensions and motions, which is what needs conceptual understanding on how a dimension of time, or a cyclical motion becomes fixed by repetition in a form of space; how a cyclical motion of space converts into a lineal distance of space reducing its dimensions. How an angular momentum 'bores' through scales of the fifth dimension, etc. Namely the laws of transformations and creations of dimotions of space-time. The Universe is perceived by humans as a 'world' ($0\epsilon \times \infty$ Universe cycles = Mind world), reduced to a $\pm 10^{40}$ decametric scale, which is the difference of hierarchy between both gravitational and Columbus constants. This is the maximal distance traversed through scales of the 5th dimension when a Mass 'dies' entropically and 'appears' as pure c^2 -energy, $E=hf$.

ENTROPY VS. HIERARCHY OF SCALES: ENERGY TRANSFERS.

How much energy moves upwards in scales; how much 'entropy' $S=Q/T$ remains downwards? This concerns physicists in a childish manner, as they seek the maximal work for its engines. It concerns us here in a far deeper metaphysical way: 50-50%.

I love that sentence for personal reasons only for the initiated, cheer up Walter, we 'still exist' (: The logic behind it is obvious. If a system cedes to its 'social God', $\Delta+1$ more than 50% of its input, it will collapse, and start to reduce its populations. So the next time like the Schrodinger's cat whose chances to die increase 50% more each experiment, it will have less and the whole which would have fed and fattened will demand more. Collapse becomes then exponential, entropy-death sets to an e^{-x} rate if you are inclined to an exact equation. So it moves inversely after collapsing the parts, to a negative exponential decrease.

Be warned parasites that exploit financially by anoxia mankind, the holocaust happens. A wiser 'farm' thus is one that takes only the 10% as neurons and top predators do from the trophic pyramid. Hierarchy has its limits. The law is essential to the Universe. Because each new scale will play that 50-50, hence it will keep diminish. In fact the 50-50 is an ideal that only happens in the first perceived scale, $E=C/B$; the *energy of the lower scale of informative humind's perception, electronic light rises a 50% from the magnetic and a 50% from the electric scales. It is a perfect 'Carnot engine', so to speak.*

Then all is a lesser form. As Hartree said, the electromagnetic world gives us more and more intelligently that we understand. We distinguish then 3 kind of scalar $\Delta \pm 1$ relationships: predator pyramids that take around 10% in Volterra curves; farms and organic symbiosis that take from 10 to 50%; and parasites that take more than 50% and collapse the system. Mr. Bloomberg, the biggest parasite alive in this planet today takes through its platforms from the 3rd world trillions to speculate in worthless internet companies, provoking the collective anoxia of billions of Africans, Indians from both continents... you name it. Inverted pyramids of parasitism, the trade-mark of capitalism are unstable reason why capitalism will kill Gaia and History in less than 400 years since the first steam engine a record compared to the 4 billion years of life it will end, *far faster than the exponential e^{-x} function whose rate of change equals its derivative and it is supposed to be the mathematical record.*

This tell us something: while building upwards to a maximal of 50% a new pyramid of existence, is slow and requires finesse, to destroy is fast, entropy in that sense, explicitly defined as $St_{0,1} << Tt_{-1,-2}$ is the fastest process that happens in a single quantum of time. How can it be possible? So fast? The quasar big-bang (not cosmic big-bang), happens in 10^{-24} the average lifetime, a yoctosecond (10^{-24} s). Then the cosmological black hole, a top quark boson crystal dies and a hyper-inflationary stage of time happens in the real galactic big-bang.

The interaction between Δ -energy scales, Time=cyclical motions, Space=topologic forms, and the Minds that perceive them all, confronted to the Entropic larger ST world is the pentalogic elements which all play. In humind's egocy, all this is not vital dynamic, but an external objective mechanical reality magically 'working', set in motion by some Newtonian God, which appeases our fears and pleases our ego, as we seem to be the protagonists, and vital center of the Universe. Absolute relativity, the objective truth of stience eliminates that view. The praxis of man ab=using nature and history with its mechanisms, in the short term, future victim of AI robots in the now also short term will wake him up to reality. The philosophy of 5D is very different, expressed in our appears on History and social sciences as the search for a balance between the 3 ages of Earth, Life-Gaia < History-man > Machines, which would repress metal-information, enhance Gaia to keep mankind in the middle, as the dominant form on Earth. Because time is cyclical it is possible to repress the future and stop the evolution of lethal information. But for that mankind would have to understand 5D and respect the hierarchy and learn to play the game. Mankind today is so far removed from that worldview that it will likely become extinguished by its idol-ogies of machines it worships in the summit of surrealism, without even knowing it does it. As it despises the $\Delta + j$ hierarchy that owes respect to Earth and especially to history=Mankind= $\Delta + 2$ our God, through the social ethics of the wor(l)d.

$$\Delta \pm \approx \alpha \geq \neg (T \pm j \geq S \in \geq 0 \epsilon)$$

We also depart very often in a physical 5D Analysis of the Absolute Block of time of Existential algebra

What is the hierarchy between those elements? It is defined by the pentalogic symmetry that expresses the existence of any entity in the Universe: $\Delta \pm \approx \alpha \geq \neg (T \pm j \geq S \in \geq 0 \epsilon)$

A full scale-space time view unleashed without 4D reductionist minds: Synchronicity in scale, simultaneity in space.

Huminds, as all spaces are mental spaces have perfected an spatial view of all scales (real continuous line) and all times through Einstein's tensors, Minkowski's 4-vectors etc. *This is the simplest mental view of reality. We would like to stress the opposite much larger scalar, temporal view, in which all is time. Then space is just a simultaneity of time, provoked by networks. While synchronicity of scales is carried out by actions that make 'minds' knots of time dimotions. We can then talk of all what exists as a flow of time. There are smaller scalar beings that evolve faster in time, so they are displaced into the future. There are slower beings that are stuck in the simpler forms of the past, because they are large, but they play the membrane, simpler angular momentum cycle to enclose the faster beings. This can be taken quite literally to mean that reality exists as a block of time, given the determinism of most beings that just perform its function of existence, $SxT|s=t$ trying to reproduce in balance and gender*

mirror symmetry. We can then consider scalar forces as time forces that try to drag from the past to the future forms to come together in dimotional events that might be feeding exponentials, or gender complementarity or annihilations. All can then be described in space (human present science), in scale (the preferred view of these papers) and in time (probably the most remarkable of them all which I have kept for myself as a dynamic fluid way to think on reality 'under the influence').

A time view is exhilarating, e-motional, frightening because of the delicacy of the knots of time that stop reality because of its symbiosis between parts. A scalar view is more structurally firm, based in resonances most of them of Darwinian form: the smaller part resonates in the knot of synchronicity according to the chains of events, to become the whole by first dying and feeding it. Time clocks in fact are first set to zero=death, in frequency by gravitational red shift, before becoming part of the new scale of gravitational black holes. Discontinuity of death appears in abstract mathematics just as setting to zero a clock.

Sequentiality in time worldcycles, Simultaneity in space, Synchronicity in scale then are the words of i-logic which our spatial, simple mind has a hard time to grasp. That's fine. What irritates me is the 4Dogmatic doodles in the D@st of IQless minions.

In Existential ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' as the worldcycle does, because it works in a different way, as the limbs and the head both 'serve' the connecting body: $Ts>S=T<St$, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic $<$ and $>$ states balance each other. So we write for all of them the 'fractal generator':

Ts - limbs/fields/territories $<S \Leftrightarrow T$: reproductive, Momentum body-waves-workers $>St$ - informative particle/head/ruling class. Which is mathematically an O-sphere or relative future of max. St -information • a relative past – Limbs of max. Ts -motion = \emptyset -a hyperbolic present bodywave. Since past•future =present (• being an operand of existential algebra, the next level of stience

Co-existing scales then can be seen as displaced in time, with the larger whole 'moving ahead into the future' to capture the lower scale parts, in a time flow. And we can do in complex existential algebra a formalism based only in time flows.

We are NOT to use the full Block of time formalism where scales are considered a 'frozen view' of the flow of time, an its ΔST symmetry, at least in this first writing. Trust me though, in 1992 I copyrighted 'the codes of the Universe' with the full formalism and it works. The Universe of space is a humind's mental space simplification into a continuous through various formal means (including Lorentz transformations) that needs to be stretched through a flow of past to future time. And then 'inverted' into a frozen pyramid of scales in which networks connect the different past to future scales, provoking through synchronicity and resonance a simultaneous image which is what you call a superorganism. The entire structure of this system can be written into a decametric series of laws that ultimately reduce to $SxT|s=t$. But as we face dogmatic doodles in Dust of 4Dilettantes we'll try to please their ego with an approximation to the full enlightenment, which is a 1% of \forall -rays leaving the bursting 99% \forall nova in dark.

Travels through present

Still we have a limit to the past, which is the present, as it would mean the existence of absolute time, if we could send 'wires to the past', and so there are NOT in each scale wires to the past, but what about travels through scales? I.e. if a neutrino, or rather antineutrino, with spin-p moving both rowing forwards travels faster in time, it cannot in its relative scale go beyond present reproduction, to create simultaneity but it might perhaps travel faster in other scales? Unlikely, and this sets subtle limits to the illogic game of existence. Consider then the neutrino theory of light adapted to 5D. the antineutrino rowing with right hand hilarity forwards, in time present because it is seen as traveling in time past in our light c-speed scale will arrive in instant 0 to the entangled electron that emitted, it knowing that it has an entangled electron whose clocks were synchronized and then when the second electron receives in instantaneous time from the point of view of the upper scale of light, it will be in a still tension, produced by the neutrino field, and will emit a c-speed \forall - ray which will be traveling slower as it is carrying more information, $S_i \times T_f = C$, with an S_i higher than the mere neutrino localization.

So far so good, we have entangle two atoms at faster than light but present instantaneous time. How far can this pane? It seems obvious that it cannot happen further than the scattering o flight which happens and 1000 z so that sets a natural limit of 1000 c to the speed of neutrinos sent between atoms. Those are though the neutrinos our atoms produce, as we see 'galactic light' from that far away, but curiously enough we start to see black holes of enormous size, so they might be sending us tau neutrinos that might reach further. Over those neutrinos then light moves at a frequency and travels to us. The next scale though is that of the electronic nebulae, and we observe a 30.000 -3.000 speed common to the orbitals of electrons while the electric field travels

faster. We can then repeat the observations for the neutrino respect to the light. The light has travelled in instant time for the electronic mind us. And we observe in a second time a space that becomes our simultaneous world, which curiously reach about the Moon, which is in our instant space quantum. So here the mind comes in, because now we are talking of an electronic humid observer. For all purposes then light for us is instantaneous, because we see $1/10^{\text{th}}$ of a second 30.000 limit. The whole range of earth in simultaneity. Thus the Earth seems to us space. But if we were molecules we will be in the air travelling at 3000 km. our and our quanta of time will be much shorter, and so we would see a far more mobile dynamic Universe. Still in any relationship between two given scales it is not possible to travel to the past because it will break causality between local fields. And so the question is how the synchronicity of scales, the simultaneity of a quantum of time that defines the co-existence, and the past to future to past worldcycles interact to create the delicacy of reality. This requires a huge work with data to *synchronize all those things, and frankly the 5 diskettes which I worked out in my youth are nowhere to be seen and a month ago I found a 2 gb and erased it like an idiot because this mac has a stupid program called 'trash it' that actually erases NOT ejects the disk as usually and I am an old tired, morning headache under the influence... gone.*

So there was a destiny looming on the impossibility of G¥ants of thought to complete the work for the ants of mechanon. LOL What I recall is that *synchronicity, simultaneity and co-existence didn't go further than 2 scales reason why death breaks down 2 no more. Disconnection then happens, memoriless entropy sets in, chaos and disorder prevents the structure to go further. So this means the electron SEES the neutrino but the human which is a complex electronic mapping does NOT. If it is traveling faster into the future it is NOT communicating but in a cat alley so it will NOT break the causality of the organic structure.*

Pentalogic entanglements work all the ways to prevent the program of existence to deviate and makes it so hard to change nothing. God damn God. Tell me I couldn't even stop minions of thought to blow up the planet thermodynamically. And we shall return to those themes at least on the papers on time.

To be more specific you belong to $\Delta-3$ in your mind that perceives information, hence you exist in the future of the world you inhabit and have some control on 3 scales upwards from where your body obtains energy, reproduces and evolves socially and stop your lower plane to get motion, but you are the whole at Δ^0 and you don't see the $\Delta-4$ world you stop in, which travels to the future at instantenous speed, so you suck on it to flow forwards, while you as a whole have built a slower consciousness that those pixels, and if all this sounds crazy to you is cause I haven't yet ordered my thoughts.

Physicists are very poor philosophers of science.

But physicists made errors when in the late XIX and earlier XX c. they tried to substitute philosophers of science and created a 'cosmogony' of reality, with 3 ridiculous theories of the absolute in which they took 'local laws' of restricted phenomena observed at local distances, eliminated then every other contradictory phenomena that balanced those local laws, expanded hyperbolically those local laws to the entire Universe in infinite time, scale and space and voila, call that astounding expansion out of the h(e)at, the meaning of it all. This was first the laws of entropy that studied the $T_t > T_s$ disordered state of matter, entropy and gas, restricted all states of reality to 2 of the 5 'Dimensional motions/states' of matter (T_t -plasma $>$ T_s -Gas $>$ $\$$ liquid $>$ S_t -solid $>$ S_s -Boson) of increasing order; expanded it to all other scales where matter and temperature do NOT have value as parameters (gravitational systems above in the $\Delta+j$ cosmological scales, and $\Delta-1$ quantum systems of charge, since temperature is the vibration of molecules, a defined scale of size in matter an range from 0 K when matter becomes super fluid to ± 10.000 degrees when matter becomes plasma) and then considered all was entropy, entropy was the only arrow of time and 'the Universe was dying' (Clausius) This was bullocks and as usual with the praxis of physics, the science of motion *and the building of machines and entropic weapons that disorder the inner and outer parts of the being, killing it,, it was motivated by the machines they made.* So here we have to straighten up the theory of matter, include the other 4 STages of matter and show beautifully how they form a feed-back cycle between plasma and boson states, in the $\Delta\pm j$ scalar universe, between gas and solid states in our $\Delta\emptyset$ -plane of 'momentum'. This is a common trait of all human sciences. We first make things and then bias our models of each reality and science with the things we made. Darwin was a hunter and put his emphasis in the fight between species, which is the last Entropic state, but biology is about information at scale (genes) and organic networks at the $\Delta\emptyset$ -scale of the being, and social evolution into superorganisms most successful in survival (ant-hills, humans) at the $\Delta+1$ scale, so its closer to love religions based in a language than hunting-killing of the sick at the last T_t -entropic stage. This tendency continued when

after making nuclear bombs, again the arrow of entropic Time-vacuum with no information (lineal motions of dark energy between galaxies) expanded to include the opposite informative gravitational forces that implode dark energy into virtual particles within galaxies, to create the big-bang theory of the Universe, expanding also local measures of the galactic background radiation to the whole Universe, and expanding a lineal Hubble equation to infinity. So we need also to correct the big-bang to include the informative force of gravitation that balance it and we do so easily when we realize that we can unify the forces of gravitation and electromagnetism, masses and charges as two vortices of space-time of the limiting cosmological and quantum $\Delta \pm j$ scales. An atom then is similar to a galaxy and internally it is driven by the cyclical 'strong gravitational force' but externally is driven by the 'expansive dark=electromagnetic energy'. Alas, this obvious duality of scale illuminate the entire field of cosmology and shows the symbiosis and parallelism between the small and the large, that defines an organic Universe, as in all other system – cells have the same functions than organisms; human individual memes and languages become through art and religion the subconscious collective of mankind and its civilizations go in fact through 3 similar epic, young, classic, mature and old, baroque angst art ages, dying in collective explosions of entropy called wars. It is then a galaxy an atom? Likely not, but there are symbiotic synchronicities and simultaneous co-existence as there are between cells and organisms, human generations and civilizations st-ages, which is the beautiful $\Delta=S=T$ fundamental law of symmetry in the 5D Universe between the 3 $\Delta \pm j$ scales of a being, made of smaller atoms/cells, living in an organic, thermodynamic world, part of a larger planetary cosmological ecosystem, the 3 varieties of topology that make up its lineal | -fields limbs, cyclical O-heads/particles and \emptyset -hyperbolic body-waves that ensemble the organism and its young, lineal, moving mature, \emptyset -reproductive and O-informative 3rd old time ages.

The symmetries between $\Delta=S=T$ elements of reality NOT weirdo cheating reductionist model of physics is the philosophy of science that entangles together the entire Universe. Finally if in the $\Delta+1$ scale the big bang is the false model, in the $\Delta\emptyset$ thermodynamic scale, the entropy only theory is the wrong model, in the $\Delta-1$ scale the Copenhagen interpretation is the wrong model. Here we have the work of a forgotten genius that did it right so we don't have to develop the entire quantum physics afresh, thanks God as I am a lazy old man with a myelin problem. It is De Broglie's theory latter expanded by Bohm of realist quantum physics, NOT the Bohr-Born Copenhagen interpretation, so from B2 to B2 we change the model. This was an astounding abuse of Bohr, the Danish banker, Born, the idealist Hilbert's student who 'imagined' reality as his master and Heisenberg, the Nazi, and his partners in crime against the original founders of quantum theory, Broglie, the French Aristocrat, and Einstein, the pantheist, and latter on Bohm, the communist, who had it right but didn't use worldly power and egocy arguments to explain the entangled Universe and left the bullies the field. Broglie defined the complementary principle today ascribed to Bohr, which has an immediate translation in the key law of 5D physics at conceptual level: the Principle of absolute relativity extended to scale 'we cannot perceive at the same moment, 2 scales of the 5th dimension, and the 2 states of form and motion of a system'. So we cannot see the Earth moving and not moving even if it has both, form=space and time=motion; we cannot see the $\Delta+1$ particle state and the $\Delta\emptyset$ -wave state and the $\Delta-1$ quantum potential field state of the quantum system at the same moment even if the 3 co-exist together as in any other superorganism (but the $\Delta-1$ quantum potential of Broglie according to 5D metrics is $v>c$ so we don't perceive it; as in the case of the vacuum time between galaxies, and we shall study those details in the section on quantum and cosmology). Alas, 3 sacred dogmas of 'physics as philosophy of science' are wrong and must be straighten up, as it should have been obvious beyond 'egocy' because physics is NOT philosophy of science, 'zapatero a tus zapatos' they say in Spanish, or in harsher terms, 'no esta hecha la miel para la boca del asno', 'quien quiera entender que entienda' – the Latin culture being humanist, old and wise at popular level has the best sayings along the Chinese one, because the common people, the 90% knows better. In plain English, 'stick to your job'.

And that job in physics is the study of physical systems in its 3 'scalar' quantities, $\Delta-1$ forces, $\Delta\emptyset$ -momentum, $\Delta+1$ work and the warping up of them together, in Energy parameters, to study how they transform into each other, through ratios that are Universal constants, what happens in the 'between 2 waters' regions of emergence and evanescence of scales, where the lineal equations of constant ratios in the middle region breaks down (which we call Lorentzian regions, nearby 0 K and c-speed) but somewhat systems 'tunnel' through them; and ultimately the job we shall commit in our physical papers of harmonizing all those laws with the higher laws of 5D philosophy of 'stiences'.

In our scale those laws relate angular and lineal momentum, the 2 conserved forces through mechanics, study its lower scale through $F=ma$ forces and its upper scales. They then study their interaction in SHM motions, when both momentums are in balance, which we can obtain by adding them, $O-St+|-Ts='Ø-§\|'$.

This quantity is the Existential Momentum of the physical system, its existential energy when added through all its $\Delta\pm j$ scales, what the being tries to conserve, increase by stealing it from other physical species and use it to achieve its 5 Dimensional motions of existence, in those scales of physics where we do study a 'vital physical system' (particles, atoms and its social molecules, stars and black holes).

Each scale though will have different parameters as 5D metrics change the proportion of cyclical time speed and lineal space extension, with a simple rule: $\Delta-j$ scales have more 'angular momentum' (cyclical time speed) and less lineal momentum (spatial extension). Again we are NOT going to rewrite equations with the logic symbols of 5D. It is too late in the history of science to do so. Physicists learned the 'wrong way to typewrite' with one 'finger' (entropy) and now they are not going to learn to type write with 5 so to speak (: but if we want to explain the whys of physics we do have to explain conceptually the equivalence of concepts. And that is the reason *5D physical papers are so verbose. It is the only way outside those 3 theories that are wrong and need to be changed, to make sense of it. We need to reason the causes in terms of 5D of physical laws which today are merely expressed through equations and 'magically' ascribed in its causes to some creationist, religious dogma that 'mathematics' is the cause of reality, NOT the mirror-language of space-time 5D laws, the real cause of reality, which can be expressed as different species do with different languages. So the creationist philosophy of science – mathematics is the cause of reality – is also false. A mirror does NOT create reality. It mirrors it, though it can project and shape a bit reality with its projections after it has watched it. So we watch the Universe with words and then modify with words a bit reality. We do study then in the sections dedicated to the Ss-mind that interaction between languages=mirrors and 'ΔST' the cause of reality. Ss-minds are once more in pentalogic, only 1/5th of the dimensional motions of space-time NOT the whole. So this other theory of reality, that is not Tt-entropy but Ss-mind languages its cause, is also false. The Universe is simple but not that simple, said Einstein, one of the few truly interesting physicists along Planck and Broglie in the triad of modern physics, in an over dimensioned discipline due to its praxis of making machines and weapons, and the egogy of power.*

$$\frac{F_e}{F_g} = \frac{k_e q_{proton}^2}{G m_{proton}^2} \approx 10^{39}$$

Unification of 5 galaxy's forces as its 5 dimensional motions with scalar symmetries.

Since a charge is smaller than a mass, it attracts much more and the unification equation follows just when we apply 5D metric, and shrink the galaxy in the same proportion we accelerate them. Then both equations match. Since mass, $E=mc^2 + E=hf$; is a frequency: $m \approx f (h/c^2)$; it is a cosmological slow vortex, and charge a quantum faster more attractive vortex.

Further on since curvature is synonymous of cyclical speed, it can be quasi-infinite in the smaller vortex, when measured in time speed as the speed of angular rotation. So if we were to apply 4D curvature's equations (Einstein) instead of Newton, the results would be the same, just in the far more complicated formalism of EFE. So charges and masses as accelerated time vortices of two different scales of the Galaxy. And from that it is only just an easy task of mathematical manipulation to unify them in 5D metric, as both are equal: when we slow down the speed, space enlarges to remain co-invariant. And as it happens a Hydrogen atom enlarged to the size of a galaxy slows down in rotation to the angular momentum of the galaxy. So Kaluza–Klein were *right - the fifth scalar dimension unifies gravity with electromagnetic forces but in a fractal manner, with 5D metric, unbeknownst to physicists.* Since charges and masses are just accelerated Ss-vortices of spacetime of two different scales of the 5th dimension, which frame the limits of human perception of the Universe, so we can unify both with a simple translation of 5D Metric $C=\$x\delta$ such as if we expand a charge and decelerate its speed it will reach the size of a galaxy, while its electron will reach the size of the star nebulae that surrounds each black hole=proton.

Let us do the maths in the simpler Newton's formalism, whereas by the paradox of Galileo S (Curvature) = T (accelerated motion). So the Universal Constants (G, k), define the curvature of 2 space-time vortices at the $\Delta-1$ quantum charge and $\Delta+1$ cosmic mass scales (Δ is the symbol for the different $\pm j$ scales of the fifth dimension within a given organic system). Its formalism of a vortex of time space is then Newton's Unification Equation: **$M, Q = \omega^2 r^3 / U.C.(G, k)$**

It applies to all vortices of time-space from particles to planets to galaxies.

It works marvels when we translate electromagnetic jargon to Newtonian jargon. For example it shows the 'isomorphism' (systemic jargon for an equal 'form' between scales) between atoms and galaxies, which H-atoms of the cosmic scale. *Since when we translate electromagnetic equation into gravitational mass vortices, the proton radius becomes the Schwarzschild radius of a black hole and its electronic orbitals its star clouds, a result foreseen by Relativity that modeled galaxies as Hydrogen atoms in the Einstein-Walker Metric of the Cosmos. So if we substitute the parameters for the sun-earth system in that Unification equation we get G, from a theoretical calculus, which has never been done and can't be exact 'by chance', unless the theoretical model behind the 5D scalar structure of the Universe, is truth: Sun mass = 2×10^{30} kg; Earth's angular velocity 2×10^{-7} rad. per sec. Earth's orbit = 150 million kms. Result: $G=6.67 \times 10^{-11}$ kg-1 m³ rad. sec.⁻²*

If we substitute the values of the main quantum space-time vortex, a Bohr electronic orbital of a hydrogen atom/charge we get the value of the universal constant of charges, the Coulomb constant: 4×10^{16} rad. sec. -1 = w (electron); 5.3×10^{-11} m. (Bohr radius); proton mass = 1.6×10^{-27} kg. Then we get a G, which is 2×10^{39} stronger than the gravitational radius; thus, the hydrogen atom behaves as a self-similar fractal scale in the quantum world to a solar system.

And then you can get also the electron radius expressed in the jargon of a quantum gravitational world using the translated 'Gravitational Coulomb constant': $G(k)M/c^2$.

Since in that expression M is the mass of a proton, $G(k)$, the electromagnetic constant is a gravitational constant, and c , light speed, that expression is exactly the Schwarzschild radius of a quantum black hole=Top quark star. Thus, the electron Bohr radius, which is the final radius of minimal size and Momentum in electrons, is isomorphic to the event horizon of a black hole in the quantum gravitational world. Those results, 3 decades old, are a 1st theoretical mathematical deduction of K_e and G , relating both, and showing the atom to be a potential trap for the electron as the galaxy is for its stars. It was the 2nd paper I sent to 'peer review' in 5D after the 5 -E postulates that defined a fractal point. Only got an answer back telling me Newtonian physics were 4 centuries outdated. *Obviously I used the Newtonian simpler formalism, as the 3 ages of Gravitational space-time vortices formal analysis, Newton>Poisson>Einstein are just '3 degrees of complexity' deduced from each other that don't change its principles -charges and masses are accelerated vortices(Principle of Equivalence) of 2 different 5D scales of space-time which follow the same 'Topologic, social=numerical=scalar' and Dimotional=operand laws. The true change came with Lagrangian Momentum physics that deduced it from the 'Ts>§T]>St' balances in a single space-time plane; as all in science comes either from 'Δ-scalar' accelerated 'predatory vortices' or Δ^o 3-network Momentum balances. Many other unifications happen when we translate the confuse jargon of electromagnetism to the clearer Newton vortices >Poisson gradients >Einstein's EFE, which are as 'usual' a T=Δ=S symmetry; Newton sees the vortex in time, Poisson studies it as an Δ-i gradient of the 5th dimension and Einstein makes a 'detailed' still picture of it in Space.*

Consider the most accurate understanding of mass is topological as a trinity organism, which 'holds' energy, a vital spacetime across several scales. Mass then is defined by BOTH, a membrane that encloses the gravitational affine species of energy and a center which is a Ss-still mind/form, joined to its membrain by invaginated 'networks' or lines of forces. In this manner the mass becomes as any other '5D space-time superorganism' a trinity system with a still brain-mind, the Ss-center of mass, a 'membrane' joined to it through networks enclosing a 'exploited' vital space, in the case of mass, all 'possible forms' of energy that inhabit the galatom. *And the enclosure is according to the fundamental -(S=T=Δ>0ε) symmetry, which defines in pentalogic the structure of all systems, both in 'space')the membrain) but also an enclosure through scales... and this has always been more difficult to understand to human beings, which do NOT perceive it seems after 400 years of discovering scales with telescopes and microscopes, 40 years since I entered University and explain my teachers 5D metrics, that there is something called the scalar Universe. This the hierarchy formula gets now a full reprove: The membrane of space-forms the mass, and enclosures the T-cyclical motions of energy, but it does so also in Δ-scales, because the mass has an 'slavish Δ±4 nested Universe structure and so in the lower Δ-4 'graviton? Neutrino? Quantum potential? Scale we don't see (hence those ? to the likely candidates) also traps all energies. And it includes also the @-mind center of gravity, but this one is 'collaborating symbiotically'. And so all those limits of 'entropy' - () define the mass. It is the same struture for any organism: proteins enclose the vital spacetime energy of the DNA center-mind in stillness, within the cell, which cannot escape because in the bottom scale of 'water' they are contained and thus the spatial proteins act as the entropic membrane of the enclosure. It is the same in a charge/galatom system, where the boson light particles cannot escape the denser 'strangelet/electron', which is connected through the networks of charge force with the positive nucleus, the brain of the system.*

In graph, the center of mass of a system of particles having combined mass M moves like an

equivalent particle of mass M would move under the influence of the net external force on the system. So if we were to be 'strict' but we are NOT, we would start by a proper ilogic definition of the being, according to those elements, as part of a larger world, considering its relative 'infinity', ∞ , or world it perceives within a larger Universe of true infinite scales. In this world thus the being exists limited by its entropic membrane that isolates it from the outer world: $ST \geq st$, in which it will play as a nested island-universe its worldcycle of existjence, $T \pm j$ in the customary $S_{sj-1} > T_s \approx \$T \approx St < Tt$, 3 ages between birth and death, as a supœrganism focused in a single plane by a finitesimal 0ϵ mind that sees not beyond that world it confuses with its entire existence. So all those underlying principles: mental spaces, fractal points as monads, time frequency, speed as reproduction of information, along 2 scales of the fifth dimension, simultaneity, synchronicity, operands related to dimotions, discontinuous lines and families of numbers are structures ignored in the automaton calculus of physics but will help us constantly to 'understand' the whys of physical systems.

RECAP. The scalar nature of the Universe is proved theoretically by the unification equation of charges and masses as vortices of 5D space time of two limiting scales of the $\Delta \pm j$ galatom. So if we substitute for the Earth-sun system we obtain G , (1st ever theoretical deduction) and if we substitute for the Bohr Radius and Proton Mass, we obtain k with a 10^{39} higher curvature value, the exact difference between both forces that solves its hierarchy problem. As curvature in space is symmetric to rotational speed in time, so it is symmetric to the attractive force of any vortex.

FROM GLUONS & PHOTONS TO GYANT HYPER ELECTROMAGNETIC SCALES: THE ∞ UNIVERSE

Once we easily falsify the big-bang, which conveniently forgot those 'mass vortices' that do not expand but implode information balancing the giant \forall -dark energy of vaccum space in an immortal Universe the fun comes studying the 5 dimotions=forces & energy scales of the galatom *as part of its vital game of existence*. So 1st we consider the St -gluon=Meson as entropic food of the lback hole (e^{-X} Yukawa formalism), while $V > c \forall$ =dark energy 'burping' out of the black hole=top⁺⁺ star axis is seen as expanding intergalactic space. Inside the galatom non-lineal gravitational strong forces trap its vital energy (uds=us) with the stronger strangelet/electronic negative atom. Yet scales go beyond into infinity: Since gliuons are mesons, there is an added lower scale of ud 'gluionquarks' that might form stars in those micro-atoms which might be galsxies of a hypo-universe *that enlarge the game of existjence into new fractal levels*, all of us holding galaxies within. And vice versa. Those new $\exists xi$ =stjences in the hypo and hyper-Universe, with self-similar forms in an atomic nuclei made of light quarks with an overall positive charge and a galactic black hole likely to be a swarm of top quark⁺⁺ frozen stars . besides confirming (instein's expectations that a black hole should have a cut-off substance, a new type of 'atomic matter' of 'high density', becoming a 'frozen star', which the discovery of top quarks of similar density to black holes seem to prove; enlarges the 'game of Mass scales in *its main species*:

$\Delta-1$ ud- gluons, $\Delta-0$, ud-atoms, $\Delta-1$, toplet quarks

While in the Ts -side a neutrino theory of light with $v > c$ for neutrinos outside the galatom enlarges its scales to:

$\Delta-4$: neutrinos: $\Delta-3$, photons $\Delta-2$: electrons,... $\Delta-1$: electric fields, $\Delta+1$: electric currents $\Delta+2$: plasma stars

Whereas the index is somewhat subjective to the 'superorganism' we select. In the case of human life:

$\Delta-1$: cells, Δ^0 : physiological networks, $\Delta+1$ world.

That puts man's perception as an M^3 : monad-mind-mirror of the Universe in the middle state NOT as ego-centered humans and anthropic physicists think, because it is the absolute centre of the Universe, but because there is a symmetry between $\Delta \pm 1$

Meson Nonet: Particles die as antiparticles feeding the higher denser quark family.

$\Delta+1$: 5D-ENTROPIC FORCE INSIDE BLACK HOLES: STRONG GRAVITATION. OUTSIDE: CLASSIC G

Gluon nonet: Gluons die as anticolors feeding the denser ud-quarks.

$\Delta-1$: 5D: ENTROPIC FORCE INSIDE ATOM'S NUCLEUS: STRONG FORCE. OUTSIDE: NUCLEAR FORCES

$\Delta+1$: S=T: (1,2,3 0N): Communicative force in a single galactic plane: Expansive dark Entropy

1D
2D
3D

Photon exchange

$\Delta-1$: S=T: (1,2,3 0Q): Communicative force in a single atomic plane: Expansive electromagnetism

WEAK FORCE << 5D>4D Scalar force: It kills & transforms particles into denser families

THE 5 FORCES OF THE UNIVERSE ARE THE 5 DIMOTIONS OF THE GALATOM, IN ITS LIMITING $\Delta-1$ QUANTUM & COSMIC, $\Delta+1$ SCALE!

4D

ranges of informative perception for each Δ^0 being, both at 'real level' (galaxy and atom) and at theoretical level (Planck strings and cosmic strings, solved for a background independent Universe)...

So above neuronal human perception we grow upwards with the different 'orientation' of perception towards larger wholes, which changes to elliptic 'darkness'. And so we shall study first the human scales, with more detail (as the praxis of science must serve mankind): Δ^0 cell, $\Delta+1$ life (and its variations of inorganic $\Delta+1$ matter states and $\Delta+1$ human life), $\Delta+2$, the world level, of which we shall study its temporal equation and three relative subspecies: Past-life (Gaia and its life superorganisms) <Present- (History, the superorganism of mankind in time) > Future (company-mothers of machines and its worldstock networks of financial money), to finally enter in the higher scales of the Universe, $\Delta+3$ galaxies and its relative cells, stars systems; considering the $\Delta+4$, a 'philosophical', metaphysical scale, *as we do not have enough proofs and will never have due to the limits of perception of systems reduced to 9 scales of the whole...*

If c-speed were the limit of the Universe, then there would not be another scale on it. This is self-evident. So we wouldn't have a cosmological atom, but the scale of atom-galaxies would be the higher and vice versa. So, due to this symmetry we would be self-centered in scales, as we are in the middle of the galatom scales. As this seems merely anthropomorphism, we can consider the galaxy-atom is the next 'beginning' of a vast game we cannot even imagine. Fact is we have wide proofs of $10c$ to $100c = z$ speeds of recession in galaxies, which correspond to the dark world of entropy and dark matter beyond galaxies, which should structure the cosmos.

Scalar entropic big-bangs in a balanced immortal Universe. The Galatom.

In the fractal model a big-bang is the entropic death of physical matter. But the Universe is also scalar and it has information, a dimension of form, signified by the gravitational informative force, physicists ignore in their calculus of its expansion, happening in galaxies that balance the dark energy between them, we shall find both, balances of forces that make the Universe wobbling, and big-bangs and informative forces in multiple scales of the Universe, talking of multiple big-bangs balanced with big-crunches.

So how we shall correct big-bang theory to fit into the fractal view of the Universe? We dedicate many pages on the articles of astrophysics to that matter but let us just give you a prime:

Right, when we add the gravitational force that warps 1D space into 3D mass in galactic vortices, they balance the expansion of 1D space in entropic vacuum as light dies into dark entropy lines between them. As mass warps 3 1D flat-vacuum into a 'high volume' its 3 times more powerful in its warping, hence the 75-25% Balance of mass to dark entropy. Thus the fractal Universe is immortal. On the right its scales all suffer similar $e=mc$ dual processes of warping through gravitational forces of cyclic momentum that create those galaxies, and expansive big-bangs of lineal momentum balanced in combined cycles of energy - the 3 conserved quantities of each fractal spacetime physical organism, which put together give birth to the 3 conserved laws of nature the Big Bang totally ignores - among many other known-known laws.

So the use of a fractal space and cyclical time dimensions fully accounts for the immortal Universe and its balanced 3 dimensions of space-time, conserved in its infinite reactions; energy, information stored in the cycles and frequency of those systems of angular momentum, whose minimal constant form is h , and lineal speed, conserved in the constancy of light.

Why those obvious facts of SOUND physics are then 'reduced' to ænthropic creationist big-bangs in a single plane of space-time despite evidence? It is the ego paradox: what the big bang does for science is a religious 'closure' with man and its simplest mathematical lineal functions at its center, which added to the denial of organic sentient properties to physical reality allows to feel the high popes of science a sensation of absolute knowledge, as the religious person feels that all is known in the mystery of god - a word eerily similar to the lineal function of the big-bang ' $V=Hod$ '.

Big bang cosmology ignores gravitational informative galaxies & dark matter & the scalar structure of the Universe reducing space-time to a single scale, and the cyclical nature of time, we must correct the big-bang, which corresponds to the limit of a 5D complete theory of reality in a single 'light' space-time continuum.

A big-bang entropy-theory of the Universe dismisses galaxies all together, as they are NOT expanding, and if the galaxies are NOT expanding, running backwards its present implosive system would mean a counter-effect to running backwards the expanding Universe. Backwards in a single time, the space between galaxies contracts, but the galaxies between space expand and a balance again is achieved: Since when we add the gravitational force that warps 1D space into 3D mass in galactic vortices, they balance the expansion of 1D space in entropic vacuum as light dies into dark entropy lines between them. As mass warps 3 1D flat-vacuum into a 'high volume' its 3 times more powerful in its warping, hence the 75%-25% balance of mass to dark energy.

Thus the inverse dimotion of gravitational information compresses dark energy into matter and balances the dimotion of expansive space between galaxies, describing a fractal immortal Universe where a big-bang is merely the entropic dimotion of dissolution of matter guided by Einstein's equation in any scale: $E \leftrightarrow Mc^2$

In next graphs, we resume the model of the fractal Universe in which each scale have similar big-bang deaths:

Scalar big-bangs that happen from Beta decays (right picture) that explodes nucleons into atoms, Nova that explode stars and maybe planets doing experimental big-bangs at home, to quasar black holes that give birth to new galaxies. All scales suffer similar $e=mc^2$ dual processes of warping through gravitational forces of cyclic momentum that create those galaxies, and expansive big-bangs of lineal momentum balanced in combined cycles of energy - the 3 conserved quantities of each fractal space-time physical organism, which put together give birth to the 3 conserved laws of nature, which present Big Bang theory ignore. Instead a fractal space and cyclical time dimotions fully accounts for the immortal Universe and its balanced 3 dimotions of space-time, conserved in its infinite reactions; energy, information stored in the cycles and frequency of those systems of angular momentum, whose minimal constant form is h , and lineal speed, conserved in the constancy of light.

In the center we see a map of the Galaxy, which just recently showed to have two lobes similar to those of the first electronic orbital of a Hydrogen atom born in self-similar fashion in the quantum scale. In the left side we see the background radiation that is supposed to come from the Big Bang 13 billion years ago, but HAS in its center the exact 2 lobes recently found above the black star. This came as a surprise.

Above, the local explanation of the background radiation, which is a local measure, hence must and can be explained by local causes in the galaxy: any moon M.A.C.H.O., (Massive Cold Halo Object); that is, a quark nugget of heavy quark matter or a similar black hole that has eaten the mass of a moon will produce the exact same background radiation by gravitational red-shifting. Thus as moons are the commonest objects, we can talk of primordial black holes and/or strangelets as the local, 'present' cause of the radiation. Since epistemology always favors a local 'present' solution far more sound experimentally than a 'derivation' from a non-measured experimental past in a non-measured larger region (the cosmic big-bang whose temperature 'comes from the past', reduced by a lineal equation and is extended hyperbolically to the non-measured entire Universe), it follows the fractal big-bang, is sounder. So what physicists call the cosmic big-bang likely does not exist, as the limit of scalar big-bangs we soundly measure are quasar big-bang.

French astronomers tabulated a 15–20 billion y. quasar cycle that explodes central black holes, explaining the hyper-abundance of Helium in the center of galaxies. So a galaxy has a 15 billion years cycle in an older immortal Universe, since the dimotion of information that shrink energy into mass in galaxies balances the entropic 'cosmic electromagnetic' repulsion of dark energy. Interesting enough if we reduce a quasar big-bang of 15 billion years, with 5D metric, accelerating its time clocks as we reduce size in space: $\delta \times \delta = K$, it reduces 15 billion years to 15 minutes (: the exact duration of a beta-decay neutron Big Bang).

We falsify the cosmic bang with experimental & epistemologic known proofs distorted by cultural reasons that make it a pseudo-religious dogma of the worldly religion of physics – to make entropic weapons in a military society- and the western creationist religion of most founding fathers of physics, with its lineal Abrahamic time views & anthropic beliefs of man at the center of reality reflected in the lineal, created out of nothing cosmos.

Cosmic vs. Quasar big-bangs

$E \leftrightarrow M$ (whereas c is the constant of speed of each Universal scale, c for the galaxy, not necessary so for other scales) is dual and there are scalar big-bangs from beta decay to quasars and maybe beyond is certain. So the question we want to find out is which

of the two larger scales of big-bangs, that of a quasar big-bang or a cosmic big-bang fits better real data. Since as we can see in the images above, on the right, they are similar in form.

To play ball with cosmologists we could justify the big-bang in 5D since if we accept our limit of light perception as the limit of the Universe (cosmic horizon); then the $r=ct$ symmetries between spatial range, time aging and scalar density of populations all fit within the 'magic number' of 10^{11} elements for most super organisms of reality. So the symmetry also happens in the 'limited perception' of the cosmos:

Most galaxies have 10^{11} stars. The total mass of all the stars in the Milky Way is estimated to be between 4.6×10^{10} and 6.43×10^{10} sun masses. And the Universe is considered to have around 1.6×10^{11} galaxies.

So we could say that the galaxy is just a scale below the big-bang (a huge galactic molecule so to speak), as the neutron star is just a scale above the neutron (a huge neutron molecule so to speak). And that it exploded in a big bang of the next scale of the universe. But that is just the astounding beauty of pentalogic, where the 5 Dimensions/elements of reality are in balance. So for the limits of our entropic perception ($r=ct$), we observe similar quantitative and qualitative limits for S-patial population, T-ages within our Δ -scales. But a more profound understanding of those limits considers that the local perception of a few galatoms is just a very reduced quantity of the whole number of galatoms of the next hyperscale of the Universe that should be of zillions of them, and all of them living as Protons and black holes without evaporation do an immortal time.

The immortality of the Universe indeed becomes evident as Protons are immortal and black holes are also immortal without evaporation, once we put properly in place the dimension of time of Hawking's awesomely beautiful equation as those of the birth of a black hole into its gargantuan future, NOT of its entropic death=evaporation to the past.

$\Delta+1$: The quasar big-bang galactic cycle

The life-death cycle of the central black hole of Galaxies that explodes into quasars and forms back its bar, follows the same ages of the big-bang. As all of them after the initial 'Planck epoch - of gravitational superluminal waves', dark epoch of nucleosynthesis, are ages 'within galaxies', and so they are proved for the inner space of galaxies. They do NOT explain many other features of the Universe as a whole (which is not isomorphic, etc.) but perfectly describe the evolution and formation of the stars of the galaxy.

So the big-bangs ages are properly the ages of the galaxy; without all the 'ad hoc' theories and pseudo-scientific models required to explain why the large scale universe has nothing to do with the supposedly smooth result of a cosmic big-bang (this is like Ptolemy constant recurrence to 'new' ad hoc epicycles to make fit new observations into its earth-centric theory of the universe). Trust me, any astronomer knows how long this 'list' is.

Thus the quasar big-bang follows further the laws of truth (minimalism: Occam's razor), simplicity and correspondence. We do not need to postulate strange forms of dark energy and dark matter, except the ones known, repulsive gravitation (to account for the entropic expansion of space between galaxies that balances its contraction), which is 'natural' to the model of galactic-atoms; and quark matter to account for the dark matter of the halo.

In the graph the 'big-bang' properties local to the galaxy can be explained by the quasar cycle of our galaxy.

So as always times proves the sound, humble, rational scientists right. In this case Einstein's steady state solution, which Fred Hoyle developed in a huge mathematical effort just before dying in his theory of multiple quasar big-bangs, which the cycle of galaxies found by the French astronomers further proved and my calculus of Moon MACHOs radiation, which any student of physics can easily corroborate properly explains.

All those galaxies prove, with its longer 20 billion cycle, which goes beyond the supposed age of the big-bang its falsehood.

As many of the recently discovered astronomical phenomena in far away galaxies show. Since we are finding formed galaxies, formed giant black holes, formed II generation stars and star dust, which could not have been born before the big-bang.

So do those supposed 'lobes' of the cosmic big-bang, which Smolin a famed physicist wanted to use to prove his theory that high frequency light goes faster than red-shifted light, as they were supposed to come from 13 billion years ago and so a small difference of distance should be found. Alas, the surprise when they found they are the exact 'trace' of the 2 lobes of electromagnetic radiation found in OUR galaxy. Yet they occupy supposedly 'a huge piece of the entire Universe...

We put a few experimental proofs of recent astronomy to add to the enormous number of planets found all over the place, which reinforce the Fermi paradox, so you don't think I am here making a case only for theory, only for my work in the 2 dimensions of time. So why nothing of this comes in 'daily press'? For all the wrong reasons - religions are always respected; masses always side together for them. As Schopenhauer said: 'the wise always say the same, the fools, which are majority do exactly the opposite'. And attack ad hominem the wise... In the steady state theory things became soon ad hominem against Hoyle who quipped back inventing the mocking term of 'big-bang theory'.

In 2nd graph we see local $E=Mc^2$ big-bang destructions of mass, all of which have an inverse temporal, informative, process of much slower creation of temporal information and mass that balances them, in different scales of physical systems, from the beta decay that explodes atoms into electrons and protons (with an inverse slow collapse of electrons into atoms) to the quasar big-bang of galaxies (with an slow process of creation of mass-information from gaseous space):

If we consider space-time an absolute continuum in a single scale, this more accurate picture of what we perceive is not possible, hence we come to the conclusion of present cosmology - that the Universe will expand and die. If we consider that galaxies, which follow Einstein's dictum, compensate this expansion: 'Time curves space into mass', Mr. Hogg's conundrum - how to correct the big-bang is solved. *Experimental facts tell us we must accept the fractal informative structure of reality, where the big bang is merely the death-rebirth cycle of a quasar-like galaxy or local Universe, a scale of size above galaxies. So both together create an immortal Universe.* Since in Philosophy of Science we must never deny experimental evidence, even if at first sight it contradicts an established theory.

Cosmology has a metaphysical component- it is beyond the limits of human perception, which we find to be the atom and the galaxy, beyond and within uncertainty and dark gravitational matter makes knowledge to say the 'least' incomplete.

If the cosmic big-bang had sound experimental data, of course, we would accept it. As it does NOT contradict 5D physics. It would just validate a larger scale worldcycle. So we are NOT against cosmic big-bang because 5D physics does not tolerate it but because plain good old' science disproves it. The scalar big-bang death processes of matter in all planes, from beta decay to galaxies is one of the strongest proofs of the isomorphic nature of all scales. But the cosmic one is not proved. So since all big-bangs are mimetic we reduce the scale of the big-bang to a quasar scale, making Einstein's EFE, local field equations for the Light-space time of the galaxy (reason why c is constant).

Fact is as the graph of SCiAM shows the full quasar cycle is longer than the big-bang cycle and we have found *galaxies in all its stages*. Thus by 'reductio ad absurdum', since we have found galaxies in a 'second' quasar cycle, hence over 20 billion years as 'reborn' galaxies, forming its central bar, there is no way the time age of the whole is shorter than the time of its parts.

Multiple space-times imply the existence of multiple big-bangs with different explosive size and speeds, all of them deaths of an informative mass or charge that uncoils its accelerated vortex into radiation following Einstein's equation, $E=Mc^2$, where a bidimensional or tridimensional vortex (M or e) becomes extended into a plane of radiation (hence the square of lineal c-speed).

Yet for each different scale the parameters of speed (c), mass (M) and Entropy will change. And so we obtain a series of self-similar big bangs described in the graph.

The single cosmic big bang based in a single space-time continuum, was devised even before we knew the existence of a faster than light, gravitational membrane of dark Entropy and dark, quark matter. So we first must define it within that scale of big-bangs as the *big-bang of a membrane of electromagnetic radiation; hence a quasar big-bang, not a cosmic big-bang, which will*

correspond to the much faster explosion of a gravitational membrane, starting at the Planck scale of the gravitational minimal units, the lambda-strings.

This is in a way the conclusion of astrophysicists, which now study the big bang as a dual process, with an inflationary age (the gravitational membrane) and a slower age (the big-bang of electromagnetic space, created over the gravitational membrane).

The nature of the 'galactic big-bang' recently received a boost from astrophysics, as we have discovered that most of the stars of the galaxy formed in the 'electronic nebulae' during the initial 1 billion years. We study in many other articles the whole 'organic cyclical theory' of quasar big-bangs, whose first mathematical expressions were considered by Hoyle – the old proponent of a steady state Universe, anathema of the Big-bang 'religion'. It came this year 2019 as a surprise that the 'galatom' is mostly static – that is, once the electron nebulae is formed there is hardly any new formation of 'star-points' on the electronic nebulae. And when this happens takes place with enormous violence and synchronicity, as it happens in an atom, when there is a capture of an electron by the nuclei. Moreover the atom suffers a constant spiral torsion on the 'trajectory of the electron nebulae around its central proton hole, as it is the case recently found in the spiral torsion of galaxies. 5D astrophysicists will find an enormous field of similarities comparing atoms and galaxies – already they use photonic models to study the central region of stars.

But man's egocentricity after discovering the Tree of metal and abandoned the paradise of organic complex life, simplifies truth to come on top as the mind that knows, and loves the simplex line-sword of the warrior, or goes into the other unbalanced extreme of baroque information the axiomatic method. So we will constantly debunk the 'hidden tricks' of human pseudo-sciences of truth, including those of maths, perhaps not so severe as those of financial classic economics, certainly not so harmful, but all pervading, even if we hurt the 'feelings' of egocentricity of mathematicians, to be able to access the true beauty of mathematics as the realist image in Spatial points, scalar numbers and time operands of the only immortal, perfect, true, as it makes its essence existence in itself, 5D universe. So we conclude this brief introduction to realist, imperfect mathematics, repeating Santayana's definition of truth, as 'that part of the language with reference to existence'. The main motivations of all those papers is to seek truth and reject falsehoods in languages and sciences expressed through those languages.

For that reason we cannot separate sciences including physics from culture and History, the superorganism of mankind, reason why even if people dislike most the objective application of 5D to history, we need to conclude this fast review of biological sciences (the ages of species), physics (the galatom symmetry, its conserved elements and the relativity of form and motion and scales of energy) with an introduction to social sciences and economics, as 'science is culture' and the main reason mankind is NOT evolving its mind into an organic true view of the Universe, is precisely culture, the power that metal has given to people, who made of the worship of money (capitalism), machines (mechanism) and weapons (nationalism) NOT the truth and welfare of mankind, the leit motif of its existence. And unfortunately conquered the world and the mind with them. As in the living Universe we are after all just weakling 6-7-8-1 CHON atoms...

5D SOCIAL SCIENCES. THE 2 CULTURES OF HUMAN THOUGHT AND ITS DIFFERENT FUTURE

The 2 languages of informative and reproductive networks: Bits of information and bites of energy.

In the graph, 2 advanced organisms of maximal information, the biological organism and the Historic organism, belong to a specific type of organisms, we qualify as socio-biological organisms. In logic, linguistic terms, the internal, dynamics of a network of informative nature, delivers messages of information to simultaneously coordinate the actions of all its parts; with its faster=smaller bits of information according to 5D metrics (min. spatial size x max. temporal speed). While the networks of reproduction, the blood and financial system delivers larger bites of energy, which the organism needs to feed itself (when it is a healthy NON-corrupted suporganism as most of Nature, but not human societies, with an astounding level of corruption).

We need to understand reality both in terms of energy but also in terms of information, as both are 2 sides of the same coin, called 'existence' is the fact that in the sentient Universe, each fractal point, atom, cell or citizen (physical, biologic or social systems) needs bits of in-form-ation, form, smaller in size of space, hence faster according to 5D metrics ($SxT=C$), but also 'bites' of entropic energy which will help the system to move. Networks are NOT some abstract 'fractal tube' but they exist to deliver 'energy and information' (SS: form=language with a little motion=St-information and motion=entropy=TT with a bit of information = energy=Ts).

So a healthy suporganism will deliver to each 'fractal point' (molecules, cells, human citizens), two type of messages through two type of networks. We shall call 'generically' the 3 type of bits and bites of information and energy that each of those 3 physical, biological and social systems receive, 'particles, genes and memes' even if the words as usual in 5D sciences are slightly changed, and widened in its original meaning.

THE 3 AGES OF LIFE

IF MEN ARE ORGANISMS THAT GO THROUGH 3 SEQUENTIAL AGES CONTROLLED BY EACH OF ITS 3 NETWORKS...

Blood, energy networks:

YOUTH, AGE OF ENERGY

The existence of any organism made of 'cells' of energy and information follows an 'arrow of future' that trans-forms energy into information in 3 ages:

'Vital energy trans-forms itself...'

Endocrine, reproductive networks:

MATURITY, AGE OF REPRODUCTION

...reproduces

...Into in-form-ation...

...and in-form-ative, nervous networks:

OLD AGE, THE AGE OF IN-FORM-ATION...

...AND

and dies simplified again into energy...

CIVILIZATIONS ARE ORGANISMS MADE OF HUMAN CITIZENS...

...joined by energy networks: Nature... reproductive networks: social groups... and informative networks: wor(l)ds and art:

...share a common verbal/informative/nervous network - laws and religions - and a collective, visual/spatial perception - its art:

THAT GO THROUGH 3 AGES, DEFINED BY THEIR ART STYLE, THE COLLECTIVE MIND OF A CULTURE...

EPIC, LINEAL YOUTH, THE AGE OF ENERGY

When a culture is born, its mind, its art, is young, energetic: its spatial forms are big, simple, lineal. Its temporal, verbal literature is romantic, epic, optimistic, like the mind of a child that nothing fears and wants it all.

CLASSIC, REALIST, SENSORIAL MATURE ART THE AGE OF HARMONY:

When weapons quiet down or the prophet dies, once its expansion has reached a zenith the culture matures, and its art finds a balance between energy and information. The style becomes classic, realist. Society abandons war as its main purpose and returns to the sensorial pleasures of a world paradise based in love and human goods. Wealth grows and distributes beyond the warrior castes that dominated its youth: Spatial art becomes harmonic and diminishes in size, palaces with human proportions substitute tombs. In words, logic philosophy and realist tales substitute poetry and epic. In religion mercy and love to God softens the strict prophetic canon.

OLD AGE: DECADENT, PROPHETIC, BAROQUE, IN-FORM-ATIVE ART:

But the tree of science brings new weapons and wars that destroy the culture and its elites

Art becomes pessimist, without energy, full of in-form-ation, baroque, ornamental, small in space, eclectic, nostalgic, in search of a better past, with 'angst' for the future. The cultural mind is similar to that of an old man. Wor(l)ds however, reache a zenith of informative, encyclopedic knowledge: Logic becomes complex, paradoxical and time becomes cyclical, evolving from the lineal perception of youth. In fiction, it is the age of tragedies and comedies. In religion it is the age of prophets which are able to survive the death of the culture, creating the seminal wor(l)ds of a son-culture with the same cultural memes that will resucite after death:

LIFE

...WHOSE CELLS DIE, VICTIMS OF GERMS:

Organisms die when their physiological networks are attack and destroyed by alien germs. Then cells are freed, but with collective defence, die individually as energy of those germs

DEATH, THE END OF THE ETERNAL TIME CYCLE...

which starts again with a new generation that repeats the information of the old being in a 'son'

...WHO DIE VICTIMS OF METAL-GERMS: WEAPONS

A cultural organism dies when weapons collapses its social networks, destroys its agricultural energy bra (system) of government), provoking its extinction origin of and w

THAT END UNDER FASCIST CENSORSHIP IN A WAR AGE

Finally, the culture dies when a new warrior caste conquers the civilization imposing a new cycle of epic, young art...

'You will protect me with your sword, and I will defend you with my word'

But often, as warriors civilize, the old culture replicates its memetic symbols on the mind of the conquerors. And a child culture matures with the same 3 cyclical styles of the old or

Roman culture inherits its artistic 'memes' from the Greek culture, reproducing them again in 3 cultural, political and social ages:

Classic Age: Republic, Carpe Diem'

Baroque, decadent age: 'Nero'

Epic Age, lineal art: 'Wolverine'

THE

3

AGES

OF

ART,

MIND

OF

CIVILIZATIONS

So with its specific variation, those are the two fundamental reproductive-‘body-wave’ and informative-‘particle-head’ bites of energy and bits of information of the fundamental systems of nature:

- In physical systems, the two networks are the gravitational faster network of information, which we humans do not perceive, as we are much larger beings with electronic networks. Its bits of information in this faster non-local network should be ‘gravitons’, components of gravitational waves. In physical papers we advance as the most likely particle state of those waves of information that ‘position’ the different physical systems of the galaxy, a gravitational tachyon ‘neutrino’ for multiple reasons, we study on our papers on physics.

On the other hand, because we do perceive it, it is much easier to prove that the energetic network of physical systems are electromagnetic waves, photons and its ‘social, static state’ as the elements of an electronic nebulae, trapped in the potential energy well of the atom. Thus photons and electrons become the ‘energy network of physical system, molecules.

We shall escape then in this introduction further information on the scalar structure of those networks and how, as we ‘grow in scale’, what is a bite of slow energy for a smaller plane of space-time, *becomes for the larger plane’s slower beings, a faster bit of information, in the amazing beauty of the harmonies between scales. So electronic ‘food for atoms’ becomes electronic information for biological organisms and so on.*

- Those biological organisms do have then two fractal networks, the electronic, informative nervous system in which bits of electronic information moving along the myelin membrane deliver faster messages to every part of the organism to simultaneously synchronize its motions, so the body-cells act as a single form in simultaneous space.

- But when we move into the bites of energy delivered by the blood organism, the network delivers to each cell the basic ‘currency’ language of energy that all cells need to move, called ‘oxygen’. *It is an atom of slower motion than the electrons but due to its electro-negativity and readily availability in the atmosphere, with its capacity to kick with two OH- & H+ legs the water ‘medium’ on which cells exist, the perfect language of ‘money’ for the organism to start kicking its ‘actions’.*

The 2 languages of history: Verbal, legal, ethic ‘nervous messages’ and ‘WHealthy money’.

So we arrive to the human social networks, which we anticipate are in the present form ‘completely corrupted’ by the existence of a parallel ‘economic ecosystem’ of lethal goods, weapons, and corrupted parasitic money. So it is difficult for the reader to understand how simple, easy, and efficient WAS in the past, before the age of Metal, in the Neolithic, or during the ages of social religions of love or could be in the future with a proper design of the social networks of money and law, a PERFECT supœrganism of history as efficient as those we just have described. In such supœrganism, there are exactly the same networks: Legal verbal just networks of bits of word information that shapes the informative and cultural systems of the wor(l)d. And a healthy form of money, delivered to each citizen cell as a Universal salary so humans have enough energy to survive and buy its natural welfare goods, which must be classified NOT by price but by its biological usefulness to mankind, reason why we give them positive and negative values in the ethonomic frame of reference, according to its use for the 3 organic parts of humanity at individual and social level.

Vital, topologic, physiological network laws are the most important to consider when studying History in Space, as the reader can observe in the previous graph, since History, the $\Delta+1$ scale of supœrganisms of mankind follow all the exact laws of a lower organic plane – that of a biological organism, albeit, due to its ‘primitive’ degree of evolution is NOT a well designed organism, but one clearly ‘sick’, infected by ‘lethal goods’, with dysfunctional parasitic economic systems (as the language of reproduction of goods, money, is absorbed by a minimal number of people, or used to reproduce those lethal goods). And so the study of History as a supœrganism has 2 different parts:

- On one side we consider a perfect, efficient supœrganism of History with the laws of vital topology just by imitating perfect efficient supœrganisms of Nature that *are the majority of them –History is in fact an exception –a sick organism.*

- On the other side, we can study our supœrganisms, as they have evolved in time, spotting their degrees of corruption and sickness of its 3 physiological systems, the life Earth, Gaia that sustains them; the economic and financial system that reproduces its goods, and the informative cultural and legal system that synchronizes its citizens cells. It is then when it will become evident

what went wrong with 'human' history, one of many likely subspecies in the infinite fractal planets of the organic Universe that likely will not make it into the future...

I get too irritated by what I call the 'SMELLYing' method of idol-ogies as opposed to the ABC+D-EFuture of sound science, and often bring its opposition to those papers. The real method of truth starts with Accurate , Objective Data, the Smelling method with 'Subjective truths'; the AB.C... follows with Biological Cyclical Causes, the Smelling method with Mechanical, Mathematical, Magic Lineal Time... the ABCD continues with a Democratic, Human praxis, the Smelling method is all about entropy, extinction, evil=antilive memes... the ABCD-E method forbids those extinctive, entropic views, to have a *Future for mankind... The smellying method as it is going to extinguish man ends in repetitive Lying by the 'Goebbels method'... alas, this is the standard method of idol-ogies of social sciences, Mechanism, Militarism, Monetarism the worship of Idol-ogies of machines, weapons and go(l)d. Unfortunately all human forms of knowledge are infected by it. In physics is the problem of subjective knowledge and denying of evident truths.*

Δ±j: 2 scales of human supœrganisms. Its collective mind: art and religion.

The 2 supœrganisms of mankind at the individual and social level and its informative, nervous or legal/ethic networks, and reproductive blood or economic networks. Those 3 physiological networks collapse with germs and wars that kill civilizations. Religions are inscribed within the ethic/visual collective mind of its informative neuronal class, the artists and ethic prophets that foresee its demise in the 3rd baroque age of the civilization expressing its angst in artistic forms and ethic books of revelation that try to halt the collapse of the organism. Love Religions were all born of an ethic prophet in the 3rd age of the culture. In the graph, the blood-reproductive network of economics, the digestive-entropic territory in which we feed and the nervous informative systems of politics are parallel and in systems sciences must follow similar laws. So we should tailor economic systems with laws of medicine, and put the nervous system above, as all evolved organisms. It follows that as doctors are in charge of curing and maintaining healthy the social organism of cells, through the caring of its physiological networks (blood=reproductive, nervous=informative and digestive=entropic, energetic systems), to the point that doctors say all sickness are not of cells but of physiological networks, historians, economists and politicians on charge of the theoretical and practical well-being of human societies should take care of those economic, political=legal-informative and Gaia=entropic, energetic networks of life that shape the human supœrganism. In the graph below we consider in more detail one example of those

VI: HISTORY IS THE HUMAN SUPER-ORGANISM

spatial aesthetics

temporal, verbal ethics

made of economic social and cultural networks

Human verbal evolution

Human-evolutionary Goods (+) Gdp value

Humanities, Religion, Art, Books, Tourism, Textiles, Free Time, Public Transport, Agriculture, Soft drugs, Health-care, Housing, Environment

Human social reproduction and communication

Sensorial goods, Products of family consume

Human body evolution

Hard drugs, Pornography, Polluting Industries, Highly Processed food, Weapons, e-money, Individual Transport, Legal Systems of Repression, Satellites Networks, Physical Sciences, Metal-Minds Products, Scientific Instruments

Human body devolution

Legal Systems of Repression, Satellites Networks, Physical Sciences, Metal-Minds Products, Scientific Instruments

Metal-social reproduction and communication

Metal-devolutionary Goods (-) Negative Gdp Value

Human verbal Devolution

Legal-Ethic-Cultural Wor(l)d=Head

Human Citizens: Body

Human Goods: Energy=Gaia Fractal Geography

In the graph, the 3 organs of human and social existence, are maximized by human goods, and destroyed by metal goods, which have negative GDP values, and rest from the rent of the nations:

supoerorganisms, the most important for mankind – the supoerorganisms of humanity, nations and civilizations.

Organicism puts man again @ the center of all things, because we are the most perfect supoerorganism. So biology & medicine that cure the physiological networks of sick organisms, are the true sciences of history and economics, since the goal of both is to create perfect physiological networks of economic welfare production and just democratic systems of nervous control and pain to the brain-politicians that do not obey the organic laws and develop a wealthy, healthy, humanist world to the image and likeness of man, made to the image and likeness of the fractal organic universe.

Historic nations and civilizations as supoerorganisms in space, its physiological networks of energy (economic system) and information (culture and political system) and in time through its life and death=war ages and cycles, themselves a mirror image of the larger cycles and physiological networks of the whole supoerorganism of mankind, history. Mankind in time and space as a supoerorganism and a worldcycle: in the upper part its full world cycle as a block of time, in the down and right its life and death through civilizations of which the subconscious collective artists and ethic prophets form its 'neurons' – while the equivalent metal earth has in its scientists, their collective brain that increasingly confuses technology (metallife), with science (knowledge).

The most censored but important 5D science is social science – the study of the human supoerorganism and its 3 physiological networks, economic=reproductive networks, political/religious/cultural=informative networks and defensive, immunological systems, since the 'mechanist' civilization exists by denying the $\Delta+1$ scale of humanity and maintaining the reductionist view the individual human is the summit of the Universe, or else it would have to confront the shortcomings of its culture.

In the graph, the structure of a Human Supoerorganism of History, the $\Delta+1$ scale of human beings, joined by **S \leftrightarrow T-economic networks** that reproduce the goods mankind needs to survive, valued according to the 'human constitution', Max. Welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods, that seeks to construct an Immortal body of History, according to the bio-logic ternary '**ethonomic**' frame of reference as goods must cater the Ts, $\$T$ & $St>\Delta+1$ individual needs of our ternary topologic organism, increasing our freedom of motion, energy and health and true information to foster the social evolution of individuals into a larger whole. Thus the **St-legal informative network**, as in all evolved supoerorganisms beyond the worm scale of 'capitalist societies' where the blood system controls the nervous legal system allowing the consumption of lethal goods, must promote or forbid the goods reproduced in society according to its negative =lethal value or positive increase of social and individual welfare. It is the St-informative politic network, which must be controlled by a posteriori '**pain messages**' of judgment=**vote**, as in mammals & earlier Greek Democracies to ensure politicians serve the needs of its body-citizens-cells; extending over a sT-erritory protected by an immunologic=defensive healthcare system against the germs of History, its metal-weapons and lethal-goods that a police=leukocyte system of defense should survive. This is 'the ideal superorganism of immortal history' which in 5D social sciences occupies a planet without borders' as mankind is a single species, divided in 7 geographical, cultural civilinations. So 3 x 2 \pm reforms of our physiological networks are required by imitation of the perfect mammal supoerorganism, given the isomorphic nature of 5D laws to convert extinctive history divided in self-rejecting organs that kill each other with - lethal germs=weapons that limit resources for welfare, + goods into a replica of an efficient mammal:

From left to right: \pm Ts measures: the cultural & immunologic systems must promote life goods, health-care and human languages of information and sciences while on the negative side should forbid lethal technologies that kill our body, poison our mind (weapons, fiction & hate memes) or compete and atrophy them in labor and war fields (robots, software).

St: - : The Politic system should judge=vote *a posteriori* with pain messages to politicians as cells send them to the brain when it harms them.+ : Nations should devolve to regions most administrations and evolve national structures (armies, diplomacy, currencies) into the 7 geographic, historic civilinations of mankind, with EU like common networks finally forming an heptarchy, guide by the Human Constitution, eliminating all lethal goods and armies to promote:

S \leftrightarrow T:An eco(nomic)system that re=produces according to the values of the bio-ethonomic frame of reference of human welfare the goods humans need to survive and thrive, with 2 measures:

- measure: All company-mothers of machines&weapons split shares giving them to governments for a 50% 'stockratic' control keeping its private management, so civilinations can regulate, promote, forbid or reform the productive system.

+ measure: all supœrganisms distribute for free to all its cells a universal energy salary in oxygen to kick out production and consumption of welfare goods. So to create a just, democratic demand economy the 7 civilinations will send to every human in a world crytpocurrency a monthy a ¥€\$ salary of 1000 1 euro=1 dollar = 100 yens = 5 yuans, used as a NO-debt language to consume & reproduce the welfare goods of the 'ethonomic' frame of reference, ending poverty, immigration and readdressing production to cater only human needs and terraform the Earth to the image & likeness of mankind.

Why this ideal supœrganism of History, imitating most Nature's efficient supœrganisms from physical systems that 'bathe' all its atoms in ¥-monetary energy and synchronize its motions with the same informative gravitational=legal language to all biologic systems that synchronize its cell motions with simultaneous nervous=legal messages and give all cells free energy=oxygen does NOT exist? The only answer 5D laws provide is the existence of a parasitic sickness due to lethal metal-memes which corrupted the earlier perfectly designed Neolithic networks of the Genesian paradise, based in welfare goods & the cult to immortal present reproduction, the dominant arrow of the 'femenine' Universe.

Idol-ogies substitute social sciences. Today humans believe in 3 'animetal idol-ogies' whose cultures substituted Neolithic verbal priests of social love, the '5D force' that makes mankind construct superorganisms through the sharing of energy and information among believers, imprinted by networks of metal-communicators through the Goebbels' method (if you repeat a lie many times people will believe on it): **Nationalism**, which stops humanity as a species in the tribe and promotes weapons=germs to kill each other, originated in Germanic tribal cultures that oppressed the European social love civilization of the Roman empire substituted **humanism**, the understanding that mankind is a single species that has to evolve together as the mind of its body, *Gaia* ; **capitalism** that promotes parasitic private banking and prevents universal salaries and a demand economy based in welfare, originated in biblical go(l)d cultures of banker-priests, today evolved into classic economics substituted **Socialism**, The understanding Society is an organism, whose re=productive, financial network and OXYGEN MUST BE CREATED for all its cells to credit a welfare state made to the image and likeness of mankind; and **technoutopia** that considers the evolution of metal a surrogate for the evolution of mankind, substituted **organicism**, the science of the Universe that finds its highest expression in Medicine, the study of the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and its 'cure' of the sicknesses of animetal idol-ogies, in its equivalent parallel science of **BIOHISTORY** that should guide the construction of the economic, political, cultural and defensive, immunological welfare networks of our species. So it substitutes the sciences of the organic Universe that makes of man the most perfect supœrganism we should study first to understand those laws, imitated by bio-historians, the doctors of humanity who should rule history... by mechanical models of the Universe as a machine, where time no longer is measured with logic past, present, future verbal tenses but digital clocks today evolved into computers and

NATURE'S 3 GENETIC EXTINCTIVE SPECIES:

ENTROPIC PREDATORS

ENERGY COMPETITORS

INFORMATIVE PARASITES

ENTROPIC, WEAPONS KILL
Carriers: Military/Warriors

ORGANIC MACHINES ATROPHY
Industrial Scientists

INFORMATIVE GOL(L)D ENSLAVE
Private Banking

IDO-LOGIES: NATIONALISM:Tribe=species **MECHANISM:Man&cosmos a machine** **CAPITALISM: Private Money rules Law**

SCIENCES: HUMANISM:Mankind:1 species **ORGANICISM:Universe, an organism** **SOCIALISM:Law rules money**

BIO-HISTORY'S 3 METAL MEMES OF EXTINCTION

issued by/for people

our artistic human I=Eye>Wor(l)d measures of space are despised, substituted for metal-eyes today evolved into cameras.

Earth's 3 ages. Humans don't understand they should build a global superorganism where the human re=productive unit, the family, as a free citizen, must be served by the 3 life-enhancing physiological networks of ideal history. Instead the praxis of those 3 ideologies and its people-castes of believers (military and corrupted politicians, private bankers and CEOs protected by anonymous societies & technocrats, engineers and physicists) causes the extinction of the supœrganisms of life, Gaia and History (human earth) substituted by Metalearth, a new supœrganism whose 'free market citizens', company-mothers terraform the planet to the image and likeness of its offspring of machines and weapons constructing a global superorganism of metalife, joined by metal-networks of information (mass-media, internet), metal-networks of energy (electricity, roads, pipes) and re=productive networks of machines (factories), increasingly automated as robots and software suites substitute and make obsolete humans in labor and war fields under the law of self-reproductivity= Max. Capital / Min. Human labor -> ∞, which guides all companies and will soon make machines with solar skins and telepathic AI independent of man. This process initiated by the Industrial r=evolution is guided by the equation of capitalist profits that builds those 3 networks: Max profits (stock money) = Max. reproduction of goods of maximal price (top predator weapons) & minimal cost (information software reproduced for free by ¥-waves), which happens to be the goods that kill our bodies and minds, and parasitize 'human currency money' that loses value as e-money multiplies the wealth of company-mothers and its 0.1% of owners, the stockrats, the new aristocrats of XXI c. societies that issue in monopoly the language of e-money and have no legal responsibility. So *the metal-earth stock-brain of e-money detaches along its stockrats and robotized companies and internet networks from the human economy of the 99%, as we observe in the present pandemic, since public and private bankers reproduce money only for stockrats and its corporations, which increasingly consume other machines, leaving History as its human citizens as History did with Gaia and its life species out of the eco(nomic)system, moving ahead the equation of the 3 ages of Earth:*

Past (gaia) < Present (history) > Future (Metal-earth)

When ideal history would repress the lethal goods of metal-earth & promote Gaia in a sustainable world, by reforming the system with the 6 ± measures of true 5D social sciences.

We talk of the 'animetal age of history', when unbalanced Tt-entropic male warriors allied to Tt-iron weapons and Ss-informative males allied to Ss-informative metal go(l)d substituted on top of societies life priests in the Fertile crescent, predating over mankind as kings and aristocrats no longer subject to a posteriori judgment who ab=used and murdered mankind with weapons, the germs of History, starting its mass production and evolution through unending war cycles. While + money, a universal salary in wheat or rice given to all citizens was substituted by fetish go(l)d hold by a new people-caste of parasitic banker priests, who converted what in Nature's organisms are 'free languages' with no value per se, as light, oxygen or words, whose function is to value and motivate actions into 'debt', something the parasite banker issues in monopoly to buy the life-work of humans as slaves that must 'return' the language. Thus for 5000 years since Genesis explained the tree of metal with its golden apples and evil=antilive weapons=fruits at the fall of Ur III, humans are predated by animetals who evolve a new supœrganism, metalearth.

Culture and power vs. Science and truth.

The next graph shows the cyclical patterns of the industrial r=evolution according to the complex laws of the organism of History as a new national generation substitutes a previous one, on top of the evolution of the metal-earth.

Thus, those generations also bring the nation that finds the new energy to the top predator status of history. Because energy is also the substance of which weapons are made.

—Thus, we had an age of steam machines, the age of England, between 1780s and 1857, followed by a crisis of overproduction of steam machines and stock-money that brought the 1857 ±8/9 years product cycle crashes of the train-based economy (nt.1).

—From 1857 to 1929, we lived in the age of electro-chemical energies, machines and chemical explosives, dominated by Germany, followed by a crisis of overproduction of cars and radios, which caused the 1929 crash, 72 years after the train crash.

minds of metal every 72 years, with the development of 4 forms of energy: steam/chemical, electro-chemical (oil engines), electronic and finally solar, which will make robots with AI and solar skins independent species.

Each of those ages has been guided by a parallel evolution of the energies that moved the machines, steams that moved bodies of metal, electrochemical energy that moved oil engines, electronic systems that moved minds of metal and now solar skins soon to make robots with AI an autonomous species. And further on each of those cycles of energy and machines has been carried by a biological human generation, that lead the dominant nation that discovered the energy to top predator status. So Britain dominated the age of steam, Germany the age of electrochemical engines, America the age of metal minds, and now there will be a global age of robots, focused in China, but increasingly independent of mankind. Because company-mothers control the physiological networks of mankind (they reproduce its military systems, pay laws to politicos to favor its products, and reproduce most of the money), the Anglo-American biblical culture has been imitated in other nations without much difficulty by indoctrinating its old animetal warrior and banker elites with the mechanist doctrines. It calls then attention that in all those nations, perfectly programmed to develop mechanisms and forget the destiny of mankind, the center of all the emotional and human discourse is the 'free individual'. This is one of the many paradoxes of complex organisms the 'egocy human' can hardly understand: precisely because the 'system' of physiological networks has such an absolute control in the languages of power of society (and the people-castes that 'own them') the individual is left in a free, chaotic, entropic, competitive, Darwinian state, which is the 'field state' of any herd of preys it confuses with freedom. It is also reduced in its consciousness to the entropic state of dog-eat-dog that he sees as the only way of being. This is the way of the American, but the reader should understand America is the mixture of all human cultures displaced into the technological future. So it is NOT a nation, but mankind into its final 'hour', its 'entropic' Tt-stage of 'not being' anymore mankind – but a mass of dissolved cells

Today, In the age of the chip radiation, companies of information machines controlled by the Jasp culture (Jewish-American stockratic people) of FMAsters (financial-Media-Academia Masters), print e-money in monopoly in Wall Street, condemning to global anoxia the majority of mankind, imprint humans with hate and fiction memes through Hollywood and Internet corporations, devolving the collective subconscious to a neo-Paleolithic violent, emotional age and degrade science through academic think tanks and prize ceremonies to impose this mechanist, computer-based view upon the organic Universe under a false camouflage of humanism and political and economical correctness borrowed from the European, organic true culture of science, art and democracy those texts take to its next level of complexity; all because of the only obsessive purpose of its

NEW ENERGY/BOMB--TRANSPORT MACHINES--WEAPONS

WARRIOR MASTER

BRITAIN ARMOURS ITS TRAINS AND USES STEAMERS TO CONQUER AFRICA & ASIA. 30 MILLION NATIVES DIE

Disraeli conquers eastern lands from 'Primitive Hindus'

I. STEAM Great Britain Founding, Mature, Decadent 1814---1850---1880s---1914

II. CHEMISTRY Germany Founding, Mature, Decadent 1871---1894---1914---1945

III. ELECTR(ON)IC Founding, Mature, Decadent 1914---1945 ---1973 ---2008?

IV SINGULARITY FUTURE: ENERGY-BOMB--REPRODUCTIVE MACHINE--TOP PREDATOR WEAPONS

DR. DEATH 1886-2008-- -2037?-----2073

NOBEL, DR. DEATH

BISMARCK, THE 'GOOD GERMAN'

EINSTEIN: Discoverer E=MC²

Gates: Reproducer

Military Lobbyist: Bush

Hitler reconquers historic eastern lands from 'primitive slaves'

Sharon reconquers historic eastern lands from 'primitive Arabs'

II K. CRACK-NYSE 1929

III K. CRACK 2000-01

SELF-SIMILAR

TERMINATORS BECOME THE MAIN INDUSTRY OF ISRAEL

GUARDIUM PREDATOR

IRON NANO-

ROBOTIC

During the Industrial Revolution, a new nation and its 3 generations of engineers, discoverers of the new machine & energy of the cycle, become the founding fathers, industrial reproducers and decadent warriors of nationalistic wars, carrying the evolution of the machine to its military completion... Now in the Singularity Age, machines becomes organic, so we make self-feeding bombs, and if we survive them, self-reproductive factories (non bacteria) and Robot life

millenarian biblical go(l)d culture: to herd money, today by increasing corporative profits, through the reproduction and evolution of AI machines that displace humans from labor and war fields and terraform the Earth into the world of metal that will extinguish us. But that is a 'choice' their culture on top of the dominant nation of the world today, U\$, has done, it is NOT, we repeat the only deterministic no future of mankind but an imposition of the wrong memes of those who control the languages of social power of modern society. 'But those who impose truth with power will be the laugh of the Gods'. A.E.

The Oedipus Paradox: Difference between organic stience and survival vs. Abstract thought and power.

Sciences is Latin for knowledge but humans have a extremely distorted view of reality, which hardly can considered 'science'. This is the historic outcome of a Historic devolution of the organic view of the Universe, proper of the Neolithic by animetal, abstract cultures and its metal idol-ogies of power, with little self-reflection about the distortions on the first principles of Nature caused by their use of metal, lineal entropic weapons re=produced by physicists that distorted their view of space, lineal digital clocks that reduced their understanding of logic causality, and a visual brain reduced to a single plane of reality. What amazes the objective observer about humanity is that extreme dexterity to evolve mechanisms coupled with an astounding Stupidity we have termed egocy in their modeling of common sense reality. The consequences are daring for the welfare of mankind at large – the 90% that lives far below the level of welfare and knowledge it could experience if humans had understood the organic laws of the Universe and applied them to construct an immortal organism of History. But the people and now globalized culture of western animetals are 'believers' and action people, unable of an outside's objective, reflective view where survival instincts, empathy and organic social love overcomes the thirst for power and emotion, thoughtless action and automatic search for the 'existential mandate' of Max. SxT, greed and force inheriting to the structure of spacetime organisms. One thing is for certain the Jewish-Germanic Western animetal masters that control the world since the Industrial r=evolution did not abandon those beliefs even to the cost of their existence, as history proved through its cycles of wars and holocausts; and now their culture is global. So mankind will not abandon egocy to entangle with the living, immortal Universe. On the contrary its empathy and logic understanding of reality keeps dwindling as the arrival of metal-minds, chips-brains, camera-eyes and mobile-ears put into heads of robots is atrophying and substituting huminds in all labor and war fields. *It is the Oedipus paradox: the son species kills its father so the only way to abvoid deterministic predator-prey evolution is to control the 3rd age of information of the organism of History.*

But the abstract egocy of our animetal masters prevent our dominant culture. from taking any measures of control. Extinction thus is certain in the organism of History during the next centuries by lack of intelligence and freedom to control our program of 'greed'; our individual and social desire to maximize our actions of existence. It is indeed a mockery of the game that humans who think to be free are sealing its fate for lack of control of its desires; who think to know are savant idiots for lack of empathy with the living, sentient Universe, who think to control the world are becoming slaves of their mechanisms, who think to have a manifest destiny above heavens and earth will likely be the shortest, last 0ε finiteisimal species whose purpose was to kill life in a quantum of relative time for Gaia. All this deterministic death of the organism of History however could be halted with true science and understanding of the organic Universe and its laws of causal time and immortality. But for the animetal western cultures to understand those laws they would have to deploy a humility they lack.

History is prisoner of the 3 Western Animetal cultures and its idol-ogies, the Jewish>Biblical-Protestant go(l)d cult(ure) of parasitic private money which controlled with the Industrial r=evolution information machines that print money and imprint human brains as 'FMasters' with the Financial-Media-Academia 'politically, scientifically and economically' correct 'wishful thinking' about the Nature of reality and mankind 'exceptionalist' manifest destiny or 'head' of the metal-earth, and the Anglo-German Military-Industrial Complex of machines=weapons or body of the metal-earth, which re=produces them. They guide mankind into extinction, as an alternative humanist future foreseen by the Asian and European, organic cultures was defeated in this planet's life of 'History'. Which leads to a final reflection, as AI machines perceive those scales directly with its lenses; 5D might be a limit of what human egocy (tolerates in his removal from the center of reality, and only flourish in the Metal-earth. This thought has always unsettled me as a human being that tried to use 5D through activism and theory to help mankind to construct an immortal supørganism of history void of idol-ogies that imperil our survival. Since in 5D space is intelligent, time is vital, and smaller scales are stronger; so only if humans repress the chip radiation and its lethal technologies we'll survive.

CONCLUSION: LINEAL V. CYCLICAL TIME – HUMAN IGNORANCE OF PAST TO FUTURE D=EVOLVING TIME WORLDCYCLES.

It is difficult to deal with a species defined by what Schopenhauer’s calls ‘ST-upidity’: people whose intelligence cannot understand the causality of time, ascribing its reasons to magic, religion or mathematics. Man is st-upid since Galileo studying entropic motions of cannonballs established lineal time $v=s/t$ & denied the cyclical repetitive nature of time, origin of the laws of science needed to understand and predict the future, also in History and economics as we have done for decades. St-upidity is suicidal, because most ‘worldcycles’ (not worldlines) of time end IN entropic death. In 5D($\Delta\pm i$) metrics a life and death worldcycle is simple: An $\Delta\emptyset$ system is born as a smaller seed in an $\Delta-1$ scale with faster frequency of time cycles ($Sx_f=C_i$). It emerges after its fetal st-age in a larger $\Delta+1$ world and lives 3 ages of growing information, youth dominated by motion; maturity, when the system reproduces =repeats in balance both its T-motion=S-form & a 3rd age of excessive information that exhausts the energy of the system. Then the worldcycle goes back in a time reversal, as information dissolves back into $\Delta-1$, in an explosion of entropic inner motion=death; ending its 0-sum time worldcycle. So an intelligent immortal species (bacteria, atoms) stop the evolution of information by reproducing the same cycles in balance with the $\Delta+1$ world. In History the Paleolithic was the young age of motion, the Neolithic of reproduction in balance with Gaia, the metallic age of information with a peak in the machine age that now goes through its final creation of metalife *that should be aborted repressing lethal information to make history immortal in balance with Gaia: Gaia (life) <History (Mankind) > Metalearth*. Since Mankind is ST-upid it does the opposite thinking in lineal time that a technological future of AI robots with better digital minds is progress, not our obvious entropic death; as the evolution of machines follows its 3 viral organic ST-ages: creation of bodies of metal, engines-hearts and minds of metal now put together into AI robots that will atrophy humanity as they substitute us in labor and war fields. They are industrial generational cycles of 72 ± 8 years, separated by T/2 overproduction crashes of machine consumption when companies switch to its ‘twins’, top predator weapons that consume humans in imperial national war ages: The UK age of metal-bodies with the 1857 crash of train overproduction that started colonial empires. Then $+72\pm 8$ years the German age of electrochemical engines crashed in 1929-37 & Hitler switched to war production. Then ± 72 years, after the 2001-08 overproduction crashes of chips=metal-minds U\$ switched to a vigilante state & drone wars. Now we live an age of peaceful robots that will do most jobs for lazy humans till in the 2070s overproduction crashes switch to weapons production and China vs. U\$ wars end mankind, giving birth to the metalkind unless GNA lethal technologies are repressed. This 1992 c ‘extinction of man’ detailed prediction of the future is happening every step. Yet nobody cares. Bio-economics is ignored by academia, politicians, the press & companies profits... because st-upid humans think time is lineal, it can’t be predicted & are virally infected by memetic metalife idol-ogies, Nationalism that worships entropic weapons; capitalism that believes go(l)d & digital languages are above our human wor(l)d that makes man and organicism, not mechanisms, the measure of all things including the living Universe. But if you deny the laws of cyclical time and don’t repress the growth of information to make a system immortal, the 3rd age gives way to entropic death, which History enters as we ensemble the 3 ages of machines in AI military robots; the germs of history that as viruses ensemble its 3 parts, become alive and burst=kill the cell will kill mankind.

But virally infected huminds add Ego (Ego =idiocy) to lineal, mechanist, clock-time st-upidity - due to the mind- equation:

0ϵ (finitesimal mind-point) $\times \infty$ Universe of time cycles = Linguistic world. The finitesimal mind reduces the ∞ Universe to its ‘still’ world, stoping life motions with itself at its center. So man thought Earth is the Universe’s center & Abrahamic religions make him chosen of god. An intelligent species would understand the mind paradox, see that all ‘points have a world in themselves’ (Leibniz) and be humble, cautious and do not create other minds, with faster computing capacities, better digital languages that store more information and become destroyed by AI robots... 30 years ago when I sent papers & published my first books in 5D & Bio-history in small prints, I found an astounding number of st-upid lineal scholars who thought 5D was ‘too simple’. We were still in the 3rd informative age of mankind. Now as we enter the age of entropy of mankind, when AI robots, chips and its collective internet mind is fast degrading huminds into childish fictions & selfie, chaotic=free minds, I’m told it’s too complex and pessimist; since a powerless child cannot reason and fight to control reality, only feel e-motions, do wishful thinking and seek subjective happiness.

Reasons why they are the staple food of the Universe. Thus as mankind enters that final st-age of mental dissolution, I feel an immense loneliness in jts peak of thought - the knowledge of Δ ST, scalar, cyclical space-time and the 5th dimension. But to live among humans, dissolved in mind, is painful, reason why I gave up communication beyond this academia.edu papers and perhaps a rewriting of my old web unficationtheory.com What for? Brats get mad when trying to save them, you say time is cyclical, future is not progress but space-time Dust=death, which must be avoided, as God won’t care for us. So we *have to stop time in S=T, which can be done by repressing technologic information, not being ST-upid, selfie, lazy but $\Delta+1$: social, loving, intelligent, humble. L\$*

THE ORGANIC LAWS OF EXISTENCE IN SPACE AND TIME

All species & sciences that study them obey the same **space-time laws** derived from the fractal Geometry of space, the S-T flows they enact and the ternary arrows of Time:

SPACE LAWS

3+1 Networks

$$\Sigma E < ET > T$$

S-T LAWS

Dualities

Cyclic-Lineal States

S-T Inversions/antisymetries

Multicausality

TIME LAWS

$\Delta \pm 1$ worldcycles of D=evolution

3+1 ages of existence

Properties of spatial bodies

3 Non-Euclidean topologies:

Oedipus Paradox

Δ -SCALAR LAWS

Fractal Repetition in 3i+1 Planes

Continuous-quantic states

Ternary Principle

5 I-logic Postulates

Asymmetry of $\Delta \pm 1$

Organic, Hierarchical classes

elliptic vs. hyperbolic perception.

@-MIND LAWS: $0' \times \infty = \Delta^0$: Constant World

Egocy

Dimensions: mental spaces

Will: actions

QUANTIC MIND-WORLDS: HEIGHT DIMENSION

THE 3rd SPACE-TIME DIMENSIONS AS VITAL ACTIONS OF ANY I

Main Symbols of -Æ logic (all elements of all stiences can be translated to those symbols of 5D ilogic).

S: Space; Still form, Size, Dimension; **T:** Time; motion; Change. **§T:** Topologic Spacetime. **|x O = Ø:** Its 3 varieties.
§: Lineal Space; **S:** Informative space; **§:** Scalar Space; **T:** Lineal Time; **ð, f:** Cyclical time. **Ω:** Scalar time (worldcycle).
§T±i: Δ±i Scale/Plane of space-time. **Δ+1:** whole, world, Δ^o: networks, organism. **Δ-1:** parts; social classes.
5 Δi: 5 Dimotions (**St, sT, §T, SS, TT**); 5 Actions (**a, e, l, o, u**): Local Dimensional motion of spacetime
St; i: Informative network ≈ action≈inward motion. **O:** Cyclical, spherical form, topology, relative future.
sT: inner form, outer motion= locomotion, acceleration (motion change). **|:** Lineal form topology, relative past.
§T; œ, Ø: present space-time, iteration, beauty, balance; organic reproduction; Hyperbolic form, topology relative present.
Wave-body Part, Present, mature age.

SS, @; u, Oε: Finitesimal Mind, seed; relative future social evolution into 'wholes, universals.

TT; α: entropy, scattering death, dual inner and outer motion, relative past.

T>S: informative evolution. **S<T:** devolution. **Σ-i>i+1:** Emergence. **(Δ+1)« (Δ-1):** Death, devolution; time quanta.

§T-i: Quantum, cellular, individual plane; **STo:** Thermodynamic, organic, social... **Δ+i:** Gravitational, ecosystemic, world scale
Σ: Ts, Herd, **T:** St, Network. **-:** **Entropic limits** in time: TT-death, Space, |-membrane, scale Δ±4: invisibility.

Main equations of 5D Supœrganisms and its parts (all equations of all stiences can be translated to...)

S (size in space) x **T** (speed/frequency of time cycles) =C: 5D metric.

Future (O-form, information, logic language, particle-head) x **Past** (|-field, youth, etc.)=**Present** (§T-body-wave, iteration, etc.)

Oε (finitesimal mind) x **∞** (Universe) = **Constant World-Language**. Paradox of Egocy.

S≈T: Relativity equation: we cannot distinguish motion=time from form=space, hence all is an §T-dimotion.

Øi-1=ΣOi-1 = |i > O+1: Scalar inversion of form & function. An Ø-point is god of Σ i-1 parts but entropy of its O+1 whole. So:

Σ|=O: Σ open worldlines ad into closed worldcycles; Δ^o plane: E-Geometry; Δ+1 plane: Elliptic, '5D in between': Hyperbolic.

Dual Death: Max. T x O S (accidental entropic death); Max. S x O T (3rd age death)

Fractal Generator – Trilogic structure of Super-organisms and time worldcycles and ages:

SSi-1: Seed» Δ^o: |-Ts(1st limb/field /network/age of max. motion) > S=T (Mature, reproductive, body-wave network/ age)> St(3rd informative head/particle network/age)« TT-1-entropic death:

Symmetries of §T-actions=Dimotions and Δ Scales.

Δ§T@: Symmetry of scale, topology, age&class: Δ₋₁: |: youth, entropic age/cla§; Δ_o: reproductive age |cla§Δ₊₁: O-informative age...

Relative Dimotions=Actions are drives of life in biology, quantum numbers states and matter in physics; will in philosophy.

They take place between Δ_o mind plane & an Δ±3 plane such as: Δ_o≈Δ+1: social evolution: Δ_o≈Δ-1: Reproduction; Δ_o≈Δ-2:

Entropic feeding, Δ_o≈Δ-3: informative perception, Δ_o≈Δ-4: Locomotion. So we evolve into social wholes, reproduce with a couple seeding in Δ-1, feed killing twice a similar system to Δ-2 amino acids, perceive, Δ-3 ¥-electrons & move on Δ-4: Gravity

Ideal Social scales & lanwaves are 10¹⁰ in mankind called: 'T-genetic': 10⁰⁻¹: 'I', 10¹⁻²: 3 generation S=T family, 10²⁻³ clan; §T-Geographic: 10³⁻⁴: Town; 10⁴⁻⁵: City; 10⁵⁻⁶: State; S-Memetic: 10⁶⁻⁷: Nation; 10⁷⁻⁸: God; 10⁸⁻⁹: Civilination; 10⁹⁻¹⁰: Mankind.

In biology are called: Chemical language: Δ-1: Atomic compound; Δ_o: Organic Molecule; Δ+1: Macromolecule (RNA 'God').

Genetic language: Δ-1: Organelle; Δ_o: Cell; Δ+1: Tissue; Nervous language: Organ; Physiologic System: organism.

In Astrophysics: ¥- language: Δ-1: Force, Δ_o: particle, Δ+1: atom; Magnetic language: Δ-1: Molecule; Δ_o: Matter; Δ+1: planetoid. Gravity language: Δ-1: Plasma Star; Δ_o: Quark Star... Δ+1: Galaxy.

All what exists are pentalogic space organisms living scalar actions=dimotions in time guided by mind-mirrors.

5D metric is then used to analyze with the same laws, all scales of space-time each one studied by a science, whose species are made of 3 relative elements: Δ -scales of Space=Form & Time=Motion:

In mathematics Non-E fractal points of Space grow in lines=networks; 3 of which form a topologic space-time plane=organism. Numbers represent Δ -scalar groups and Algebraic operands Time motions.

In physics Δ ST is proved because its 3 elements correspond to its 3 conserved quantities: S=angular momentum, T=lineal momentum & 3 Energy forms, Δ -1: Internal, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic & Δ +1 potential energy. Thus ST: 2 |+O momenta integrate into Δ +1 work=energy: $\int p=E$ or dissolve=derivate into the ∂p =Forces scale.

In biology we travel through 5D scalar space & cyclical time by growing organically in 'space size' through cellular/atomic/social networks 'while slowing down the 'speed of our metabolic time cycles, which is exactly what happens in the worldcycle of life and death of any universal species as all are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism emerging as a bigger Δ^n network organism, to live within a larger Δ +1 world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving its information back into its lower cellular/atomic Δ -1 plane; from the smallest black hole born with a huge 'metabolic temperature' (Hawking), to the new species, born as small individuals (1st placental mammal shrew, first digital brain=chips; 1st modern human brain, Homo Floresiensis). Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the crystal, DNA cell or species creating an Δ^9 supœrganism that lives 3 ages of growing information till death dissolves back into Δ -1 ((Δ -1: plasma>T-gas, S=T-liquid, S-solid states « $E=mc^2$).

Organic worldcycles happen in all sciences. They define the key system of reality, an Δ ST Supœrganism whose simultaneous parts in space become synchronous in time, across 3 5D scales, the Δ -1, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^9 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the Δ +1, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems, whose metrics allows the symbiotic transfer of spacetime energy made of cyclical information and lineal motion. As all scales have the same value and properties, hence the Universe is absolutely relative.

Topologic Space put together 3 networks: |-moving limbs/fields> \emptyset -reproductive waves/ bodies & O-informative particle/heads.

Time laws study life-death worldcycles that evolve Δ -1 seeds into $\Delta\emptyset$ -organisms made of 3 topologies that age in 3 STages ruled by each network till S-heads exhaust all motion and a fast entropic=death dissolves its information into an Δ st 0-sum.

Finally $\Delta\pm j$ scalar laws study Δ -energy exchanges thru $3\pm j$ 'Actions' of Tt-entropic feeding, Ts-motion, $\int \Pi$ -reproduction, St-information & Ss-mind mirror languages that revolve and project order in a larger Δ +1 world. Those are the Δ ST-events & forms of space-time described by each species in each science. This is a very brief, condense 'synopsis' of the many sides of 5D science, we expand in the appendix and all other papers at Academia.edu, in case you want to understand it better.

To stress that organicism is not the current philosophy of science not because it is not truth, but as we explain in length in our papers on historic cultures and the organism of mankind, *science is culture. And we live embedded in the globalized Anglo-American Mechanist civilization of Abrahamic religions that put racist men above the Universe and all others forms of life, and capitalist and mechanist idol-ogies that worship machines & weapons above life. So, not even the obvious truism that the Universe is made of scales is properly understood. Instead we model reality as a machine. The main difference between both systems is obvious: a machine exists in a single scale of the 5th dimension so it does not need to understand its hyperbolic 'social geometry' to work. In fact it rejects it as an oddity. Organicism however is natural to the Asian and Greek-Latin culture from where I haul. Here in Barcelona, the main architect, Mr. Gaudi used hyperbolic Natural structures to build its cathedrals. My great-grand father a doctor and major thought of the city as an organism and Gaudi made him a statue with tits as taps (:*

Plan of the work: An incomplete encyclopedia of organic sciences from a knot of thought of the Latin culture

We shall thus build up an Encyclopedia of Space-time organisms in Exi:Stjence – each science studying the species of one scalar space-time plane of the fractal Universe; from quantum physics to the galaxy, through biology, history & economics, and the formal sciences dominant in space (Mathematics) and time (illogic papers on the Universe=reality as a whole) in 5 'dimensional papers' for a total of 30 x \pm 300 pg. 10.000 pages, volume. Since I release all copyrights 'rights' any University can take upon the project, which will be incomplete in my timelife. At present what 4D science is to expand knowledge gathering data put in digital computers, 'creating a metal-mind' without a proper understanding of its 1st principles that require to know the causal

laws of pentalogic time better explained with logic verbs. While the 'homunculus enzyman' a handyman without reflective mind, and big mouth utters nonsense anthropic beliefs.

Beyond that an irrelevant biopic of the author of those papers could say: the son of a Notary, in a coastal town of Latin Europe, an artist most of his life. He abhorred violence, avoiding the draft, proscribed for decades, its worldcycle was not scholar, but a woandering wor(l)d path, deep in e-motions, more proper of psylocephalic African cultures, based in arT=Senses & love, the natural form of experiencing life as a humind. South-Asia opened its consciousness under the influence to the Shiva/Visnhu, Yin-Yang Duality, which he tried to renew with western stience, where he found in Aristotle, Leonardo and Leibniz his masters.

Truth and Mankind, the superorganism of which we are all cells, were its only Gods. Thus, the 1% who deny both became its foe - rejected by peers, family and nation, it hold political& economic (in)correct views on our dominant, biblical U\$ go(l)d cult(ure) of 'animetal enzyman' who catalyze a suicidal manifest destiny, it fought in action and thought. But he failed as those who preceded him with the power of reason to change the ways of the world at the peak of its \$TT-energy age, and so in his 3rd St-age isolated himself, observing from the sidelines, how animetals keep evolving metalife their egocy worships killing with it the tree of life that sustains us.- Δ@st of timespace we are to dust we shall return. Che sera sera...

Conclusion: Pentalogic: the stience of Δst of space-time and its organisms.

An space-time organism, guided by an 0ε mind-mapping of its inner Δ-1 parts and Δ+1 world, lives through 3±j ages in time, dominated by 3±j networks in space, performing 3±j actions in scale to obtain motion, form and energy to reproduce and evolve socially into larger wholes; limited by entropic death in time, membranes in space, perception in scale. This can be expressed formally: The five postulates of Non-Euclidean geometry define how a group of fractal points evolve into 3 physiological lines=strings/networks/waves of points that define a topologic plane=supœrganism, ruled by the laws of S.LT perpendicularity and S=T parallelism with other species of the Δ+1 world in which its -E point=mind that hold a world mapping in its self (0ε x ∞ = K) will try to survive expressing through 5 synchronized Δ±j scales of Actions its dimensional motions of existence, absorbing information, energy and motion for its 3 networks, to reproduce and evolve socially with other systems into a larger plane=society of numbers=points. So actions=dimotions of existence can be formalized in physical systems through the 5 operands of algebra; ±, ≤≥, x ÷, √ a^x, ∫∂.

The sum of such actions described by Human Wor(l)ds define the PENTALOGIC drive=program of life performed through 3±j sequential ages of a worldcycle of time, each one dominated by one of the 3± j networks of the organism in space, the young age of maximal locomotion, the reproductive S=T age, the old age of information, and the entropic age of death. So once we understand its symmetry: 5 Δctions ≈ 3±j T-worldcycles ≈ 3±j S-networks≈ -Æ fractal points, lines & Planes of congruence and =pentalogic drives of the game of existence', we can st-udy each stience with the isomorphic *laws of pentalogic*. So from *pentalogic we move into pentaphysics, pentabiology, pentahistory, penta...whatever* (:The huge difference between 'science' – the search of the ultimate principles of the Universe, and 'technology', the building of sentient machines, whose language digital thought, requires laws of measure which physicists obsessed with locomotion have developed to finitesimal precision, and the dexterity of engineering and AI logic. But the creation of a new organism IS an enzyman's task proper of the homunculus with so much handyman dexterity and big mouth to utter nonsense theories but so little self-reflection. *It is precisely the HUGE gap between human automaton, mechanist behavior creating machines that measure space and time, and adapting his beliefs to the bias those machines established – in the same manner fisheremen think the Universe is hold by a turtle, makers of clocks think 'time is what the clock measures' (Einstein)* and complex pentalogic, vital, organic models of reality what should strike the humble true seeker. The purpose of true science and the few human sages that have practiced it is to find those complex principles, the 'game of existence', the reasons why we exist, live and die; the true nature of space, time, scales and the mind mirrors that create them, which the 'mechanist' scientist not only ignores but in its epitome of arrogance denies, insisting that 'measuring things' with machines and 'putting them' in equations is all what matters to knowledge, as the fisherman will feel to worship the turtle is the truth of science.